

THE EMPLOYER VALUE PROPOSITION
DEVELOPMENT CYCLE:
A SYSTEMATIC FRAMEWORK FOR
CRAFTING COMPELLING EVPs

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the requirements of the University of the
West of Scotland
for the award of Doctor of Philosophy

FOR ALL PEOPLE WITH HEART.

ESPECIALLY MY LOVING WIFE AND MY HUNCHBACKED FRIENDS,

AS WELL AS MY SUPPORTIVE SUPERVISORS.

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Abstract

This research aims to address a knowledge gap by systematically identifying and comparing the requirements for Employer Value Proposition (EVP) development from both theoretical and practical perspectives. The overarching objective is to enhance the EVP development process by introducing a novel optimisation phase designed to bridge the reality-ambition gap, ensuring the creation of authentic and effective EVPs that benefit both employers and employees.

There is a need for a clear strategic approach to profiling a company as an attractive employer, otherwise known as employer branding. This thesis begins with the synthesis of a conceptual EVP development model based on existing theory and literature. This model is then refined and expanded through original empirical research. Moreover, a total of 27 requirements were identified in the literature. This is followed by a comparison with the experiences of experts in the field.

The methodology consists of a literature review and a qualitative study on the experiences of experts. This is using a qualitative, exploratory research design, employing semi-structured expert interviews. Twenty-eight experts, primarily from the UK, Germany, and North America, were selected through purposeful sampling based on their extensive experience in EVP development. The verbal data were analysed using thematic analysis.

This research process has resulted in the reconstruction and validation of 50 requirements for the systematic development and design of an EVP. Empirical research reconstructed 48 practical requirements for EVP development and categorised them under situation analysis, creation, EVP characteristics and optimisation. Key insights from expert comparisons revealed distinct priorities relating to differences in country, experience level, whether the expert was internal or external (i.e. a consultant), and academic and field background. The requirements that should be taken into account when creating a clear EVP, as well as an assessment tool for reflecting on existing EVPs, were proposed in this way.

This research fills a knowledge gap by compiling an extensive, empirically derived list of EVP development requirements. It provides a comparative analysis of theoretical and practical perspectives, emphasising the multi-disciplinary nature of EVP development and detailing how different contexts and levels of expertise influence its implementation. This contribution has generalisable implications for further research, the professional practice of HR, marketing and consultants. The comparison of theory and empirical findings highlighted strong alignment on core EVP requirements (e.g. employee-centricity and authenticity). However, the experts provided more detailed analytical insights and practical EVP characteristics that were not always explicitly stated in the theory. The comprehensive and detailed list of 50 requirements constitutes an adaptable *middle-range theory* that provides a systematic framework for practitioners to develop and evaluate EVPs more effectively. This framework validates that while the process is *transferable*, the content requires cultural calibration.

Limitations include those inherent in qualitative research, such as limited generalisability, potential researcher/interviewee bias and reliance on indirect information. Specific to this study are potential interviewee agendas, varying levels of consultant involvement, small sample sizes for subgroup analyses and a primary regional focus.

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1. Introduction, context and rationale

The context of the thesis is that changes in labour markets lead companies to the response strategy of employee orientation or centrality (Harrison, 2018, p.24; Holbeche, 2022, p.114; Wölki, Gibb and Pfahler, 2025, p.365) and an interest in employer branding (Kucherov *et al.*, 2022, p.127). Within employer branding, the *employer value proposition (EVP)* plays a central role (Goncalves, 2017, p.232). How companies currently *develop EVPs*, and what can be done to improve that is the *knowledge gap* and concern.

This chapter introduces the research context, the previous research on EVP requirements, the research significance and research gap, the research question and the research objectives. The contribution to knowledge is presented and the research structure of the thesis is outlined.

1.1 Research context

“The EVP work is what HR is all about, and everything else should be in support of that work” (Fox, 2012, p.42).

The concept of the EVP has gained substantial traction as a strategic tool within human resources practices (Sahoo and Srivastava, 2024, p.1298). The EVP is the *value proposition* given by the company, as an employer to the employee upon employment (Kriegler, 2022, p.192). The EVP “is a *succinct crystallization* of what makes your organization a *desirable place to work*” (Auger-Domínguez, 2022, p.70).

This section provides a framework for research on the topic of EVP. It describes the developments in the labour markets, then explains the resulting power shift from employers to employees, and examines the challenges that companies are facing as a result.

1.1.1 The nature of the labour markets is changing

Labour markets are changing due to developments within our society and economy (Jung, 2017, p.837; Scholz, 2014, p.8; Stock-Homburg and Groß, 2019, p.4; Trank, Rynes and Bretz, 2002, p.332). The following nine *external factors* have an impact on the labour markets (Agarwal, Nguyen and Aponte, 2023; Brasse *et al.*, 2024; Hagemann and Klug, 2022; Jalil and Isfianadewi, 2024; Lindner-Lohmann, Lohmann and Schirmer, 2023; Lussier and Hendon, 2020; Mazurchenko, 2025; Milhem *et al.*, 2025; Mölk, 2018; Stock-Homburg and Groß, 2019; Suša Vugec, Pivar and Stjepić, 2024; Ulrich and Dulebohn, 2015; Wölki, 2020):

1. *Economic globalisation*, including the internationalisation of labour markets, with an increasing number of competitors for the most sought-after employees, has increased the pressure on companies to adapt,
2. *Technological development* (e.g. digitalisation / AI), resulting in new solutions, shortened product life cycles, increased product variety, and changed skill sets,
3. The fundamental *structural change* in the economy (towards services: tertiarisation), and the development towards a knowledge society,
4. *Demographic change* (in general, and implications due to the new generations),
5. The *shortage of skilled workers*,
6. *Educational behaviour*,
7. Changes in the media and *media consumption*,
8. *Value dynamics* and change – especially with the upcoming new generations, e.g. society demands that companies assume *social responsibility (CSR)*, and
9. Changed employee requirements due to *generational change* (increasing influence of generation Y and Z).

As a result of these factors, changes can be observed on both sides of the labour market: on the one hand, among employees, and on the other, among employers. Firstly, for many employers, *labour* is becoming an *increasingly important* production factor, and in many cases, it is even the most important

production factor (Fulmer, Gerhart and Scott, 2003, p.966; Kokovikhin, Kulkova and Wang, 2018, p.326; Mei-Pochtler *et al.*, 2014, p.3; Merhar, Höllthaler and Berger, 2019, p.283; Trank, Rynes and Bretz, 2002; Troger, 2022, p.iv).

Second, employees' values are increasingly shifting, resulting in a *decline in the importance of work* in relation to leisure time, often referred to as work-life balance (Braun and Pundt, 2020, p.214; Einramhof-Florian, 2022, pp.1–2; Helmold, 2022, p.9; Lasseben and Hofmann, 2023, p.546; Stavrou and Ierodiakonou, 2016, pp.845–869; Wang and Verma, 2012, pp.407–408). This value shift will also have an impact on the issue of *value congruence* between employer and employee (Dutton, Dukerich and Harquail, 1994, p.245; Kumar, Devadas and Dhammika, 2021, p.24), within the field of matching of employer and employee (Weller *et al.*, 2019, pp.188–214).

1.1.2 Background of the problem: The shift of power from the employer towards the employee

The nine external factors and the resulting changes on the part of employees and employers are leading to a *paradigm shift in labour markets* from sellers', i.e. employers', markets to buyers', i.e. employees', markets.

And this means a *shift of power* from the employers to the employees (see Fig. 1) (Dannhäuser, 2015, p.9; Dorozalla and Hegewald, 2016, p.7; Eichenberg *et al.*, 2019, p.58; Lippold, 2023, p.103; Stotz and Wedel-Klein, 2013, pp.18 and 45; Wölki, 2020, p.125). In this context, the exchange relationship is revealed as a manifestation of the power relationship inherent in the new institutional economics (Burmam *et al.*, 2023, pp.25–26; Küpper, 1998, p.276; Macharzina and Wolf, 2023, p.66). This shift has consequences for the employment deal between the employer and the employee (Wölki, Gibb and Pfahler, 2025, pp.352–365).

Fig. 1: Fundamental change in the employer-employee relationship resulting in a shift of the power role

This shift in power from employer to employee has the potential to bring about fundamental changes to their *relationship*. These developments will present companies with major and conflictual *challenges*. Leadership and human resource management (HRM) will be particularly in demand here. The loss of power of the employers may prompt a fundamental *rethink* in corporate management (Wölki, Gibb and Pfahler, 2025, p.351).

1.1.3 Business problem focus and project purpose: Resulting challenges for the companies

What is definitely known is that employees are increasingly becoming a *bottleneck factor* for companies (Jung, 2017, p.837; Scholz and Scholz, 2019, p.139). It is estimated that by 2030 there will be a shortage of 85.2 million workers and therefore \$8.5 trillion in *unrealised global income* (Korn Ferry, 2018, p.6). The association of German chambers of industry and commerce, called DIHK, notes that in 2024, 43% of German companies cannot fill jobs in the long term because they do not find suitable employees (Hardege and Zimmermann, 2024, p.4). 57% of the SMEs surveyed even complain about a loss of *turnover* due to the shortage of skilled workers (EY, 2018, p.12). The shortage of skilled workers has been identified as the *greatest threat to the development* of the company by 59% of the companies surveyed (EY, 2019, p.12).

Competition over employees among employers will increase (Hansen and Hauff, 2019, p.37; Stock-Homburg and Groß, 2019, p.31). Consistent *employee-centricity* is due to become a part of corporate governance (Harrison, 2018, p.24; Scholz, 2014, p.5; Trank, Rynes and Bretz, 2002, p.332). If companies fail to establish themselves as *attractive employers*, then unacquired employees will become future growth inhibitors (Esch, 2015, p.26; Scholz and Scholz, 2019, p.143).

In this environment, companies cannot rely solely on personnel marketing as it is regarded as an operational instrument (Kriegler, 2022, p.42). A more strategic approach is needed; the profiling of a company as an attractive employer is defined as *employer branding* (Kracht, 2007, p.270; Scherb, 2014, p.35).

Establishing, building and maintaining *attractive employer brands* are essential investments in the future of companies (Larkan, 2007, p.31; Parment, 2013, p.119; Siebrecht, 2012, p.105). According to Kracht (2007, p.270), companies with a strong employer brand and good communication concepts have a significantly better chance of meeting their needs. Employer branding could even be seen as a prerequisite for surviving as a company in the future (Stotz and Wedel-Klein, 2013, p.205).

In this context, *differentiation* might become of paramount importance, when more companies compete for fewer workers. However, many companies have similar instrumental attributes, job- and/or company-wise. This may indicate that the strategy should concentrate on the symbolic attributes and the employer brand (Lievens, 2007, p.52; Lievens and Highhouse, 2003, p.98; Tumasjan *et al.*, 2020, p.85). This employer brand is also useful as many attributes cannot be directly observed by the potential employee, but brands can be experienced (Connelly *et al.*, 2011, pp.41–42).

In employer branding the EVP plays a *central role* (Chambers *et al.*, 1998, 50–52; Goncalves, 2017, p.232; Sponheuer, 2010, p.124). It is intended to ensure that the company as a whole is perceived as an attractive employer (Chambers *et al.*, 1998, p.50; Michaels, Handfield-Jones and Axelrod, 2001, p.44; Trost, 2013, p.16). The EVP is responsible for *profile-building* and communicating the *core message* of the employer. It is the promise which the employer makes to the employee. Due to this significance, the determination of the EVP should be developed consciously, authentically, and thereby systematically.

However, Veldsman and Pauw (2018, p.78) say: "in practice, the EVP has largely been diluted to either an unarticulated concept that occurs 'by accident,' or as yet another people practice for which the box is ticked because it is 'the right thing to do'". This thesis wants to contribute to changing this.

In summary, the context of the thesis is that changes in labour markets lead companies to the response strategy of employee-centricity and an interest in employer branding. In the context of employer branding, the EVP occupies a pivotal position. The present thesis sets out to explore the knowledge gap and associated concerns regarding the current methods employed by companies in the development of EVPs and to propose improvements to these methods (see Fig. 2).

Fig. 2: Scope of research in context

In this regard, it is imperative to establish precise *requirements for the EVP*, thereby initiating the EVP development process, to ensure a conscious, systematic, and authentic EVP.

1.1.4 Alternative approaches for the thesis

The EVP has been chosen as the focal concept due to its *explicit, strategic* and *intentionally defined nature*. This distinguishes it from the more implicit constructs of the psychological contract and employer brand. Unlike unwritten expectations or subjective perceptions, which are vague, the EVP crystallises the employment deal into a concrete, written statement developed through deliberate managerial processes (Dubey and Rana, 2021, pp.97–104; Lane, 2016, pp.38–47; Mosley, 2014, pp.33, 55; Nankervis *et al.*, 2020, p.360; Sibly, 2016, p.665). This makes it a strategic instrument capable of guiding organisational differentiation, talent attraction and internal alignment.

This proposition includes tangible aspects, alongside subjective employment factors that often influence decisions more than compensation alone (Reed, 2022, p.99). Crucially, the EVP is *aspirational*, but must be *credible* (Lane, 2016, p.41). Organisations must adhere to the principle of not making “promises that the business is unable to keep”, as this can undermine its effectiveness. The employer acts as the primary sender of this defined promise (Lane, 2016, p.51). Ultimately, the EVP is the management-articulated vision of the exchange, often referred to as the “espoused psychological contract” (Nankervis *et al.*, 2020, p.360).

Psychological contract

In contrast to the explicit nature of the EVP, the psychological contract is inherently *implicit* and “*assumed and unspoken*” (Hook and Jenkins, 2019, p.92). It is defined as “*unwritten expectations* that operate between employees and managers” (Rousseau, 1989, p.126). The psychological contract represents a system of *beliefs* encompassing “reciprocal promises and obligations” as perceived by both the organisation and the individual (Guest, 2007, p.133).

As they are subjective, psychological contracts are conceptually vague and constantly evolve over time (Anderson and Schalk, 1998, p.638). They focus

on abstract factors such as fairness, trust, commitment, and loyalty (Anderson and Schalk, 1998, p.642; Armstrong and Taylor, 2023, p.544).

The contract is strategically significant as it is viewed as an “intermediate variable between HRM practices and firm performance” (Nankervis *et al.*, 2020, p.12). The employee is the key sender/perceiver in this relationship, as the psychological contract is based entirely on their subjective interpretation (Rousseau, 1990, p.390; Rousseau and Rousseau, 1995, p.9).

Employer brand

The employer brand represents the outward *image* of the organisation as a place of employment, aimed at both internal and external labour markets (Armstrong and Taylor, 2023, p.94). While the EVP provides the concrete, strategic content (the promise) (Dubey and Rana, 2021, p.103), the employer brand is the perceived outcome of that promise. The employer brand operates under both explicit, written communication, and the implicit perceptions of employees.

The management of the employer brand is an *intentional* process (Backhaus and Tikoo, 2004, p.502). The nature of the employer brand is *holistic* and generally *vague*, encompassing both functional and symbolic attributes such as culture and prestige (Schröder and Lüdtkke, 2023, p.101).

The employer brand is a *strategic* instrument used to attract, recruit, and retain talent (Grigore *et al.*, 2024, p.447). Its effectiveness as a market signal is entirely dependent on the consistency, clarity, and credibility of the communication and associated investments (Crişan and Borţun, 2017, p.280). However, the employer brand itself is shaped by market perception (Mosley, 2014, p.4), making its ‘sender’ a collective group of employees, applicants, and customers, rather than solely the employer. A comparative analysis of the three approaches is presented in Tab. 1.

The EVP is the explicit strategic message developed to communicate the desired “identifiable and unique employer identity” that defines the employer brand (Backhaus and Tikoo, 2004, p.502).

aspect	EVP	psychological contract	employer brand
nature	explicit, strategic, intentionally defined by management	implicit, subjective, evolving over time	holistic, perception-driven, implicit and explicit elements
form	written statement, concise	unwritten, assumed, unspoken expectations	image of the organisation as employer in the minds
conceptual clarity	concrete/focused	vague/subjective/abstract	vague/holistic
sender	employer/management	employee as interpreter	collective (employees, applicants, customers, employer)
focus	employment deal and differentiation	fairness, trust, reciprocity, commitment	external and internal reputation; prestige and culture
strategic use	core platform for talent attraction, retention and alignment	intermediate variable between HRM and performance	strategic tool for attracting and retaining talent
limitations	risk of aspirational over-promising; employer-driven	conceptually vague; highly individualised	dependent on market perceptions; less under managerial control

Tab. 1: Comparison EVP, psychological contract and employer brand

The EVP is therefore the most suitable focus for this study. Unlike the psychological contract, which is implicit and subjective, or the employer brand, which is broad and perception-driven, the EVP is a deliberate, explicit, and strategically defined construct. It functions as the organisation’s promise to employees, combining the tangible and intangible elements of the employment deal. This makes it the most actionable mechanism for improving employer practice, as its development can be systematically planned, articulated and implemented.

However, at the same time, the EVP reflects management’s intentions. This means that there is *potential for misuse* if the promises made are too aspirational or simply not true. This thesis therefore emphasises the importance of raising employer awareness of EVP requirements to ensure authenticity and alignment between strategic intent and employee experience.

1.2 Prior research on EVP requirements and development

“EVP is about characterizing *quintessence*, *personality* and *distinctiveness* of the organization for workers” (Dubey and Rana, 2021, p.104). The EVP should cover the *unique* and *differentiating* messages that are valuable for the chosen target group (Kucherov *et al.*, 2022, p.135). This differentiation is critical as companies recruit for top talent to fill critical positions. The alignment of messages with both existing employees and future recruits can be ensured by EVPs (McLean-Conner, 2015, p.18).

The task of the EVP is to attract talent to the organisation and retain those won (Sparrow and Makram, 2015a, p.252). The EVP should provide responses to the following questions relevant to both prospective employees and existing personnel (Minchington, 2010, p.106; Rideout, 2014, p.66):

- a. What are the key benefits of joining this organisation?
- b. What are the key benefits of staying?
- c. What are the key benefits of giving one's best?
- d. What are the key benefits of recommending this organisation as an employer and business?
- e. What are the key benefits of re-joining this organisation (for former employees)?

The potential significance of the EVP becomes apparent. “The real key is to [...] inspire, inform and reinforce our employer value proposition” (Goncalves, 2017, p.232). It should be possible to derive the information base required for the development of the EVP from the requirements themselves, as well as to create an evaluation system for EVPs.

The formulation of the EVP is a conceptually *creative act*, but it must follow an overarching *strategic logic* (Kremmel and Walter, 2016, p.61). Trost calls finding the EVP the search for the *soul* of the company (Trost, 2013, p.38).

The process of developing an EVP is challenging, but when executed effectively, it can serve as a valuable *strategic tool* for attracting and retaining employees (Nawaz *et al.*, 2020, p.38).

In the field of HR, the term 'requirements' is frequently used to denote the mutual expectations of both employees and employers. These requirements can be interpreted as demands placed on the other party (Armstrong and Taylor, 2023, p.267). This is not the case here. Requirements of the EVP in the EVP development refer to what should be considered while developing the EVP.

In the domain of project management, requirements emerge from the project objectives, which, in turn, are informed by the needs of the various stakeholders. Defining requirements describes a process that is part of requirements engineering and plays a prominent role in technical disciplines. For example, in the automotive industry, the aerospace industry and software development. Systems engineering is geared towards the early clarification of 'customer' needs and the required functionality and requires the documentation of all requirements before an integrated solution is developed with the design and validation (Meyer and Reher, 2020, p.107).

Requirements are derived primarily from the expectations of the stakeholders, in particular the client and the users (Meyer and Reher, 2020, p.112). In the context of the thesis, the relevant parties include management, the human resources department, and, indirectly, the employees.

Stakeholder satisfaction is one of the most important factors for the success of a project. Consequently, when analysing requirements, it is important to know to what extent customer satisfaction and the degree of fulfilment of product or service attributes are related. The distinction between objectively measurable quality and subjectively perceived quality of a product or service helps here (Meyer and Reher, 2020, p.114).

Quality is the degree of conformity of elements (objects, products, services, process models, processes) with the requirements (Dechange, 2024, p.114). It is ultimately a form of target/actual comparison (Dechange, 2024, p.15). Projects fail due to inadequate requirements (Meyer and Reher, 2020, p.118). In conclusion, requirements must be analysed (Meyer and Reher, 2020, p.114).

1.3 Research significance and research gap

At this stage, it is sensible to define the knowledge gap that the research is addressing, formulate the problem, and establish the theoretical and practical significance of the thesis.

Knowledge and research gap

Existing theory and practice still lacks a comprehensive *overview of the professional standards and requirements for EVP development*. Current literature often treats the EVP as a static outcome, overlooking the procedural requirements necessary for its creation. This prevents organisations from moving beyond ad hoc approaches. Rather than discovering a single, objective *truth* about the EVP, closing this gap lies in developing a robust framework that synthesises theoretical rigour with practical expertise to guide systematic development.

Problem statement

It is well-established that employer branding is important, with the EVP being central to this practice. However, as Veldsman and Pauw point out, the EVP is often an “unarticulated concept that occurs ‘by accident’” (2018, p.78). This *unsystematic development of the EVP* can lead to considerable risks, including a lack of authenticity and an inability to attract talent.

Providing a structured overview of EVP requirements can facilitate the transition from intuitive to systematic management, serving as a pragmatic tool for evaluating compliance.

Theoretical and practical significance

This research is significant because it is committed to generating “actionable knowledge” (Patton, 2015, p.303).

- *Practically:* The research contributes to the discipline by converting abstract concepts into a practical management framework. The research aims to solve the specific business problem of unsystematic EVP development by providing managers with a validated set of requirements for creating effective and authentic EVPs that benefit employers (in terms of retention and attraction) and employees (in terms of clarity and experience).
- *Theoretically:* The study bridges the gap between the prescriptive models of academic literature and the complex reality of expert practice. By identifying areas where industry practice diverges from theory, the study refines existing models, reflecting the interdisciplinary nature of EVPs at the intersection of HRM, marketing and organisational theory.

1.4 Research aim, question and objectives

Research aim of this thesis

The aim is to compare the existing knowledge of EVP and its development, with actual practice. This will facilitate the establishment of theoretical and practical conclusions that can address the existing knowledge gap in this area.

Research question of this thesis

The thesis will examine the topic of requirements within the EVP development process, with a view to improving the process of determining the EVP.

Research question:

What are the potential requirements for developing the employer value proposition (EVP)?

Analogies have been proven to facilitate visualisation in discussions. When I started working for an internet agency in 1998, it was obvious that many of our customers had no prior knowledge in this area, despite their status as multinational companies. It was often the case that our team created the customers' first websites and intranets. At that time, one of our most important tasks was to provide our clients with a comprehensive list of 'their' specific requirements. The quality of the result, e.g. the website, depends on the requirements. It was therefore deemed imperative to devise a list of requirements prior to commencing the discussion, with the subsequent adaptation of this list to the specific situation being a key point of the discussion. The present study is similar to the creation of a general list in 1998.

Research objective of this thesis

The objective is to develop a set of requirements for systematically determining the EVP:

1. Identifying the *requirements* for the EVP and its development *in theory* (literature review).
2. *Requirements currently used in practice*, as reported by experts in the field.
3. A *comparison* and *analysis* of literature and practice.
4. *Conclusions* for theory and practice based on the comparison.

1.5 Research contribution to knowledge

This thesis makes a distinct and original contribution to the fields of HRM, marketing and organisational theory by establishing the *EVP development cycle*, a systematic framework for creating compelling EVPs. While existing literature offers only brief descriptions, this research provides a novel and comprehensive systematisation of the EVP development process, synthesising theoretical foundations with original primary data derived from 28 expert interviews.

Specifically, this research makes the following unique contributions:

- *Theoretical innovation* (the net benefit concept): This work uniquely transfers the net benefit concept from marketing to the EVP context. It defines *employee net benefit* and *employer net benefit* in order to rigorously theorise the give and get dynamic of the employment deal. It also introduces *employer USP* and *employer UAP*.
- *Bridging the Gap* (original primary material): This thesis does not merely apply existing theory; it empirically extends it. The original primary material, generated from in-depth interviews with 28 experts, reconstructed 48 practical requirements for EVP development. Crucially, this empirical data reveals 24 new requirements which are not mentioned in the existing theoretical literature (see Tab. 33, p.235). Consequently, the resulting model is not a theoretical abstraction but an empirically grounded framework that closes the discrepancy between academic concepts and the operational reality of high-level practice.
- *New Process Model* (the optimisation phase): This introduces a novel four-stage development process that includes a dedicated *optimisation* phase. This phase is specifically designed to close the *reality-ambition gap* and ensure authenticity in the employer promise.
- *Granular expert analysis*: It provides a detailed comparative analysis of how EVP priorities diverge based on national cultures (UK, Germany and USA), professional backgrounds (HR vs marketing) and expert perspectives (consultant vs in-house), revealing the distinct lenses through which the EVP is constructed.

The culmination of this work is a validated list of 50 requirements that transforms EVP development from an intuitive exercise into a systematic, measurable management discipline.

The disciplinary field: an interdisciplinary synthesis

This research claims a unique disciplinary field situated at the precise intersection of HRM, marketing, and organisational theory. While traditional approaches view the EVP primarily as a functional HR instrument for recruitment and retention, this thesis argues that HR logic alone is insufficient to address the power shift in modern labour markets.

Consequently, this study makes a distinct contribution by importing the *communicative logic* of marketing – specifically the rigour of brand differentiation, segmentation, and customer-centricity – into the *functional logic* of HRM. This synthesis is anchored by organisational theory, which provides the necessary *cultural logic* to ensure that marketing promises are legitimate and grounded in organisational identity. The unique field of this thesis is, therefore, the symbiotic convergence of these disciplines, positioning the EVP as a *boundary object* that forces the *employment deal* (HRM) to align with the competitive *brand* (marketing) and the authentic *culture* (organisational theory).

1.6 Research structure

The structure of this thesis is outlined in Fig. 3. Chapter 2 identifies the listed EVP requirements through a systematic literature review of the EVP literature. Chapter 3 describes the methodology and research design used in the study, and chapter 4 presents the findings from the expert interviews. The analysis of the data is presented in chapter 5, including comparisons of groups of experts and the theory-practice gap. Chapter 6 concludes the study with the presentation of a new model for EVP development, derived from the analyses.

Fig. 3: Structure of the thesis

Chapter 1 underscored that significant shifts in labour markets, driven by factors such as demographic change and a shortage of skilled workers, have resulted in a paradigm shift of power towards the employee. Consequently, companies face escalating competition for talent, positioning EVP development as a strategic necessity to attract, retain, and engage employees. The core research gap identified was the lack of a comprehensive, systematised framework articulating the requirements for this critical process, leading to the central research question: "What are the potential requirements for developing the employer value proposition (EVP)?". The overall aim was set to compare theoretical knowledge with practical insights to develop a robust, systematic framework.

2. Literature review: EVP requirements and development

“Research is an orderly investigative process for the purpose of creating new knowledge” (Swanson and Holton, 2005, p.4). Building on the power shift from employer to employee established in chapter 1, this chapter plays a key role in developing a comprehensive understanding of the EVP. It identifies the EVP’s role in employer branding, defines its relevance and scope, and focuses on the ‘value proposition’ aspect. Theories from HRM and marketing are employed to further enhance this understanding.

Even before the term was coined, the authors Ambler and Barrow discussed the necessity of an EVP. They argued that employer brands, just like product brands, need to have a distinct personality (1996, p.187). The first explicit reference to EVP was made in 1998 (Chambers *et al.*, 1998, p.46). The concept of the EVP has gained substantial traction as a strategic tool within human resources practices (Sahoo and Srivastava, 2024, p.1298). The EVP is the *value proposition* offered by the company, as an employer to the employee upon employment (Kriegler, 2022, p.192).

In this way, the EVP captures the essence of what the organisation wants to be in the minds of potential and current employees (Arriscado, Quesado and Sousa, 2019, p.395). It can be seen as the top management’s explanation of why a person wants to join (or stay) in the organisation (Stahl *et al.*, 2009, p.105). This approach allows us to think of it as an *HR elevator pitch* (Wölki, Gibb and Pfahler, *in print*). The EVP should be an explanation of what the employer is and what it stands for (Sparrow and Otaye-Ebede, 2015, p.5). Thus, every company offers a value proposition for employees (EVP), consciously or unconsciously (Minchington, 2010, p.71), positively or negatively.

The EVP is a selected set of attributes that employees perceive as the value they gain through their employment in the organisation (Alloush, 2020, p.3; Pawar and Charak, 2014, p.4). However, the EVP is *not* merely a *list of attributes*; rather, it is a *developmental process* that commences with the

identification of value attributes through listening and observing employees. This is followed by the development of a value delivery system (Nawaz *et al.*, 2020, p.38). What makes your organisation a desirable place to work is captured in a succinct yet comprehensive way by the EVP (Auger-Domínguez, 2022, p.70).

There is a close connection between the concepts of *employer branding* and the employer *value proposition* (EVP) (Soeling, Ajeng Arsanti and Indriati, 2022, p.2). Therefore, the following section analyses employer branding.

2.1 Employer branding

In light of an ever-increasing global talent shortage, organisations are seeking comprehensive strategies to attract and retain potential and current employees (Theurer *et al.*, 2018, p.155). The significance of employer branding has grown since the mid-1990s (Kucherov *et al.*, 2022, p.127), which is based on the need to differentiate and distinguish oneself as an employer (Rietz and Lohaus, 2013, p.1418). Employer branding has become an important and widespread HRM tool (Mölk and Auer, 2018, p.485). It is a *long-term strategy* (Kumar, Devadas and Dhammika, 2021, p.21; Mehta and Kappal, 2024, p.4).

Employer branding is defined as an interdisciplinary *integration of branding, marketing and human resources* (Deepa and Baral, 2021, p.883; Kucherov *et al.*, 2022, p.127). Despite the wealth of research contributions in employer branding, the inter-disciplinary nature of the construct has not been fully explored (Deepa and Baral, 2019, p.78).

Employer branding is characterised as the strategic effort on the part of an organisation to *promote its EVP*, with the objective of *enhancing recruitment and retention*, thereby increasing the *value of human capital* (Backhaus and Tikoo, 2004, p.510). Employer branding means *profiling* a company as an attractive employer (Dineen and Allen, 2016, p.91).

In other words, employer branding is about the organisation's efforts in maintaining a *long-term relationship* with its employees (Deepa and Baral, 2019, p.78). Employer branding also helps to establish a psychological contract between both parties based on the perceived fulfilment of the brand promise (Deepa and Baral, 2021, p.884; Hoppe, 2018, p.452). It also encompasses motivation, employee engagement, and the retention of talent (Elegbe, 2018, p.266). Employer branding addresses actual and potential employees (Botha, Bussin and Swardt, 2011, p.4; Deepa and Baral, 2021, p.883; Theurer *et al.*, 2018, p.155).

It is challenging to quantify the direct impact of employer branding on organisational performance. However, there is a growing body of evidence suggesting that it can influence a company's resources and, subsequently, employee behaviour (Deepa and Baral, 2019, p.79).

Therefore, building and maintaining attractive employer brands is a sustainable investment in the future of the company (Eger *et al.*, 2019, p.521; Larkan, 2007, p.31; Olesch, 2012, p.70; Parment, 2013, p.119; Schmidt, 2007, p.17; Siebrecht, 2012, p.105). Employer branding is perceived as a *key part of the overall HR strategy* and therefore *penetrates most of HRM practices* (Kuchеров *et al.*, 2022, p.128) (see also Fig. 4).

Fig. 4: The EVP, as centre of employer branding, as key part of overall HR strategy

All *employer branding activities* are based on the *EVP* (Setiawati, 2019, p.148). Therefore, employer branding *needs an effective EVP* (Bronlet *et al.*, 2024, p.280).

2.2 EVP within employer branding

The EVP is considered to be *the starting point* for all employer branding activities (Backhaus and Tikoo, 2004, p.502; Behrends, Baur and Zierke, 2020, p.9; Nawaz *et al.*, 2020, pp.37–38). In employer branding, the organisation delivers its *brand promise, EVP*, to employees in terms of *EVP attributes* (Backhaus and Tikoo, 2004, p.506; Botha, Bussin and Swardt, 2011, p.3; Deepa and Baral, 2021, p.883). They are the job and organisational attributes such as employment offerings, working hours or location (Deepa and Baral, 2021, p.883).

“An EVP is an *exchange*” (Kowalski and Elliott, 2020, p.58). The EVP is “a *balance of ‘get’ and ‘give up’*” (Pucik *et al.*, 2017, p.181). It also includes a healthy balance of *current strengths* and *future aspirational stretch* (Aldrich and Pullman, 2019, p.323; Mosley, 2014, p.142). However, the EVP must be *authentic* (Behrends, Baur and Zierke, 2020, p.10). In order to maintain authenticity, it is incumbent upon the employer to *enhance their attributes* (Pattnaik and Misra, 2016, p.15), in order to align with the stated goals. This creates a reciprocal process that constantly improves the company as an employer (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5: EVP as central element within employer branding

In addition, the EVP forms the basis for all subsequent *communication activities* (Landes and Steiner, 2012, p.777). The EVP is the *centre point* of all employee communication and experience management (Guest, R., 2017,

p.199), as it serves as a *content compass* (Kremmel and Walter, 2021, p.510).

The EVP is the *centre* of employer branding (Chambers *et al.*, 1998, pp.50–52; Goncalves, 2017, p.232; Mehta and Kappal, 2024, p.4) (see Fig. 5), because the *creation of an employer brand* is to be achieved through the implementation of an EVP (Rideout, 2014, p.90). The objective is to cultivate an appealing employer brand in the perceptions of both existing and prospective employees (Kracht, 2007, p.270; Scherb, 2014, p.35; Stritzke, 2010, p.42; van Dam, 2006, p.13; Wiese, 2012, p.31). The subsequent section will address the critique of the EVP concept.

2.3 Criticism of the EVP concept

While poor communication undermines the effectiveness of the EVP, fundamental critiques are aimed at the concept's managerial ideology, ethical underpinnings, and inherent structural inconsistencies.

The EVP can be seen within the academic field of strategic human resource management (SHRM), which itself is defined as the interface between HRM and strategic management (Armstrong and Taylor, 2023, p.7), which has been heavily criticised for its philosophical stance.

A critical discussion of the EVP reveals three main areas of contention. Firstly, from an ideological standpoint, the EVP is criticised for being based on a unitarist worldview which assumes shared interests between management and employees, whilst consolidating managerial control (Nankervis *et al.*, 2020, p.19). According to this view, employee concerns are secondary and the EVP risks serving as a vehicle for narrow performance goals.

Area of Critique	Core Criticism of the EVP Concept	Counter-Arguments and Justification
Ideological and Political Stance	The EVP can be rooted in a unitarist ideology (Armstrong and Taylor, 2023, p.527; Collings, Wood and Szamosi, 2025, p.11) which assumes shared interests despite conflict being inherent in the employment relationship (Hook and Jenkins, 2019, p.42).	HRM, and thus the EVP, aims for a 'mutual gains' perspective (Wood, 2025, p.83), offering a win-win situation for both employee well-being and organisational performance (Wood, 2025, p.83).
	It reinforces managerial control by framing employee involvement "on the company's terms" (Fowler, 1987, p.3) and views employee concerns as a "secondary consideration" (Guest, D. E., 2017, p.22).	A pluralist view, deemed "more realistic" (Armstrong and Taylor, 2023, p.28), accepts that multiple interests exist and that cooperation remains a "worthwhile to explore" possibility (Wilkinson <i>et al.</i> , 2019, p.xxxi).
Ethical Concerns and Objectification	The instrumental use of EVP treats employees as 'resources' or 'commodities'. This approach violates "ethical duties owed to employees" (Nankervis <i>et al.</i> , 2020, p.24).	Ethical HRM requires managing based on principles of "respect for the individual, mutual respect, justice, procedural fairness and transparency" (Armstrong and Taylor, 2023, p.379). The EVP should facilitate "self-worth, dignity, psychological involvement, and identity for the individual" (Armstrong and Taylor, 2023, p.210).
	The managerial perspective may lead to the "intensification of work and their systematic exploitation" where profits are valued "before people" (Armstrong and Taylor, 2023, p.10).	The EVP's goal is fundamentally to ensure the "employee experience is a good one" (Armstrong and Taylor, 2023, p.248). Ethical practice is promoted when HR professionals act as the "conscience of employers" (Marchington <i>et al.</i> , 2021, p.156).
Conceptual and Structural Limitations	The design of the EVP, particularly its 'total reward' structure (Dubey and Rana, 2021, p.95), can be used to "shift risk from employer to employee" (Brown, 2019, p.4), undermining fairness.	The EVP is necessary for "differentiation from competitors" (Lippold, 2019, p.121) by establishing a unique employer brand identity (Güntürkün, Haumann and Lukaszcyk, 2015, p.65).
	EVP suffers from the 'black box' problem (Wright, Gardner and Moynihan, 2003, p.21), lacking "conclusive and causal evidence" linking EVP practices to performance (Purcell, 2014, p.248).	Decision-making must be evidence-based (Andresen, 2015, p.6; Rousseau and Barends, 2011, p.221), and HRM research is continually improving the measurement of the link between HR practices and positive outcomes (Wilkinson <i>et al.</i> , 2019, p.xxxv).

Tab. 2: Criticism on the EVP concept and counter-arguments

However, counterarguments suggest that pluralism, which enables a more realistic recognition of different interests, can also be implemented in the EVP if it is geared toward a perspective of 'mutual benefits'. In this way, employee well-being and company performance can go hand in hand (van de Voorde, Kilroy and Peccei, 2025, p.427; Wood, 2025, p.83). This perspective suggests that HRM practices should provide benefits for employees, particularly in terms of well-being, while simultaneously increasing organisational performance, creating a "win-win situation for both parties" (van de Voorde, Kilroy and Peccei, 2025, p.427).

Secondly, ethical critiques emphasise the risk of treating employees as expendable resources, raising concerns about commodification and exploitation. EVP criticisms often relate to a lack of authenticity. This is addressed by the principle of “delivering the deal” (Armstrong and Taylor, 2023, p.461), meaning management must keep its word and act fairly, justly, and consistently (Armstrong and Taylor, 2023, p.461). When pay and reward systems are perceived to be legitimate, employee motivation improves (Bassett-Jones, 2023, p.147). However, when grounded in fairness, respect and transparency, the EVP can enhance dignity, identity and the overall employee experience (Armstrong and Taylor, 2023, p.299).

Finally, structural criticisms emphasise weaknesses in the EVP’s total reward model, particularly risk-shifting and the lack of causal evidence linking EVP practices to performance. These can be mitigated through effective implementation practices, stakeholder engagement and the adoption of evidence-based HR models, such as AMO (ability, motivation, opportunity). These models provide mechanisms for linking the EVP to performance (Boxall *et al.*, 2022, pp.180,201). However, proponents argue that the EVP remains essential for employer differentiation and that ongoing empirical research continues to strengthen its legitimacy (Purcell, 2014, p.251). Tab. 2 summarises all points of criticism and counterarguments.

In conclusion, the EVP must be implemented with critical consideration: When properly aligned, the EVP functions not merely as a managerial signal, but as an authentic and negotiated employment deal that fosters trust and credibility, and differentiates the organisation in competitive labour markets (Dubey and Rana, 2021, p.88; Mosley, 2014, p.142). Thus, its enduring value lies in reconciling strategic differentiation with employee voice, ethical integrity, and mutual gains.

2.4 EVP within HRM, organisational theory and marketing

The EVP has emerged at the intersection of HRM, organisational theory, and marketing. It serves as a strategic and symbolic mechanism in the employment relationship. From an HRM standpoint, the EVP aligns talent management with corporate strategy, underpinning critical practices such as recruitment, retention, and reward (Binder, 2016, p.408; Dessain, 2016, pp.4–5; Lane, 2016, p.41). Organisational theory enriches this perspective by situating the EVP within broader cultural, identity-based and institutional legitimacy frameworks (Schreyögg and Geiger, 2024, pp.7–9). Meanwhile, marketing provides conceptual and methodological tools to frame the EVP as a differentiated and credible brand promise that must resonate with internal and external stakeholders (Kotler *et al.*, 2019, p.21; Kotler *et al.*, 2020, pp.45, 259). Examining the EVP through these three lenses reveals its dual nature as a managerial strategy and a social construct that fosters organisational distinctiveness and legitimacy in competitive labour markets.

1. The employment relationship as a power relation

According to resource dependence theory, power in an employment relationship is determined by how critical the resources controlled by each party are (Pfeffer and Davis-Blake, 1987, pp.437–455). Historically, drawing on Marxian political economy, employers held structural power through the exclusive ownership of the means of production and capital (Hyman, 1975, p.23; Marx, 2024, p.576). However, as knowledge has become the critical resource, the locus of power has shifted. As Trost (2020, p.62) notes, the increasing scarcity of knowledge has led to a “reversal of dependency relationships”, whereby “the employee is no longer dependent on the company, but vice versa”.

In this context, the EVP functions as a mechanism to manage this dependency. When talent becomes scarce and critical, employees with differentiated human capital find themselves in a “strong bargaining position relative to the organization” (Morris, Shenkar and Mackey, 2019, p.115). Consequently,

organisations are forced to negotiate terms rather than dictate them, as highly skilled workers can effectively claim exclusive access to the solutions required for business success (Kispal-Vitai and Wood, 2025, p.258).

2. Asymmetry and the psychological contract

Despite the shift towards employee-centricity, the employment relationship retains an inherent asymmetry, which is defined by its *indeterminacy* (Boxall *et al.*, 2022, p.22). Unlike a commercial sales contract, the employment contract is “inherently incomplete” because it involves the sale of labour power (the capacity to work) rather than a specific quantum of work effort (Boxall *et al.*, 2022, p.22). Employers face the “implacable dilemma” of converting potential capacity to labour (labour power) into productive work (Klerck, 2025, p.326). The EVP is a strategic tool that can help to bridge this gap by shaping the psychological contract (see section 1.1.4, p.7), which is defined as a “*unwritten expectations* that operate between employees and managers” (Rousseau, 1989, p.126).

This shift in market power necessitates a change in managerial strategy. As employers can no longer rely on coercion or financial dependency alone, they find themselves resorting to *ideological control*. As noted by critical theorists, the EVP functions as a mechanism of *soft power* or hegemony. By shifting from direct control to *responsible autonomy*, employers attempt to harness employees’ loyalty to the firm’s ideals ideologically (Friedman, 1977, p.6; Johnson and Szamosi, 2025, p.40). Through the EVP, the organisation seeks to align employees’ identities with corporate goals, thereby manufacturing consent.

3. Dynamics of the deal

Consequently, the EVP reflects the explicit employer offer of the presumed negotiation of these power relations. It attempts to transform the potential conflicts of interest inherent in the pluralist view, where conflict is viewed as a rational result of divergent interests (Budd and Bhawe, 2019, pp.46–49), into a mutually beneficial exchange akin to the mutual gains perspective. This perspective proposes that employment policies should produce benefits for

both employees (well-being/security) and organisations (performance) (Kochan and Osterman, 1994, p.46). By articulating a compelling value proposition, the employer attempts to secure not just the employee’s physical presence, but also their *discretionary effort* (Armstrong and Taylor, 2023, p.211), thereby stabilising the power equilibrium in a volatile labour market.

Therefore, the EVP is not merely theorised as a marketing slogan, but as a strategic management technology designed to reduce the *indeterminacy* of the labour contract by aligning employee volition with organisational goals (Boxall *et al.*, 2022, p.22).

2.4.1 Strategic HRM and reward strategy

To understand the strategic function of the EVP within organisational theory, it is necessary to distinguish between two competing views of the employment relationship: transaction cost economics (TCE) and the resource-based view (RBV).

dimension	Transaction Cost Economics (TCE)	Resource-Based View (RBV)
view of employee	cost factor: employees are viewed as actors with <i>bounded rationality</i> who may act opportunistically. The focus is on the costs associated with the exchange relationship (Williamson, 1975, pp.63–64).	strategic asset: human capital is viewed as a vital source of sustained competitive advantage because valuable talent is scarce, inimitable and non-substitutable (Barney, 1991, p.116).
economic logic	minimise transaction costs: the organisational objective is to minimise labour costs and the associated costs of monitoring and controlling the exchange (Lazarova and Reichel, 2021, p.585).	maximise value creation: the objective is to treat human capital as an asset that creates value (Paauwe and Farndale, 2017, p.103).
strategic focus	generic / standardised: the relationship is purely transactional. The strategic impulse is to reduce costs rather than invest in a unique proposition (Stock-Homburg and Groß, 2019, pp.59–61).	specific / unique (inimitable): the strategy focuses on attracting specific human capital to create a “human resource advantage” that is difficult for competitors to replicate (Boxall, 1996, p.67).

Tab. 3: Comparison of transaction cost economics (TCE) and the resource-based view (RBV) in the context of EVP

To clarify the divergent strategic rationales underlying the employment relationship, Tab. 3 contrasts the TCE logic with the RBV logic. This juxtaposition highlights why the EVP is inherently aligned with the latter: while TCE treats labour as a cost to be contained, RBV treats it as a unique asset to be leveraged.

Strategic alignment: from universalism to contingency

While the resource-based view provides the rationale for the existence of an EVP – to secure valuable human capital – it does not dictate its specific content. In the wider debate about HRM strategy options, particularly between *Best Practice* (universalism) and *Best Fit* (contingency), the development of an EVP is firmly aligned with the contingency approach.

The *best practice* perspective assumes that a standard set of superior HR practices exists that will improve performance in any organisation. However, this research argues that the EVP must follow a *best fit* logic. This approach posits that, in order to yield a sustainable competitive advantage, the EVP cannot simply replicate generic market standards, but must instead be vertically aligned with the organisation's specific strategic goals and unique cultural context (Gerhart and Weller, 2019, p.226).

This theoretical distinction is crucial as it underpins the subsequent empirical findings (see chapter 4, p.134) that a robust EVP must be *specific* (Requirement H7) and grounded in the organisation's unique strategy (Requirement A19) and structure (Requirement A20). This ensures that the EVP is *ownable* (Requirement C8) rather than interchangeable.

Although the content of the EVP must follow a *best fit* logic to ensure distinctiveness, the process of developing it requires a rigorous *best practice* framework to ensure validity.

Theorising reward strategy: The EVP as total reward

The operational mechanics of the EVP are best understood through the theory of total reward. This holistic approach moves beyond simple remuneration to integrate the financial (transactional) and non-financial (relational) aspects of work into a cohesive package (Armstrong and Taylor, 2023, p.411).

- The EVP as *manifestation*: The EVP serves as the visible manifestation and communication of the total reward strategy. It clarifies the *give and get* of the employment deal by articulating what the organisation expects and what it offers in return (Dubey and Rana, 2021, pp.86–87).
- The *composition*: A robust EVP combines extrinsic financial rewards with intrinsic relational elements. This includes traditional remuneration (transactional rewards such as pay and benefits), as well as intangible factors such as learning and development, organisational culture, and the nature of the work itself (Nankervis *et al.*, 2020, pp.354–356). The EVP should encompass both tangible and intangible rewards, capturing what an employee values in the employment relationship and serving as a counterweight to the required contributions (Dubey and Rana, 2021, p.94; Hook and Jenkins, 2019, p.348).

The mechanistic logic: Incentive-Contribution Theory

These theoretical pillars provide the functional logic for the EVP. According to this theory, the stability of the employment relationship depends on the balance between the *contributions* provided by the employee (e.g. effort and loyalty) and the *inducements* offered by the employer (March and Simon, 1958).

The *incentive contribution theory* (Barnard, 1968, p.253; Barnard, 1970, pp.122–123; March and Simon, 1993, p.103) deals with the decision-making behaviour of both the potential employee and the employer with regard to joint cooperation (Barnard, 1970, pp.122–123; Berthel and Becker, 2017, pp.53–57; Holtbrügge, 2022, pp.19–20; Jung, 2017, pp.404–405; Kniessel, 2014, p.34; March and Simon, 1993, p.103; Scholz, 2014, p.113; Simon, 1997, p.140). This concept is also referred to as inducement-contribution

theory or balance (Atchison and Lefferts, 1972, p.61; Lee *et al.*, 2011, p.203; Powell, 2024, p.122).

Both sides make their decision by assessing a conceivable exchange relationship (Simon *et al.*, 1995, p.141). Employers are willing to provide benefits for employees, called incentives in the model, if they receive adequate compensation in the form of employee contributions (Atchison and Lefferts, 1972, p.54; Coleman, 1992, p.137; March and Simon, 1958, p.93; Snell and Dean, 1994, p.1111; Strother, 1976, p.19; Tosi and Gomez-Mejia, 1989, p.184).

On the other side, employees and potential employees weigh up too (Lynch, Eisenberger and Armeli, 1999, p.467; Simon *et al.*, 1995, p.141). They are willing to provide contributions to an employer if they receive adequate compensation, i.e. incentives, from the employer (Coleman, 1992, p.137; Küpper and Felsch, 2000, p.63; March and Simon, 1993, p.104; Simon *et al.*, 1995, p.146).

Fig. 6: The employment deal illustrated using the elements of the (extended) incentive contribution theory (Wölki, 2020, p.132)

The assessment of incentives and contributions by employees is based on individual norms and expectations (Fig. 6). Thus, the incentive contribution theory focuses on the *individual motivation structure* (Menne, 2000, p.174).

Barnard identifies the incentives of being positive or negative (Barnard, 1938, p.140). The classical *incentive contribution theory* presumes, at least indirectly, that the contributions are received positively. Nevertheless, this may not be the case, as every human being possesses both positive and negative attributes, and this is similarly true of employees. Therefore, the model needs to be *extended* to include *negative perception of the employee benefits: contributions*.

This model extension is crucial, because the employers will also factor in the negative aspects in their calculations. Therefore, for both sides we need to take positive and negative benefits into account, being the own benefits that are provided and negative benefits from the other side (as a result: the double arrows also on the employee side in Fig. 6. Hence the negative received benefits need to be compensated too (Wölki, 2020, p.132).

Hence, the incentives and contributions can be perceived as either positive or negative by the recipient (see Tab. 4).

recipient	benefit (originator)	perception by recipient	examples
employee	incentives (employer)	positive	salary / contacts / bonus / good location / fun at work / reputation / T&D
		negative	bad location / shift work / boring colleagues / cut-throat society
	contribution (employee)	positive	something to do / joy of working / private social recognition
		negative	working hours / physical work / stress
employer	contribution (employee)	positive	labour and manpower / ideas creativity / contribution to culture and community
		negative	mobbing / bad influence on culture / silo mentality
	incentives (employer)	positive	positive reputation by incentives (e.g. kindergarten, bonus, gadgets)
		negative	wage and salary / non-wage labour costs / recreation facilities

Tab. 4: Positive and negative perception of incentives and contributions

This extension of the incentive contribution theory is supported by the *relative deprivation theory* (Crosby, 1984, pp.53–93; Crosby and Gonzalez-Intal, 1984), and basically the *social exchange theory* (Blau, 1964, pp.193–206; Gouldner, 1960, pp.161–178; Homans, 1958, pp.597–606).

An interaction relationship is maintained as long as both parties mutually benefit – the guiding *principle of gratification* according to the incentive contribution theory (Atchison and Lefferts, 1972, p.54; Foscht, Swoboda and Schramm-Klein, 2017, p.318). Employers show commitment and honour employees through the rewards and benefits they provide, while employees show their commitment by doing what their job requires and going the extra mile for their employer (Lee *et al.*, 2011, p.206).

Following a power shift in the labour markets (see section 1.1.2, p.3) – employers must increasingly consider both perspectives. Ultimately, employers must ensure that the employee benefits from the relationship. This way, the employer can maintain a balance of incentives and contributions for the employees (Isomura, 2021, p.21).

Thus, the EVP is not just a marketing slogan; it is the strategic communication of a total reward package designed to tip the incentive-contribution balance in favour of the organisation. It ensures that the incentives offered to a person are equal to or greater than the contributions provided (Stock-Homburg and Groß, 2019, p.78), thereby satisfying the specific needs of the target talent pool and helping the organisation to create a proposition that makes employees “want to work for and stay with” the business (Armstrong and Taylor, 2023, p.248).

This theoretical foundation dictates that a robust EVP development process must analyse both the *inducements* (what the employer offers – Requirement A17) and the *contributions* (what is expected – Requirement A18) in order to ensure that the proposition is a viable economic and social contract.

2.4.2 Psychological foundations: beyond the transaction

While the incentive-contribution theory provides a robust framework for understanding the employment relationship as a rational economic exchange, or *deal*, it is insufficient for fully explaining the complexities of employee behaviour in the modern workplace. Viewing the EVP solely as a transactional balance sheet of incentives and contributions can reduce employees to rational economic actors and overlook the intrinsic drivers of human behaviour.

In order to understand how the EVP influences employee behaviour, moving beyond simple retention (staying for the deal) towards genuine engagement (discretionary effort), the analysis must be expanded beyond economic exchange models. Motivation is fundamentally defined as a force that energises, directs and maintains behaviour (Steers and Porter, 1975, p.22). This definition shifts the analytical focus from viewing the EVP as a contractual obligation to viewing it as a driver of intrinsic motivation. Therefore, the economic basis of the *deal* must be supplemented by psychological motivation theories, particularly Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory and Self-Determination Theory (SDT).

Hygiene factors versus motivators

Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory (Herzberg, 1966, p.91) is a useful framework for categorising EVP attributes, as it distinguishes between the *deal* and the *experience*. It distinguishes between *hygiene factors* (e.g. salary and working conditions), which prevent dissatisfaction, and *motivators* (e.g. recognition and responsibility), which generate intrinsic motivation. When applied to the EVP, this theory dictates a dual structural requirement: the proposition must ensure robust hygiene factors to mitigate attrition (retention), while also offering distinct motivators to stimulate discretionary effort (engagement).

Self-Determination Theory (SDT)

Furthermore, SDT posits that sustainable motivation is rooted in the satisfaction of three fundamental psychological needs (Ryan and Deci, 2020, p.1).

This framework offers a lens to understand how employees construct value from the intangible elements of the EVP:

- *Competence*: The need to feel effective and overcome challenges is critical to the importance of EVP attributes related to professional development and *career growth* (Requirement A17). This validates why experts emphasise learning opportunities as a key driver of attraction.
- *Relatedness*: The desire to feel connected to others is the psychological driver behind the importance of corporate culture (Requirement A10) and the need for a sense of belonging.
- *Autonomy*: The desire to regulate one's own actions highlights the growing importance of flexible working models and empowerment within the EVP strategy (Requirement A12: Leadership Behaviour).

Consequently, a robust EVP is not merely theorised as a marketing message, but as an environment designed to support these needs, thereby fostering meaning and growth (Requirement A21: Purpose/Mission).

2.4.3 The disciplinary formation of the EVP

The EVP is not merely a practical tool; it represents a theoretical convergence where the boundaries between HRM, marketing, and organisational theory (OT) become permeable. To understand the disciplinary formation of the EVP, it is necessary to theorise the interrelationships between these fields not as separate silos, but as a dynamic triad of tension and collaboration.

1. The marketisation of HRM

The emergence of the EVP signifies the 'marketisation' of the HR domain. Theoretically, this marks a transition from administrative personnel management to "internal marketing", where jobs are conceptualised as products and employees as customers (Berthon, Ewing and Hah, 2005, p.151). Marketing provides the instrumental logic necessary to manage the power shift in the labour market described in section 1.1.1, p.2. HR professionals now adopt

the logic of segmentation: rather than a one-size-fits-all approach, organisations must create an employee experience that appeals to different needs, effectively treating staff as “internal customers” (Torrington *et al.*, 2020, p.15).

2. Organisational theory as the anchor

While marketing provides the form (the promise), organisational theory provides the substance (the reality). Without OT, the application of marketing to HR risks becoming superficial *spin*. Theories of organisational identity and culture ensure that marketing promises are grounded in the firm’s sociological reality. As Schein notes, organisational culture encompasses the shared assumptions that guide behaviour (1985, pp.18–21). The EVP must therefore capture the “quintessence of the organization” (Dubey and Rana, 2021, p.89) to ensure validity. If the brand promise is unfulfilled in the eyes of the employees, it creates a breach in the psychological contract, leading to cynicism rather than engagement (Rousseau and Rousseau, 1995, p.215).

3. The EVP as a *boundary object*

Consequently, the EVP is theorised here as a “boundary object” (Star and Griesemer, 1989, p.393). It acts as a translation mechanism that sits between these distinct professional worlds. It forces the functional logic of HRM (retention, reward, and systems) to align with the communicative logic of marketing (attraction, reputation, and differentiation). This symbiosis is constrained by the cultural logic of organisational theory (identity and legitimacy). Ultimately, the EVP is the umbrella construct that forces *brand alignment* – ensuring that HR policies and practices support, rather than contradict, the organisation’s external brand promise (Noe *et al.*, 2022, p.278).

Fig. 7: The Disciplinary formation of the EVP as a boundary object

Fig. 7 illustrates the theoretical positioning of the EVP. The EVP acts as a translation mechanism at the centre, aligning the functional aspects of the *deal* with the *brand's communication promises*.

Conclusion: section 2.4

Therefore, the EVP is theorised as a hybrid management construct. It recognises the strategic necessity for HRM to move beyond simple transactional exchanges – the *deal* – and engage in the creation of symbolic value through the *brand*. This theoretical fusion is essential because, as established in the pragmatist epistemology of this thesis (section 3.1.3, p.85), the contemporary employment relationship is no longer merely a financial transaction, but a relational bond involving emotional attachments and identity.

The unique field of interdisciplinary convergence

The preceding analysis demonstrates that the EVP cannot be adequately theorised within the silos of a single discipline.

- HRM provides the strategic alignment and the mechanism of the *psychological contract* (Nankervis *et al.*, 2020, p.360), yet often lacks the tools for external differentiation.

- Marketing contributes the essential rigour of *customer centricity* (Holbeche, 2022, p.416; Wölki, 2025, pp.2–3) and *brand equity* (Mosley, 2014, p.13), but risks creating *marketing wash* if detached from internal reality.
- Organisational theory ensures *legitimacy* (Meyer and Rowan, 1977, p.353) and grounds the proposition in the *institutionalised competence* of the organisation (Meuser and Nagel, 2016, p.345).

Therefore, the specific field of this thesis is defined as the interdisciplinary synthesis of these three domains. By treating the EVP as a multidimensional construct, this research moves beyond the administrative view of HR. It establishes a framework where the EVP functions as a strategic integrator: it uses marketing techniques to make the HR offer attractive, while using organisational theory to ensure that the offer is authentic and sustainable (Backhaus and Tikoo, 2004, p.503; Reis, Braga and Trullen, 2017, p.1963). This synthesis constitutes the unique theoretical territory of this study.

The following section will examine the employer brand.

2.5 Excursus: Employer brand

Each company has an employer brand at the latest when it employs employees. The crucial question is how consciously the company, as an employer, is involved in shaping it (Backhaus, 2016, p.193; Näppä, Ek Styvén and Foster, 2023, p.75). The concept of the employer brand draws upon marketing theory on brand image to propose that organisations can be associated with an employer brand comprising individuals' perceptions of the distinctive, central, and enduring aspects of the organisation as a place of work (Dineen and Allen, 2016, p.91).

The employer brand, understood here as the employer branding image, bundles all the characteristics that characterise the *product* 'work' in the

respective company (Lukasczyk, 2012a, p.13). The employer image is therefore the *perception* of the company *by employees* with regard to the characteristics that reflect its *attractiveness* as an employer. One can speak of an unmistakable image that is firmly anchored in people's minds (Kriegler, 2022, p.42).

The employer brand is a melange of the *reputation* of the company as an *employer* and the reputation of the *organisation in general*. The latter includes how it does business, the quality of its products or services, its core values as revealed by its actions, and how and why it is successful are also important (Armstrong and Taylor, 2023, p.248). This represents the connection to the corporate brand and product brands. These brands could also have a brand value proposition, but in this case it would be towards customers (Wölki, Gibb and Pfahler, 2024, p.65).

2.6 Tasks of EVPs

The EVP has the following three tasks: (1) *attract* potential employees to the organisation, (2) *retain* those won, and (3) *engage* those won, even reinvigorate disenchanted employees (Bronlet *et al.*, 2024, p.280; Dubey and Rana, 2021, p.88; Green, 2019, p.101; Reddy, 2017, p.36; Sparrow and Makram, 2015a, p.252; Staniec and Kalińska-Kula, 2021, p.37).

The *engagement* is important so that the employees are satisfied with their jobs, committed and therefore productive: *create value* (Deepa and Baral, 2019, p.79; Gilani and Cunningham, 2017, p.245; Heger, 2007, p.121; Phungula, Dhanpat and Braine, 2022, p.47; Sahoo and Srivastava, 2024, 1298).

The EVP should list out the central reasons that individuals will select to *commit themselves to an organisation* (Alloush, 2020, p.2). A compelling EVP can stimulate enthusiasm and commitment among employees, fostering a sense

of pride and loyalty towards the organisation. This, in turn, can lead to enhanced levels of *motivation* and *productivity* daily (Elegbe, 2018, p.266).

The EVP is designed to guide employees' daily experiences (Green, 2019, p.101) with the objective of fostering *happiness*, as it is the most effective EVP. It is in the company's best interests to encourage happier workers (Reddy, 2017, p.36).

The EVP should be based on the reality of the day-to-day work within the organisation (Abbott, 2019, p.15; Green, 2019, p.101). Some companies promise more than they can deliver. This makes candidates feel dissatisfied. The perception must correspond to reality to improve the level of involvement of recruited employees (Bronlet *et al.*, 2024, p.280).

Psychological contract research emphasises that employee perceptions of inconsistencies in brand promise and reality can lead to a psychological contract violation, in turn, leading to *turnover* and *intention to quit* (Backhaus, 2016, p.195; Deepa and Baral, 2019, p.79; Morrison and Robinson, 1997, p.226).

Thus, the EVP also *describes* the *company's culture* to employees and prospective employees. It describes the *types of work*, the *environment* and the *people, tools, and processes*. The EVP is integrated into the company's *purpose* (McLean-Conner, 2015, p.18).

The EVP is a tool designed to showcase the employer's key competitive advantages and benefits within the context of the labour market (Kucherov *et al.*, 2022, p.135).

On the contrary, especially in the German literature, the EVP is compared to the unique selling proposition (USP) in marketing. It says that the EVP is:

- based on the USP of the product brand (Müller, Hubschmid-Vierheilig and Matt, 2022, p.8; Rose, 2013, p.63; Stähler and Apel, 2015, p.5),

- is similar to the USP (App, Merk and Büttgen, 2012, p.269; Heming, 2017, p.7),
- analogue to the USP (Gärtner, 2020, p.91),
- comparable to the USP in terms of its importance (Trost, 2009, p.16),
- is often derived from the USP in product management (Runkel, 2018, p.30),
- is the USP of the employer (Rose, 2013, p.65).

For clarification: if the competitive advantage is both absolute and objective, i.e. if it is based on functional characteristics or demonstrable, absolute advantages, it is referred to as a USP (Wölki, 2007, p.178). If there is a USP, then the company's own performance differs significantly from that of its competitors (Kreutzer, 2022, p.185). Whereas, if the competitive advantage is absolute and based on subjective added value, then it is referred to as a unique advertising proposition (UAP) or unique communication proposition (UCP) (Wölki, 2007, p.179).

Fig. 8: Transferring the USP and UAP from Marketing to HRM

Transferring those two to HRM (see Fig. 8), this results in employer USP and employer UAP (Wölki, Gibb and Pfahler, 2025, pp.361–363). The EVP, on the other hand, is a tool used to *highlight* the employer's key competitive advantages (Kucherov *et al.*, 2022, p.135), including any employer USPs and/or

employer UAPs, if applicable. This means that the EVP is clearly not the USP in employer branding.

The subsequent two sections are designed to establish the theoretical foundations for comprehending the concept of the EVP. The structure of the text is defined by the two elements of the acronym: the employer *E* in chapter 2.7, and the value proposition *VP* in chapter 2.8, p.41.

2.7 The *E* for employer in the acronym EVP

The *E* in EVP can be broken down in different ways, as the *E* in the acronym can stand for three different terms: *employee*, *employer* and *employment*. All three variants are mostly used synonymously (see the usage by author in appendix 1, p.292).

In this thesis the term *employer* value proposition shall be used. Following Kriegler, who suggested to look into branding for orientation: Just as the term *branding* always refers to its sender, e.g. corporate branding, product branding, employer branding. A *proposition* describes a special offer, a special advantage or a value proposition from the sender. A value proposition therefore refers to the promise made by a company, a product or an employer. That is why he advises to translate EVP as *employer* value proposition (Kriegler, 2022, p.192).

2.8 The *VP* for value proposition in the acronym EVP

The value proposition in marketing

A *value proposition* (*VP*) of a company is directed to the customers. This may be defined as an encapsulation of a strategic management decision regarding the identification of the elements which the company believes to be of

greatest value to its customers, and which the company is able to deliver in a manner that provides it with a competitive advantage (Rintamäki, Kuusela and Mitronen, 2007, p.624). It can thus be concluded that a VP represents an offer of a superior value package to a targeted customer base (Payne, Frow and Eggert, 2017, p.472), in other words: the key offerings (Greyser and Urde, 2019, p.84).

The value proposition (VP) is a concept used in *marketing* (Grönroos, 2009, p.353). Successful companies that are market leaders excel at the delivery of their proposition to their chosen customers. The key is a "tight, laser-like, focus" (Green, 2019, p.19).

The value proposition (VP) is a strategic tool employed by a company to convey its objective of providing value to customers. As "one of the most widely used terms in business" (Anderson, Narus and van Rossum, 2006, p.1), "the value proposition should be the firm's single most important organising principle" (Webster, 2002, p.58), given its pivotal role in value creation (Payne and Frow, 2005, p.170), and its significant implications for performance (Payne, Frow and Eggert, 2017, p.467).

In its capacity as a strategic instrument, the VP serves to direct the company in two distinct ways. In addition to communicating the potential for superior value creation to prospective customers, the VP also serves to summarise marketing strategy decisions and indicate implementation priorities for company actors (Eggert *et al.*, 2018, p.85; Grimes-Rose, Zboja and Laird, 2024, p.16).

Value Propositions (in general) refer to promises of "reciprocal value between providers and their *customers*" (Kowalkowski, 2011, p.277).

The value proposition in HR: EVP

As value propositions, EVPs represent an invitation from one party, here the employer to the other, here the employee, to engage in service (Chandler

and Lusch, 2015, p.17; Payne, Frow and Eggert, 2017, p.467), with the aim to create real value for both parties involved (Boukis, 2019, p.238; Payne, Frow and Eggert, 2017, p.486). The exchange of value between the individual and the employer in the employment relationship is known as the EVP (Schermerhorn, 2014, p.242).

These findings can be applied to the target group of employees and thus to EVP. The following constitutes the *initial working definition* of EVP in this thesis:

The EVP is a (slightly favourable) essence, in the form of key attributes offering an assertive competitive value package, that fulfils employee needs.

In examining the value inherent in the EVP, four distinct approaches emerge (see Tab. 5 and the respective authors in appendix 2, p.293).

EVP type	Content
EVP 1	Focusing on the offers of the employer
EVP 1a	Focusing on the offers of the employer as a competitive advantage
EVP 1b	Focusing on the offers of the employer as a uniqueness
EVP 2	Focusing on the offers and demands of the employer and so refer to the equity theory, the social exchange theory and the Incentive-contribution-combination.

Tab. 5: Four types of EVP definitions in the literature

The *first* approach defines the EVP by focusing on the *offerings* of the employer to attract the employees (EVP 1). So define Soeling/Ajeng Arsanti/Indriati the EVP as “the holistic sum of everything people experience and receive while part of a company” (Soeling, Ajeng Arsanti and Indriati, 2022, p.2). Mascarenhas: the EVP is “a set of traits and attributes” (Mascarenhas, 2019, pp.99–100). Further authors lend their support to this position (Armstrong and Taylor, 2023, p.248; Backhaus and Tikoo, 2004, p.502; Chambers *et al.*, 1998, p.46; Heger, 2007, p.122).

Fournier et al. include in the EVP also the goals of employer branding (2019, p.31). By that, "an EVP can be understood as a desired or ideal employer identity, i.e. how the company wants to be perceived by (potential) employees as an attractive employer" (Theurer *et al.*, 2018, p.166). Stahl et al. support this position (2009, p.105).

Two subgroups specify the offerings (EVP 1a and 1b):

- The second group of authors delineates the employer's *offerings* as a *competitive advantage* within the labour market (EVP 1a). Kucherov et al. say "... the EVP is developed to represent the employer's main competitive advantages and benefits" (Kucherov *et al.*, 2022, p.135). Other authors support this position (Kriegler, 2022, p.195; Künzel, 2013, p.51; Theys and Barkhuizen, 2022, p.3).
- The *third* group of authors enhance the competitive advantage to a *uniqueness* of the employer's *offers* on the labour market (EVP 1b). The EVP is for Mostafa "the unique set of attributes and benefits that will motivate target candidates to join a company and current employees to stay" (2022, p.2). This position is supported by other authors (Eger and Schrank, 2012, p.774; Ingham, 2006, p.21; Scholz, 2014, p.489).

The fourth group of authors focuses on the *offerings* and the *demands* of the employer (EVP 2) and refers thereby to the equity theory (Adams, 1963, pp.422–436, 1965, pp.267–299; Schermerhorn, 2014, p.322), the social exchange theory (Homans, 1958, pp.597–606), and the incentive-contribution-combination (see section 2.4.1, p.27). Dubey and Rana state the EVP "characterizes *the give* and *the get* among organization and employee" (Dubey and Rana, 2021, p.87). Additional scholars have also expressed concurrence with this viewpoint (Arasanmi and Krishna, 2019, p.388; Keohane, 2009, p.37; Lesenyeho, Barkhuizen and Schutte, 2018, p.3; Munsamy and Bosch Venter, 2009, p.187; Sartain and Schumann, 2006, p.77). In this thesis, the fourth group will be followed.

Subsequent to the determination of the fourth approach, the working definition can be adapted: the second working definition of EVP.

The EVP is a (slightly favourable) essence, of *the give and get*, in the form of key attributes offering an assertive competitive value package, that fulfils *employee and employer needs*.

To explain the decision for the fourth group, it is necessary to draw upon two theoretical pillars: The incentive contribution theory, which was outlined in section 2.4.1, p.27, establishes the fundamental logic of exchange. The Concept of Net Benefits will also be introduced in the following section. Together, these theories lend support to the fourth group.

2.8.1 The Concept of Net Benefits

As the second theory the *net benefit concept* from marketing / strategic management (Anderson, Narus and Narayandas, 2009, pp.6-8; Backhaus, 2006, p.7; Backhaus and Schneider, 2020, pp.55-61; Bauer *et al.*, 2016, p.113; Beutin, 2000, pp.12-31; Große-Oetringhaus, 1990, p.96; Plinke, 2000, pp.78-81; Zeithaml, 1988, p.14) is to be applied to HR management.

The model assumes that customers make their decision not only on the basis of the positive benefit of an offer, but also on the basis of the effort involved. This comparison results in the net benefit (Zeithaml, 1988, p.10). The new aspect – in utility theories – is represented by the consideration of negative utility, which represents the effort associated with a decision.

The goal in marketing is therefore to achieve a so-called customer advantage on the customer side. This is the case when the benefit that a customer

derives from the company's benefits offer is greater than the benefits that the customer has to provide in return (Große-Oetringhaus, 1990, p.96). This is a further development of Zeithaml's idea (Zeithaml, 1988, p.14).

This concept is now to be applied to the area of human resources, separated into employee and employer sides.

Applying the net benefit concept to HRM – employee side

Analogous to the extended incentive contribution theory, the model adopted here of the *employee net benefit concept* assumes that employees make their decision not only on the basis of the positive advantages of a job offer, incentives, but also on the basis of the associated effort involved: contributions. The *employee net benefit* is therefore to be understood as a weighing up of competing effects. As it was discussed above Tab. 4, p.31, four elements have to be taken into account from the employee side: positive own contributions + positive employer's incentives – negative own contributions – negative employer's incentives (Fig. 9).

The *positive employee net benefit* is normally a necessary condition for the offer of the employer in question to be considered relevant at all. If the net benefit is negative (*negative employee net benefit*), a contract is only signed if there are no better alternatives for the employee. In any case, the employee is not satisfied with this situation and will continue to look for alternatives.

Fig. 9: Employees' view: positive and negative employee net benefit (EENB)

Like in marketing (Beutin, 2000, pp.12-13), the employee benefit is therefore to be understood as a weighing up of competing effects.

Applying the net benefit concept to HRM – employer side

Similarly, an *employer net benefit* should be achieved on the other side. This is the case when the benefit that the employer derives from the employee's performance (contributions) is greater than the employer's own performance, in form of benefits / incentives, that the company has to provide in return to the employee (Fig. 10). As discussed before all four elements have to be taken into account for the employer: positive own incentives + positive employee's contributions - negative own incentives- negative employee's contributions.

On the employer side, a *positive employer net benefit* is normally a necessary condition for the offer to the employee in question. If the net benefit is *negative*, an offer will only be made, if there are no better alternatives for the employer. In any case, the employer is not satisfied with this situation and will continue to look for alternatives.

Fig. 10: Employers' view: positive and negative employer net benefit (ERNB)

Coming back to the EVP approaches (see Tab. 5, p.43): The fourth group of approaches (EVP 2), focusing on offers and demands, is followed due to its reference to the duality present in the two aforementioned theories.

The EVP comprises both the tangible and intangible elements of the *real* and *psychological contract* that the company establishes with its employees. It clearly spells out what the organisation brings to the table, what the employee brings to the table and what happens when they enter into a contract (Keohane, 2009, p.37).

In light of the aforementioned considerations, besides following EVP 2, it is thus proposed that the *third and final definition* of EVP is:

The EVP is a (slightly favourable) essence of *the give and get*, in the form of key attributes offering an assertive competitive value package, that fulfils *employee and employer needs*, visualising the *employee net benefit*.

The next two sections describe the give and get (offerings and demands) parts of the new definition.

2.8.2 Offerings of value within the EVP

The offerings can be characterised by the definition of the EVP from Edwards: “The presentation of the ‘package’ of reward features or employment advantages and benefits offered to employees [...] [this includes] organisational values, characteristics and attributes” (Edwards, 2010, p.2). The EVP comprises both financial and non-financial benefits for targeted employees (Biswas and Suar, 2016, p.58).

The benefits can be classified into three categories: functional, economic and psychological (Ambler and Barrow, 1996, p.187). These benefits are both tangible and intangible in nature (see some examples in Tab. 6) (Confetto *et al.*, 2023, p.123; Edwards and Edwards, 2013, p.33; Joo and McLean, 2006, p.244).

There is the potential for a significant number of benefits to be derived; however, the selected benefits should align with the distinctive and differentiating messages that are valuable (fulfil the needs) for the target group (Kuchеров *et al.*, 2022, p.135). This suggests that the benefits are subjective and may be perceived as either positive or negative by employees.

	tangible	intangible
functional	canteen / parking / public transport connectivity / onboarding process	opportunities / languages / contacts / health care / T&D / career opportunities / professional growth / health care / management improvement
economic	rewards / benefits / salary /	Perceived job security
psychological	comfort / well-being / culture / WLB	value congruence / culture / positive work environment / WLB / leadership / stability / consistency in leadership and strategy / culture dynamics / organisation performance / success / community service / progressing employee recognition and POS /

Tab. 6: Examples for EVP attributes – offers

The employees ‘get’ side, the value that the company offers, is more than simply remuneration, benefits and morale. In a similar manner to how certain customers are willing to pay a premium for a product that instils reliability or prestige, individuals frequently elect to accept a lower salary within a

company that offers a distinctive value that they place a high value on. These distinctive offerings may encompass challenging work, a high degree of autonomy, strong friendship and social bonds, learning opportunities, a reputable standing within the community, or an image of social responsibility (Pucik *et al.*, 2017, p.181)

Through the EVP, as a promise creates beliefs and expectations among employees (App, Merk and Büttgen, 2012, p.270).

2.8.3 Demands of value within the EVP

Looking at the demand side: The demands from the employer towards the employee are mostly perceived to be negative by the employee. However, this also is subjective, some demands can also be seen as a positive challenge.

As an employer, you can assume that your employees are aware of the demands of the job. To be fair to employees, you should mention any higher-than-usual demands for these jobs. If demands are lower than expected, present this as a positive. However, the EVP will usually have more positive than negative attributes.

It is possible that a number of the attributes on the offer side of the employer (see Tab. 6) may be perceived as either negative or failing to meet expectations of the employees. In some cases, this may result in a higher demand from the employees in question. To illustrate this point, consider the issue of inadequate canteen facilities. In such cases, employees may be required to bring their own food or pay for food ordered (more examples see Tab. 7).

The aspect of an EVP known as the employees' 'give up' side is frequently disregarded, despite the fact that it exhibits significant variation across different organisations. Employees relinquish certain aspects of their lives in

order to pursue a career. The willingness of talented individuals to align with expectations is contingent upon the perception of equitable compensation or value in return (Pucik *et al.*, 2017, pp.181–182).

	tangible	intangible
functional	Physical presence, physical (bodily) strain, poor ergonomics, no (or poor) canteen, no car parks, poor public transport connections, poor onboarding process, necessity to work overtime, observe the holiday ban	Obligation to be physically present, no occupational health management, lack of opportunities, demand of language or other skills (while lacking them), lack of support (T&D), no prospect of personal professional growth and career opportunities, no social interaction
economic	Expenses incurred in the course of one's employment, including costs associated with job-related investments (such as application fees and self-paid further training), travel to and from the place of work, work-related attire, and personal sustenance, as well as expenses borne by the company (such as those related to business travel), waiver of salary and rewards and benefits.	Lack of perceived job security
psychological	Mental stress, unpleasant work culture, shift work (especially night shifts), negative perceived work-life balance, lack of comfort and well-being at work.	Challenges in the job, dealing with people, no personal development, bullying, unpleasant colleagues, no recognition / attention (POS), poor company performance, poor reputation of the company, no alignment of corporate values with personal ones, unpleasant corporate culture, negative working environment, stress due to mismatch in work-life balance, poor leadership and strategic direction of the company, lack of diversity, no social commitment of the company, too little inclusion, no management improvement

Tab. 7: Examples for EVP attributes – demands

The exchange of value propositions should ultimately result in the creation of real value for both parties, which constitutes one of the key steps in the value creation process (Boukis, 2019, p.238; Chandler and Lusch, 2015, p.8; Pawar, Beltagui and Riedel, 2009, p.477). The employee experience (EX) is central to this (Bridger and Gannaway, 2024, p.53; Veldsman and van der Merwe, 2025, p.5).

2.9 Relevance of the EVP

A review of the EVP literature reveals the existence of both direct and indirect factors influencing the performance of the company.

The indirect influence is transmitted via the following channels:

- *recruiting performance* (Backhaus and Tikoo, 2004, p.510; Kucherov *et al.*, 2023, p.2124) the EVP *attracts* potential employees (Alloush, 2020, p.5; Botha, Bussin and Swardt, 2011, p.3; Bronlet *et al.*, 2024, p.280; Dubey and Rana, 2021, p.87; Gladka, Fedorova and Dohadailo, 2022, p.47; Kucherov *et al.*, 2022, p.127; Phungula, Dhanpat and Braine, 2022, p.48; Samoliuk *et al.*, 2022, p.62; Soeling, Ajeng Arsanti and Indriati, 2022, p.2) and raises their willingness to *join* (Theys and Barkhuizen, 2022, p.3),
- *employee performance / productivity* (Bronlet *et al.*, 2024, p.280; Phungula, Dhanpat and Braine, 2022, p.47; Staniec and Kalińska-Kula, 2021, p.38):
 - higher *motivation* (Reddy, 2017, p.34; Theurer *et al.*, 2018, p.159),
 - *employee engagement* (Dubey and Rana, 2021, p.88; Heger, 2007, p.121; Reddy, 2017, p.34; Sahoo and Srivastava, 2024, p.1298), even re-engaging disenchanted ones (Alloush, 2020, p.5),
 - *goal alignment* between employees and the company (Mandal and Krishnan, 2013, p.42) and heighten the emotional and intellectual connection (Setiawati, 2019, p.148),
 - providing a *sense of belonging* for the employees (Phungula, Dhanpat and Braine, 2022, p.47),
 - greater *employee dedication* (Dubey and Rana, 2021, p.88),
 - *aligning employees behind company purpose* (e.g. accelerate transition) (McLean-Conner, 2015, p.19),
 - *employee commitment* (Alloush, 2020, p.4; Arasanmi and Krishna, 2019, p.392; Dubey and Rana, 2021, p.88; Phungula, Dhanpat and Braine, 2022, p.47),
- *employee retention* (Backhaus and Tikoo, 2004, p.510; Bronlet *et al.*, 2024, p.289; Dubey and Rana, 2021, pp.86–87; Gilani and Cunningham, 2017, p.243; Gladka, Fedorova and Dohadailo, 2022, p.47; Heger, 2007, p.121; Phungula, Dhanpat and Braine, 2022, p.48; Staniec and Kalińska-Kula, 2021, p.38; Theurer *et al.*, 2018, p.159; Theys

and Barkhuizen, 2022, p.3) and employee loyalty (Phungula, Dhanpat and Braine, 2022, p.47; Sahoo and Srivastava, 2024, p.1298; Staniec and Kalińska-Kula, 2021, p.38), employee embeddedness (Mandal and Krishnan, 2013, p.42), employee satisfaction (Sahoo and Srivastava, 2024, p.1298), fit of personal characteristics of employees and the EVP (App, Merk and Büttgen, 2012, p.274), deepen the relationship (Kaplan and Norton, 2001, p.93),

- *workplace culture* (Backhaus and Tikoo, 2004, p.503; Heilmann, Saarenketo and Liikkanen, 2013, p.288): positive working environment (Bronlet *et al.*, 2024, p.280) and workplace happiness (Reddy, 2017, p.34),
- more *competitiveness*: better organisation of all business processes (Samoliuk *et al.*, 2022, p.62),
- *differentiating* from competition in labour markets (Confetto *et al.*, 2023, p.124; McLean-Conner, 2015, p.18) (which relevance was discussed in section 1.1.1, p.2), the EVP acts as a key differentiator from other employers (Bridger and Gannaway, 2024, p.52), even creating a competitive advantage on labour markets (Binu Raj, 2021, p.203; McLean-Conner, 2015, p.18; Samoliuk *et al.*, 2022, p.62),
- *aligning priorities* of the HR activities within the company (Alloush, 2020, p.5; Fox, 2012, p.42),
- *alignment of employee communication*: 'one voice' (McLean-Conner, 2015, p.18; Setiawati, 2019, p.148; Staniec and Kalińska-Kula, 2021, p.38),
- *consistency in messaging* and one *key message* (Backhaus and Tikoo, 2004, p.502; Kumar, Devadas and Dhammika, 2021, p.20),
- ensuring *real experience* (Green, 2019, p.101), and improving the employee experience (Armstrong and Taylor, 2023, p.411),
- *shaping and positioning the employer brand, building a profile* and creating a people brand (Alloush, 2020, p.5; Mascarenhas, 2019, pp.99–100; McLean-Conner, 2015, p.18; Mortensen and Edmondson, 2023, p.45; Reddy, 2017, p.36),

- creating *brand ambassadors* (employees and even ex-employees) (Reddy, 2017, p.35) and
- show *company's commitment* towards employees (Alloush, 2020, p.2; Deepa and Baral, 2019, p.80; Setiawati, 2019, p.142).

The direct influence is transmitted as follows:

- reducing the *recruitment costs* (Theys and Barkhuizen, 2022, p.3), however, no reward, extrinsic or intrinsic, is costless (Heneman, Judge and Kammeyer-Mueller, 2019, p.185),
- reducing *employee turnover* (Bronlet *et al.*, 2024, p.280). The implementation of an attractive EVP has the potential to reduce the compensation premiums required to attract qualified candidates, whilst simultaneously reducing the annual turnover rate by up to 70% (Kowalski and Elliott, 2020, p.59). The findings of Botha *et al.* (2011) indicated that organisations which attained a notable EVP rate and established metrics for evaluating outcomes exhibited a 20% reduction in employee turnover (Botha, Bussin and Swardt, 2011, p.9),
- reduction of *salary premiums* (Alloush, 2020, p.5; Dubey and Rana, 2021, p.88; Kowalski and Elliott, 2020, p.59) and
- risk *company's turnover*, when EVP is less competitive (Botha, Bussin and Swardt, 2011, p.3; Munsamy and Bosch Venter, 2009, p.187).

In addition, a study by the CEB Corporate Leadership Council across 40 countries and more than 22,000 employees found three benefits of a well-managed EVP: Benefit 1: Increases reach in the labour markets to 50% to attract passive candidates; benefit 2: Reduces the additional salary premiums required when hiring by 50%; and benefit 3: Reduces annual employee turnover by 69% (Corporate Executive Board, 2015, p.5).

In 2023, the main factor driving employees to consider or already leave is the search for a better work-life balance, cited by 39% of respondents. This is followed by insufficient compensation to keep up with the rising cost of living (36%). The third is a lack of opportunities for career progression, which

has prompted over a quarter of employees (28%) to seek alternative employment (randstad, 2023, p.35).

In light of these listed considerations and the link to labour market circumstances (see section 1.1.1, p.2), it can be asserted that the EVP is of significant relevance for the company in general. An EVP is more than human resource hype (Kowalski and Elliott, 2020, p.59). In the following section the EVP development shall be analysed.

2.10 Development process of the EVP

In order to transition from an intuitive to a systematic management approach, this section examines the process of creating an EVP. It outlines the fundamental tasks and provides a critical analysis of the process approaches found in existing literature. Furthermore, by identifying gaps in current employer branding processes, it introduces a new, extended EVP development process to ensure a more comprehensive methodology.

“Building the unique EVP becomes a crucial *challenge*” (Kucherov *et al.*, 2023, p.2127). With talent being a critical battleground for competitive advantage with customers, Green believes that more *focus* and *rigour* should be placed on creating a winning EVP (2019, p.101). The relevance of the development of the EVP is inextricably linked to the relevance of the EVP characteristics (see above). The question of processes in strategic management is central, as discussed by Teece, Pisano and Shuen: “the essence of competences and capabilities is embedded in organizational processes of one kind or another” (1997, p.518).

The formulation of the EVP is a conceptually *creative act*, but it must follow an overarching *strategic logic* (Kremmel and Walter, 2016, p.61). Trost calls finding the EVP the search for the *soul* of the company (Trost, 2013, p.38),

but the EVP must be employee-centred in order to be effective (Pawar and Charak, 2014, p.8).

Chambers et al. describe it in marketing terms: "Creating a winning employee value proposition means tailoring a company's 'brand' and 'products' – the jobs it has to offer – to appeal to the specific people it wants to find and keep. It also means paying what it takes to attract and retain strong performers (the 'price')" (1998, p.50).

Developing an EVP is considered a challenging process. However, studies show that a carefully developed EVP can be an effective *strategic tool* for recruiting personnel (Nawaz *et al.*, 2020, p.38). In contrast to this, there is a widespread practice in which the EVP is not clearly defined because something has been randomly selected as an EVP without a strategic basis (Veldsman and Pauw, 2018, p.78).

The aim of the following sections of this chapter is to contribute to a better understanding of the EVP development and to define practical requirements that can be used to systematically design the development process.

2.10.1 Tasks of EVP development process

The task of the EVP development process is obviously to develop an EVP for the company. Reddy sees the heart of developing an effective EVP in this question: "What would attract the best talent, motivate them to give their best at work and then make it worth their while to stick with the company without jumping ship?" (2017, p.35). Nevertheless, it is vital to acknowledge that the responsibility for fulfilling commitments lies with the employer (Bronlet *et al.*, 2024, p.281).

Though, the objective of attracting employees is twofold: firstly, to enhance the *commitment* of employees and *employee engagement*, and secondly, to

stimulate *active interest* in the company among relevant applicant groups (Armstrong and Taylor, 2023, p.248; Backhaus, 2004, p.120; Backhaus and Tikoo, 2004, p.510; Deepa and Baral, 2019, p.79; Dineen and Allen, 2016, p.91; Soeling, Ajeng Arsanti and Indriati, 2022, p.2; Tumasjan *et al.*, 2020, p.94).

2.10.2 EVP development process approaches

Only a few authors have looked at the EVP development process. Therefore, all those shall be presented here (listed by year).

Fox (2012) sees four steps in developing an EVP: (1) *Review*: Define a compelling and comprehensive package comprising culture, total remuneration and work experience, (2) *Gather Input*: Solicit input from key stakeholders: What employees perceive as valuable about their employment experience? (3) *Develop and test*: Develop the EVP brand. Do tests. (4) *Launch*: Communicate the EVP. Ensure that leaders live by it (Fox, 2012, p.42).

Pawar and Charak (2014) see three steps in developing an EVP: (a) the most vital step: selecting the attributes to include in the EVP, (b) building candidate awareness of the EVP, and (c) shaping candidate perceptions (Pawar and Charak, 2014, p.4).

McLean-Conner (2015): There are three steps involved in establishing an EVP. The first is to define the EVP. The second is to communicate. And the third is to refine the EVP to ensure sustainability and relevance (McLean-Conner, 2015, p.19).

Veldsman and Pauw (2018) see four phases in the EVP development process: Phase 1 is the research and gathering of insights from current organisational practices, current industry trends and competitors. Phase 2 includes EVP articulation and sense-checking: to ensure that the narrative is authentic,

coherent and believable (Veldsman and Pauw, 2018, p.82). Phase 3 is implementation. Phase 4 is monitoring and adjustment (Veldsman and Pauw, 2018, p.83).

For Green (2019) the creation of the EVP has four phases: (a) identifying the core themes and (b) trying to set the brand apart from the competition, (c) defining what needs to be changed or modified and creating a detailed plan to support the new EVP, and (d) testing and validating the new EVP with key stakeholders and the target group internally and externally before it is launched (Green, 2019, p.104).

Naz and Zahidi (2021) only focus on the identification of the needs of the target group: "Organizations need to identify the needs of the target group and create a unique employer value proposition (EVP) for them." (Naz and Zahidi, 2021, p.4).

McGuire and Brenner (2021) see the first phase as the core phase. It defines the target audiences, identifies and conducts meaningful research and develops strong insights to build the EVP (McGuire and Brenner, 2021, p.34). The second phase is the implementation strategy for the EVP across the employment lifecycle. The third phase activates the EVP through communication (McGuire and Brenner, 2021, p.35).

Petrov (2022) shows an example of a five-stage process: (1) put together a EVP project team, (2) define target group, (3) elaboration of the corporate values, (4) differentiation from the competition and (5) communicate the EVP (Petrov, 2022, pp.48–50). Only the points 2-4 refer to the content of the EVP development.

Bridger and Gannaway (2024) recommend starting the process with a research phase. The procurement of insight from employees enables a true understanding of your organisation's distinctive strengths as well as the current reality of the employee experience (EX). Gathering insights enables the

creation of a draft EVP, which can then be tested with employees and further refined (Bridger and Gannaway, 2024, p.53).

author \ phase	research	development	communication	controlling
Fox 2012	x	x	x	
Pawar and Charak 2014	x	x	x	
McLean 2015		x	x	x
Veldsman and Pauw 2018	x	x	x	x
Green 2019	x	x		
Naz and Zahidi 2021	x	x	x	
McGuire and Brenner 2021		x	x	
Petrov 2022	x	x	x	
Bridger and Gannaway 2024	x	x		

Tab. 8: Overview of the EVP development process phases

A comparison of the phases of the nine processes reveals that the majority of them encompass the themes of research, development, and communication (see Tab. 8, visualised in Fig. 11).

Fig. 11: Overview EVP development processes (#9)

It is beneficial to analyse the overall employer branding process, given that the development of the EVP constitutes an integrated element of this process. The establishment of a robust employer brand is not a fortuitous occurrence, nor is it a brief undertaking. Rather, it necessitates the implementation of a meticulous and systematic approach (Näppä, 2023, p.41).

2.10.3 Employer branding process

There are a number of sources available for the employer branding process. The emphasis shall be placed on the process orientation of the subject. Some literature provides a more comprehensive explanation of the framework and dependencies (Cascio and Graham, 2016, pp.186–187; Dubey and Rana,

2021, p.107; Imani, Dehghani and Amiri, 2020, p.176; Martin, 2009, p.254; Martin and Hetrick, 2009, p.295; Miles and Mangold, 2005, p.537; Theurer *et al.*, 2018, pp.156–157).

The goal is to find the quintessence of the process-orientated ones (Backhaus and Tikoo, 2004, p.503; Brast *et al.*, 2017, p.37; Buckesfeld, 2012, p.36; Heilmann, Saarenketo and Liikkanen, 2013, p.285; Immerschitt and Stumpf, 2019, p.49; Kriegler, 2022, pp.48–51; Lukasczyk, 2012b, pp.15–16; Näppä, Ek Styvén and Foster, 2023, p.77; Petkovic, 2008, p.182; Stock-Homburg and Groß, 2019, p.170; Stotz and Wedel-Klein, 2013, p.80; Theurer *et al.*, 2018, pp.166–167; Trost, 2013, pp.19–22; Wiese, 2012, p.40).

Author/phase	phase 1	phase 2	phase 3	phase 4	phase 5
Backhaus/Tikoo 2004	EVP development	external marketing	internal marketing		
Wiese 2005	planning	coordination	monitoring		
Petkovic 2008	situation analysis	planning level	action level	brand controlling	
Buckesfeld 2012	analysis	planning	realisation	brand monitoring	
Lukasczyk 2012	analysis	strategy	implementation	controlling	
Trost 2013	target group definition	analysis	strategy	realisation	
Stotz/Wedel-Klein 2013	analysis	planning	HR audit	realisation	evaluation
Heilmann et al. 2013	research	EVP definition	development of communication strategy	express EVP (words/images)	implementation and observation
Brast et al. 2017	analysis	EVP development	instrumentalisation and communication		
Stock-Homburg/Groß 2019	internal and external analyses	defining employer brand strategy	implementing employer brand	monitoring employer brand	
Immerschitt/Stumpf 2019	initialisation	problem analysis	strategy analysis	realisation analysis	evaluation
Kriegler 2022	set-up and analysis	strategy development	implementation	employer brand management	
new	situation analysis	planning	realisation	evaluation and optimisation	

Tab. 9: Overview phases of selected employer branding processes

Most of the employer branding processes in literature have four phases (see Tab. 9).

A review of the extant literature yielded the following sequence of steps: situation analysis, planning, realisation, and evaluation and optimisation. A combination of the sources resulted in the developed process presented here (Fig. 12).

Fig. 12: Newly developed employer branding process

Consequently, the resulting structure encompasses these foundational phases: situation analysis; planning; realisation; and evaluation and optimisation. This process is essential, as establishing a robust employer brand requires a meticulous and systematic approach rather than being a fortuitous or brief undertaking.

This overarching employer branding process provides the essential framework and context for developing the EVP, which constitutes an integral part of the wider employer branding strategy.

2.10.4 New EVP development process

At this point, a new EVP development process is presented. This step is regarded as a reaction to the necessity of introducing a so-called improvement phase. The reason for this is the reciprocal process between EVP and the employer attributes shown in Fig. 5, p.21. Thus, Green also defines a detailed plan within its third phase to support what needs to be modified (Green, 2019, p.104). Pattnaik and Misra conclude that the employer should also optimise their EVP attributes in the process (Pattnaik and Misra, 2016, p.15).

To emphasise the different aspects of the development phase, it is suggested that it be divided into the creation phase and the subsequent improvement phase. The communication phase and the controlling phase, which are already integrated in the employer branding process, are not considered in this new core process (see Fig. 13). Nevertheless, communication and controlling of the EVP are crucial to the success of the EVP.

Fig. 13: New EVP development process with explicit attribute optimisation phase

The new process is divided into four stages with three phases: (a) situation analysis, (b) development 1: EVP creation and (c) development 2: improvement attributes. The developed EVP is then integrated into the process to visualise this step. The integration of the EVP development process into the employer branding process is shown in Fig. 14.

Fig. 14 : EVP development process in the employer branding process

The requirements are now to be developed for the four stages: three core phases of the process and the EVP characteristics in order to be able to map the development process in a more structured way and also to be able to measure the developed EVPs against them.

2.11 Requirements for EVPs (state of research)

As mentioned before, requirements shall be understood in the idea of project management: requirements are derived primarily from the expectations of the stakeholders (Meyer and Reher, 2020, p.112). In the context of the thesis, the relevant parties include management, the HR department, and, indirectly, the employees. In human resources, the term 'requirements' is often used in connection with the requirements of the employer on the employee and vice versa. This is not the case in this work. In this thesis, it refers to the requirements for the development of EVPs and the EVP characteristics.

This section first details the systematic search and filter strategy employed across ten electronic databases to comprehensively gather all relevant academic literature pertaining to EVP requirements. This comprehensive review is summarised in section 2.11.2, which systematically distils and categorises the 27 theoretical requirements across the four phases of the newly established EVP development process. The final sub-section provides a critical reflection on the scope and integrity of these identified theoretical requirements.

2.11.1 Search and filter strategy

I conducted a comprehensive literature review for this study. I collected information using mainly ten electronic databases: emerald, ebsco, scopus, web of science, JSTOR, EconBiz, EconPapers, ProQuest, WISO and BASE.

The following systematic procedure was utilised for the literature search:

1. Database searching
2. Collection of all results (papers, articles, books etc.)
3. Elimination of duplicates
4. Screening of results, exclusion of unsuitable results
5. Assessment for eligibility, exclusion of unsuitable results
6. Inclusion of results in the study.

Search 1: 'EVP requirements', 'EVP requisites', 'EVP Anforderungen' and 'EVP Bedingungen'

The first search run used the following search string: EVP AND "value proposition" AND (requirements OR requisites OR Anforderungen OR Bedingungen). 'Anforderungen' and 'Bedingungen' are the German equivalents to requirements. The combination 'EVP AND "value proposition"' was chosen, as there are three different resolutions of the acronym EVP: employer or

employee or employment for the *E*. The ten databases found in total 700 results (see Fig. 15).

Fig. 15: Literature review flow chart 'requirements'

The 51 duplicates were then eliminated. The remaining 649 results were screened to exclude unsuitable results. In this case: 423. This number is relatively high, because there are many other resolutions of the acronym EVP, e.g.: epidural venous plexus, episcleral venous pressure, emotional value proposition, extended value proposition, executive vice president, or electronic vapor products.

Moreover, 'value proposition' is a term often used in marketing and strategic management, so as 'requirements'. These were often requirements related to the job, skill, position, role, or performance. However, also customer, service, quality or ethical requirements were found. The remaining 226 often mentioned the EVP in the sense of this work and also requirements (or requisites, Anforderungen, Bedingungen), but not in combination, so that 225 were also not helpful results. In the end one result was included.

Another attempt with the search string: "employer value proposition" OR "employee value proposition" OR "employment value proposition") AND (requirements OR requisites OR Anforderungen OR Bedingungen) brought similar results.

Search 2: 'EVP should'

The second search run used the following search strings: "EVP should" and the three long versions "employer value proposition should", "employee value proposition should", and "employment value proposition should". In some, mainly German databases (WISO and BASE) the 'should' was additionally replaced by the German 'sollte'. These searches in the ten databases found 99 results (see Fig. 16).

Fig. 16: Literature review flow chart 'should'

The duplicates were then eliminated (#8). The remaining 91 results were screened to exclude unsuitable results. In this case: 28. The remaining 63 were assessed; thereby, 15 were also not helpful results. In the end 48 results were included.

Search 3: 'EVP must'

The third search run used the following search strings: "EVP must" and the three long versions "employer value proposition must", "employee value proposition must", and "employment value proposition must". In some, mainly German databases (WISO and BASE) the 'must' was additionally replaced by the German 'muss'. This searches in the ten databases found 47 results (see Fig. 17).

Fig. 17: Literature review flow chart 'must'

The duplicates were then eliminated (#6). The remaining 41 results were screened to exclude unsuitable results. In this case: 20. The remaining 21 were assessed, after which a further 12 were excluded. In the end 9 results were included.

In total the systematic literature review brought 58 sources, 44 without duplicates. It was observed that the majority of these had only a limited number of results, i.e. requirements to offer. Taking into account only those that were numbered, the maximum number was seven requirements (see Tab. 10).

number of listed requirement IDs	source
7	Bridger and Gannaway, 2024
6	Alloush, 2020
5	Boukis, 2019
4	Hatum, 2010
3	Dubey and Rana, 2021
2	Abbott, 2019; Fox, 2012; Green, 2019; Keohane, 2014; Naz and Zahidi, 2021; Pawar and Charak, 2014.
1	Armstrong and Taylor, 2023; Backhaus and Tikoo, 2004; Botha, Bussin and Swardt, 2011; Bronlet et al., 2024; Deepa and Baral, 2019; Eribo and Andradi, 2024; Fournier et al., 2019; Heneman, Judge and Kammeyer-Mueller, 2019; Kristia, 2023; Kucherov et al., 2022; Lehmann, 2012; Mascarenhas, 2019; McLean-Conner, 2015; Mortensen and Edmondson, 2023; Pattnaik and Misra, 2016; Phungula, Dhanpat and Braine, 2022; Reddy, 2017; Setiawati, 2019; Veldsman and Van der Merwe, 2025.

Tab. 10: Number of listed requirements per source

Those results are analysed in the following section.

2.11.2 Systematic literature review: EVP Requirements

Out of the theory (identified above), the following requirements for the EVP can be distilled. The EVP requirements are categorised into four categories, corresponding to the three phases of the process (see Fig. 13, p.63): *EVP situation analysis*, *EVP development 1: creation*, *EVP development 2: optimisation* and the *EVP characteristics*.

Part 1: Situation analysis EVP

In this phase, a careful analysis of complexity takes place (Abbott, 2019, p.15), with the aim of identifying and categorising potential EVP attributes: (a) value-creating ones that add value for employees and are beneficial to them, (b) value-destroying ones that destroy value and are detrimental to employees and (c) value-neutral ones that have neither a positive nor

negative impact. In addition, an attempt is made to understand the role of the various interactions in the employee experience (EX) (Boukis, 2019, p.238).

With regard to the EVP situation analysis (S), the following performance-related requirements can be identified:

- The analysis should serve to (S1) identify the *needs* of the target group (Naz and Zahidi, 2021, p.4), (S2) determine the *preferences* of the employees and the causes of any discrepancies between the employees' wishes and the actual EVP (Alloush, 2020, p.5). In addition, insights should be gained into (S3) the current *experiences* of employees and, associated with this, into the gap between (S4) employees' *expectations* and experiences (Boukis, 2019, p.238; Bridger and Gannaway, 2024, p.53; Fox, 2012, p.42).
- The analysis should collect information about the company's (S5) *culture*, (S6) *values*, (S7) *management style*, (S8) *qualities of the current employees*, (S9) the company's *current image* and (S10) the *impression of product quality* (Backhaus and Tikoo, 2004, p.502; Bridger and Gannaway, 2024, p.53)
- The analysis should (S11) examine the (a) *requirements* of and (b) *benefits* for employees (Fox, 2012, p.42), as well as (S12) employees' perception of the *current EVP* (Boukis, 2019, p.238).

When analysing the situation, it is crucial to consider the *current* situation and the *desired target perspective* (Petrov, 2022, p.49).

Part 2: Development 1: Creation of the EVP

In the *first development phase*, a convincing and comprehensive offer for employees, the EVP, should be created (Fox, 2012, p.42). This offer describes what employees can expect from their commitment to the organisation. It should make both the advantages (value-adding attributes) and possible requirements or burdens (value-destroying attributes) transparent, thus

characterise the *give and take* between the organisation and employees (Dubey and Rana, 2021, p.87; Mosley, 2014, p.133; Pucik *et al.*, 2017, p.181).

The EVP should pursue the following goals: The primary objective is to attract potential employees, with a secondary focus on retaining and engaging those who have been recruited (Bronlet *et al.*, 2024, p.280; Dubey and Rana, 2021, p.88; Green, 2019, p.101; Reddy, 2017, p.36; Sparrow and Makram, 2015b, p.252; Staniec and Kalińska-Kula, 2021, p.37) and thus promote *satisfaction* (Reddy, 2017, p.36). The following performance-related requirements apply in the context of EVP creation (K):

- The EVP must be (K1) *employee-centred* (Heneman, Judge and Kammeyer-Mueller, 2019, p.605; Pawar and Charak, 2014, p.8), should be *attractive* and *valuable* (Kucherov *et al.*, 2022, p.135),
- in that it fulfils (K2) employee needs and being *relevant* (Dubey and Rana, 2021, p.86; Keohane, 2014, p.67; Pawar and Charak, 2014, p.6). Eribo and Andradi give a possible example of a sub-aspect when they state that the EVP should be harmonised with environmental, social and governance (ESG) priorities (Eribo and Andradi, 2024, p.55).
- The EVP should be (K3) a characterisation of *the quintessence* of the distinctive *overall workplace experience* (Botha, Bussin and Swardt, 2011, p.6), which in turn guides the daily *experiences* of employees (Green, 2019, p.101) and represents the *personality* of the organisation (Dubey and Rana, 2021, p.104),
- The EVP should (K4) ideally be linked to a *feeling* or *emotion* to encourage *associations* and facilitate *uptake* (Alloush, 2020, p.5; Hatum, 2010, p.39),
- The EVP should (K5) make employees *feel valued* (Phungula, Dhanpat and Braine, 2022, p.47), and express the company's *commitment* to them (Alloush, 2020, p.2; Deepa and Baral, 2019, p.80; Setiawati, 2019, p.142),
- The EVP should (K6) be able to assert itself in competition. Depending on the situation, this can mean *differentiation* (Alloush, 2020, p.5;

Hatum, 2010, p.39; Keohane, 2014, p.67) or even *uniqueness* (Bridger and Gannaway, 2024, p.53; Naz and Zahidi, 2021, p.4)

- The EVP should (K7) ensure *the design, positioning and development* of an *employer brand profile* (Alloush, 2020, p.5; Mascarenhas, 2019, pp.99–100; McLean-Conner, 2015, p.18; Mortensen and Edmondson, 2023, p.45; Reddy, 2017, p.36),
- The EVP should be (K8) *authentic and credible* (Fournier *et al.*, 2019, p.31) and (K9) *truthful* (Alloush, 2020, p.5; Hatum, 2010, p.39) and *real* (Abbott, 2019, p.15; Bronlet *et al.*, 2024, p.280; Green, 2019, p.101; Hatum, 2010, p.41; Kristia, 2023, p.298),
- The EVP should *be convincing* overall (K10) (Dubey and Rana, 2021, p.86).

The EVP creation should take the following factors into account:

- In principle, the *current situation* and the *target perspective* should be included in the consideration (Mosley, 2014, p.134; Petrov, 2022, p.49). The EVP should be based on the real current attributes of the employer, but also demonstrate ambition and aspiration (Baran, 2018, pp.47–48; Bridger and Gannaway, 2024, p.52). In addition, the EVP should take into account both sides, i.e. employers and employees (Boukis, 2019, p.238; Ulrich and Brockbank, 2005, p.202). Of course, the creation should take into account the results of the situation analysis.
- On the employee side, the *needs of employees* (Boukis, 2019, p.238; Ulrich and Brockbank, 2005, p.202) and the *employee experience* should be taken into account in the creation process (Bridger and Gannaway, 2024, p.53; Green, 2019, p.134).
- On the employer side, the EVP development should take the following factors into account:
 - *the strategic direction of the company* (Boukis, 2019, p.238; Ulrich and Brockbank, 2005, p.202),
 - the *brand promise* and the *value proposition* (Sousa and Ferreira, 2024, p.484) and the *corporate brand*, i.e. the reputation and image (Ployhart, Weekley and Dalzell, 2018, p.217),

- *the company's objectives* (Reddy, 2017, p.35) and thus also the company's *skill requirements* for employees, i.e. what is demanded of employees (Mosley, 2014, p.54),
 - *Employer branding* (Backhaus and Tikoo, 2004, p.502; Bronlet *et al.*, 2024, p.280; Kumar, Devadas and Dhammika, 2021, p.20; Sousa and Ferreira, 2024, p.484), which includes *employee communication* (McLean-Conner, 2015, p.18; Setiawati, 2019, p.148; Staniec and Kalińska-Kula, 2021, p.38) and the current employer branding tools,
 - the *corporate culture* (McLean-Conner, 2015, p.18; Neller, 2017, p.408) , and the company's *core values* (Mosley, 2014, p.33).
- The EVP should “endure in the long term” (Neller, 2017, p.408), but it must also be able to adapt to changes in the labour market and among employees. The EVP must therefore be continuously reviewed and developed (McLean-Conner, 2015, p.19).

The EVP should be *tested* and *validated* internally and externally with the target group prior to introduction (Green, 2019, p.104; Pawar and Charak, 2014, p.7). In order to do justice to changes in the labour markets and among employees, the EVP must be continuously reviewed and further developed (McLean-Conner, 2015, p.19).

The development of the EVP (both phases) is a conceptually *creative act* that must, however, follow an overarching strategic logic (Kremmel and Walter, 2016, p.61).

Part 3: The EVP characteristics (formalities)

This part covers formal requirements for the EVP. The EVP should contain a *clear* and *concrete* statement (Alloush, 2020, p.5; Confetto *et al.*, 2023, p.124; Hatum, 2010, p.41; Pawar and Charak, 2014, p.1). The following requirements are placed on the EVP characteristics (E):

- should be (F1) *simple* (Abbott, 2019, p.15) and therefore easy for every employee to understand,
- should (F2) also be *easy to pass on* (Boukis, 2019, p.238),
- should (F3) *express a lot with few words* (Lehmann, 2012, p.37),

- should (F4) be *measurable* (Boukis, 2019, p.238).

It is vital that the EVP considers both the *current* situation and the *target perspective* (Petrov, 2022, p.49).

Part 4: Development 2: Optimisation of employer attributes

The final phase is dedicated to the ambitious part of the newly developed EVP. The reality-ambition gap should be closed promptly and effectively. If the EVP does not correspond to everyday working life (Abbott, 2019, p.15; Green, 2019, p.101), then this contradicts the requirement for authenticity (K8). The EVP optimisation phase (O) represents a central requirement: the improvement of (O1) *EVP attributes* (Pattnaik and Misra, 2016, p.15), e.g. *improve* the employee experience (Armstrong and Taylor, 2023, p.411; Veldsman and van der Merwe, 2025, pp.8–9).

The optimisations should be based on the findings of the analysis and the EVP development phase, whereby employee centricity, brand profiling, competitive assertion and the reality-ambition gap are of particular relevance. In order to successfully implement the EVP improvement, it is essential always to evaluate it with the target group (Pawar and Charak, 2014, p.7). For example, the new office structure should be evaluated with employees. This approach enables internal and external validation to take place prior to implementation (Green, 2019, p.104; Mosley, 2014, p.158).

The analysis of the requirements for the EVP resulted in a total of 27 individual requirements (see Fig. 18). These enable systematic and structured EVP development and the resulting provision of optimised EVPs. All 27 and their literature sources are listed in appendix 3, p.294.

Fig. 18 : The 27 requirements for EVP development in theory, illustrated in the process

2.11.3 Reflection on the requirements for EVPs

This section briefly considers how the 27 theoretical requirements identified in section 2.11.2, p.69 address the research context and the critical objections raised in section 2.3, p.22 regarding the EVP concept.

(1) Response to the Power Shift and Unitarism: the theoretical framework offers an alternative approach to the critique of unitarism. By establishing requirements that explicitly mandate the analysis of employee needs (S1) and preferences (S2), the model theoretically enforces employee-centricity. It transforms the EVP from a management-imposed directive into a negotiated understanding, thereby acknowledging the power shift from employer to employee described in section 1.1.1, p.2.

(2) Response to ethical criticism: the requirements regarding authenticity (K8) and truthfulness (K9), as well as the optimisation of attributes (O1), serve as theoretical safeguards against criticism regarding 'marketing wash'. By structurally requiring the employer to close the 'reality-ambition gap' (O1), the framework protects the integrity of the psychological contract.

Conclusion: these 27 requirements represent a normative theoretical standard. Whether these safeguards are actually implemented in the commercial reality of EVP development – and thus whether the model holds up in practice – will be the subject of the empirical comparison and reflection in section 5.2 (see p.224).

Although this review adopts a structured approach to identifying existing models, the theoretical requirements are considered a basis for abductive comparisons with expert practices, rather than definitive truths (see section 3.1.4, p.88).

2.12 Conclusion: Requirements for EVPs

This chapter analysed the EVP, its central role within employer branding, and its tasks. The incentive contribution theory and the concept of net benefits were used to evaluate the EVP definitions. The relevance of the EVP was demonstrated, and a new EVP development process was established. Its role in the employer branding process was outlined.

A systematic literature review was conducted to analyse the requirements for EVPs, resulting in the identification of 27. In accordance with the newly developed EVP development process, they were categorised accordingly.

This chapter comprehensively explored the theoretical foundations of the EVP. The EVP is defined as a succinct crystallisation of what makes an organisation desirable, serving to attract, retain, and engage employees through a 'give and get' dynamic. Drawing on incentive contribution theory and the applied net benefit concept, the EVP accounts for both positive and negative exchanges between employer and employee. A novel, four-stage EVP development process was established: situation analysis, creation, the EVP characteristics, and optimisation. A systematic literature review identified 27 theoretical requirements aligned with these phases, aiming for a conscious, systematic, and authentic EVP.

3. Methodology

This chapter outlines the methodological framework used to address the research questions and objectives that have guided this study. With its roots in a pragmatic-interpretivist philosophy, the research design is constructed to bridge the gap between theoretical requirements and practical application. By distinguishing between the *truth tests* of literature and the *utility tests* of practice, the methodology ensures that the research is both academically rigorous and operationally relevant. The focus is on the empirical part, as shown on the right-hand side of Fig. 19.

Fig. 19: Methodology of the thesis

The present chapter is divided into the following nine sections: Type of research design, objective of the method, selection of the sample, conducting the interviews, data collection, methods of research data analysis, ethical aspects, critical reflection and quality assurance, and summary.

3.1 Type of research design

The research design encompasses the overarching decisions and methodologies that underpin the research endeavour, as described by Creswell and Creswell (2023, p.3). It is essentially the “logical sequence that connects the empirical data to a study’s initial research questions” (Creswell and Poth, 2018, p.5) and ultimately its conclusions, according to Yin (2018, p.26).

The research design constitutes a critical topic of central significance to research studies (Abutabenjeh and Jaradat, 2018, p.237). A research design is a blueprint that serves to guide the research process by outlining the progression from the research purpose/questions to the outcomes. It is a comprehensive planning process that is utilised for the purpose of collecting and analysing data, with the objective of enhancing comprehension of a specific subject (Abutabenjeh and Jaradat, 2018, p.238). A "good research design is the result of reflection, planning and clear decisions" (Flick, 2018, p.46). It "has a clear focus and is built around a clear research question" (Flick, 2018, p.45), influencing sampling and theoretical background.

The topic of this study, the requirements within the EVP development, has not been researched and adequately explained yet (see chapter 1.3, p.12). The purpose here is to reconstruct the requirements used in practice during the EVP development process. Thereby it is an exploratory design.

This section will provide a thorough exploration of the research design and its underlying rationale.

3.1.1 Research design

There are three overarching research designs, approaches or methodologies: (a) qualitative, (b) quantitative, and (c) mixed methods (Creswell and Creswell, 2023, p.4; Döring, 2023, p.186; Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2023, p.181).

Ad a) In the *quantitative research* approach, theoretically derived research hypotheses are examined in many units of analysis using structured data collection methods. The aim is usually to test the theory. The collected quantitative (numerical) data are statistically evaluated (Döring, 2023, p.186). This is not the case here.

Ad b) *Qualitative research* offers a distinct approach to understanding complex phenomena (Brady, 2015, p.61), but it also comes with its own set of challenges and limitations (Brodsky *et al.*, 2015, p.19). Qualitative research design, particularly when employing expert interviews, is a nuanced and iterative process that starkly contrasts with the more linear, predefined paths typical of quantitative studies.

“Interpretation is the challenge at the heart of qualitative research. Without interpretation, we cannot make sense of our data. [...] In other words, we need to make the data meaningful through a process of interpretation” (Willing, 2014, 136). “By developing the codes through an iterative process involving reading, focused coding, reflection, writing, and rereading, researchers make connections between ideas, collapse codes into larger ideas (variously called themes or categories), and begin to develop assertions concerning the phenomenon of interest” (Roulston, 2014, p.305).

Ad c) *Mixed methods research* designs integrate the use of quantitative and qualitative data collection procedures and analysis techniques in the same research project, being often associated with pragmatism and critical realism (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2023, p.187). *Sequential mixed methods* research involves more than one phase of data collection and analysis (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2023, p.188).

The present research employs qualitative methods, namely expert interviews.

3.1.2 Research design rationale

The rationale has two parts: the qualitative research and the expert interviews.

Rationale for qualitative research

There are ten general reasons for choosing qualitative research:

- (a) Exploring *complex or under-researched phenomena*: Qualitative research is particularly suited for exploring and understanding concepts or phenomena where little research has been done, or which involve an understudied sample (Creswell and Poth, 2018, pp.45–46).
- (b) In-depth understanding and nuance: Qualitative methods excel at studying issues in depth and detail, providing a complex, detailed understanding that can only be established through direct engagement with people and their contexts (Creswell and Poth, 2018, p.45).
- (c) Theory generation and development: A primary goal of qualitative research is discovery, leading to theory generation (Creswell and Poth, 2018, p.46). It is an inductive approach to theory development, which stands in contrast to the deductive, theory-testing nature of much quantitative research. It can be used to develop theories when partial or inadequate theories exist, or when existing theories do not adequately capture the problem's complexity (Creswell and Poth, 2018, p.46). The quality of the analysis, rather than the source of the data, is what ultimately matters for advancing theory (Silverman, 2017, p.111).
- (d) Giving voice to participants: Qualitative methods provide a means of giving voice to traditionally unrepresented or underrepresented individuals or groups (Creswell and Poth, 2018, p.45).
- (e) Researcher's role and reflexivity: The researcher is the primary instrument of data collection and analysis in qualitative inquiry (Creswell and Poth, 2018, p.43). Reflexivity, an active self-reflection on the researcher's subjectivity and potential biases, is a core strategy for managing this inherent involvement (Creswell and Poth, 2018, p.44). The practice of writing reflexively, whereby researchers are present throughout the text, is a method of addressing representation. This is because qualitative inquiry is relational and co-constructed (Mayan, 2023, p.67). This means that researchers should continually examine their beliefs, values, and assumptions throughout the research process, which can be achieved by maintaining a reflective journal or through memoing (Naeem *et al.*, 2023, p.5).

- (f) Flexibility and openness: Qualitative methods are characterised by openness, flexibility, and an emergent and evolving design (Flick, 2018, p.16). This flexibility is evident in the process of formulating research questions, which may need to be rewritten after reviewing literature or refocusing on the significance of the research (Marshall, Rossman and Blanco, 2022, p.81).
- (g) Exploratory design: Qualitative research can be used where no acceptable, valid, and reliable quantitative measures exist. It is also appropriate to follow up quantitative research and help explain the mechanisms or linkages in causal theories or models (Creswell and Poth, 2018, pp.45–46).
- (h) Embracing complexity over simplification: Qualitative studies typically focus on complexity, whereas quantitative approaches foreground simplicity (Braun and Clarke, 2022, p.27). This allows for a richer, more nuanced, and contextually-situated understanding of human experiences and social phenomena (Braun and Clarke, 2022, p.55).
- (i) Transferability (non-statistical generalisation): While qualitative research is generally not meant to be statistically generalisable to larger populations, its findings can be transferable to similar cases or settings. The value lies in providing thick, rich, detailed description that enhances the reader's ability to apply insights to other contexts (Braun and Clarke, 2022, p.140; Creswell and Creswell, 2023, p.222).
- (j) Practicality and resource constraints: While not solely a methodological justification, practical factors such as costs, time, and resources can lead researchers to choose qualitative methods, which often work with smaller sample sizes due to the intensive effort per case (Patton, 2015, p.372). However, the conscious and purposeful selection of cases in qualitative research is aimed at gathering "information-rich sources" rather than achieving statistical representativeness (Creswell and Poth, 2018, p.368).

Many of the ten principles are applicable to this thesis. The four main principles that underpin this qualitative research are: (a) exploring complex or under-researched phenomena, (b) in-depth understanding and nuance, (c)

theory generation and development and (h) embracing complexity over simplification.

In this study, the qualitative research is chosen over quantitative methods for several reasons, primarily due to its research objectives. The research question is: *What are the potential requirements for developing the employer value proposition (EVP)?* The decision was predicated on the necessity to explore the perceptions in practice with regard to the EVP requirements within EVP development process.

The following assumptions have been made:

- a) The experts do not have a list of requirements to hand.
- b) The list might be as extensive as in the theory (there: #27, see chapter 2.11.2, p.69), or even more so.

Following the assumptions, a questionnaire will not be a useful tool. In personal interviews, while asking the topic from different angles, more results can be expected.

Returning to the website programming analogy from section 1.4 (see page 14), it is clear that requirements are crucial for each project. Therefore, it is important to have all the requirements listed before starting the programming. In accordance with this analogy, the objective of the research is to identify, if possible, all requirements for the EVP development.

Qualitative research has several *characteristics*: Natural setting, researcher as key instrument, multiple methods, involves using multiple methods, complex reasoning through inductive and deductive logic, participants' multiple perspectives and meanings, context-dependent, emergent design, reflexivity, and holistic account (Creswell and Poth, 2018, pp.43–44). This study meets these characteristics (see Tab. 11).

characteristics of qualitative research	apply to this study	rationale
Natural setting: Is conducted in a natural setting (the field)	yes	EVP development in practice, interviewees in office environment
Researcher: Relies on the researcher as key instrument in data collection	yes	Interviews by researcher
Methods: Involves using multiple methods	yes	Systematic literature research and expert interviews
Complex reasoning: Involves complex reasoning going between inductive and deductive	yes	Inductive and deductive category building
Multiple perspectives: Focuses on participants' multiple perspectives and meanings	yes	Research the EVP development process from different backgrounds of participants
Context-dependent: Is situated within the context or setting of participants or sites	yes	EVP development depends on the company and market situation
Emergent design: Involves an emergent and evolving design	yes	Design change over the time of research, focusing in the end on the requirements
Reflexivity: Is reflective and interpretive of researcher's background influences	yes	the personal research background (teaching marketing and brands and human resources) is certainly subliminally influential
Holistic account: Presents a holistic, complex picture	yes	Research takes the requirements in the complex picture of the EVP development within employer branding

Tab. 11: The nine characteristics of qualitative research from Creswell/Poth (2018, pp.43–44)

Döring continues by explaining that the qualitative research approach means (Döring, 2023, p.186):

- *open research questions* are examined in great detail using unstructured or partially structured data collection methods,
- with a *small number* of units of analysis,
- the qualitative (non-numerical, i.e. verbal, visual) data collected are *evaluated interpretatively*, and
- the aim is to produce a description of the subject matter including *theory formation*.

Summary of the rationale: fit between problem and design

The choice of qualitative, interpretivist research design is ultimately dictated by the nature of the research object itself. As the literature review established, developing an EVP is not a linear, mechanical process governed by universal laws; rather, it is a complex social construction involving negotiation, perception and strategic intent.

Therefore, quantitative methods would be premature in this context. As there is no established variable model for EVP development requirements in the current literature, a deductive, hypothesis-testing approach would lack a validated theoretical basis. Attempting to measure 'how much' a requirement applies before defining 'what' the requirement is would be methodologically flawed.

Instead, this thesis requires an approach capable of opening the 'black box' of expert practice. By adopting a qualitative exploratory design, the research can:

1. *Capture complexity*: This allows nuanced, context-dependent requirements to be identified that would be missed by a standardised survey.
2. *Understand the 'why'*: It goes beyond simply listing tasks to gain an understanding of the strategic reasoning employed by experts.
3. *Generate theory*: The abductive approach enables the synthesis of fragmented practical knowledge into a coherent theoretical framework, such as the EVP Development Cycle.

Therefore, qualitative design is not just a preference, but a methodological necessity in order to answer the research question: *What are the potential requirements for developing the Employer Value Proposition?*

3.1.3 Philosophical foundations: ontological and epistemological commitments

The present study takes a pragmatic-interpretivist epistemological approach. This philosophical stance directly informs the research strategy, which is detailed in section 3.1.4, p.88.

This research is explicitly committed to a subjectivist ontology and an interpretivist epistemology, both of which are grounded in the tradition of social

constructionism. In the context of management and organisational research, the argument is made that the EVP is not an objective, physical entity ready to be measured, as one would approach a subject in the natural sciences, but rather a complex social phenomenon shaped by the strategic intent and professional logic of its *architects*.

1. Ontological commitment: relativism and multiple realities

Ontologically, this study rejects the *realist* or *positivist* assumption that a single, objective reality of the EVP exists independent of social actors. A realist ontology assumes a “mind-independent truth” where the world is knowable through systematic observation (Braun and Clarke, 2022, p.164). In contrast, this research adopts a *relativist position*. Relativism rejects the notion of a singular reality and instead views realities as plural and “the product of human actions and sense-making” (Braun and Clarke, 2022, p.294).

From this perspective, the *reality* of an EVP is multiple and relative; it exists differently in the minds of the management who design it (Requirement A19), the consultants who shape it (Requirement A26), and the employees who experience it (Requirement A8). As Mayan argues, social realities are not “static or fixed, but rather dynamic, fluid, and subjective” (2023, p.19). Therefore, the *requirements* identified in this thesis are not discovered natural laws, but socially constructed standards. They reflect *multiple truths* that endure only to the extent that they enable understanding of a particular social reality (Lincoln and Guba, 1985, p.77; Mayan, 2023, p.5).

Ontologically, this research focuses on the *construction* of EVP reality rather than its *consumption*. Consequently, the epistemological focus is on accessing the institutionalised competence of the people responsible for building the EVP, as detailed in the definition of the target population (see section 3.3.1, p.94).

2. Epistemological commitment: interpretivism and co-construction

Epistemologically, this ontological stance necessitates an interpretivist approach. Since the EVP is conceptualised as a social construct, knowledge about it cannot be acquired through detached observation or statistical deduction alone. Instead, knowledge is understood as *co-constructed* between the researcher and the participant. As Braun and Clarke note, in this paradigm the researcher does not “discover” meaning but plays an active role in “meaning creation” (2022, p.193).

As this study adopts an interpretivist approach, it acknowledges that the researcher enters the field with specific “sensitizing concepts” (Blumer, 1954, p.7). The researcher’s professional background in marketing and HR was useful for building rapport and understanding technical terminology. However, this positionality also required rigorous management to prevent the uncritical application of marketing logic to HR practices. Section 3.8.3, p.129 provides a detailed critical reflection on the researcher’s positionality, the specific benefits and risks of their background, and the measures taken to manage subjectivity, such as keeping a reflective journal.

Consequently, the researcher does not seek to excavate a static truth about the EVP, but interprets the *institutionalised competence* of experts (Meuser and Nagel, 2016, p.345) to reconstruct the subjective motivations and strategic logics that underpin the EVP.

The pragmatic challenge to established theory

This dialectical approach enables the research to progress beyond a mere summary of the context. The expert insights act as a pragmatic corrective to the literature, highlighting the discrepancies between academic theory and the practical reality of EVP development. Prioritising the functional expertise of practitioners challenges previous ways of thinking that rely solely on theoretical models. Evidence of this can be seen in the reconstruction of 24 practical requirements, such as the need for an *ownable* or *structured* EVP, that

are currently absent from theoretical discourse (see section 5.2.2, p.231). This proves that practice has outpaced theory in specific operational areas.

3.1.4 The philosophical foundation of the research strategy

Adopting a pragmatic-interpretivist philosophy is not just a matter of semantics; it provides the structural framework for the entire research design. Specifically, this research strategy aims to bridge the gap between the truth tests of academia and the utility tests of practitioners (Patton, 2015, pp.728–730).

While the academic requirement for a PhD necessitates rigorous adherence to validity and theoretical credibility (the *truth test*), the business problem of unsystematic EVP development demands actionable relevance (the *utility test*). Consequently, rather than viewing the tension between theory and practice as a conflict, this thesis utilises distinct data sources to satisfy both criteria simultaneously.

The Truth Test: literature as theoretical baseline

The systematic literature review provides the contextual foundation. Conducted in a post-positivist manner, it rigorously reconstructs the existing normative professional knowledge in current scholarship (Guba and Lincoln, 1994, p.110). This establishes the necessary theoretical baseline and answers the question: What does the discipline currently believe is necessary? In this sense, the literature provides an objective *map* of the territory.

The Utility Test: expert interviews as a pragmatic corrective

Conversely, the semi-structured interviews provide the pragmatic basis of the thesis. Accessing the institutionalised competence of experts (Misoch, 2019, p.27) enables the primary data to challenge abstract theoretical assumptions against operational reality. This approach goes beyond static definitions to ensure that the findings are not only plausible but also generate “actionable

answers” (Patton, 2015, pp.171–177). Here, the experts provide the subjective *compass* with which to navigate the theoretical map.

The pursuit of actionable knowledge

The philosophical commitment of this study is therefore not to interpret for interpretation's sake, but to produce knowledge as a “tool for action” (Cornish and Gillespie, 2009, p.800). By combining the contextual systematisation of the literature (Truth) with the pragmatic utility of expert interviews (Utility), the research creates an abductive cycle. This enables the study to identify instances where theory aligns with practice, as well as instances where practice has surpassed theory and necessitates new categories (see section 5.2, p.224).

1. From philosophy to research approach

Based on the interpretivist stance established in section 3.1.3, the approach is necessarily both inductive and abductive. Within this paradigm, knowledge is not discovered as an external fact, but is “socially constructed among people engaged in the research process” (Mayan, 2023, p.22).

This philosophical commitment necessitates a qualitative design capable of capturing the “complexity” and “depth” of the phenomenon (Mayan, 2023, p.3). Furthermore, the adopted abductive logic enables the researcher to move “back and forth between the general and the specific in order to solve a problem” (Patton, 2015, p.157). This logic is operationalised by constantly comparing emerging empirical themes against 27 theoretical requirements (section 2.11.2, p.69) to identify where industry practice aligns with and diverges from literature. This enables the research to extend and refine existing theory rather than simply testing it.

2. From approach to research strategy

The pragmatic element – focusing on actionable solutions to the business problem of unsystematic EVP development – guided the strategy towards *expert interviews*. Pragmatism focuses the inquiry on “getting useful answers

to practical questions” (Patton, 2015, p.157). In order to access the specific *institutionalised competence* to construct reality (Misoch, 2019, p.27) possessed by experts, a dialogue-based strategy was required rather than mere observation. The semi-structured interview format was influenced by the interpretivist need for openness to the expert’s perspective, while also addressing the pragmatic requirement for structure in order to derive a usable framework. As Misoch notes, expert knowledge consists not only of systematised facts, but also of practice or action knowledge that structures the conditions for other actors (2019, p.27).

3. From strategy to techniques

Finally, the philosophical commitment to knowledge as co-construction informed the choice of reflexive thematic analysis as the analytical method. Unlike mechanistic word counting (content analysis), reflexive thematic analysis allows researchers to identify patterns across the dataset interpretatively (Braun and Clarke, 2022, p.214). By adopting this technique, the researcher acknowledges their subjectivity as an integral part of the analytical process, rather than as a bias. Section 3.1.5 provides a detailed theorisation of how this subjectivity functions as an epistemic resource.

layer	selected approach	justification and rationale
1. philosophy	subjectivism, interpretivism and pragmatism	The study views reality as socially constructed and ‘co-constructed’ through interaction. A pragmatic orientation is adopted to generate ‘actionable knowledge’ that solves the business problem.
2. approach to theory development	inductive and abductive	An inductive approach is used to explore meanings experts ascribe to the EVP. Abductive logic allows moving ‘back and forth’ between specific data and general theory to solve the problem.
3. methodological choice	qualitative	Quantitative surveys were rejected in favour of qualitative research to capture the ‘complexity’ and ‘depth’ of the phenomenon.
4. strategy	basic qualitative inquiry	Adopts a basic qualitative inquiry strategy to access experts’ ‘institutionalised competence’ through dialogue to reconstruct strategic logics.
5. time horizon	cross-sectional	Data collection captured a specific snapshot of expert knowledge between Feb–May 2024.
6. techniques & procedures	semi-structured interviews and reflexive thematic analysis	Data collection via semi-structured interviews allows openness to the expert’s perspective. Analysis via Reflexive Thematic Analysis acknowledges researcher subjectivity as a resource, not a bias.

Tab. 12: The research onion (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2023) of this thesis

Tab. 12 summarises these methodological decisions aligned with the layers of Saunders et al.'s (2023, p.131) research onion, demonstrating the coherence between the philosophical stance and the chosen techniques.

3.1.5 Theorising objectivity and subjectivity

From bias to epistemic resource

To fully ground the research design, it is necessary to theorise the interplay between objectivity and subjectivity. This is particularly important given the tension between the systematic aim of this thesis (creating a standardised list of requirements) and the constructivist nature of the data source (expert interviews). This study rejects the traditional positivist dichotomy where objectivity is equated with truth and subjectivity with error. Instead, subjectivity is considered an essential epistemic tool for knowledge production (Braun and Clarke, 2022, p.11).

The researcher as the primary instrument

A central tenet of this research design is the recognition that the researcher acts as the "primary instrument" of enquiry (Patton, 2015, p.119). Unlike quantitative research, which uses standardised tools to distance the observer from the observed, qualitative research relies on the researcher's professional ability to interpret complex social realities. Consequently, identifying EVP requirements is an interpretive process; these are not *discovered* lying dormant in the data, but are generated through engagement with it. Here, subjectivity is re-conceptualised as a resource that fuels the analytic process rather than a contaminant that threatens it (Braun and Clarke, 2022, pp.12–13).

Intersubjectivity and the co-construction of knowledge

The *objectivity* of the resulting requirements list does not derive from a positivist *view from nowhere* (Nagel, 1986, p.70), but from intersubjective

comprehensibility. Knowledge regarding EVP development is co-constructed through interaction between the researcher and the expert (Brinkmann and Kvale, 2018, p.37). The research aims to access the implicit professional knowledge of the field – the logic that guides practice but is rarely made explicit. Accessing this requires the researcher’s subjective engagement to transform the experts’ narratives into a systematic theoretical framework.

3.2 Objective of the method

This section is divided into two parts. The objective of qualitative research and its contribution to research objectives.

3.2.1 Objective of qualitative research

The overarching aim of qualitative research is to identify and comprehend the significance of a social or human problem (Misoch, 2019, p.2) that is transferable (Morse, 2015, p.1213) in order to solve problems (Patton, 2015, p.154). In certain cases, a higher goal of social justice is also pursued (Roulston, 2014, p.297).

The aim of this research is to identify and understand the significance of the requirements used in practice when developing EVP. The objective is to create a comprehensive list of requirements to ensure the transferability of these findings to future cases. This will facilitate the resolution of issues and the development of a high standard of EVPs.

As discussed in chapter 2.9, these advanced EVPs lead to optimised resource allocation, enhanced team performance and improved outcomes. From an employee's perspective, the provision of assistance in the form of informed decision-making is conducive to the enhancement of work life. However, it

would be inaccurate to assert that this study perceives itself as pursuing the goal of social justice.

3.2.2 Contribution to research objectives

The planned contribution to knowledge of this empirical research is to incorporate the practical aspect into the comprehensive list of requirements for the EVP and the EVP development.

The research question and research objectives from section 1.4 (p.13) are listed again in Tab. 13. This shows that the research question and all the research objectives except research objective 1 are addressed in the empirical research.

	literature review	empiric research
research question: What are the potential requirements for developing the employer value proposition (EVP)?	yes	yes
research objective of this thesis: The objective is to develop a set of requirements for systematically determining the EVP:	yes	yes
1. Reconstructing the normative <i>requirements</i> for the EVP and its development <i>in theory</i> (literature review)	yes	no
2. <i>Requirements currently used in practice</i> , as reported by experts in the field.	no	yes
3. A <i>comparison</i> and <i>analysis</i> of literature and practice	yes	
4. <i>Conclusions</i> for theory and practice based on the comparison	yes	

Tab. 13: Overview of the research question and objectives and the two research parts

3.3 Selection of the sample

As participants are chosen because “they have the life experience to provide rich information and throw particular light on the issue under investigation” (Edwards and Holland, 2023, p.7), sampling for qualitative interviews is a crucial step (Flick, 2018, p.33).

Unlike quantitative approaches that prioritise broad generalisation, qualitative studies “aim for depth and crafting relationships with participants rather than conducting studies with large-scale randomly selected participants” (Marshall, Rossman and Blanco, 2022, p.49).

Patton advocates for “purposeful sampling” (Patton, 2015, p.264) where researchers strategically select information-rich sources that can illuminate the phenomenon under investigation. Ultimately, “what you end up having something to say about depends on whom you sample” (Patton, 2015, p.285).

This section is divided into four parts: the target group; the selection criteria; the recruitment methods; and the sample size.

3.3.1 Target population

Döring (2023, p.294) states that the target population results from the respective research interest of a study. This means that the selection of individuals or groups is driven by the specific research question.

Misoch (2019, p.200) further illustrates this by describing a ‘field’ as potentially a specific group of people, a specific institution, a specific culture or subculture (e.g. emos, punks, hipsters), or people with specific characteristics, backgrounds, or experiences (e.g. relatives of dementia patients; Holocaust survivors) (Misoch, 2019, p.200).

Theorising the expert

In the context of this research, the term *expert* is not used merely to denote a professional with experience, but is theorised as a specific subject formation. Drawing on the sociology of knowledge, experts are defined by their institutionalised competence to construct reality (Meuser and Nagel, 2016,

p.345). Unlike the *lay person*, the expert possesses *specialised knowledge* relating to a specific problem area – in this case, the EVP development – that is socially recognised as exclusive (Meuser and Nagel, 2016, p.346).

In the specific context of the *War for Talent*, these experts (consultants and HR strategists) do not simply describe the labour market; they actively shape the narrative around it. They possess *Deutungsmacht* (interpretive power) – the authority to impose binding definitions of reality upon other actors in the field (Helfferich, 2019, p.681). Consequently, the interviewees in this study are treated as representatives of a specific functional context who possess the authority to define industry standards, rather than as private individuals (Meuser and Nagel, 1991, p.442).

In line with the interpretivist framework outlined in section 3.1.3, the sample focuses on individuals with normative professional knowledge (i.e. *architects*), rather than individuals with descriptive experiential knowledge (i.e. *residents*).

Institutionalised competence and reality construction

In the context of this study, EVP consultants do more than simply describe the labour market; they actively shape the narrative around the *talent shortage*, translating demographic shifts into a strategic imperative that necessitates specific management interventions, such as EVPs. As noted by Deresky and Miller, HR experts argue that the challenges of attraction and retention have become "downright hard and complex" (2022, p.360). By framing the environment in this way, consultants validate their own indispensable role as "itinerant experts in a knowledge economy" (Kunda and Barley, 2004, cover). They define the parameters of the problem – the *war* – to justify the strategic necessity of their solution (the EVP). They are interviewed not as private individuals, but as representatives of this specific functional context (Meuser and Nagel, 1991, p.442).

The expert as a product of discourse and hegemony

The *EVP expert* subject is formed by the shift in power dynamics described in section 1.1.2 of the introduction. Trost (2020, p.62) observes a “reversal of dependency relationships” caused by scarcity. Perceiving the employee as a “valuable and rare” bottleneck factor creates the structural necessity for the expert subject who claims exclusive access to securing these assets (Becker, Brandt and Eggeling, 2015, p.226). This subject is the expert, who claims exclusive access to the mechanisms required to secure these assets. This aligns with Bogner and Menz’s characterisation, which posits that experts are distinguished by their ability to make their perspectives *hegemonic* within a specific organisational context (2009, p.19). Thus, the expert is constituted by the power to enforce their interpretation of a problem and its solution on other actors in the field.

Clarification of expert qualification versus analytical variables

It is important to distinguish between the criteria used for comparative analysis and those used to qualify the expert. Although this study employs quantitative metrics such as *years of service* as variables for group comparisons in section 5.1 (see p.180), these do not constitute the primary academic definition of *expertise* for this research.

Instead, expert status is defined by possession of specific “technical, process and interpretive knowledge” (Bogner, Littig and Menz, 2009, p.54), as well as *practical and action-oriented knowledge* (Gläser and Laudel, 2009, p.12). This knowledge is largely *tacit* – comprising *unwritten laws* and internalised routines (Meuser and Nagel, 2016, p.347) – which enables the researcher to reconstruct the complex social phenomenon of the EVP development cycle.

Therefore, the quality of the data does not derive solely from the participant’s seniority, but from their *institutionalised competence to construct reality* (Meuser and Nagel, 2016, p.345). It is this specific *information advantage* (Ullrich, 2006, p.101) and socially institutionalised expertise (Sprondel, 1979, p.141) regarding the development process, rather than just the outcome, that validates the sample. Consequently, an individual with fewer years of

service who has actively managed a complex EVP cycle is considered to have more relevant expert knowledge for this study than a senior executive who has only observed the process from a distance.

Although the sample of interviewees consists mainly of consultants, the range of firms covered is extensive. Through the combined project portfolios of these 28 experts, the research draws on insights from around 2,000 EVP projects spanning various industries. Consequently, the field is characterised not by the interviewees' current employer alone, but by their collective knowledge of processes across the Western corporate landscape (UK, Germany and North America). However, there is a bias towards large-scale enterprises that engage external consultancy in this field, which could result in micro-businesses being under-represented.

3.3.2 Selection criteria

The sampling strategy employed in this study was purposeful and intentional (Döring, 2023, p.303). Rather than aiming for statistical representativeness, the objective was to select 'information-rich cases' that could shed light on the complex phenomenon of EVP development (Edwards and Holland, 2023, pp.6–7; Misoch, 2019, p.211; Patton, 2015, p.264). To this end, a stratified purposive sampling strategy was adopted, combining homogeneous and heterogeneous elements in order to balance depth with validity.

The core strategy: Homogeneous sampling

The primary foundation of the sample follows a homogeneous sampling strategy. Based on the rationale that external consultants manage a significantly higher volume of EVP projects than internal employees, the study primarily targeted employer branding consultants. This focus ensures a high density of expertise, leveraging their institutionalised competence (see sections 3.1.3, p.85 and 3.3.1, p.94) to reconstruct processes across the Western corporate landscape (UK, Germany and North America).

Expanding the scope: Heterogeneous contrast cases

To challenge the potential biases of a purely consultant-based sample, the scope was expanded to include strategic heterogeneity (Döring, 2023, p.306). This involved deliberately selecting contrasting cases to enable data triangulation:

1. *In-house experts*: Non-consultants were included to verify whether the consultant perspective aligns with internal corporate reality.
2. *Non-Western contexts*: To examine whether the identified EVP principles are universally applicable or culturally specific, experts from non-Western markets (e.g. Iran and India) were included alongside the primary Western cohort.

The specific inclusion criterion was operational rather than demographic: participants had to have actively managed or executed the EVP development process. Consequently, active process knowledge was prioritised over job titles; for example, a junior expert who has managed a complex EVP cycle operationally is considered more relevant than a senior executive who has only observed it from a distance. No selection criteria were applied regarding gender, age or ethnicity as these factors were not considered relevant to the distribution of technical expertise in this field.

Critical reflection on the expert sample and data validity

Although the selection of experts was intended to capture in-depth knowledge of processes, critical reflection is required regarding the specific agenda inherent in the composition of the sample. Since 25 of the 28 experts are external consultants, their responses must be analysed bearing in mind their specific professional positioning.

As Meuser and Nagel argue, experts are not neutral repositories of objective facts, but act within a specific functional context. Their knowledge is inextricably linked to their "action system" and status group (1991, p.466, 2016, p.350). Consequently, there is an inherent risk that consultants may frame EVP development through a *commercial imperative*, portraying it as a highly

complex strategic necessity in order to legitimise their own professional utility. This reflects the experts' tendency towards "*impression management*" (Meuser and Nagel, 1991, p.461) seeking to present themselves and their organisation in a competent light.

To mitigate this risk, the research design does not treat expert statements as unquestionable truths, but rather scrutinises them for potential bias. Drawing on the methodological principles of Meuser and Nagel, the validity of the data is strengthened by interviewing multiple experts from the same field, as this creates an "immanent constraint to plausibility", whereby experts are aware that their peers are also being consulted (1991, p.466). Furthermore, the analysis systematically contrasts the views of external consultants with those of in-house experts (see section 5.1.4, p.203).

This comparative approach, a form of "triangulation of qualitative data sources" (Patton, 2015, pp.661–663), ensures that statements align with accepted professional standards rather than being mere sales rhetoric. This scrutiny reveals that, while consultants advocate comprehensive analysis, this is often driven by the necessity of maintaining professional reputation and standards rather than commercial gain alone.

3.3.3 Recruitment methods

Participants were contacted via email and professional networking sites such as LinkedIn and Xing.

Experts are frequently challenging to reach, as their time is a precious resource (Helffferich, 2011, p.165, 2019, p.682). Thus rendering strategies such as snowball sampling are valuable (Edwards and Holland, 2023, p.7; Lamnek and Krell, 2016, pp.688–689).

In line with the interpretivist framework established in section 3.1.3, p.85, the target population was selected to access specific *normative professional knowledge* regarding EVP development. While a sample of employees could provide descriptive accounts of their experience of an EVP, the aim of this study is to define the systematic requirements for its development. Therefore, the target population is restricted to the *architects* – consultants and HR strategists – who possess the institutionalised competence (Meuser and Nagel, 2016, p.345) necessary to define the professional standards and strategic logic that structure the field.

Snowball sampling means that individual members of the population are asked to recruit other people for the study through their personal social networks (Döring, 2023, p.310). Snowball sampling was utilised to identify more relevant experts.

In eight cases, the experts who had already been interviewed, or were scheduled to be interviewed, were confirmed. In seven cases, experts were suggested and then interviewed. However, it is important to note that each recommendation was meticulously reviewed to ensure its appropriateness.

3.3.4 Sample size / participants

Unlike quantitative research, where the sample size is calculated upfront to achieve statistical probability and generalisation, qualitative sampling aims for depth and understanding (Mayan, 2023, p.145).

Tab. 14 provides an overview of the 28 interview participants. More information on the experts is in appendix 5, p.298.

#	interviewee	company	position	country	# projects (interviewee)	Years of experience
1	I1	Consultancy	Head of Division	Germany	30	8
2	I2	Consultancy	Country Manager Germany	Germany	10	11

3	I3	Consultancy	Research Lead	UK	15	5
4	I4	Consultancy	CEO	UK	200	17
5	I5	Consultancy	Co-Founder and MD	CAN/USA	200	25
6	I6	Consultancy	Employer Branding Lead & Principal	Germany	250	23
7	I7	Consultancy	CEO	UK	10	18
8	I8	Consultancy	CEO	UK	100+	27
9	I9	Consultancy	CEO	USA	35	13
10	I10	Consultancy	CEO	UK	60	25
11	I11	Consultancy	Client Partner	UK	30	6
12	I12	Consultancy	CEO	UK	100	20
13	I13	Consultancy	Head Operations (Employer Branding)	India	3	5
14	I14	Consultancy	Solutions and Strategy	UK	100+	20
15	I15	Consultancy	Founder, MD	Germany	100	16
16	I16	Consultancy	Founder and CEO	Germany	50	9
17	I17	Company	Head of HR	Germany	1	3
18	I18	Consultancy	Co-Founder / MD	Germany	10	10
19	I19	Consultancy	CEO	USA	50+	15
20	I20	Company	Employer Branding Strategist	Iran	2	3
21	I21	Company	Head of Global Employer Brand	USA	4	7
22	I22	Consultancy	Partner	UK	15	3
23	I23	Consultancy	Co-Founder	Denmark	20	3
24	I24	Consultancy	VP Employer Brand Strategy	USA	350	20
25	I25	Consultancy	Founder / CEO	UK	35	20
26	I26	Consultancy	Founder / CEO	UK	5	7
27	I27	Consultancy	CEO	Germany	300+	18
28	I28	Consultancy	Strategy & Consulting Director	UK	30+	25

Tab. 14: List of participants in the expert interviews

During the interview period, experts involved in up to 350 EVP developments were interviewed. The 28 experts interviewed had collectively experienced over 2,000 EVP developments and 382 years of experience in the field.

The ‘*how many*’ question in relation to sample size is common. Morse (2015, p.1214) explains that it “depends on the nature of the phenomenon, its concrete versus subjective nature, the amount of complexity and scope of the phenomenon, and of course, how much is already known about the topic”.

A key concept here is *saturation*, originating from grounded theory, where data collection concludes “interviewees are not telling them anything that they have not heard before” (Edwards and Holland, 2023, p.70).

Saturation has attained widespread acceptance as a methodological principle in qualitative research. It is commonly taken to indicate that, on the basis of the data that have been collected or analysed so far, further data collection and/or analysis are unnecessary (Saunders *et al.*, 2018, p.1893).

	I1	I2	I3	I4	I5	I6	I7	I8	I9	I10	I11	I12	I13	I14
requirements	16	20	21	14	16	8	18	12	18	14	17	20	8	27
# new ones	16	12	6	2	5	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0
sum new ones	16	28	34	36	41	42	43	44	45	45	46	46	46	46
	I15	I16	I17	I18	I19	I20	I21	I22	I23	I24	I25	I26	I27	I28
requirements	15	17	3	7	16	3	14	13	11	12	22	15	10	10
# new ones	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
sum new ones	46	46	46	48	48	48	48	48	48	48	48	48	48	48

Tab. 15: Requirements per interviewee and cumulative unique requirements

Tab. 15 shows this research reached the saturation point after the 18th interview. Although it was foreseeable that saturation had been likely reached, the study was continued, because: (a) to ensure consistency and robustness of findings (validation and confirmation), (b) to capture more diversity in perspectives (two additional countries: Iran and Denmark and three more interviewees from the USA and two more in-house interviewees). The study was finished after 28 interviews.

Justification for the sample range and composition

Although data saturation regarding the identification of the list of requirements was achieved by interview 18, data collection was deliberately extended to include 28 participants. This range was necessary to ensure sufficient data density for the intra-group comparisons conducted in section 5.1, p.180. As Patton cautions, it is risky to assume that saturation has occurred

based on early interviews if the participants share similar characteristics. Expanding the sample is often necessary to reveal how responses might “vary in important ways” according to role or context (2015, p.195).

To adequately address the required breadth of expert perspectives, the sample size had to exceed the minimum required for simple thematic redundancy. A sample size of 28 provided the necessary volume of data points to validate the findings across distinct professional and regional contexts:

- *Professional Perspective*: The extension enabled comparisons between consultants and in-house experts (section 5.1.4, p.203). This ensured that the final model was not solely shaped by external advisory perspectives, thereby preventing the analysis from becoming “idiosyncratic or particular” to a single subgroup (Silverman, 2013, p.143).
- *Field background*: A critical mass of interviewees was required to meaningfully differentiate the priorities of HR versus marketing professionals (section 5.1.6, p.217). As Kuckartz and Rädiker note, even in qualitative research, it is valuable to compare coded segments across groups (2019, p.152).
- *Regional Nuance*: The range was expanded to capture diverse cultural interpretations of the EVP, specifically enabling a comparative analysis between the UK, Germany and North America (section 5.1.2, p.184). This aligns with the sampling strategy of *phenomenal variation* to explore the range of cases and the diversity of factors impacting the phenomenon (Rapley, 2014, 61).

Consequently, while 18 interviews sufficed for identifying the requirements, the full cohort of 28 was essential for contextualising and validating these findings across diverse subgroups. This decision reflects the principle that sample size in qualitative research is a matter of intellectual judgement based on the logic of making meaningful comparisons (Mason, 2018, p.222) rather than rigid statistical rules. Data collection concluded at 28.

Clarification of the field of firms and indirect representativeness

The *field of interviewees* is categorised primarily as the employer branding consultancy sector (25 out of 28 participants). Methodologically, these experts are treated as *boundary spanners* who possess aggregated knowledge of the wider corporate landscape. Although the interviewees are physically located within the consultancy field, their “interpretive knowledge” (Bogner, Littig and Menz, 2009, p.99) extends to a broad range of firms.

By interviewing these *aggregators*, the research gains access to a wide range of firms (over 2,000 projects spanning various industries), which would be impossible to reach through direct sampling alone. Consequently, the field is constituted not by the interviewees’ current employer alone, but by their collective “process and interpretive knowledge” (Bogner, Littig and Menz, 2009, p.100) of the Western corporate landscape, particularly in the UK, Germany and North America.

While this specialised knowledge (Gläser and Laudel, 2009, p.12) enables broad insights, it is important to recognise that the field is characterised by a bias towards large enterprises and multinationals with the capacity to hire external consultants, which could result in an underrepresentation of micro-businesses and the unique dynamics of the gig economy.

The interviewees	
Who will the research focus on?	HR-managers, employer branding managers, consultants (experts who developed or oversaw one or more EVP developing processes)
How are the participants chosen?	Focus on experts with multiple cases of expertise, i.e. consultants in this area
Contrasting cases	Small group of company employees with EVP development experience (#3) / some other countries
How many participants will be interviewed?	28
What inclusion and exclusion criteria will be used to identify eligible participants?	Inclusion: Having developed EVPs for companies or having been part of the team managing the EVP development process / Exclusion: Not personally involved in the EVP development process
How were the participants contacted?	Mail, networks (Xing, LinkedIn)
Place and area of study?	Virtual meetings, area: mostly UK (#12) and Germany(#8), North America (#5)
period	Feb 15 th – May 14 th 2024

Tab. 16: Sampling plan for the interviews

Conclusion: A total of 28 interviews were conducted, with the inclusion criterion: The participants were required to have developed EVPs for companies or to have been part of the team managing the EVP development process (see Tab. 16).

3.4 Conducting the interviews

Conducting interviews is a process that aims to explore subjective experiences and meanings in depth, rather than simply collecting factual information (Creswell and Creswell, 2023, p.193; Misoch, 2019, p.126).

This section is divided into four parts: Type of interviews, interview guide, interviewer and procedure and organisation.

3.4.1 Type of interviews

Qualitative research employs diverse forms of interviews (Keuneke, 2017, p.304). Most textbooks position interviews along a *continuum*, ranging from structured to semi-structured and unstructured (Döring, 2023, p.355; Edwards and Holland, 2023, p.3). Qualitative researchers primarily inhabit the semi-structured and unstructured ends, characterised by “increasing levels of flexibility and lack of structure” (Edwards and Holland, 2023, p.3).

Semi-structured interviews typically involve a “list of questions or series of topics” the researcher wants to cover, but with flexibility in their delivery and the interviewee’s response (Edwards and Holland, 2023, p.29). The interviewer can “probe answers, pursuing a line of discussion opened up by the interviewee”, allowing for dialogue (Edwards and Holland, 2023, p.29). Unstructured interviews, in contrast, are even less pre-structured, giving participants the space to say what they want to say using their own terms

(Helfferrich, 2019, p.672). This allows for detailed and in-depth exploration of individual perspectives (Döring, 2023, p.303).

The special feature of qualitative interview techniques is that the course of the interview is *structured* less by the interviewer and more *by the interviewee*. This is because in a qualitative interview, open-ended questions are asked, to which the interviewees provide comprehensive answers in their own words. In addition, the interview process is designed to be *flexible* so that new questions can be raised and followed up spontaneously if the interview situation warrants it (Döring, 2023, pp.360–361).

A specific form is the *expert interview*. Selecting people “who are influential, hold positions of power, and have knowledge that is not easily accessible to researchers” (Mayan, 2023, p.161), these interviews often seek factual information or specialised knowledge (Keuneke, 2017, p.308; Lamnek and Krell, 2016, p.687). However, such interviews may require less open narration than other qualitative types (Helfferrich, 2011, p.162).

Expert interviews hold a prominent, yet often debated, position within qualitative research, frequently employed to gather rich, specialised insights. At their core, expert interviews are characterised by the special selection and status of the respondents, as noted by Helfferrich (2011, p.163), distinguishing them from other interview forms.

Regardless of the specific type, the purpose of qualitative interviewing is to provide a framework where participants can “express their own understandings in their own terms” (Patton, 2015, p.442). The choice of interview type should always “relate to the aims and underlying framework of the research” (Edwards and Holland, 2023, p.36).

This research was conducted on the basis of semi-structured expert interviews.

3.4.2 Interview guide

The data collection instrument was a semi-structured interview guide. This tool served as a *common thread* for collecting qualitative data, providing a thematic framework and listing relevant topics to be addressed (Misoch, 2019, p.66).

It balances flexibility and structure

A key characteristic of qualitative interview guides is their flexibility (Keu-neke, 2017, p.308; Lamnek and Krell, 2016, p.690). Unlike standardised questionnaires, the exact wording and order of the questions are not pre-determined, enabling the interviewer to adapt to the linguistic context of the situation (Lamnek and Krell, 2016, p.322). However, in the context of this study, it was acknowledged that expert interviews benefit from a higher degree of structure (Helfferich, 2011, p.162). While open-ended prompts are valuable, too much ambiguity can confuse professionals accustomed to concise dialogue. Therefore, the guide was designed to be structured enough to target relevant information directly (Helfferich, 2011, p.179), yet flexible enough to allow "fruitful and appropriate" deviations (Edwards and Holland, 2023, p.56).

The structure and content of the guide

In practice, the guide was prepared in advance as a one- to two-page protocol (Creswell and Creswell, 2023, p.203). Following Creswell and Poth, the questions were primarily framed using 'what' and 'how' to encourage descriptive exploration rather than causal justification (2018, p.137).

The interview guide used in this empirical research contained the following core questions:

- What is your understanding of the EVP?
- What are the requirements for a good EVP? / What would be considered a bad EVP?

- What should the information base be for developing the EVP?
- What is the optimal procedure (steps to be taken)?
- How will EVP development evolve in the future?

Interview guide topic	Search for ...
EVP definition	Sharing the same understanding of the EVP
requirements for a good EVP	EVP requirements
information base	EVP requirements within the information base
optimal procedure / process	EVP requirements within the process
The future of the EVP	Future EVP requirements

Tab. 17: The topics of the interview guide and the reasoning behind them

The first topic established whether the expert concurred with the thesis's underlying understanding of EVP, while the subsequent four topics were designed to pinpoint specific requirements from various angles (see Tab. 17).

The protocol did not simply list topics, but used specific “question types” (Brinkmann and Kvale, 2018, pp.67–68) to ensure depth. First, it used *introductory questions* to establish the definition of EVP. Then, it used *specifying questions* to drill down into requirements and *interpreting questions* to validate the expert’s interpretation of future trends. This combination ensured that the conversation remained structured yet open.

The application of the guide aimed to ensure consistency of topics across the sample while maintaining the balance needed to allow novel, expert-driven insights to emerge.

Consistency was achieved by rigorously applying the thematic framework. By systematically guiding every expert through the same core structural trajectory, the guide ensured that the data remained comparable across all 28 interviews. As Flick argues, this consistency increases the “similarity of the research situations” (2018, p.36), ensuring that observed variations are attributable to the interviewees' views rather than the context of data

collection. Furthermore, this structure prevented conversations from drifting into unrelated biographical narratives (Gläser and Laudel, 2009, pp.14–17).

Balance was maintained by adhering to the methodological maxim, as open as possible, as structured as necessary (Helfferich, 2019, p.670). While the guide provided the framework, the researcher engaged in permanent spontaneous operationalisation (Gläser and Laudel, 2009, p.190) to translate academic queries into the experts' language. This flexibility enabled the specific institutionalised competence of the experts to emerge, providing practical insights that expanded upon the theoretical assumptions.

3.4.3 Interviewer

The interviewer acts as a key *instrument* in qualitative data collection (Creswell and Creswell, 2023, p.193; Misoch, 2019, p.213). As Misoch emphasises, the responsibility for the methodological and theoretical conceptualisation, preparation, execution, transcription, and evaluation of the data lies with the researcher. The *goodness* and *quality* of the collected data are contingent on the competence of the interviewer (Misoch, 2019, p.213).

Qualitative researchers should embrace this *subjectivity*, viewing bias not as a negative, but as a strength and a characteristic quality unique to a particular researcher (Mayan, 2023, p.6; Roulston and Shelton, 2015, pp.337–340).

Helfferich (2019, p.672) stresses that qualitative research commits to the greatest possible *openness* to allow the interviewees' subjective truth to unfold, giving them the space to say what they want to say using their own terms. Lamnek and Krell (2016, p.322) highlight that the interviewer should adapt and formulate the questions to the interviewee's language.

For interviewers, openness means not taking their own horizon of understanding as the measure of all that can be understood and being able to

engage with very different kinds of normalities that have their own meaning. Here, it is helpful to recall the roots of qualitative social research in ethnographic cross-cultural understanding (Helfferich, 2019, p.672).

Active listening and skilful probing are crucial (Edwards and Holland, 2023, pp.76–79). Edwards and Holland describe active listening as multitasking: attending to what is said, assessing relevance, recalling earlier points, and formulating the next question. They emphasise that listening is “the foundation of being able to respond to what the interviewee is saying, and able to probe and follow up their answers to your questions effectively and sensitively” (Edwards and Holland, 2023, p.77). Patton (2015, p.27) underscores “skilful questioning, and the capacity to establish rapport” (Patton, 2015, p.27). Lamnek and Krell (2016, p.332) suggest paraphrasing, asking follow-up questions, and careful interpretation to encourage elaboration.

It is imperative to establish rapport and trust as a priority (Wintzer, 2015, p.128). Similarly, Lamnek and Krell (2016, p.335) advise maintaining a confidential and relaxed atmosphere, neutral to soft, but above all non-directional style.

Skilled interviewing involves “asking genuinely open-ended questions; being clear so that the person being interviewed understands what is being asked; asking follow-up questions and probing [...] for greater depth and detail; and making smooth transitions” (Patton, 2015, p.427). “Being non-judgmental matters. Being authentic and trustworthy matter” (Patton, 2015, p.630).

Patton says: “The researcher is the instrument of inquiry” (Patton, 2015, p.xiv). Nonetheless, irrespective of the researcher’s awareness of this fact, it is inevitable that they will invariably bring certain beliefs and philosophical assumptions to the research process (Creswell and Poth, 2018, p.19), more on this in chapter 3.8.3, p.129 and 5.4, p.249.

The interviewer (the author) was aware of all these factors and attempted to implement them to the best of his abilities.

3.4.4 Procedure and organisation

The interview setting is important, as Marshall and Rossman (2022, p.117) assert that "human actions are significantly influenced by the setting in which they occur". Edwards and Holland (2023, pp.43–44) advise selecting a space that is "convenient and accessible to participants and researchers, where you could avoid interruption and make an adequate sound recording".

For recording, Creswell and Creswell (2023, p.203) suggest handwritten notes, audio recording, or video-recording. Pilot testing the interview questions and procedures is also recommended to refine instruments, assess observer bias, and adapt procedures (Creswell and Creswell, 2023, p.166).

The interview guide was prepared prior to the first interview. The initial interview was conducted as a pilot interview. All interviews were audio- and videorecorded.

The interviewees were offered the option of a personal interview in their location, but all expressed a preference for the virtual format.

The duration of qualitative interviews is highly flexible and can vary considerably (Lamnek and Krell, 2016, p.335), unlike the more fixed times in quantitative surveys. It is not "pre-determined" and depends on the research subject, the population, and the interviewee's willingness and articulation (Lamnek and Krell, 2016, p.335).

The duration of each interview is shown in Tab. 18.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14
time	53:43	28:53	31:39	81:18	36:50	57:22	47:34	30:22	37:05	27:42	39:21	34:37	33:45	53:27
	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28
time	24:31	45:21	23:23	55:36	66:09	17:44	21:46	36:09	32:47	51:17	48:18	29:53	40:17	38:23

Tab. 18: Duration of the 28 interviews (in minutes)

Conclusion: A total of 28 semi-structured, one-to-one, in-depth interviews were conducted. The author of the thesis conducted the independent research. The interviewees selected the option of conducting the interview via recorded video conference. The length of the interviews ranged from 17 minutes 44 seconds to 81 minutes 18 seconds, with an average length of 40 minutes 11 seconds (median: 36 minutes 57 seconds). The period in question extends from 15 February to 14 May 2024.

3.5 Data collection

This section provides a detailed description of the data collection process. The collection of data in expert interviews is a distinctive yet frequently employed practice in qualitative research (Misoch, 2019, p.119). Unlike general participants, an 'expert' is not merely someone who offers a personal narrative (Wintzer, 2015, p.82), acting as representatives of an organisation or institution rather than an individual whose personal life experiences are the primary focus (Keuneke, 2017, p.307; Lamnek and Krell, 2016, p.687; Meuser and Nagel, 2016, p.346).

The overarching goal in such interviews is primarily information gathering (Gläser and Laudel, 2009, p.15) or to elicit factual information (Helfferich, 2011, p.35), often aimed at categorisation or "Typlogisierung" (typed classification) (Misoch, 2019, p.125).

The aim is to describe the subject matter and develop a theory. The collected qualitative (non-numerical, i.e. verbal, visual) data are analysed interpretatively (Döring, 2023, p.186). The data was collected from a total of 28 semi-structured, one-to-one, in-depth interviews.

3.5.1 Recording procedure

Audio recordings are considered *indispensable* (Gläser and Laudel, 2009, p.158). Although interviewers can take handwritten notes, at least one audio recording or, better still, a video recording is recommended in order to capture the wealth of information (Lamnek and Krell, 2016, p.335). This also allows the interviewer to be “more attentive to the interviewee”, as taking verbatim notes can interfere with active listening (Patton, 2015, p.472). The recordings are then transcribed (Döring, 2023, p.355; Lamnek and Krell, 2016, p.335). All 28 interviews were recorded.

3.5.2 Transcription

Transcription, the conversion of spoken material into text, is the next step (Edwards and Holland, 2023, p.3).

However, for expert interviews, the approach to transcription often differs. Unlike other qualitative interviews that might require highly detailed, verbatim transcripts capturing every ‘hm, hms’ and sound particle, expert interviews generally do not necessitate elaborate notation systems (Meuser and Nagel, 1991, p.455; Ullrich, 2006, p.103). The focus for expert interviews is on “jointly shared knowledge” and thematic relevance, rather than finer-grained interactional details (Meuser and Nagel, 1991, p.455).

Thus, selective transcription is a common and pragmatic choice, where “only those passages are transcribed that are of thematic relevance” (Misoch, 2019, p.123). This approach, however, means a prior interpretive decision on

relevance, and carries the risk of “relevant passages in an interview being easily overlooked” (Misoch, 2019, p.127).

Anonymisation or pseudonymisation should occur at the earliest possible time – preferably during transcription stage, by replacing names or other identification features by a marker (Helfferich, 2011, p.191) and removing other identifying details (Döring, 2023, p.581).

The 28 interviews were fully transcribed. Two of them were anonymised.

3.5.3 Storage and backup of data

Qualitative studies, including expert interviews, produce extensive and heterogeneous data like field notes and recordings. The aim is to develop a robust system for securely handling the databases (Creswell and Poth, 2018, p.175).

The data was stored and backed up in a conscious manner. This involved ensuring strict separation and secure storage of original and anonymised materials along with anonymisation lists, like recommended by Paus-Hasebrink et al. (2017, p.215).

3.6 Methods of research data analysis

The aim is to describe the subject matter and develop a theory. The collected qualitative (non-numerical, i.e. verbal, visual) data are analysed interpretatively (Döring, 2023, p.186).

In qualitative research, the analysis of data from expert interviews is a complex and iterative process rather than a linear, step-by-step procedure (Mayan, 2023, p.197).

This continuous engagement means that data “analysis begins during field-work” (Patton, 2015, p.630), evolving as understanding deepens. Silverman (2017, p.17) further emphasises this, stating that data collection, analysis, and writing are “virtually inseparable”.

Expert interviews specifically aim to uncover specialised knowledge and practical and action-oriented knowledge, including often tacit knowing and relevance aspects that experts may find challenging to articulate (Gläser and Laudel, 2009, pp.12–15). “Linking data involves recognizing substantive rather than formal connections between things. Formal relations are concerned with how things relate in terms of similarity and difference. ... Substantive relations are concerned with how things interact” (Maxwell and Chmiel, 2014b, p.24).

This focus on in-depth, nuanced knowledge necessitates an analytical approach that can capture such complexity. This section is documenting: The analysis method employed was thematic analysis, with a coding process, software support and validation of results.

3.6.1 Analysis method: thematic analysis

Once transcribed, the “initial work with the text” involves familiarisation and exploration (Kuckartz and Rädiker, 2023, pp.91–93). Naeem et al. (2023, p.15) describe this as “familiarization with the data, and selection of quotations”. This early engagement can involve reading, reflecting, and making notes or memos (Kuckartz and Rädiker, 2023, p.91; Marshall, Rossman and Blanco, 2022, p.235; Roulston, 2014, p.305), which are “invaluable for generating the unusual insights that move the analysis from the mundane and obvious to the creative” (Marshall, Rossman and Blanco, 2022, p.241).

Qualitative analysis, as Braun and Clarke assert, is “always an interpretative activity” (Braun and Clarke, 2022, p.196). This initial, systematic process of organising and interpreting the raw data, such as identifying key words and phrases (Naeem *et al.*, 2023, p.7), then paves the way for more structured, category-based approaches like thematic analysis.

Thematic analysis (TA) was developed in particular by Virginia Braun and Victoria Clarke (University of the West of England, Bristol). This method is used to identify, analyse and report patterns (themes) within the data. It is flexible and can be applied both inductively (data-driven), and deductively (theory-driven). The thematic analysis is a widely used qualitative method for identifying, organising, and offering insight into patterns of meaning (themes) across a data set (Mayan, 2023, p.191).

Braun and Clarke outline a six-step process for conducting thematic analysis: (a) familiarising oneself with the data, (b) generating initial codes, (c) searching for themes, (d) reviewing themes, (e) defining and naming themes, and (f) producing the report (Braun and Clarke, 2022, pp.35–36) (more in chapter 3.6.2).

A central tenet of their reflexive TA is the active, interpretive role of the researcher, asserting that “data do not speak for themselves” and “themes don't emerge” (Braun and Clarke, 2022, p.91). Instead, the analyst must interpret the data, focusing on “what the data and your themes mean and why they matter” (Braun and Clarke, 2022, p.91).

This interpretive stance is particularly pertinent when engaging with expert interviews, which delve into specialised knowledge, as discussed by Gläser and Laudel (2009, p.36).

Braun and Clarke caution against common pitfalls, such as simply paraphrasing the data, stressing that true analysis involves interpretation that “goes beyond what is contained in the extracts” (Braun and Clarke, 2022, p.138).

They advocate for embracing partiality in findings rather than seeking a “final, absolute analysis” (Braun and Clarke, 2022, p.142). They also distinguish between ‘small q’ and ‘Big Q’ qualitative approaches to TA, noting they are “not complementary and cannot simply be combined” due to underlying conceptual clashes (Braun and Clarke, 2022, p.235).

In summary, the distinction highlights that ‘Big Q’ embraces the interpretive and subjective nature of qualitative inquiry within its own distinct philosophical framework, while ‘small q’ applies qualitative techniques within a quantitative, often positivist, paradigm, frequently seeking objectivity and generalisability akin to quantitative methods.

This contrasts with the illusion of the researcher as a “tabula rasa” or “blank slate”, as prior knowledge always influences the research process, according to Kuckartz and Rädiker (2023, p.14).

All interviews were transcribed in full, and a thematic analysis was subsequently conducted.

3.6.2 Coding process

The coding process for qualitative expert interviews serves as the analytical bridge, transforming raw verbal data into meaningful insights. It fundamentally involves “segmenting and taking apart the data [...] and putting it back together” to “make sense out of text and image data” (Creswell and Creswell, 2023, p.205). Researchers can initiate this analytical work “while collecting the data” by identifying “keywords commonly used by participants”, which are essential for creating codes that accurately reflect the underlying meaning of the data (Naeem *et al.*, 2023, pp.6–7).

A key characteristic differentiating expert interview coding from other qualitative approaches is its focus. Unlike interviews aiming to reconstruct subjective sense or individual lived experience (Silverman, 2017, p.199), expert interviews prioritise “jointly shared knowledge” and factual information (Meuser and Nagel, 2016, p.350).

Far from being a mere technical chore, coding represents the crucial interpretive work through which researchers begin to make sense of complex textual and visual data, ultimately leading to the identification of meaningful patterns and themes (Braun and Clarke, 2022, p.79). Coding is the “process of cataloguing information (keywords) according to a predetermined structure that leads to making data take on a more theoretical and conceptual form” (Naeem *et al.*, 2023, p.7).

At its core, coding involves systematically working through a dataset in a “fine-grained way” (Braun and Clarke, 2022, p.35), segmenting the data into smaller, manageable pieces, and assigning descriptive labels or tags to these segments (Naeem *et al.*, 2023, p.7). These “pithy, analytically-meaningful descriptions (code labels)” (Braun and Clarke, 2022, p.35) are designed to capture potentially interesting, relevant, or meaningful aspects related to the research question. Braun and Clarke distinguish between semantic coding, which stays close to the explicit or surface meaning, and latent coding, which delves into the more conceptual or implicit meanings within the data. This flexibility allows researchers to tailor their coding depth to their interpretive goals (Braun and Clarke, 2022, pp.57–58).

The approach to coding in TA is highly flexible, embracing both deductive and inductive strategies, and even abductive reasoning (Naeem *et al.*, 2023, pp.14–15). Deductive, or a priori, coding involves applying predetermined codes based on existing theory, hypotheses, or a review of relevant literature (Riger and Sigurvinsdottir, 2015, p.33). Conversely, inductive coding is data-driven, with codes and categories emerging directly from the material through repeated readings and close engagement (Morse, 2015, p.1216). Many researchers adopt a hybrid approach, using “sensitising concepts” from

their discipline to guide initial coding but remaining open to new, emergent categories (Brodsky *et al.*, 2015, p.17). (see appendix 6, p.301)

This section outlines the application of Braun and Clarke's six-phase thematic analysis process to this expert interview study (Braun and Clarke, 2006, pp.87–93, 2022, pp.35–36).

1. Familiarising yourself with your data: The researcher repeatedly read and listened to the transcripts, making initial notes and observations. This iterative process of familiarisation is vital as reading a transcript is an interpretative task, according to Braun and Clarke (2006, p.87).

2. Generating initial codes: This phase involves systematically organising the raw data into meaningful *codes*. Following Naeem *et al.* (2023, p.7), keywords were selected based on the "6Rs: realness, richness, repetition, rationale, repartee, and regal". These keywords are then used to interpret the data, ensuring that the analysis remains grounded in real information.

3. Searching for themes: Once initial codes were generated, the next step involved grouping conceptually similar codes to identify potential overarching themes. Braun and Clarke underscore that "themes don't emerge" but are actively constructed through the researcher's interpretive engagement with the data (Braun and Clarke, 2022, p.91). This is where the researcher begins to move "from particulars to more general perspectives", as noted by Creswell and Poth (2018, p.52). Themes should be based on the participants' own words.

4. Reviewing themes: This iterative phase involved refining and ensuring the coherence of the identified themes at two levels. Firstly, at the within-theme level, it is necessary to verify that the codes grouped under each theme form a coherent, meaningful, and relevant pattern (Braun and Clarke, 2006, p.91). Secondly, at the between-theme level, it is necessary to assess whether the

themes accurately reflected the entire dataset and addressed the research question. This is also a point raised by Braun and Clarke (2022, p.91).

5. Defining and naming themes: In this phase, each theme was concisely defined and given a clear, evocative name. This involved articulating the “essence” of what each theme represented and its significance to the research question (Braun and Clarke, 2006, p.92). Braun and Clarke advise against one-word theme names, which “can capture a topic but rarely the patterning of meaning evident in a theme” (2022, p.112), as they explain.

6. Producing the report: The final phase involved crafting a compelling “analytic narrative” that presented the identified themes supported by “compelling, vivid data extracts” (Braun and Clarke, 2022, p.36).

The author adhered to the six-phase process, with the sixth phase being documented in chapter 4, p.134.

3.6.3 Software support

The software support for qualitative expert interviews is increasingly recognised as an “essential tool” (Gibbs, 2014, p.277) and a “practical as well as legitimate ingredient” in qualitative research (Bruhn Jensen, 2021, p.305). Qualitative Data Analysis Software (QDAS) addresses the challenges by providing systematic support (Döring, 2023, p.598).

However, it is paramount to understand that software “does not do the thinking for you” (Silverman, 2017, p.373). As Patton cautions, “the real analytical work takes place in your head”, (Patton, 2015, p.531) and QDAS is primarily a tool to “facilitate data storage, coding, retrieval, comparing, and linking” (Patton, 2015, p.529).

The software MaxQDA was used to support this data analysis.

3.6.4 Validation of results

It is vital to establish the credibility and trustworthiness of findings by validating qualitative research results, especially from expert interviews (Brodsky *et al.*, 2015, p.14; Marshall, Rossman and Blanco, 2022, p.47).

As Silverman reminds us, “validity is another word for truth” (Silverman, 2017, p.400). For expert interviews, where the focus is often on jointly shared knowledge and factual information rather than subjective experience, ensuring that the gathered specialised knowledge is accurately represented is crucial (Gläser and Laudel, 2009, p.12).

Qualitative methodologists, such as Lincoln and Guba, propose several criteria to assess the rigor and trustworthiness of qualitative research (Brodsky *et al.*, 2015, p.18; Lincoln and Guba, 1985, p.327; Mayan, 2023, p.226; Riger and Sigurvinsdottir, 2015, p.36):

- *Credibility*: Whether the findings are accurate and believable from the perspectives of the researcher, participants, or readers (Riger and Sigurvinsdottir, 2015, p.36).
- *Transferability*: The extent to which findings can be applied to other settings or contexts (Creswell and Creswell, 2023, p.222).
- *Dependability*: Consistency of findings over time or across different researchers,
- *Confirmability*: Objectivity in data collection, analysis, and presentation, ensuring findings are not biased by the researcher’s values.

The validation of expert interview results involved the implementation of the following five strategies:

(a) Triangulation is a powerful approach, involving the use of “multiple types of [...] data (e.g. observations and interviews), [...] collection time points (e.g. multiple interviews, several questions and follow-up prompts to ascertain the participants’ viewpoints), [...] data sources, and [...] ways of analysis” (Brodsky *et al.*, 2015, p.18). Comparing empirical results with the literature can be seen as a form of theory triangulation. This involves taking several “theoretical perspectives on an issue under study” (Flick, 2014, p.12).

Theoretically, triangulation with employees would be conceivable. However, this would relate to individual cases and individual organisations. It would also depend on the design and implementation of the EVP within the company. The requirements for the EVP and its development could not be verified. Employees are normally only indirectly involved in this, e.g. through surveys, interviews and workshops.

(b) Rigorous record-keeping and maintenance of an audit trail contribute to transparency and auditability (Kuckartz and Rädiker, 2019, p.115). This includes documenting the original recordings of interview videos, the transcriptions, the developed categories and their definitions, the category system and its development (Kuckartz and Rädiker, 2023, p.210).

(c) Researcher reflexivity is vital, requiring researchers to comprehensively document and critically reflect on their subjective views, values, and experiences, and how these might influence the research process and interpretation (Brodsky *et al.*, 2015, p.18; Creswell and Poth, 2018, p.281; Marshall, Rossman and Blanco, 2022, p.53). Maintaining a reflective journal or memoring throughout the process helps ensure interpretations are not “overly influenced by pre-existing philosophical or theoretical stances” (Naeem *et al.*, 2023, p.5).

Throughout the TA process, reflexivity must be maintained by consistently situating the researcher’s background and experiences within the study, a method of addressing representation discussed by Mayan (Mayan, 2023, pp.250–251). This transparent approach counters “positivism creep” (Braun

and Clarke, 2022, p.7) and fosters a “qualitative sensibility” essential for rigorous inquiry, as further elaborated by (Braun and Clarke, 2022, p.7). Methodological coherence was ensured by aligning the study's paradigm, theoretical orientation, methodology, and research question.

(d) The role of quotes and ‘quantising’: Direct quotes are powerful; they “animate the data” and “provide a vivid portrayal of the subject matter” (Naeem *et al.*, 2023, p.5). They are illustrations of the content argument and should not be overused to replace analysis (Gläser and Laudel, 2009, p.274; Kuckartz and Rädiker, 2023, p.212). Quotes should be “contextualized” and “interpreted” (Creswell and Poth, 2018, p.232; Marshall, Rossman and Blanco, 2022, pp.276-277). While qualitative analysis emphasises words and meaning, “simple counts of well-defined phenomena have been included in the findings chapters where appropriate” to increase credibility and guard against “accusations of anecdotalism” (Silverman, 2017, p.408). However, Patton cautions against ‘quantising’ qualitative data without substantive meaning, especially with small sample sizes, as it “diminishes the meaning of both ‘content’ and ‘analysis’” (Patton, 2015, p.558). The focus should remain on “substantive significance” (Patton, 2015, p.572).

(e) Searching for deviant or negative cases strengthens validity by looking for data that “do not fit prior expectations” (Maxwell and Chmiel, 2014a, p.545). Analysing these exceptions can refine and deepen interpretations, guarding against “anecdotalism” (Silverman, 2017, p.414).

In essence, validating expert interview results is an iterative and systematic process that demands constant reflection, transparency, and a multifaceted approach to convince the audience of the findings' plausibility and credibility (Kuckartz and Rädiker, 2023, p.195).

The researcher followed the five strategies: theory triangulation, rigorous record-keeping, researcher reflexivity, the role of quotes and quantifying and searching for deviant or negative cases.

3.7 Ethical aspects

Regardless of the discipline, qualitative researchers must adhere to all relevant professional and personal ethical guidelines. This is essential to ensure the well-being, confidentiality and dignity of study participants, non-participants and research product recipients (Brodsky *et al.*, 2015, p.18).

Ethical principles are (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2023, pp.256-257):

- integrity, fairness and open-mindedness of the researcher,
- respect for other,
- avoidance of harm (non-maleficence),
- privacy of those taking part,
- voluntary nature of participation and right to withdraw,
- informed consent of those taking part,
- ensuring confidentiality of data and maintenance of anonymity of those taking part,
- responsibility in analysis of data and reporting of findings,
- compliance in management of data, and
- ensuring safety of researchers.

The author was aware of these principles and tried to act according to them to the best of his knowledge and belief.

A prerequisite for the approval of my research proposal was the favourable opinion of the UWS research ethics committee. This was approved on 10th June 2022 (see appendix 7, p.302).

3.7.1 Declaration of consent

It is vital that ethical research is subject to the criteria of 'informed consent' (Brodsky *et al.*, 2015, p.18; Edwards and Holland, 2023, p.8; Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2023, p.257), whereby all participants, voluntarily consent to their involvement. This consent is given subsequent to the provision of comprehensive information regarding their participation and the intended utilisation of the data collected (Anderson, Fontinha and Robson, 2020, p.160).

It is strongly advised that researchers obtain a written informed consent from the interviewees to document their voluntary participation and agreement for data recording and its scientific use (Misoch, 2019, p.20).

All 28 participants signed a declaration of consent.

3.7.2 Anonymisation

The declaration of informed consent should also clarify the anonymisation of the data and data protection (Misoch, 2019, p.20). The anonymisation of expert interviews is a critical ethical imperative, safeguarding participants and bolstering findings' trustworthiness (Lamnek and Krell, 2016, p.368). According to Mayan, "Anonymity in research means that individuals outside the study team will not be able to identify participants", and this extends beyond names to "location, a unique saying, expressed opinions and/or behaviors, life circumstances, or social categorization" (Mayan, 2023, p.211). Wintzer emphasises that statements and quotes must always be anonymised (no naming and no disclosure to third parties) (Wintzer, 2015, p.86).

In accordance with the wishes of the two individuals who wished to remain anonymous, their transcripts have been anonymised.

3.7.3 Data protection

Data protection in expert interviews is an ethical imperative (Lamnek and Krell, 2016, p.364; Misoch, 2019, p.19), underpinning the integrity and protection of the interview partners (Lamnek and Krell, 2016, p.364; Nierobisch, 2016, p.158).

Practical measures for data security require that interview material must be kept locked and inaccessible to unauthorised persons (Döring, 2023, p.364). Researchers should “protect the anonymity of participants by masking their names in the data” (Creswell and Poth, 2018, p.175), and if a master list of aliases is needed, it must be stored separately (Creswell and Poth, 2018, p.175).

3.8 Critical reflection and quality assurance

Moving beyond the procedural steps of data collection, this chapter critically examines the research design and its inherent limitations. In qualitative research, where the researcher is the “primary instrument” (Patton, 2015, p.119) and knowledge is “co-constructed” through interaction (Braun and Clarke, 2022, p.176), it is insufficient to provide a static list of procedural weaknesses. Instead, this study uses reflexivity to explore how particular sampling choices, the nature of expert knowledge and the researcher's position have actively influenced the findings.

Consequently, this chapter views bias not merely as an error to be eliminated, but as an epistemic characteristic that must be transparently understood (Mayan, 2023, p.6). This critical reflection is structured into four dimensions: sample composition (section 3.8.1); boundaries of knowledge (section 3.8.2), researcher positionality (section 3.8.3) and quality assurance measures (section 3.8.4).

3.8.1 Critical reflection on sample composition and expert knowledge

To contextualise the findings, it is necessary to consider the specific formation of the *expert* subject within this study. As theorised in section 3.3.1, p.94, experts are not neutral repositories of facts but actors within a specific functional context. As detailed in the methodology, the final sample comprises 28 experts, 25 of whom are external consultants (section 3.3.4, p.100). This imbalance requires reflection on the commercial imperative and the distinction between normative and descriptive knowledge.

The commercial imperative versus operational reality

This composition sheds light on a specific bias: the *commercial imperative*. Consultants have a vested interest in presenting EVP development as a complex necessity requiring external support. Helfferich (2019, p.682) describes this phenomenon as the *staging*. This bias was evident in practice: consultants recommended significantly more extensive, data-driven steps (e.g. analysing labour market trends) than their in-house counterparts (see section 5.1.4, p.203). Consequently, the resulting knowledge must be categorised as normative professional knowledge – a *maximum professional standard* defined by the industry elite – rather than a descriptive account of the average operational reality.

Mitigation and validity: the inherent constraint on plausibility

However, this elite bias does not invalidate the findings. The validity of the data is supported by what Meuser and Nagel term the immanent constraint to plausibility (1991, p.466). Experts are aware that their peers and competitors are also being interviewed, which discourages the fabrication of needs and encourages adherence to professional standards. Furthermore, the bias was mitigated by the experts' own insistence on requirements that force the *elite* to listen to the *base*, such as analyse employees' experiences (A8). By prioritising employee-centricity, the experts effectively bridge the gap between their strategic design and the operational reality of the workforce.

While consultants may inflate complexity for commercial gain, in-house experts may be constrained by organisational politics or a *status quo bias*. Triangulating these perspectives (see section 5.1.4) enables the research to filter out these positional distortions.

3.8.2 Critical reflection on the boundaries of knowledge

A critical distinction must be made regarding the epistemological status of the data. Based on the definition of the expert's institutionalised competence (see section 3.3.1, p.94), the interviews produced professional ideological knowledge in the form of normative statements about how things should be done, rather than a descriptive account of operational reality. The 50 reconstructed requirements (see section 6.2, p.262) therefore represent the industry elite's definition of a maximum professional standard or best practice framework, rather than reflecting the status quo. This explains why high-effort requirements, such as optimising employer attributes (O1), are highlighted as essential quality standards within the normative model, despite being frequently neglected in daily corporate practice. The model represents the discipline's aspirational standard.

Linguistic boundaries and the reduction of nuance

Given the international scope, critical reflection on language is necessary. A significant proportion of the interviews were conducted in English as a lingua franca. As one expert in the field has noted, working in a second or third language requires simplicity (see p.171). While business English is sufficient for structural requirements (e.g. H5), it acts as a filter for psychological concepts. This is particularly relevant to Requirement A5 (Analyse employees' work emotions) (see p.140), where linguistic limitations may have favoured tangible process requirements over complex emotional narratives.

Transferability

Finally, in line with qualitative research, this study does not claim statistical generalisability. The findings are largely confined to Western, developed economies (the UK, Germany, and the USA). Distinct results were obtained from the 'other' group (Denmark, Iran and India), whose focus was on fundamental employee understanding rather than strategic branding (see section 5.1.2, p.184). This suggests that the 50 requirements may need to be adapted for different cultural contexts.

3.8.3 Critical reflection on researcher positionality

The professional lens: marketing vs. HR reality

The researcher's positionality is heavily influenced by their experience of over 20 years as a lecturer in marketing and human resources. Furthermore, the researcher's professional background in advertising was acknowledged by experts during the interviews (see p.166), providing specific *sensitising concepts*.

- The *benefit*: This prior knowledge enabled the researcher to establish a rapport with the participants quickly. As the interviewees were industry experts, the researcher's familiarity with technical terminology (e.g. USP and brand equity) enabled a level of dialogue that would not have been possible with a lay researcher.
- The *risk*: However, this background introduced the risk of imposing a marketing logic (prioritising differentiation and communicative impact) onto HR realities (prioritising operational feasibility and contractual fairness). There was a tendency to view the EVP primarily as an advertising asset rather than an operational HR reality. To mitigate this risk, a rigorous reflexive approach was employed to ensure the analysis remained open to HR-specific nuances, such as the *psychological contract* and *labour relations*, rather than exclusively forcing the data into marketing frameworks exclusively.

Managing subjectivity through reflexivity

To ensure trustworthiness, subjectivity was managed through reflexive journaling. This involved constantly questioning whether emerging codes (Create an ownable EVP, for example) were truly present in the participant data or reflected the researcher's professional desire for brand distinctiveness. The study aimed to prioritise the perspectives of the experts over the researcher's assumptions by strictly adhering to the six-phase thematic analysis process (Braun and Clarke, 2022, pp.34–36) and grounding themes in verbatim quotes, the study aimed to prioritise the perspectives of the experts over the researcher's assumptions.

3.8.4 Quality assurance measures (trustworthiness)

In qualitative research, traditional positivist criteria such as validity, reliability, and objectivity are often deemed inappropriate for the interpretive nature of the study (Marshall, Rossman and Blanco, 2022, p.47). Consequently, this study adopts Lincoln and Guba's (1985, pp.289–331) framework of trustworthiness, which involves demonstrating credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability (Morse, 2015, p.2).

Rather than treating these criteria as a static checklist, specific quality assurance measures were implemented throughout the research process to address the biases identified in sections 3.8.1 to 3.8.3. Tab. 19 provides a comprehensive overview of these measures, mapping the identified methodological risks (e.g. *consultant bias* and the risk of *anecdotalism*) directly against the specific countermeasures employed (e.g. theory triangulation, achieving interview saturation, and maintaining rigorous audit trails).

Taking a comprehensive approach, this thesis aims to move beyond the "technical essentialism" of a mere "checklist" exercise (Barbour, 2014, p.507), demonstrating a deep commitment to the integrity of the research process.

area of reflection	specific challenge / bias	quality assurance / trustworthiness measures
sample composition	<p>consultant bias / commercial imperative: risk that findings reflect sales rhetoric due to high proportion of consultants (25/28).</p> <p>elite bias: capturing the view of the <i>architects</i> rather than the <i>inhabitants</i> (employees).</p>	<p>(a) <i>purposeful sampling:</i> Selection of "information-rich cases" (>2,000 combined projects) to ensure depth.</p> <p>(b) <i>data triangulation:</i> Systematic comparison of consultant views vs. in-house experts to isolate commercial bias.</p> <p>(c) <i>employee-centric requirements:</i> Inclusion of requirements like "Analyse employees' experiences" (A8) to force the elite view to account for the employee view.</p>
boundaries of knowledge	<p>normative vs. descriptive: data represents professional ideological knowledge (what <i>should</i> be done) rather than a descriptive account of the status quo.</p> <p>linguistic barriers: English as a <i>lingua franca</i> may have reduced the nuance of emotional requirements (A5).</p>	<p>(a) <i>theory triangulation:</i> validating empirical findings against the 27 theoretical requirements (section 2.11.2) to distinguish best practice from opinion.</p> <p>(b) <i>thick description (transferability):</i> providing detailed context and verbatim quotes to allow readers to assess transferability to specific cultural settings.</p>
researcher positionality	<p>marketing lens: risk of imposing marketing logic (e.g. USP thinking) onto HR realities due to researcher's background.</p>	<p>(a) <i>reflexivity (confirmability):</i> active journaling to question if codes (e.g. ownable EVP) were data-driven or researcher-imposed.</p> <p>(b) <i>hybrid coding:</i> balancing inductive (data-driven) and deductive (theory-driven) coding to remain open to HR nuances.</p>
methodological rigour	<p>anecdotalism: risk of selecting only quotes that fit the narrative (cherry-picking).</p> <p>quantification envy: risk of reducing qualitative meaning to numbers.</p> <p>lack of auditability: risk that the analytical path is untraceable.</p>	<p>(a) <i>systematic thematic analysis (dependability):</i> rigorous application of Braun and Clarke's 6-phase method.</p> <p>(b) <i>saturation:</i> data collection continued beyond saturation point (interview 18) to 28 interviews.</p> <p>(c) <i>qualitative dominance:</i> using counting only sparingly to show prevalence, prioritising narrative explanation.</p> <p>(d) <i>audit trail:</i> documentation of the code book (appendix 6) and coding evolution.</p>

Tab. 19: Overview of implemented specific quality assurance measures

This chapter demonstrates that the validity of qualitative research lies not in the pretence of objectivist neutrality, but in the transparency of its limitations and the rigour with which it is conducted. By acknowledging *consultant bias* (section 3.8.1) and defining the findings as *professional ideological knowledge* (section 3.8.2), the study clarifies that the 50 identified requirements constitute a high-standard normative framework – the *maximum viable product* of EVP development – rather than a descriptive baseline of average organisational behaviour.

Although the results are specific to Western strategic HR, the rigorous application of trustworthiness criteria such as theory triangulation, saturation and the audit trail ensures their credibility. Consequently, the identified

requirements serve as a robust, empirically grounded framework for subsequent analysis. From a pragmatic perspective, this Western focus does not invalidate the framework, but rather defines its current context of utility. The model is valid where the *War for Talent* discourse is active. Section 5.4 (p.249) discusses limitations, delimitations and assumptions.

3.9 Summary

This chapter outlined the qualitative methodological framework for investigating EVP development requirements. The study adopted a qualitative, exploratory research design using semi-structured expert interviews. This approach was selected to gain in-depth understanding of a complex, under-researched phenomenon and to facilitate theory generation. The research design ensures both academic rigour and practical relevance by combining the theoretical *truth* of literature with the pragmatic *utility* of expert insights.

A sample of 28 seasoned experts in EVP development, primarily drawn from the UK, Germany, and North America, were intentionally selected to provide information-rich data. The resulting verbal data underwent thematic analysis, informed by the six-phase process articulated by Braun and Clarke. Tab. 20 provides an overview of the methodology of the study.

Rigorous quality assurance measures, including triangulation, reflexivity, and systematic documentation, were applied to ensure credibility and trustworthiness. Ethical considerations such as informed consent and anonymisation were meticulously upheld. These foundational steps ensured a rigorous framework for the empirical investigation and subsequent comparative analysis.

category	specific methodology detail
(1) epistemology / epistemological positioning	A <i>pragmatic-interpretivist</i> approach that combines a <i>post-positivist</i> systematic literature review with <i>interpretivist</i> expert interviews to acknowledge both structured evidence and co-constructed, contextually embedded knowledge.
(2) purpose statement	get an understanding of the EVP development requirements in practice
(3) research design	qualitative research, exploratory design, expert interviews (with systematic literature review a pragmatic-interpretivist epistemological approach)
(4) objective of the method	<p>research question: What are the potential requirements for developing the employer value proposition (EVP)?</p> <p>research objective of this thesis: The objective is to develop a set of requirements for systematically determining the EVP:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Identifying the requirements for the EVP and its development in theory (literature review). 2. Requirements currently used in practice, as reported by experts in the field. 3. A comparison and analysis of literature and practice. 4. Conclusions for theory and practice based on the comparison.
(5) selection of the sample	experts, defined by EVP development expertise (inclusion: at least one development project), 28 interviews (saturation point), with in sum over 2,000 developments, mainly in UK, Germany and North America.
(6) conducting the interviews	expert interviews, with interview guide, researcher is interviewer, in-depth interviews, semi-structured, one-to-one interviews, held on videoconference.
(7) data collection	audio- and video-recorded. Fully transcribed
(8) methods of research data analysis	Transcription of the interviews, thematic analysis (Braun/Clarke), coding the data
(9) ethical aspects	declaration of consent, anonymisation (2/28), data protection
(10) weaknesses and quality assurance	<p><i>4 main weaknesses</i>: specific biases: consultant bias (commercial imperative), normative nature of expert knowledge (elite view), and researcher positionality (marketing lens) and</p> <p><i>7 quality assurance strategies</i>: reflexivity, purposeful sampling and <i>depth over breadth</i>, thick description, theory triangulation, systematic documentation and auditability, rigorous and systematic analysis, clarity and persuasive writing.</p>
(11) expected outcome	requirement for the EVP development in practice

Tab. 20: Overview methodology of the study

The subsequent chapters are dedicated to the realisation of this research. Chapter 4 contains the empirical findings, and chapter 5 (p.180) contains the analyses and comparisons.

4. Empirical Findings

This chapter presents the results of the empirical research outlined in the previous chapter.

It should be noted that the reiteration of contributions from multiple experts does not serve to elevate the significance or relevance of the requirement in question but rather indicates the level of professional consensus and prevalence within the current expert community. The relative importance or relevance of individual requirements cannot be determined by the author. The repeated citation of the requirement suggests that it is more prevalent, but it is not within the author's competence to make such a judgement. It is conceivable that the minority viewpoint may be correct and that the majority is lagging behind. These findings provide a comprehensive heuristic framework that invites further testing to establish its usefulness in a variety of organisational settings.

The interviews revealed a total of 48 requirements for the EVP. In line with the theoretical requirements (section 2.11.2, p.69), the requirements should also be assigned to the new EVP process (see Fig. 13, p.63) in this section.

Expert I8 explicitly states that a good EVP involves *“hoping to retain them as much as you are trying to attract people into an organisation”*. He views the EVP as a vital business tool. Expert I7 defines EVP as *“the key factors, why people join and stay with an organisation”*.

Expert I18 defines the first step as the *“Ist-Analyse”*, the current or situation analysis.

4.1 EVP situation analysis

Expert I7 states “a good EVP needs to be thoroughly researched”. The EVP cannot be merely “marketing wash” (Expert I25) by distributing “claims out there that really are not in touch with reality” (Expert I2), as this leads to frustration and high turnover (Expert I1, Expert I25). The EVP needs to be “rooted in data” (Expert I5).

The requirements associated with this phase of the process can be divided into three areas: employee / candidate descriptive analysis, employer descriptive analysis and market descriptive analysis. In total this phase of the process has 26 requirements.

All the following phases are based on the analysed situation, and the results form the basis for the development of the EVP.

4.1.1 Employee (and candidate) descriptive analysis

The experts defined seven requirements within the descriptive analysis of the employees: (A1) Employee needs, (A2) Employee preferences, (A3) Employees’ prior experiences, (A4) Employee relevance, (A5) Employees’ work emotions, (A6) Employees’ expectations towards the employer and (A7) Employees’ willingness to contribute and discretionary effort (see Fig. 20).

Fig. 20: EVP requirements: Employee descriptive analysis

Expert I16's credo is very clear: People must be consulted before developing any EVP. Expert I10 wants to *"speak directly to employees"*. Researchers aim to understand *"attraction attributes"* for new hires and *"engagement and retention attributes"* for long-tenured staff (Expert I4). *"All voices across the organisation need to be listened to"* (Expert I7). Expert I21 stresses that insights from employees are crucial because they reveal *"what they like and what they do not like, and also what they would like to have changed"*.

A fundamental part of the situation analysis phase of EVP development is to gain a full understanding of both existing employees and potential new employees. This critical step involves in-depth research into both internal and external perspectives to uncover what truly resonates with employees. This comprehensive employee analysis ensures the EVP is relevant for the target audience.

For current employees, the aim is to grasp their needs, motivators, and experiences. This is achieved through various methods, including internal surveys, interviews, and focus groups. Expert I20 highlights investigating *"what they like in this company"*. Such insights are vital for shaping culture, driving engagement, and ensuring retention (Expert I4, Expert I5, Expert I3).

For potential employees, the focus shifts to attraction attributes, expectations, and also the labour market situation. This involves external surveys, analysis of competitor offerings, and understanding *"the inherent motivations of the people you're trying to hire"* (Expert I9). *"The information that you*

gather represents people at all kind of levels within the organisation, across all different functions, across all different demographics, etc. Because otherwise you won't achieve that objective and ensuring it's relevant for everybody" (Expert I26). Ultimately, an effective EVP must authentically connect internal realities with external appeal to attract and retain the right talent.

Requirement A1: Analyse employee and candidate needs

Expert I5 focuses on the candidates, underlining that the EVP must *"connect to top talent outside the organization and really align to what their needs are"*. Expert I8, on the other side, refers to the importance of understanding *"the hopes and dreams of people within the business"*. Therefore, it is necessary to analyse the needs of both.

A need is called: This feeling of a deficiency and the desire to eliminate (Hermann, 1870, p.5). Expert I9 calls it: *"The inherent motivations of the people you're trying to hire"*. Expert I1 specifies it: their needs regarding the *"Arbeitswelt"* (working world).

Expert I15 suggests to directly address motivators beyond rational benefits. He states people make decisions emotionally and justify them rationally, so working with the right emotions is key. Expert I10 stresses the importance of hearing it directly from employees.

Expert I24 states: *"The overwhelming majority of people in job search will search by their career goals or aspirations"*. He outlines four impacts people consider: financial, professional (growth, learning, development), cultural (how things are done, community, collaboration), and organisational (company's purpose, stability, leadership).

Expert I26 notes that employee expectations have moved beyond basic needs to higher-level motivations like believing in the company's purpose and values, especially for younger generations who ask about sustainability agenda and how diverse the employer is.

Requirement A2: Analyse employee preferences

The EVP should be aligning with the employee preferences. Therefore, understanding and later addressing employee preferences is key to developing an EVP that fosters genuine *“engagement and retention”* (Expert I4). Expert I1 aims to understand what makes employees feel satisfaction, happiness, pride in their work. Expert I13 emphasises understanding *“What is it that people like?”*.

Expert I7 uses Amazon's pioneering mindset as an example of attracting specific preferences. He also notes that successful companies engage employees by understanding what makes them enjoy their work and creating the right talent model for people who want to work in that environment. Expert I21 notes that people are naturally attracted to well-known brands like *“Google, Meta / Facebook or Apple”*.

Expert I19 highlights a cultural shift where talent attraction is less transactional and more about shared values, culture, and emotional connection, emphasising that employees increasingly look for purpose and cohesion. Expert I16 observes that the value of work has decreased, and newer generations might quit if the job *“war Scheiße”* (was `shit`), reflecting evolving expectations (Expert I16).

Requirement A3: Analyse employees' prior work experiences

One could argue that employees' prior work experiences shape their preferences (A2) and therefore they do not require a separate point, as this is already included. However, previous work experience can provide guidance on selecting and improving employer's attributes. So they are listed as A3.

Beyond initial attraction attributes, the conversations with the employees delve into *“how their experiences here are different to their experiences elsewhere”* (Expert I19). Experts state that *“recent joiners immediately compare*

everything to the last place they worked" (Expert I14), often finding it "very easy to say 'this thing is amazing'. We never used to get this at my last place" (Expert I14). In order to capture this valuable perspective, Expert I16 recommends conducting individual interviews with new hires as well, as they will have a fresh perspective.

The experts have a wealth of information to explore on the employee preferences. Here are some example questions to ask:

- How did the employees perceive the employer from the outside? Three or four months ago, why did they apply? (Expert I16),
- "What attracted them? [...] differences with their previous company. Best practice from their previous company" (Expert I4),
- "Where did they work before, where were they considering working, who was on their consideration list" (Expert I22),
- "What of those things, if any, did you not get at your last company or the company before that?" (Expert I9).

Expert I25 suggests that these in-depth comparative analysis of new employees' perceptions is balanced by the addition of exit interviews, which can reflect "quite polarised views".

A4: Analyse the relevance of employer attributes to employees

For Expert I11 it is crucial to understand: "what parts of the EVP are going to be important to them?". Ideally, the EVP should be relevant to those out there (Expert I1). He provides an example to illustrate this point: If we discover through extensive analytical research that employees place the greatest value in their employer on the canteen, it may not be the most effective feature to emphasise in an EVP, as it may not be a key concern for potential employees (Expert I1). It is concluded that the relevance or importance of the attributes is a necessity. Therefore, Expert I8 tries to find "the sweet spot of people".

Although many experts do not mention the importance of attributes in general, they do highlight specific attributes as being important. The following attributes were listed:

- Compensation and benefits (Expert I2, Expert I24, Expert I12, Expert I22),
- Work experience, culture, and environment (Expert I20, Expert I9, Expert I26, Expert I3, Expert I7, Expert I22),
- Career growth, personal development and progression (Expert I20, Expert I24, Expert I12, Expert I3, Expert I22),
- Social and future-oriented aspects: health (Expert I16), diversity and inclusion and sustainability agenda (Expert I26, Expert I7), purpose (Expert I25) and meaning in work (Expert I25).

A5: Analyse employees' work emotions

Expert I1 discusses the importance of asking employees about their feelings at work. All forms of work and performance have emotional contexts (Gibb, 2011, p.235). What moments make you feel satisfied, happy or proud at work. Expert I10 and Expert I26 emphasise the importance of incorporating sentiment analysis into research. Expert I7 is also gathering emotional insights from employees because they contribute significantly to an EVP.

Expert I6 collects employee feedback through broader surveys to understand the "*Gesamtstimmungslage*" (overall mood) and tenor, and also conducts deeper qualitative 'story camp' sessions with representatives to get emotional experiences and stories.

A6: Analyse employees' expectations towards the employer

As the EVP is a promise made to employees, it is crucial that this promise meets their expectations in order to be effective. Expert I13 is asking: "*What is it they expect from the organisation?*". Expert I23 calls it the demand side of the deal between employer and employee.

Expectations are for Expert I9: "*What does a candidate want when it comes to a job*", such as rewards, work experience and mission or goal of the employer. Expert I25 also includes the current employees and their expectations. Expert I21 wants to understand what employees "would like to have changed".

The experts highlight that the expectations of candidates and employees have changed significantly over the last four years (Expert I16):

- Expert I26 highlights especially the generation Z, which is focused on sustainability and diversity.
- Expert I17 underlines that employees are increasingly demanding flexible working hours, health and well-being, and want a diverse working environment.
- Expert I25 observes a shift from a focus on salary and benefits to a greater emphasis on corporate culture and meaningful work. Flexibility remains a key issue and is becoming even more important.
- Expert I7 points out that the modern workforce expects to see the organisation's attitude towards diversity and inclusion, sustainability, and they want so see "*what the people are like, what the culture is like*".

Expert I14 summarises that "*expectations have changed a lot. And it's not just the young people's expectations*". The power shift from chapter 1.1.2 (see p.3) is showing its impact here.

A7: Analyse employees' willingness to contribute and discretionary effort

While some practitioners define the EVP purely in terms of what the employer provides for employees (Expert I14, Expert I8, Expert I12), others view it as a give and take dynamic (Expert I11, Expert I24, Expert I28, Expert I23, Expert I3). For the latter, "*the balance of the two things [is] really really*

important" (Expert I28). This perspective highlights the need to understand what the employees *"put in"* (Expert I22) and what they offer in the deal between the two parties (Expert I23).

Expert I13 provides an example to illustrate that some employees have a preference for the start-up culture, perceiving it as dynamic and energetic. Stability and structure are priorities for others. It is also important that these attitudes determine their personal willingness to contribute.

Expert I19 specifically looks for employees who go the extra mile: *"If you work for me, you every day have the decision about whether to give me the gift of your discretionary effort. You can decide to engage with your job at your highest degree of professional competence"*. Expert I22 looks for those people, she calls them *"progress champion or internal champion"* especially for the EVP development workshops.

The next section is analysing the employer.

4.1.2 Employer descriptive analysis

Understanding the employer is also for the experts a foundational element in EVP development, requiring a multifaceted investigation into the organisation's current state and future aspirations. Firstly, it involves deeply understanding the internal reality from the perspective of current employees.

The core purpose of the EVP is to capture *"the undeniable truths about working for an organisation"* (Expert I7). The intention is to *"get a feeling for what it means to work at that company"* (Expert I2). *"What does the staff think it's like to work there right now?"* (Expert I9). *"Because the management and the employees often have slightly different opinions"* (Expert I2). This analysis focuses on the factors within the company / employer that potentially influence the employee.

Secondly, the leadership's future vision is paramount. Understanding where the company is headed, what new skills and talents will be needed, and what behaviours leaders aim to shape is crucial for a future-proof EVP.

A total of 16 requirements were reconstructed for this section: A8: Employer describing employee experience (EX), A9: Employer describing employee behaviour / commitment, A10: Employer culture, A11: Employer values, A12: ER leadership and corporate behaviour, A13: Employer internal communication, A14: Employer: Quality of current employees, A15: Employer brand, A16: Employer product and corporate brand, A17: Employer benefits for employees, A18: Employer expectation for employee contributions, A19: Employer corporate strategy, A20: Employer company structure, size and location, A21: Analyse employer purpose, mission, vision, A22: Employer HR- / people strategy and A23: Employer strengths and weaknesses.

A8: Analyse employees' experiences describing the employer

Although employee experience is a characteristic of employees, this point describes the employer and is therefore included in this section.

Expert I12 defines employee experience in pragmatically: *"So if I walk into your organisation, what's my experience going to be? And that's broken down into: training, development, career growth [,] [...] communications, that sense of engagement, that sense of: Do I know where this organisation is going, and do I understand how my contribution is helping to drive that change that journey? Do I fit? What's the sense of teamwork? What's the sense of engagement? What's the sense of belonging and being together?"* (Expert I12).

Expert I9 focuses on *"What is the work experience?"*. Expert I4 and Expert I27 also include the candidate experience in their analysis. Expert I25 analyses the recruitment touchpoints, in order to map the stages from the first point of contact with an organisation onwards. Expert I3 wants to hear *"real*

life examples and stories that really share and reflect that internal experience", "to try to find the red thread that connected the workforce experience" (Expert I19).

Expert I24 points out that it is "not even exactly an experience that can be promised, because the person has a role to play in their own experience that can change [...] their impression, their view, the quality of their experience".

Expert I12 also wants to understand how people's preconceptions prior to joining compare "with the reality of their employment experience" (Expert I12). Others agree (Expert I3, Expert I7, Expert I22). Expert I22 talks about mapping the "whole wheel of employee experience [...] from sort of before you even come in to [...] all the way through to the exit".

Some experts underline the emotional side of the experience, raising questions such as:

- "Wie fühlt es sich an, dort zu arbeiten?" (How does it feel to work there?) (Expert I27),
- "How people have been treated"? (Expert I7),
- "What are the troubles that the people are going through?" (Expert I13),
- Expert I26 is asking employees directly: "are you proud to work for organisation X".

Expert I28 and Expert I5 state that the customer experience and the employee experience are connected. This lends further business relevance to the EVP. Expert I5 highlights Covid-19's impact, shifting "to [...] flexibility and well-being", indicating a change in desired employee experience.

A9: Analyse employee's behaviour (ethnography)

As with A8, although the issue under discussion relates to the behaviour of the employee, this point actually describes the employer. For that reason, it is included in this section.

Apart from the information one gets verbally from the employees, Expert I14 looks for anything that reveals the current employees' opinions. Expert I10 looks for *"what sort of language that people tend to talk in [...]? When do their eyes really light up?"*

Expert I13 analyses employees' engagement with partners and clients. Expert I19 mentions that for *"Marriott we would observe transactions in the lobbies, [...] we would look at gestural motions, [...] some of them also indicated degrees of personal engagement or disengagement"*. Expert I6 uses a variety of employee-related data to gain a comprehensive understanding of an organisation's internal reality, including employees' highlights, hurdles and heartfelt matters.

A10: Analyse employer's corporate culture

Expert I24 describes: *"Culture is how we do things here"*. He points out that *"there tend to be microcultures within organizations"* that are perceived differently. Expert I28 sees culture as *"an ecosystem of many parts"* and accentuates that culture is not owned by the HR team: *"culture is owned by everybody"*.

Expert I20 explains *"culture is important"*, because the new generation wants to have a *"great corporate culture"* (Expert I20). Therefore, candidates want to know: *"What is the work culture? Is it going to be aggressive? Is it going to be comfortable? Is it going to be balanced?"* (Expert I9). Expert I22 starts by asking for a *"baseline of the current culture"*.

Expert I4 stresses the importance of asking *"questions about the [...] culture of the company"* (Expert I4) in order to understand it and actively shape it. To shape it one needs to ask the management: *"What kind of organisation*

do you want to create? What does the culture look like? [...] How does that culture manifest itself in behaviours at any given point" (Expert I11). Expert I1 accentuates that a credible EVP must be deeply rooted in the corporate culture to avoid frustration. Expert I27 emphasises that 70% of employer branding analysis is "*Kulturanalyse*" (culture analysis). He specifically uses focus groups to 'truffle' for positioning-relevant aspects of culture (Expert I27).

In conclusion, culture is becoming an increasingly important consideration, in the context of EVP (Expert I15). Expert I8 and Expert I9 emphasise that there is a reciprocal relationship here, i.e. strong EVP promotes corporate culture. "*The EVP [...] enables [...] to drive culture, [...] to increase the efficiency of recruitment, to increase engagement of everybody who works in a brand ecosystem with us, customers or stakeholders or its people, it becomes a materially vital tool and stops doing something that just focuses on recruiting*" (Expert I8).

A11: Analyse employer's corporate values

When developing an EVP, it's important to analyse existing company materials, including company values. (Expert I2, Expert I7). Expert I27 views corporate values as part of the normative elements of corporate management that provide guidance for the entire organisation.

It is important to understand "*what the valency of it is within the business*" (Expert I14). The EVP should reflect the "*heart and soul and the centre of an organisation*" (Expert I25). An EVP aims to articulate "*why people join and stay with an organisation*" (Expert I7), and corporate values often are "*absolutely essential*" (Expert I25). Some companies explicitly "*link the values [...] to the pillars of their EVP*" (Expert I28).

A12: Analyse employer's leadership and corporate behaviour

Expert I14 notes that leadership principles define “*how the leaders are intending to behave*” (Expert I14). In one of the projects undertaken by Expert I14, the most important information “*was the leadership principles*”.

“*Amazon is run by and organized around a set of 14, now 15 leadership principles. And so what Amazon has done is they've pushed most decision making very far down in the organization. But [...] the number one leadership principle is customer obsession*” (Expert I19).

Expert I9 discusses the Facebook approach of incentivising those who ‘move fast and break things’. He highlights that rewards for staying late or dropping everything promote work ethic, work addiction and flexibility, as well as team spirit (Expert I9).

Leaders define “*what kind of organisation*” they want to create (Expert I11). Expert I6 emphasises that understanding a company's attractiveness is contingent on its collaborative culture and the written and unwritten rules that govern it, underscoring the significance of corporate behaviour.

Expert I9 succinctly states, “*what you reward is who you are*”, directly linking corporate behaviour to the true nature of the EVP. “*Companies care about making money, saving money, getting customers, limiting risk and stroking the ego. That's all the business cares about*” (Expert I9).

A13: Analyse employer's internal communication

The experts often begin the “*internal research*” (Expert I3) phase, by requesting existing internal company communication documents: “*Vision, mission, company values*” (Expert I2). Expert I5 suggests a “*solid audit of their communications platforms and the artifacts that are their commitment*”. Expert I7 wants to see “*how they speak to their people?*” (Expert I7) to understand

their *“tone, the language that they use, but also just to see what they're talking about”* (Expert I7).

A14: Analyse employer's quality of current employees

Expert I23 directly questions the quality of current employees: *“What are the people like? Which kind of people do you have within the company. What are the competencies levels at? Where are they dicks, or are they actually nice people? Are they something you want to be around?”*

Expert I19 directly observes the physical condition and professional engagement of a workforce. At one client he noticed that the employees *“looked tired, they looked stressed, they were overweight, their complexions were pasty”*, giving him the impression of *“a massively unfit, overworked, unhealthy workforce”* (Expert I19).

Expert I22 links employee happiness to productivity: She references *“you know, the classic Harvard business chain [: 'service profit chain']. If people are happier, they're more productive, [...] They make you more money”*. She also explicitly questions the performance of employee segments: *“How do they perform together”*.

A15: Analyse the employer brand

“An employer brand is what people think it's like to work at your company” (Expert I9), *“and what that looks like externally to talent”* (Expert I28). The EVP serves as the foundational blueprint for the employer brand (Expert I7).

“We measure the employer image from outside” (Expert I4). So does Expert I15: *“wie nehmen Menschen mich als Arbeitgeber wahr”* (how people perceive me as an employer). The employer brand is analysed through *“scanning [...] Glassdoor, Indeed”* (Expert I21) and *“through social channels”* (Expert I28).

Expert I15 addresses the "*Branchenhaftungsthema*" (industry liability issue), which directly relates the employer image to the industry image.

A16: Analyse the employer's product and corporate brands

Expert I3 notes that while the corporate brand is "*obviously consumer focused*", the employer brand "*should feel similar to that, but should be slightly different*" (Expert I3).

Expert I16 states that the employer brand is a daughter of the brand and personal marketing is a daughter of marketing, indicating a clear relationship between the corporate brand and the employer brand. Expert I19 views the employer brand as "*an extension of the master brand into the employment space that has a very specific job to do*" in distinguishing the employer.

The employer brand communication messages, which articulate the EVP, "*have to share DNA with what that organisation is saying to different audiences, consumer audiences*" (Expert I12).

Expert I1 highlights the concept of "*Markenpassung*" (brand fit), asserting the importance of not creating a parallel world with the employer brand that contradicts the existing corporate brand or the consumer brand. Expert I25 says, the EVP is "*really connected to the brand*".

The perception of a company's products can profoundly influence its attractiveness as an employer; for instance, companies like Google, Meta, or Apple attract people simply alone, from their name (Expert I21), making the employer branding task easier.

Conversely, a product brand's image can highlight areas for the employer brand to differentiate, as seen with the work Interviewee 1 did with Porsche, whose 'sexy, but very unapproachable' consumer image led their employer brand to focus on familial and human aspects (Expert I1).

Expert I19 advocates therefore for working *“early and often with the brand team”*, to ensure consistent messaging and alignment with the company's overarching vision and values.

A17: Analyse the employer’s benefits for employees

The benefits offered to employees are what an organisation gives to its employees (Expert I11, Expert I28). Experts emphasise that a compelling EVP must showcase both tangible and intangible rewards. This includes *“monetary benefits, flexibility, ways of working career, development, experience, learning and development”* (Expert I11).

However, it's not merely a *“list of benefits”* (Expert I7), it must capture *“emotional things”* (Expert I7), describing how it feels to work there. The EVP is about emotional benefits too, fostering *“identifikationsstiftende Botschaften”* (identity-forming messages) (Expert I27). Expert I24 adds the following points: The nature of your professional relationships, community collaboration, the development of personal relationships, team cohesion, the sharing of resources and mutual support.

The EVP must reflect *“What is it that people like?”* and *“What is it they expect from the organisation”* (Expert I13). Expert I15 has stated that initially, EVP promises were very benefit-oriented, but that there has now been a strong shift towards culture.

A18: Analyse employer expectation for employees’ contributions

This is the other side of the give and get (Expert I3), from the employer’s perspective: the get from the employee’s side. This is what is *“expected of the employee in return”* (Expert I14) for the benefits (A17). As Expert I10 explains, it is *“everything that you're being asked to do for that employer”*.

This may also imply that employees are expected to go the extra mile (Expert I16) or work at a fast pace (Expert I14). Depending on individual employee preferences, this could potentially result in employees choosing to self-identify out (Expert I19). Expert I19 illustrates this with Amazon's focus on a pioneering mindset, which is designed to attract individuals who embrace risk and innovation.

Expert I3 is exploring the demanding side of the employment deal by asking: *“what performance looks like, how performance is evaluated”*.

Expert I16 points out that the EVP can and should also formulate certain expectations for its own staff internally. Expert I25 highlights that it is a two-way deal, where the employer is in charge of *“making sure it's fair and balanced”*.

With this requirement, the four parts directly influencing the employment deal of the incentive contribution theory (see section 2.4.1, p.27) are completed (see Fig. 21).

Fig. 21: Requirements within the incentive contribution theory

A19: Analyse employer's corporate objectives and strategy

In order to establish the company's future direction, leadership interviews are conducted by many experts (Expert I4, Expert I11, Expert I14, Expert I8, Expert I9, Expert I2, Expert I12, Expert I16, Expert I25, Expert I10, Expert I18, Expert I15). The reason is: *"we need to align the EVP to the future of business"* (Expert I4). For Expert I25 the *"EVP is so tightly connected and coupled with the strategy of the organisation"*.

A good EVP will *"have an eye to the future"*, but also *"respect the heritage in the past"* (Expert I8). Expert I11 focuses more on the culture and states that conversations with C-suite and Chief Execs aim to understand the kind of place they want to create. Expert I4 notes *"once you change your company strategy, business strategy you need different skills so you need to attract different people to your company and you change the way you pose yourself as an employer to attract those people"*. Expert I8 states that the EVP *"sits underneath business strategy, with people strategy and before communications"*.

A20: Analyse company's structure, size and location

Company size

"If you're working with a big global business [...] different things matter" (Expert I14). The size influences research methods (Expert I11, Expert I14, Expert I12, Expert I21, Expert I5), and the number of interviews conducted (Expert I4, Expert I2). Furthermore, the duration of the EVP project *"depends on the size of the organisation"* (Expert I12), *"and the complexity of the client"* (Expert I19). Additionally, the resistance to new ideas is higher *"if the company is more than 2,000 people"* (Expert I4).

Company structure

In contrast, an increase in size is typically accompanied by the presence of additional structures (Expert I16) and *"a more settled culture"* (Expert I23). Expert I14 points out that *"businesses that are more like federations,"* grown by acquisition, might have a *"head office that has one culture and then a sub business over there that has a very different culture"*. Expert I2 agrees, acknowledging the difficulty of dealing with a parent company, and lots of subsidiaries that are *"autonomous and have a completely different company culture"*.

In many cases, the company's organisational structure results in a higher number of interviews than necessary, *"because of internal politics: this person needs to be involved"* (Expert I2). The project duration also *"depends on how diverse it is in terms of employee groups"* (Expert I12).

Company location / locations

Expert I3 points out that one has *"to think about those different locations, because of the cultural nuances"*. Expert I5 has expressed a desire *"to learn some of the nuances in each region"*. Furthermore, specific content may be impacted by geographical location: *"benefits, packages are enormously important in America, and [...] in Europe, [...] it's just not as important"* (Expert I14).

Therefore, one *"needs to involve people from all those regions, all those cultures"* (Expert I12), as this may require *"regional tailoring"* (Expert I4). In this instance, the duration is influenced by *"geographies as well"* (Expert I12). There is also a *"version of that for a remote worker"* (Expert I14).

A21: Analyse employer's purpose, vision and mission

The necessity to align the EVP with the purpose, mission and vision of the company has been highlighted by the experts. Expert I25 mentions purpose-

led branding, she believes that the *“meaning in work is going to become even more important to people”*. Expert I26 notes that candidates even *“want to be able to believe in the purpose”*.

The EVP *“must be aligned with the vision of the company”* (Expert I5). *“Because if I do not align everything to what the leadership vision is, the EVP isn't going to serve the right purpose”* (Expert I5). Expert I11, Expert I28, Expert I16, Expert I25, Expert I15 agree. Expert I9 is asking: *“What is the mission”?*. Expert I27, Expert I19, Expert I16, Expert I25, Expert I3 agree.

A22: Analyse employer’s people strategy

Expert I8 notes that in EVP projects, *“if I was working with the UK business, I would typically begin with organisational strategy, people strategy”*.

A23: Analyse employer’s strengths and weaknesses

Expert I2 notes that when conducting internal surveys or focus groups with current employees, they identify *“What are the strengths? But also what are the weaknesses”*. Expert I21 emphasises looking also at online review sites to gain insight into how a company is performing, asking: *“What's good, what's bad”*. Expert I10 asks the employees why they stay and why they joined, focusing on what makes the organisation ‘sticky’.

Expert I18 mentions his *“Stärkenkompass”* (Strength Compass) tool which aims to identify what makes us unique? What makes us great, and where are our currently existing strengths. So we call that excellence strengths. And what are our leverage strengths and blind spots that we should develop in the future?. Expert I24 and his team *“create a scorecard”*, with which they identify strengths and weaknesses of the employer.

As part of the approach endorsed by Expert I23, it is essential to emphasise openness regarding weaknesses. He is an advocate for transparency, even

regarding less favourable aspects of the company. *"I think there's a lot to win there, because if you are just open about some of the areas that are shit. You become a lot more relatable, because people know that things are shit. People know that every company isn't like rainbows and fairy tales"* (Expert I23). This approach has the potential to engender a sense of trust, thereby facilitating a more informed process of self-selection.

The third and final component of the situation analysis pertains to the labour market analysis.

4.1.3 Labour market descriptive analysis

It is vital for experts to understand the external markets and the competitive landscape if they are to achieve distinctiveness. This process entails the thorough examination of competitor offerings, their employer branding messages, and the manner in which target talent perceives various employers (Expert I20, Expert I4, Expert I14, Expert I2, Expert I1, Expert I19, Expert I25, Expert I10, Expert I3, Expert I7, Expert I22).

The objective is to articulate *"why that audience should consider that organisation as an employer"* (Expert I11), whilst simultaneously distinguishing the company from its competitors (Expert I14, Expert I2, Expert I7, Expert I19).

The following characterisation of the labour markets was provided by the experts:

- *"ever crowded market"* (Expert I2),
- the 'developments' on the labour market (Expert I1),
- shortage of specialists (Expert I16),
- labour markets are tightening (Expert I16),
- *"War on talent"* (Expert I14, Expert I2),

- power shift on the labour markets (Expert I25) and, as a result, increasing demands placed on employers by employees (Expert I16, Expert I25).

A24: Analyse the labour markets

Only one expert explicitly mentions the analysis of labour markets: “*We do a number of external surveys that really aim to understand [...] those different labour markets*” (Expert I3). However, many experts describe the labour markets as an influencing factor (Expert I14, Expert I2, Expert I16, Expert I1, Expert I25).

A25: Analyse labour markets influencing trends

A predominant trend is observable in the labour market: Expert I22 and Expert I25 assert that the balance of power has shifted decisively to the employee. Therefore, as Expert I14 notes, the “*deal between employers and employees*” is changing rapidly. This has resulted in a significant shift in expectations (see requirement A5, p.140). It is important to note that this is not merely a matter of young people’s expectations (Expert I14).

Furthermore, the experts have identified several key trends in the labour markets:

- ‘value of work’ has decreased (Expert I2, Expert I1),
- growing importance of ‘meaning in work’ (Expert I25),
- intensifying desire for ‘flexible working models’ (Expert I1, Expert I25),
- increasing relevance of employee ‘health and well-being’ (Expert I1, Expert I26),
- ‘secure position’ as attribute more relevant (Expert I2),
- shift from pay to ‘culture’ (Expert I25, Expert I15),
- ‘sustainability’ (Expert I26),

- 'diversity, equity, and inclusion (DEI)' and 'Black Lives Matter' (Expert I26),
- desire for 'remote work' (Expert I7).

Expert I26 states that practitioners must ensure their development considers 'societal change' and 'workplace trends' that will change future roles. A detailed analysis of the prevailing trends within specific labour markets is imperative.

A26: Analyse the competition

As outlined in A25, there has been a notable shift in power within labour markets, as Expert I25 noted. This shift has led to increased competitiveness and the need to differentiate from competitors in the current market, as Expert I14 and Expert I7 have highlighted. This is particularly relevant in the context of the increasingly crowded labour markets and the war for talent, as Expert I2 has emphasised.

The scope of the competitive analyses carried out varies greatly:

- as a rule, you do not need a competition analysis (Expert I27),
- conduct a "view of the competition" (Expert I10),
- "look at their EVPs" (Expert I2),
- we usually do a small competitive analysis (Expert I15),
- "I like to do a benchmark audit of what their communications looks like versus what I see from their top competitors" (Expert I5),
- looking at the 100 most attractive employers to identify very strongly occupied fields and advising clients not to enter these themes 1:1, essentially a form of benchmarking for differentiation (Expert I1),
- "We've got a kind of spreadsheet which has about 70 different questions that allows us to interrogate the employer brands and EVPs of competitors" (Expert I7).

The objective is to comprehend “*what they are doing, what they are offering*” (Expert I4) and to “*create space between what we are going to say [...] and what the competition is saying*” (Expert I12). This helps avoid me-too brands (Expert I12) by identifying common, highly saturated themes to avoid (Expert I1).

Fig. 22: Expert requirements in the situation analysis phase

Selecting the competitors means “*looking at talent competitors*” and not “*to focus on the commercial competitors*” (Expert I10, Expert I26), often companies from “*completely different industries*” (Expert I14). This often means that the question of who the competitors is not so easy to answer (Expert I1).

These were the 26 requirements for information gathering from the experts' perspective (see Fig. 22). The following section is devoted to creation, i.e. the practical development of the EVP. The points refer to the situation analysis.

4.2 EVP creation

The creation of an EVP is a process. It systematically defines and articulates what an organisation promises to its employees and potential talent.

After gathering comprehensive data, the next step is analysis and synthesis, distilling the information to identify core themes and “*common themes that are emerging*” (Expert I7). These themes “*naturally group together into stories [...] EVP pillars and the foundations*” (Expert I7). The goal is to articulate “*what makes your company special as an employer*” (Expert I4). The final EVP is then typically delivered as a “*strategic framework*” (Expert I22), often a “*short paragraph*” (Expert I20), or an “*EVP guidebook*” (Expert I2) containing the core statement and supporting pillars (Expert I2, Expert I16, Expert I13, Expert I26).

The creation of an EVP is governed by several critical requirements that ensure its effectiveness and longevity.

Please note that the nature of requirements in this section differs from those in the previous section. In this case, the emphasis is on the tangible development, rather than on the accumulation of information. These elements refer to the frequently numerous requirements from the situation analysis.

This section holds 13 requirements: C1: Create relevant EVP, C2: Create an attractive EVP, C3: Create a motivating and engaging EVP, C4: Create EVP reflecting current and future employee experience (including culture) and aspiration, C5: Create an EVP reflecting sentiments, C6: Create competitive EVP, C7: Create a profiling EVP, C8: Create an ownable EVP, C9: Create a believable and honest EVP, C10: Create an effective EVP, C11: Create a deal-related EVP, C12: Create a brand-aligned EVP and C13: Create a selective EVP.

C1: Create a relevant EVP

The requirement 'relevance for the employee', as analysed in A4 (see p.139), should be taken into account during the creation process. This is because, it *"should resonate with target talent, so it has to be closely connected to what's important"* (Expert I25). It must be relevant for the target group (Expert I15), which, for Expert I26, shall be "everybody".

After time, or in the case of creating a new culture, it is important to ensure that *"the EVP is still relevant"* (Expert I28, Expert I3).

C2: Create an attractive EVP

An EVP's purpose is to be *"attractive to the audience you care about"* (Expert I9), serving as *"the common reason why talent are inspired to join, stay and give their best to an organization"* (Expert I5).

The attractiveness encompasses both rational and emotional dimensions (Expert I11). While *"pay and perks"* (Expert I25) are considered, the emotional aspect is crucial (see also requirement C5, p.164), as *"if emotion didn't matter in this, our business [, employer branding consultancy,] wouldn't exist"* (Expert I14).

It is vital that the offer clearly articulates *"what's in it for me"* (Expert I3) and this needs to be attractive (Expert I9, Expert I2, Expert I16, Expert I10, Expert I7) for both prospective and current employees. Expert I14 speaks of *"it's got to be compelling"*, demonstrating the combination of creating attractive and relevant (see requirement C1).

C3: Create a motivating and engaging EVP

Expert I5 states: *"I am so passionate, Philip, about this missed lens of EVP being the secret sauce to driving engagement. It's a much simpler, more important way to drive employee engagement. And every time we have customers that do it with that approach their scores skyrocket"*.

The EVP has been shown to contribute to employee engagement, motivation and productivity (Expert I8). The EVP can resonate “with target talent, [...] [if it is] closely connected to what's important for [them and] [...] motivates them” (Expert I25).

Expert I14 considers internal focus groups to be more than just a research tool; he sees them as “an engagement tool”.

C4: Create an EVP reflecting employee experience including culture and aspiration

There are four points to this requirement: (1) the employee experience (EX) and culture determining the EVP, meaning the EVP reflecting the former, (2) the aspired EX and culture must also determine the EVP, (3) the EVP driving the EX and the culture and (4) the existing EX and culture must serve as a proof point for the EVP (see Fig. 23).

Fig. 23: Interrelationship between EVP and EX / Culture

Ad 1: An EVP must accurately reflect “the undeniable truths about working for an organisation” (Expert I7) and genuinely portray the “actual work reality” (Expert I6). Expert I3 asserts that the EVP must be “reflective of the experience” and that an “inauthentic representation of the business” is “likely to affect retention”. She underscores the importance of collecting “real-life examples and narratives that authentically convey that internal experience”.

Expert I21 stressed the importance of the cultural aspects of the EVP, stating that a good EVP must *"match what the culture is"*. Although the corporate culture is part of the employee experience it shall be named explicitly due to the relevance it has within the EX.

Ad 2: Moreover, the EVP *"will also have an eye to the future, so what the company is working towards and what it will be in the future"* (Expert I8).

To develop an aspirational EVP, it is critical to engage with leadership. *"I want to know what the leaders want. What is missing today to get them there? What are the behaviors they're looking to shape? What are the talents they're going to need in the future? What is this company gonna look like that's gonna be exciting for people in the future. And I want to make sure I've got that really clearly articulated at the leadership lens"* (Expert I5). *"Because the future and the direction and the trajectory of that company is driven by leaders"* (Expert I9).

"And the whole point about an EVP, you're reflecting the direction of that organisation" (Expert I12). Expert I16 sees it as *"ein Licht, wo wir auch alle gemeinsam hinlaufen"* (a light, where we also all run together) for existing employees. *"So you're saying to people: Do you want to be part of our journey? This is where we're going. Do you want to take on that challenge? Do you think your career would benefit from what we're going through"* (Expert I12).

Expert I5 explicitly states that her agency's primary belief is to use *"the EVP to shape culture. Not just great recruitment marketing"*. She aims for the EVP to *"steer your future"* by including an *"aspirational element"* and being *"aligned with the vision of the company"* (Expert I5). Expert I11 asks *"what kind of organisation do you want to create? What does the culture look like?"* (Expert I11). Expert I21 advises that it should be *"a little aspirational, but it's got to be realistic"*.

While it is somewhat optimistic, it is clear that this is the direction in which things are heading (Expert I2). *"I think to some extent it should be stretching, but not too far. I think that credibility is very, very, very important for an EVP"* (Expert I25). *"You want to kind of bring in some of the aspiration in the future vision of the business as well, because otherwise it will date very, very quickly. so you want to kind of have a what we call a bit of stretch in there"* (Expert I7).

"We advocate that every EVP should reflect reality to 85%, but to 15%, it should reflect what we call 'aspirational reality'" (Expert I16). Expert I21 and Expert I7 agree on 80% today's reality and 20% tomorrow's aspiration. Expert I12 and Expert I26 do not give numbers, but they talk about a balance between aspiration and authenticity.

Expert I12 draws a comparison: *"In the UK. we've got a vitamin drink, called Berocca. It's sold with the advertising line 'you on a good day'. So by taking Berocca, you feel a bit better and you feel a bit more, you. And that's effectively, ultimately what we're trying to get in on terms of an organisation. So it has to look forward"*.

Furthermore, the aspirational element encompasses the evaluation of identified external societal changes and workplace trends, such as the impact of AI or remote working, to anticipate how roles might evolve and ensure the EVP looks genuinely forward (Expert I26).

Ad 3: Expert I5 believes the EVP *"must be internally applied to drive the results"*. Expert I10 states that the EVP aims to influence *"how people feel about working at the organisation"*. Expert I4 also says that *"you promise something you say come and work with us, you will get this this is the promise they need to have that experience"*. Expert I22 highlights building a *"culture you need to succeed in the future"*.

Expert I8 states that the EVP is used as a tool to “*drive culture*” and its outcomes include “*a changing culture and improvement in performance for the business*”. Expert I16 believes a good EVP should influence how onboarding, performance reviews, and meetings feel internally.

Ad 4: Expert I22 sees the EX and culture as proof point for the EVP. Expert I25 adds: culture is the “*essential proof point of the EVP*”.

C5: Create an EVP reflecting sentiments

The purpose of an EVP is to facilitate the formation of a well-informed employee decision that is grounded in emotional intelligence. Expert I27 states that an EVP must describe: “*Wie fühlt es sich an, dort zu arbeiten*” (how it feels to work here), which is about describing emotional benefits. He criticises many EVPs for lacking “*emotionale Zugehörigkeit*” (emotional belonging) (Expert I27). Many experts see the relevance of emotions in the EVP (Expert I14, Expert I16, Expert I10, Expert I26, Expert I7).

It is therefore incumbent upon the EVP to translate hard facts into emotive causes. “*It is how people choose jobs. When someone leaves an employer. It's normally because they were upset. They were angry, they felt overlooked. They'd have an argument with their manager. It's a moment of annoyance. And when they choose a new job, it's a triumph of hope. It's: 'I think this one will be better', and I've got to believe this one*” (Expert I14).

Decisions are made in an emotional state, yet rational justifications are then provided to support them. In such circumstances, it is advantageous to employ the appropriate emotions (Expert I6). Expert I26 suggests that the emotional aspect of choosing a job is much more important than just the transactional elements. She compares it to buying a T-shirt that expresses one's beliefs and ethics.

Even factual traits must be translated from the feature into the benefit, into the emotion (Expert I15). Expert I10 stresses the emotionalisation to the narrative of the EVP pillars (Expert I10), focusing on the emotional experience of people (Expert I6).

Ultimately, an emotionally attuned EVP builds "*an emotional connection*" (Expert I7), that connects people to their workplace, in the sense of 'their people' (Expert I22). Expert I6 states: It is important to work with the right emotions that ultimately have a positive impact on people.

C6: Create a competitive EVP

In today's "*very competitive market*" (Expert I25) characterised by a "*war on talent*" (Expert I2), an EVP must answer the fundamental question: Why should people choose to work for you rather than for anyone else? (Expert I14). A strong EVP needs to be "*distinctive, not generic*" (Expert I25), and "*differentiated*" (Expert I2, Expert I26, Expert I7, Expert I15).

If necessary, this can be resolved simply by adjusting the tone of voice (Expert I23) or as Expert I14 puts it: "*say it better and say it more succinctly*" than the competition. However, the EVP still has to be honest (see also C9): be "*unique but also ownable*" (Expert I12).

Without this competitive focus, an employer risks creating a bland employer brand (Expert I7) or a me-too brand (Expert I12) that fails to "*stand out from the crowd*" (Expert I2, Expert I25). This requires focusing on "*what makes them special*" (Expert I8, Expert I2) and leveraging these distinctions.

C7: Create a profiling EVP

Expert I18 uses his tool to visualise identity-creating features. Expert I27 employs the direct phrase "*wenn du es nicht schaffst, zu profilieren, zu*

differenzieren. Ja, dann hast du halt gelust" (if you don't manage to profile, to differentiate. Well, then you've simply lost) (Expert I27).

C8: Create an ownable EVP

Expert I12 emphasises that the EVP needs to be *"also ownable"* and that the organisation *"owns that kind of space"* (Expert I12). *"Like all marketing, what we're trying to find is a value proposition that's competitive that you uniquely can own"* (Expert I19). This is in line with the resource-based view (see section 2.4.1, p.27), where the EVP becomes a unique, inimitable resource.

C9: Create a believable and honest EVP

It is important to note that believable and honest are different concepts. It is possible for something to be true and unbelievable, or believable and untrue. Expert I14 says: An EVP must be *"credible, not true"*; *"there is no point promising people things that they're never going to believe"* (Expert I14). Expert I19 adds: *"And as you'll know from your own background in advertising, when the word in the street doesn't match the words on the ad, the word on the street always wins"*.

However, it should as well *'be true'*, because exaggerated claims will inevitably *"get exposed"* (Expert I21). This results in a phenomenon known as *"marketing wash"* (Expert I25). It *"is terrible to have an EVP like that, because then people come into the organisation and then they find there's no proof, and there's a credibility gap, and then they leave"* (Expert I25).

Expert I3 emphasises this point, noting that *"an inauthentic representation of the business"*, *"is likely to affect retention later down the line"* (Expert I3). *"And it's got to be real. You can't lie your way through it"* (Expert I9). The EVP is not about drawing colourful pictures that are not real (Expert I6). Expert I25 warns that *"the worst sin that you can ever commit"* is a proposition that is not true.

As demonstrated, honesty and credibility are interrelated. Moreover, dishonesty leads to turnover and a *“bad reputation in the job market”* (Expert I4), if former employees are *“out in the marketplace talking about your employer brand and destroying it”* (Expert I22).

Therefore, in this instance, the combination of the two believability and honesty are one requirement in itself. Notably, Expert I27 has expressed concern over the tendency of many companies to prioritise authenticity in their EVP. He expresses his view that it is unfortunate that one must emphasise one's honesty.

C10: Create an effective EVP

Expert I24 has voiced concerns about certain approaches to the EVP, stating that they are *“not very effective. It's not very helpful. It certainly doesn't make value clear for anyone”*, implying that effectiveness is a key goal (Expert I24). Expert I9 clarifies that the primary function of an EVP is to *“influence people's perceptions”*.

The objective of the EVP is to *“influence, how people feel about working at the organisation and taking them to your point of view”* (Expert I10). The EVP should therefore tell its story *“with real conviction, with real consistency”* (Expert I12). Expert I2 states that an EVP should *“resonate internally as well as externally”*.

EVP is a strategy for fostering an emotional connection with employees, and its importance in employee retention is growing (Expert I7). An EVP should have a positive impact on emotional belonging and encourage identification with the company (Expert I27). It is therefore vital that an EVP is both influential and effective. Expert I14 provides a concise summary: *“it's got to be compelling”* (Expert I14).

C11: Create a deal-related EVP

Many of the experts refer to the give and get model (Expert I11, Expert I14, Expert I2, Expert I26, Expert I3). Expert I14 discusses two major views of EVP, one being *“what does the employer bring to the table?”* and a more recent one that includes *“what's expected of the employee in return”* (Expert I14).

Expert I8 elaborates on the deal: *“What do I get into? How and where is the place? How does the environment look? How long is it commutes? All the other things maybe also the feeling in the positive or negative. And then what do I get out of it? Money, but career opportunities, something on the CV”?*

Referring to the book of Adam and Marshall ‘Give & get employer branding’ he finds it *“too thin because I think it looks at it in one way. So what does the company give and what does the company get?”* (Expert I8). Expert I24 agrees: *“I don't think that's broad enough”* and it *“is a little bit too employer-centric way of thinking”* advocating instead for a focus on helping *“the job seeker make a better decision”*.

C12: Create a brand-aligned EVP

Expert I12 asserts that employer branding messages *“have to share DNA with what that organisation is saying to different audiences, consumer audiences”*. *“We don't want our employer branding messages to clash or dilute with what they're saying to consumer audiences clearly”* (Expert I12). Expert I1 highlights that one should not create formally a parallel world with the employer brand but rather operate *“im Schulterschluss”* (in shoulder-to-shoulder action) with the corporate brand and / or consumer brand. This alignment ensures that the employer brand feels like *“facets of the same thing”* (Expert I19).

Experts have differing views on the extent to which the employer brand should align with corporate and consumer brands. On one side are Expert I19, Expert I9 and Expert I10. Expert I19 explicitly states that his consultancy *“doesn't see employer brand and master brand as separate things”*. He conceptualises the employer brand as an *“extension of the 'master brand' into the employment space”*.

Expert I9 is of the opinion that *“there is one brand”* which serves various stakeholders including candidates, investors and consumers. This suggests that the EVP is a facet of this single brand. Expert I10 believes *“the organisation's brand is paramount”* and that *“the employer brand is either a subset of it or [...] looking at the organisation's brand through a different lens”*.

Expert I5 and Expert I3 are positioned in the middle ground, seeing it different but related. Expert I5 says the EVP *“must be aligned [...] to [...] the purpose, vision, values, behaviors. We want to make sure that this is going to be a part of that entire story, not a standalone. It needs to be part of that culture story”* and *“it has to tie to the brand and the vision of the company perfect”*. Expert I3 suggests that the *“employer brand should feel similar to that [corporate brand], but should be slightly different”* and *“should be kind of hand in hand”*.

Expert I11 would give the company more ‘freedom’ here: The organisation has to decide *“How far away from that brand they feel comfortable, whether they want to create something that looks entirely different, sounds entirely different, or whether they want to do something that kind of looks and feels like them”*.

In terms of practical implementation, Expert I24 notes that in the initial stages of a project, they *“will ask for corporate brand guides”*. Expert I14 emphasises adapting the EVP's format to align with existing corporate identity, stating that for companies like GSK and Deutsche Bank, the EVP needed

to “*feel the same*”, “*have the same tone of voice*”, and “*look the same on the page*” as their corporate brands, making it “*feel very familiar*” to the internal audience (Expert I14). “*We try to work early and often with the brand team*” (Expert I19).

Aside from the alignment, Expert I21 highlights that well-established company or product brands such as Google, Meta and Apple, significantly influence attraction, thereby making the employer branding work “*probably easier because there's not a lot of selling people because they know who you are*” (Expert I21).

C13: Create a selective EVP

A EVP is strategically designed to be selective and self-selective by attracting precisely “*the right people on the bus and let the wrong people self-select out of the process*” (Expert I11). By selecting the desired candidates and swiftly eliminating those who do not meet the criteria, the recruitment process can be significantly streamlined (Expert I16).

The objective is to “*create a differentiating message that helps me decide whether I'm in or out*” (Expert I19). He employs Amazon as a case study, where messaging aimed to help “*people self-identify out and say, that doesn't sound good to me. I don't want to do that*” (Expert I19).

As Expert I23 contends, being “*very specific towards who shouldn't apply*”, engenders a heightened level of magnetism, thereby attracting individuals who are more closely aligned with the company's cultural and professional values.

Fig. 24: Expert requirements of the creation phase

The creation phase is subject to a total of 13 requirements, as mentioned by the experts (see Fig. 24).

4.3 EVP characteristics

Following the process, the EVP is developed after the creation phase. In this section, we will be examining the requirements for the EVP itself.

The present section comprises a total of 8 requirements: H1: clear, H2: concise, H3: measurable, H4: robust but flexible, H5: structured, H6: practical, H7: specific, and H8: validated.

H1: Ensure the EVP is clear

Expert I1 states that an EVP must be simply written and understandable. *"You want to get the simplest possible definition that you can, down on a piece of paper"* (Expert I14). He prefers clarity, especially, *"if you are a multinational business where lots of people like yourself are working in a second or possibly third language"* (Expert I14). Expert I24 states that *"the more complicated the problem, the simpler we have to make the solution"*. *"I think one of the challenges of our sector and landscape is potentially over-complicating things"* (Expert I12).

H2: Ensure the EVP is concise

Expert I8 acknowledges a simple statement (H1) is important, but it can be *“too simplistic”*, if it lacks underlying depth (Expert I8). Expert I9 insists it has to be specific enough that it's meaningful. Others agree: *“zugespitzt und fokussiert”* (pointed and focused) (Expert I1), the shortest, most compressed answer (Expert I16), *“one sentence that is powerful”* (Expert I21), *“succinctly”* (Expert I11, Expert I14), *“a little phrase that encapsulates everything”* (Expert I7).

H3: Ensure the EVP is measurable

Expert I13 posits the observation that human resources departments encounter significant challenges in justifying the associated costs, because demonstrating *“that employer branding is what is getting you the right candidates”* remains a prevailing concern. Furthermore, he emphasises the necessity for *“statistically significant”* data to ensure a tangible impact on the study's outcome (Expert I13). Expert I11 confirms that the *“The ROI of an employer brand is always a question we get asked. The best answer for that, by the way I was given was, what's the ROI of a desk? What's the ROI of a roof? You don't need to know, to know that it's important”*.

As Expert I12 observes, one of the *“key challenges that the industry faces is coming up with metrics, and that impress senior leaders”*. Furthermore, to demonstrate how EVP investment has *“shaved this off the bottom line, or we've added this to the bottom line”* (Expert I12). Expert I9 poses the question, *“How do you measure the value of the employer brand?”* and links it to business outcomes such as the recruitment of high-calibre personnel and achieving a growth rate that exceeds the previous one. He emphasises that *“without value, what the hell are you doing all day”* (Expert I9).

Expert I5 characterises the EVP as a *“much simpler, more important way to drive employee engagement”*, and provides *“beautiful metrics on how it can*

shape the business", citing examples like *"the single biggest jump in employee engagement we have ever seen"* and an *"employee net promoter score went from negative 10 to plus 65 within 12 months of launching their employer brand"*. She stresses that the EVP's impact *"must be internally applied to drive the results"* (Expert I5).

Expert I26 makes reference to the use of *"sentiment analysis"* from review platforms to gauge *"negative versus positive sentiment"* about an employer brand. This analysis contributes to the comprehension of the effectiveness of the EVP. Expert I14 discusses the utilisation of internal staff surveys for the purpose of 'sense checking' and tracking trends over time, as a means of measurement. Expert I25 alludes to be using metrics under the excellence dimension for the evaluation of the *"strength and health of the culture and people"*, signifying a quantitative assessment approach. She also refers to *"tangible proof points"* to substantiate the commitment to the EVP.

H4: Ensure the EVP is robust but flexible

Expert I10 explains, an EVP *"should be almost permanent"*, with its core source material remaining *"largely [the] same"*. An EVP should be robust (Expert I11, Expert I12, Expert I25). In terms of longevity, Expert I2 states an EVP should be *"valid for the next three to five years, maybe even longer"*.

Although the EVP is intended to be robust, there are also voices calling for a certain degree of flexibility. Expert I11 asserts that an EVP *"should naturally have flexibility in it"* while remaining *"one overarching one"*. Expert I8 poses the explicit question about the EVP: *"is it flexible, does it allow an organisation to change what it says to a different group based on what that particular group is interested in?"* Furthermore, he also states that *"the EVP should evolve. It's a practice, not a project"* and *"it will also have an eye to the future"* (Expert I8).

Expert I3 defines the EVP as *"what the organisation is doing for talent to make them want to join the business?"*. Because of that, she highlights the

"ability to flex it" for "different circumstances or for different talent audiences" (Expert I3).

H5: Ensure the EVP is structured

Expert I26 advocates for "one unifying EVP", "one thing that's relevant to everybody" (Expert I26). It "should bind everyone together" (Expert I2). He insists, "they should only be one, no matter how big a company is", and it "really should be one leading idea for everyone something that's memorable". Expert I16 uses two pictures: "einen roten Faden" (a common thread) and "das Dach ist für alle gleich" (the roof is the same for everyone) (Expert I16). Expert I11 and Expert I3 agree on one overarching EVP.

The EVP can be seen as a tagline (Expert I23, Expert I3) or a slogan (Expert I24). "When we deliver the EVP statement, it's almost never a single statement. It has to have its pillars. It has to have its associated content themes" (Expert I13).

Expert I21 explains that the concise main EVP is supported by "pillars behind that" which "remain in the background" and "build it up to be who they are" (Expert I21). Expert I16 elaborates that under the EVP, there are certain pillars of arguments, dimensions, and perhaps one needs to focus a little more on pillars 1 and 2 for one target group and pillars 2 and 3 for target group two (Expert I16).

Expert I7 explains that research insights "quite naturally group together into stories". Each pillar must be provable, verifiable, authentic and substantiated (Expert I16).

A more elaborated version has some more elements (see Fig. 25):

- The EVP has a tagline and a story or narrative (Expert I23, Expert I3),

- The pillars have a narrative and emotionalisation (Expert I10, Expert I7),
- Additionally there is a list of proof points (Expert I25, Expert I7).

Fig. 25: Different EVP structures / houses

H6: Ensure the EVP is practical

Expert I11 sees the EVP as a *“functional thing”*. The EVP must be usable for further work (Expert I1). Expert I12 explicitly includes *“actionable”* as a requirement for an EVP.

Expert I14 explicitly states there is *“no point creating a model that no one can use”*, concluding the importance of *“practicality”*. He clarifies that an EVP must be *“unambiguous to the people who are actually going to use it every day”* and enable them to *“write better job ads”*, *“write the onboarding”*, *“talk to existing employees”*, and *“inform”* various communications. He advocates for testing of the *“pragmatism of the model itself”* to ensure its ease of use.

In the opinion of Expert I8 the EVP *“becomes a value-adding business tool”* and a *“proper business tool”* that *“enables the employer brand to work”* and

is a "*materially vital tool*". Furthermore, he emphasises that a successful EVP must be flexible (see H4, p.173), allowing an organisation to adapt its message to different groups based on their individual interests (Expert I8).

Expert I4 stresses the necessity of implementing the EVP at various touch-points, stating that "*most of the projects stop here because implementing is different and difficult*" (Expert I4).

H7: Ensure the EVP is specific

Expert I9 explains: "*So it's got to be specific; meaning, if it's not specific, it's just platitudes. It's just broad. It's not about this company. It's about any company*". Expert I25 agrees that one requirement is that it is "*not generic*". "*Let's just nail this thing down as something very precise*" (Expert I14).

H8: Ensure the EVP is validated

Validation is multi-faceted. The EVP needs "*to land internally*" (Expert I21). This often involves internal validation (Expert I27). Expert I4 notes that after gathering information, they present findings to a large audience, including top management, to get "*the confirmation of our ideas, we have ideas they confirm*".

Expert I23 has a quick validation test: "*What is filmable about this?*" (Expert I23). Some experts do the validation in a focus groups (Expert I4, Expert I2, Expert I27, Expert I15). Expert I27 calls it "*Rückpass an die Mitarbeiter*" (pass back to the employees).

Expert I7 presents questions like: Does this feel accurate to you? May I kindly enquire as to whether there is anything missing? Could you please advise whether there are any items that should be included? Furthermore, it is imperative to select elements that exude authenticity and align with you (Expert I7).

Expert I24 identifies retention and attrition rates as “*the best metric*” to validate an EVP. Expert I20 adds: “*It's not the one-time thing, you have to always look at it and renew it and check if it's still valid for the employees*”.

Fig. 26: Expert requirements of the EVP characteristics

The experts mentioned eight requirements for the EVP characteristics in total (see Fig. 26). In the following section, an analysis will be conducted on the second part of the creation phase.

4.4 EVP creation 2: Attribute optimising

A core aspect of optimisation is balancing authenticity with aspiration. While an EVP must fundamentally represent “*the undeniable truths about working for an organisation*” (Expert I7) and be credible and true, it can also incorporate a future-oriented dimension (see C4, p.161).

O1: Improve employer attributes

The ongoing improvement of the employer attributes ensures that the EVP “*promise became an experience*” for employees (Expert I4). In other words, the aspirational part of the EVP has now been realised.

This “*balance between aspiration and authenticity*” (Expert I12) allows companies to indicate future improvements without making “*false promises*” (Expert I2), which could result in high staff turnover and a “*bad reputation*” (Expert I4). If claims “*are not in touch with reality*”, current employees will feel dishonoured and annoyed (Expert I2). The gap between the current reality and the desired future makes improvement a necessity for authenticity and sustained success.

The initial situation analysis in EVP development is designed to identify areas for improvement. This involves deeply understanding the internal reality. These insights often expose “*what's not so good*” (Expert I2) or “*where your biggest hole is right now*” (Expert I5). For instance, a drop in engagement scores necessitates probing “*what is behind that?*” (Expert I4) to identify underlying issues. Moreover, as time progresses, it is essential to assess the continued relevance of the EVP (Expert I28, Expert I3).

Expert I22 talks about assessing “*the health of the internal culture*” and defining “*where the culture is now versus where they would like to see it*”, which implicitly means working towards improving it. She also references a stop, start, continue model which directly addresses areas to stop (behaviours getting in the way) and start (new initiatives), leading to positive change.

Therefore, the EVP acts as a “*blueprint*” (Expert I7), guiding the organisation towards necessary changes. Ultimately, improving as an employer is an ongoing journey that continuously refines the organisation's promise to its talent.

Fig. 27: Expert requirement of the second creation phase

In total, the experts identified one requirement for the second creation phase (see Fig. 27). They identified a total of 48 requirements for EVP development.

Conclusion: chapter 4

This chapter presents the empirical findings from 28 expert interviews, identifying a total of 48 practical requirements. These were categorised systematically into the process phases of situation analysis, creation and optimisation, as well as the structural characteristics of the EVP characteristics.

This comprehensive dataset forms the empirical basis for the comparative analysis in chapter 5. While the frequency of expert mentions indicates prevalence within the sample, it does not automatically equate to universal relevance.

5. Analysis and comparison

This chapter analyses the empirical data and presents findings by grouping the experts and comparing those groups (intra-empirical analysis). Furthermore, the total results of the interviews are compared to the theoretical results from section 2.11.2 (see p.69). Subsequently, reflecting on the analysed data places the findings in a broader academic and strategic context with regard to shifts in power and marketing frameworks. Finally, the assumptions, limitations and delimitations of this research are discussed.

5.1 Analysis: Empirical data by group

Please note that also here multiple mentions of different experts do not make a requirement more important or relevant. Multiple mentions merely indicate that the requirement is more widespread.

This section employs a systematic approach to analyse the views of the experts by grouping and comparing them. The following comparisons were made:

- over all experts,
- by country/region,
- by expertise (years in field),
- by view: internal or external (in-house or consultant),
- by experts' academic background and
- by experts' field background.

5.1.1 Comparison across all experts

A detailed comparison demonstrates significant differences in the prevalence of various requirements.

(1) Summary of requirements by expert mention frequency

Most frequently mentioned requirements

These tasks were mentioned more frequently, indicating a strong consensus regarding their prevalence:

- A8: Analyse employees' experiences describing the employer (18 experts; a list of the experts with the mentioned number of requirements can be found in appendix 5, p.298),
- A4: Analyse the relevance of employer attributes to employees (17 experts),
- C4: Create an EVP reflecting EX including culture and aspiration (15 experts),
- A6: Analyse employees' expectations towards the employer (14 experts).

Least frequently mentioned requirements

These are the least frequently mentioned requirements. However, it is imperative to acknowledge that this phenomenon may be attributable to a number of factors. The following three possibilities could be considered: (a) the requirements could be of lesser importance, (b) it could be one that is rarely used, because it is rarely important, or (c) it could be one that is rarely used, and only a few experts are aware of its importance. It is recommended that this topic be the subject of further research.

- A22: Analyse employer's people strategy (1 expert).
- C7: Create a profiling EVP (2 experts).
- A5: Analyse employees' work emotions (3 experts).

- A14: Analyse employer's quality of current employees (3 experts).
- C3: Create a motivating and engaging EVP (3 experts).
- H1: Ensure the EVP is clear (3 experts).
- H7: Ensure the EVP is specific (3 experts).

It is evident that all requirements are mentioned by at least one subject matter expert, given that these requirements were developed by said experts.

(2) Areas where differences are apparent

Analytical tasks (A):

This category demonstrates the widest range of expert consensus, with A8 being mentioned by 18 experts and A22 being mentioned by only one expert. It is clear that a significant emphasis is placed on understanding the perspectives, characteristics, and experiences of employees (A8, A4, A6, A2), suggesting that these elements are widely considered in the development of the EVP. Conversely, analyses such as personnel strategy (A22), work emotions (A5) and the quality of current employees (A14) are mentioned significantly less frequently.

Creation tasks (C):

There is a high level of consensus on the creation of an EVP that reflects employee experience and culture, and is believable and honest (C4, C9). However, more specific or niche creation tasks, such as creating a profiling EVP (C7), or an motivating and engaging EVP (C3), receive much fewer mentions. It can be deduced that the broad, fundamental aspects of EVP creation are more universally agreed upon.

Improvement / optimisation (O):

Only one requirement, O1, is listed: ‘Improvement of employer attributes’. This requirement is mentioned by a significant number of experts (9), which indicates its widespread prevalence.

Characteristics (H):

While the requirement of a structured EVP is acknowledged (H5: 12 experts), characteristics related to conciseness (H2: Ensure the EVP is concise), or specificity (H7: Ensure the EVP is specific, H1: Ensure the EVP is clear) are less frequently mentioned. This finding suggests that more experts view the completeness and organisation of an EVP as a requirement than its brevity or narrow focus.

The following table (Tab. 21) provides an overview of each requirement, the total number of experts who mentioned it, and their respective IDs.

ID	requirement description	number of experts	expert IDs
A1	Analyse employee and candidate needs	9	I5, I9, I10, I15, I23, I24, I25, I26, I28
A2	Analyse employee preferences	13	I1, I2, I3, I7, I13, I14, I16, I19, I20, I21, I22, I25, I26
A3	Analyse employees’ prior work experiences	7	I4, I9, I14, I16, I19, I22, I25
A4	Analyse the relevance of employer attributes to employees	17	I1, I2, I3, I5, I7, I8, I9, I11, I12, I15, I16, I20, I21, I22, I24, I25, I26
A5	Analyse employees’ work emotions	3	I1, I3, I6
A6	Analyse employees’ expectations towards the employer	14	I5, I7, I9, I10, I12, I13, I14, I16, I17, I21, I22, I23, I25, I26
A7	Analyse employees’ willingness to contribute + discretionary effort	11	I3, I8, I11, I12, I13, I14, I19, I22, I23, I24, I28
A8	Analyse employees’ experiences describing the employer	18	I1, I3, I4, I5, I6, I7, I9, I10, I12, I13, I17, I19, I22, I24, I25, I26, I27, I28
A9	Analyse employee’s behaviour (ethnography)	8	I5, I6, I9, I10, I13, I14, I19, I23
A10	Analyse employer’s corporate culture	13	I1, I4, I6, I8, I9, I11, I14, I15, I20, I22, I24, I27, I28
A11	Analyse employer’s corporate values	8	I2, I4, I7, I14, I18, I25, I26, I28
A12	Analyse employer’s leadership and corporate behaviour	6	I3, I6, I9, I11, I14, I19
A13	Analyse employer’s internal communication	5	I2, I3, I5, I7, I12
A14	Analyse employer’s quality of current employees	3	I18, I22, I23
A15	Analyse the employer brand	6	I4, I7, I9, I15, I21, I28
A16	Analyse the employer’s product and corporate brands	8	I1, I3, I4, I12, I16, I19, I21, I25
A17	Analyse the employer’s benefits for employees	10	I3, I7, I9, I11, I13, I15, I18, I24, I27, I28
A18	Analyse employer expectation for employees’ contributions	7	I3, I10, I14, I16, I17, I19, I25

ID	requirement description	number of experts	expert IDs
A19	Analyse employer's corporate objectives and strategy	12	I2, I4, I8, I9, I10, I11, I12, I14, I15, I16, I18, I25
A20	Analyse company's structure, size and location	11	I2, I3, I4, I5, I11, I12, I14, I16, I19, I21, I23
A21	Analyse employer's purpose, vision and mission	11	I3, I5, I9, I11, I15, I16, I19, I25, I26, I27, I28
A22	Analyse employer's people strategy	1	I8
A23	Analyse employer's strengths and weaknesses	6	I2, I10, I18, I21, I23, I24
A24	Analyse the labour markets	6	I1, I2, I3, I14, I16, I25
A25	Analyse labour markets influencing trends	7	I1, I2, I14, I15, I22, I25, I26
A26	Analyse the competition	11	I1, I2, I4, I5, I7, I10, I12, I14, I15, I26, I27
C1	Create a relevant EVP	4	I3, I15, I25, I28
C2	Create an attractive EVP	9	I2, I3, I5, I7, I9, I10, I11, I14, I16
C3	Create a motivating and engaging EVP	3	I5, I8, I14
C4	Create an EVP reflecting EX including culture and aspiration	15	I2, I3, I4, I5, I6, I7, I8, I9, I11, I12, I16, I21, I22, I25, I26
C5	Create an EVP reflecting sentiments	9	I6, I7, I10, I14, I15, I16, I22, I26, I27
C6	Create a competitive EVP	11	I1, I2, I7, I8, I12, I14, I15, I19, I23, I25, I26
C7	Create a profiling EVP	2	I18, I27
C8	Create an ownable EVP	6	I1, I2, I12, I14, I19, I25
C9	Create a believable and honest EVP	13	I1, I2, I3, I4, I5, I6, I9, I14, I19, I21, I22, I25, I27
O1	Improve employer attributes	9	I2, I3, I4, I5, I7, I12, I15, I22, I28
H1	Ensure the EVP is clear	3	I1, I12, I14
H2	Ensure the EVP is concise	6	I1, I7, I8, I11, I16, I21
H3	Ensure the EVP is measurable	8	I5, I9, I11, I12, I13, I14, I25, I26
H4	Ensure the EVP is robust but flexible	6	I2, I8, I10, I11, I12, I25
H5	Ensure the EVP is structured	12	I2, I3, I7, I10, I11, I13, I16, I21, I23, I24, I25, I26
H6	Ensure the EVP is practical	4	I1, I4, I8, I14
H7	Ensure the EVP is specific	3	I9, I14, I25
H8	Ensure the EVP is validated	8	I2, I4, I7, I15, I21, I23, I24, I27

Tab. 21: Detailed comparison table of requirements across experts

5.1.2 Comparison by country / region

This analysis identifies differences and similarities based on the expert's location. Here are the country groupings and the number of experts in each:

- *United Kingdom* (UK): 12 experts (I3, I4, I7, I8, I10, I11, I12, I14, I22, I25, I26, I28)
- *Germany* (D): 8 experts (I1, I2, I6, I15, I16, I17, I18, I27)
- *USA* (including Canada): 5 experts (I5, I9, I19, I21, I24)
- *Other* (Denmark, Iran, India): 3 experts (I13, I20, I23)

As the number of experts per country varies, it makes more sense to use percentages for comparison purposes (see Tab. 22).

Analysis (A) Requirements	UK (N=12)	Germany (D) (N=8)	USA (N=5)	Other (N=3)
A1: Employee & candidate needs	33.3%	12.5%	60.0%	33.3%
A2: Employee preferences	50.0%	37.5%	40.0%	66.7%
A3: Employees' prior work experiences	33.3%	12.5%	40.0%	0.0%
A4: Employer attributes relevance	66.7%	50.0%	80.0%	33.3%
A5: Employees' work emotions	8.3%	25.0%	0.0%	0.0%
A6: Employees' expectations	58.3%	25.0%	60.0%	66.7%
A7: Willingness to contribute	58.3%	0.0%	40.0%	66.7%
A8: Experiences describing employer	75.0%	50.0%	80.0%	33.3%
A9: Employee's behaviour (ethnography)	16.7%	12.5%	60.0%	66.7%
A10: Employer's corporate culture	50.0%	50.0%	40.0%	33.3%
A11: Employer's corporate values	50.0%	25.0%	0.0%	0.0%
A12: Leadership & corporate behaviour	25.0%	12.5%	40.0%	0.0%
A13: Internal communication	25.0%	12.5%	20.0%	0.0%
A14: Quality of current employees	8.3%	12.5%	0.0%	33.3%
A15: Analyse the employer brand	25.0%	12.5%	40.0%	0.0%
A16: Product & corporate brands	33.3%	25.0%	40.0%	0.0%
A17: Employer's benefits for employees	33.3%	37.5%	40.0%	33.3%
A18: Employer expectation for contributions	33.3%	25.0%	20.0%	0.0%
A19: Corporate objectives & strategy	58.3%	50.0%	20.0%	0.0%
A20: Company's structure, size, location	41.7%	25.0%	60.0%	33.3%
A21: Employer's purpose, vision, mission	41.7%	37.5%	60.0%	0.0%
A22: Employer's people strategy	8.3%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
A23: Employer's strengths & weaknesses	8.3%	25.0%	40.0%	33.3%
A24: Labour markets	25.0%	37.5%	0.0%	0.0%
A25: Labour market influencing trends	33.3%	37.5%	0.0%	0.0%
A26: The competition	50.0%	50.0%	20.0%	0.0%
Creation Requirements (C)	UK (N=12)	(D) (N=8)	USA (N=5)	Other (N=3)
C1: Create a relevant EVP	25.0%	12.5%	0.0%	0.0%
C2: Create an attractive EVP	41.7%	25.0%	40.0%	0.0%
C3: Create a motivating and engaging EVP	16.7%	0.0%	20.0%	0.0%
C4: Create an EVP reflecting EX	75.0%	37.5%	60.0%	0.0%
C5: Create an EVP reflecting sentiments	41.7%	50.0%	0.0%	0.0%
C6: Create a competitive EVP	50.0%	37.5%	20.0%	33.3%
C7: Create a profiling EVP	0.0%	25.0%	0.0%	0.0%
C8: Create an ownable EVP	25.0%	25.0%	20.0%	0.0%
C9: Create a believable and honest EVP	41.7%	50.0%	80.0%	0.0%
C10: Create an effective EVP	33.3%	12.5%	20.0%	0.0%
C11: Create a deal-related EVP	41.7%	12.5%	20.0%	0.0%
C12: Create a brand-aligned EVP	41.7%	12.5%	80.0%	0.0%
C13: Create a selective EVP	8.3%	25.0%	20.0%	33.3%
Optimising (O) Requirements	UK (N=12)	(D) (N=8)	USA (N=5)	Other (N=3)
O1: Improve employer attributes	50.0%	25.0%	20.0%	0.0%
Have (H) Requirements	UK (N=12)	(D) (N=8)	USA (N=5)	Other (N=3)
H1: Ensure the EVP is clear	16.7%	12.5%	0.0%	0.0%
H2: Ensure the EVP is concise	25.0%	25.0%	20.0%	0.0%
H3: Ensure the EVP is measurable	41.7%	0.0%	40.0%	33.3%
H4: Ensure the EVP is robust but flexible	41.7%	12.5%	0.0%	0.0%
H5: Ensure the EVP is structured	50.0%	25.0%	40.0%	66.7%
H6: Ensure the EVP is practical	25.0%	12.5%	0.0%	0.0%

Analysis (A) Requirements	UK (N=12)	Germany (D) (N=8)	USA (N=5)	Other (N=3)
H7: Ensure the EVP is specific	16.7%	0.0%	20.0%	0.0%
H8: Ensure the EVP is validated	16.7%	37.5%	40.0%	33.3%

Tab. 22: Requirements by country group (in percent)

Note: Bold percentages indicate the highest or lowest (0%) mentions within that specific row across the groups. Percentages are calculated relative to the total number of experts within each country group.

(1) General trends across groups

UK experts generally exhibit high engagement across most categories, often leading or being among the top in analysis of employee experiences (A8), employer corporate values (A11), and corporate objectives and strategy (A19). In terms of EVP creation, they are notable for focusing on creating an EVP that reflects employee experience (EX), including culture and aspiration (C4) and is attractive (C2). They also place a higher emphasis on the EVP being robust but flexible (H4) and structured (H5).

German experts show a notable focus on internal aspects and existing structures. They have the highest mention percentage for analysing employees' work emotions (A5) and the labour market requirements (A24 and A25) and are equally high with UK experts in analysing corporate culture (A10) and competition (A26). In EVP creation, German experts uniquely mention the need to Create a profiling EVP (C7) (25.0% vs 0% in all other groups) and show a strong focus on EVP reflecting sentiments (C5), and being believable and honest (C9).

USA (including Canada) experts show a particularly strong emphasis on analysing employee and candidate needs (A1), employee behaviour (A9), and employer's purpose, vision, and mission (A21), often having the highest percentage of mentions in these areas. They also lead significantly in the creation of an EVP that is believable and honest (C9) and brand-aligned (C12). This suggests a focus on understanding the workforce deeply and ensuring the

EVP aligns with the core identity and values of the organisation (A1, A9, C9, C12).

'Other' (Denmark, Iran, India) *experts*, despite being a smaller group, show a very high percentage in analysing employee preferences (A2), employees' willingness to contribute and discretionary effort (A7), and employee behaviour (ethnography) (A9). This suggests a strong emphasis on understanding the individual employee and their direct contributions. They also have the highest percentage for a structured EVP (H5).

(2) Specific differences: in relation of country / region

(2.1) Areas where one group is significantly *more mentioned*

UK:

- EX and culture-centric EVP: They stand out in mentioning creating an EVP reflecting EX including culture and aspiration (C4) (75.0% vs. 37.5% in Germany, 60.0% in USA, 0.0% in Other).
- EVP characteristics: They lead in the importance of an EVP being robust but flexible (H4) (41.7% vs. 12.5% in Germany, 0.0% in USA/Other), and measurable (H3) (41.7%).
- Corporate values: They place a higher emphasis on analysing employer's corporate values (A11) (50.0% vs. 25.0% in Germany, 0.0% in USA/Other).

Germany:

- Internal emotional & profiling aspects: German experts show the highest focus on analysing employees' work emotions (A5) (25.0% vs. 8.3% in UK, 0.0% in USA/Other). They are also unique in mentioning creating profiling EVP (C7) (25.0% vs. 0.0% in all other groups).

- Analyse labour markets (A24 and A25): German experts lead in the mentioning (37.5%, higher than all others).
- Sentiment reflection: They show the highest percentage for creating EVP reflecting sentiments (C5) (50.0% vs. 41.7% in UK, 0.0% in USA/Other).

USA (including Canada):

- Employee/candidate focus: They lead in analysing employee and candidate needs (A1) (60.0% vs. 12.5% in Germany, 33.3% in UK and Other), and employees' experiences describing the employer (A8) (80.0% vs. 50.0% in Germany, 75.0% in UK, 33.3% in Other).
- Organisational understanding: They have the highest focus on analysing employees' relevance of the employer attributes (A4) (80.0%) and company's structure, size and location (A20) (60.0%).
- EVP messaging: They overwhelmingly prioritise creating a believable and honest EVP (C9) (80.0%) and brand-aligned EVP (C12) (80.0%), significantly more than any other group.

Other (Denmark, Iran, India):

- Employee engagement & behaviour: These experts lead significantly in analysing employee preferences (A2) (66.7%), employees' willingness to contribute and discretionary effort (A7) (66.7%), and employee behaviour (ethnography) (A9) (66.7%).
- EVP structure: They have the highest percentage for having a structured EVP (H5) (66.7%).

(2.2) Areas where specific requirements are *less or not mentioned*

UK:

- Generally, UK experts mention most categories at some level, with no 0.0% mentions in any of the analysis categories. Their lowest percentages

(8.3%) are A5 (work emotions), A14 (quality of current employees), A22 (people strategy) and A23 (strengths & weaknesses).

- They only show 0.0% for C7: Create a profiling EVP, which is uniquely mentioned by Germany.
- They show the lowest compared scores in analysing employer's strengths & weaknesses (A23), creating validated (H8), and selective EVPs (C13).

Germany:

- Lower focus on employee contribution & behaviour: German experts show 0.0% for analysing employees' willingness to contribute and discretionary effort (A7) and 12.5% in employee's behaviour (ethnography).
- Less need-oriented: only 12.5% in employee & candidate needs (A1).

USA (including Canada):

- Absence in market & internal quality analysis: USA experts do not mention the analysis of labour markets (A24), labour market influencing trends (A25), or the quality of current employees (A14). This is a distinct difference from UK and German experts, who mention these areas significantly.
- Less on specific EVP attributes: They also do not mention creating a relevant EVP (C1), creating EVP reflecting sentiments (C5), creating profiling EVP (C7), and have low percentages (20.0%) in: creating motivating and engaging EVP (C3), creating an effective EVP (C10), or creating a deal-related EVP (C11).
- EVP clarity/robustness: They show 0.0% for having a clear EVP (H1), robust but flexible EVP (H4), and practical EVP (H6).

Other (Denmark, Iran, India):

- Broad absence in organisational and brand analysis/creation: This group shows a significant number of 0.0% mentions across various aspects, particularly in the analysis of employer's corporate aspects like values (A11), leadership (A12), internal communication (A13), employer brand (A15), product/corporate brands (A16), corporate objectives and strategy (A19),

purpose, vision, and mission (A21), people strategy (A22), labour markets (A24, A25), and competition (A26).

- They also have no mentions for most EVP creation categories (C1-C12, C14, C15, C17, C18), except for C13 and C6. Similarly, they do not mention improving employer attributes (O1) or many of the 'Ensure the EVP is clear' criteria (H1, H2, H4, H6, H7). This could imply a focus on the fundamental aspects of employee understanding and EVP structure, perhaps indicating a less mature or different approach to comprehensive employer branding from these regions within the given expert set.

(3) Specific differences: in terms of content

External market focus vs. internal people focus

Germany shows a stronger emphasis on analysing the competition (A26) (50.0%) and labour markets (A24, A25) (37.5% for both) compared to USA experts, who do not mention these at all. This suggests German experts integrate a competitive and market-driven perspective more strongly into their analysis.

Conversely, USA experts strongly prioritise understanding the internal employee experience and perceptions (A1, A8, A9), even if it's less about the broader market context.

EVP authenticity and alignment

The USA group distinctly focuses on EVP being believable and honest (C9) (80.0%) and brand-aligned (C12) (80.0%). This suggests a strong emphasis on internal consistency and authenticity in the EVP message.

Germany also highly values believable and honest EVP (C9) (50.0%) and EVP reflecting sentiments (C5) (50.0%), pointing to an emphasis on genuineness and emotional resonance.

Emphasis on 'how' to create EVP (UK vs. others):

UK experts show a broader and more frequent mention of the practical aspects of EVP creation, such as being attractive (C2) (41.7%), effective (C10) (33.3%), deal-related (C11) (41.7%), and reflecting EX including culture and aspiration (C4) (75.0%). This suggests a comprehensive approach to crafting the EVP to resonate with employees and market needs.

Uniqueness of 'other' group:

The 'Other' group's high percentages for employee-centric analysis (A2, A7, A9) combined with the near absence of mentions for broader organisational, market, and many EVP creation/characteristic elements is a significant distinction. This could imply a more focused or perhaps nascent stage of EVP development in these regions, concentrating on core employee data rather than extensive strategic, brand, or competitive analysis from the given expert perspectives.

Internal corporate analysis:

German and UK experts both show a strong emphasis on analysing the employer's corporate culture (A10) (50.0% for both), and corporate objectives and strategy (A19) (50.0% for Germany, 58.3% for UK). This indicates a shared understanding across these European contexts that the EVP must be deeply rooted in the company's internal fabric and strategic direction. However, the USA group is much lower on A19 (20.0%) and A10 (40.0%), and 'Other' is even lower or absent in these areas, highlighting a divergence.

In summary, while there are common threads, the comparison highlights distinct priorities. *USA experts* appear to focus heavily on employee insights and brand authenticity. *UK experts* lean towards a comprehensive and actionable EVP rooted in employee experience and cultural alignment. *German experts* show a strong emphasis on internal emotional aspects, sentiment, and competitive market analysis. The '*Other*' group appears to prioritise fundamental employee understanding and EVP structure from the data.

(4) Comparison of the findings with established literature on national cultures

The comparative analysis illuminates the distinct priorities in EVP requirements (A1–A6) and creation strategies (C5, C7, C9) among the three countries. An analysis of the presented findings reveals differences that resonate with established literature on national cultures.

The United Kingdom (UK)

It is evident that UK experts generally demonstrate high levels of engagement across a wide range of categories. This observation suggests the adoption of a broad and flexible approach, which is a characteristic of a liberal market economy (LME) (Marchington *et al.*, 2021, p.144).

1. *Broad engagement, low emotional focus:* As stated, the majority of UK experts referenced most analysis categories to some extent. The lowest recorded percentage (8.3%) includes employees' work emotions (A5), indicating a shared, albeit less extreme, lack of focus on this internal measure compared to the USA (0.0%). A frequent comparison drawn between the UK and Germany highlights the former's status as an LME in contrast to Germany's coordinated market economy (CME) status (Brewster *et al.*, 2023, p.115).
2. *Market adaptability and HR practices:* The United Kingdom has been observed to have a long-standing tradition of international trade and a proclivity for free trade agreements, coupled with minimal business regulation, rendering it a highly appealing destination for foreign direct investment (FDI) (Torrington *et al.*, 2020, p.27). The present study finds that the prevalence of performance appraisals is higher in LMEs such as the UK than in CMEs such as Germany (Brewster *et al.*, 2023, p.115). Moreover, within the UK, performance appraisal interviews are typically characterised by a stronger emphasis on the discussion of employees' results and potential promotion, reflecting an individualistic cultural paradigm (Brewster *et al.*, 2023, p.113).

3. *Convergence and flexibility*: While the UK belongs to the Anglo cluster globally (Stock-Homburg and Groß, 2019, p.501), it operates within a unique context given the implications of Brexit, necessitating continuous adaptation (Marchington *et al.*, 2021, p.47; Torrington *et al.*, 2020, p.94). The UK's HRM approach has been observed in a number of international studies, yet evidence suggests that strong forces for divergence persist, thus ensuring that HRM systems remain distinctive despite trends toward commonality (Marchington *et al.*, 2021, p.151).

Germany

German experts have been observed to demonstrate a notable priority for internal, emotional, and structural aspects of the organisation, which is highly consistent with Germany's institutional context as a coordinated market economy (CME) (Marchington *et al.*, 2021, p.132).

1. *Emotional and profiling emphasis*: German experts demonstrate the highest percentage of mentions for analysing employees' work emotions (A5) (25.0%). Furthermore, they uniquely mentioned the need to Create a profiling EVP (C7) (25.0%). This focus on internal sentiment and the creation of a distinctive profile suggests an emphasis on internal fit and organisational commitment, which may reflect the importance of long-term careers and succession planning in Germany's social market economy (Brewster *et al.*, 2023, p.258). German performance management systems characteristically prioritise the identification of training requirements and career progression, where the correlation with remuneration is of lesser significance than in the UK, thereby reinforcing a developmental, internal orientation (Brewster *et al.*, 2023, p.257).
2. *Institutional and labour markets*: The following section will address institutional and labour market requirements. German experts demonstrate a marked tendency to prioritise the analysis of labour markets (A24 and A25) (37.5%). Germany is recognised as a nation with a highly regulated environment, characterised by the presence of extensive labour market institutions, including co-determination and vocational training (Brewster *et al.*, 2023, p.258). The

involvement of worker co-determination has been shown to have a significant impact on the implementation of International Performance Management (IPM) practices (Klimkeit, Wang and Zhang, 2024, p.651). This institutional environment necessitates careful and continuous analysis of labour market mechanisms.

3. *Communication and honesty (precision)*: German experts demonstrated a pronounced emphasis on EVP reflecting sentiments (C5) and being believable and honest (C9). This demand for explicit believability aligns with the communication style of the Germanic cluster (Germany, Austria, Switzerland), which is characterised by high directness and precision (Stock-Homburg and Groß, 2019, p.501). Germans typically expect systems – including goal definition and measurement methods – to be precise and formalised (Brewster *et al.*, 2023, p.258).

United States of America (USA)

The data indicates that US experts continue to prioritise external, performance-oriented metrics and individual needs, consistent with the country's high individualism and Liberal Market Economy (LME) orientation (Marchington *et al.*, 2021, p.125).

1. *Individualism and achievement orientation*: In the USA, experts have demonstrated a high percentage of mentions for Employee and candidate needs (A1) (60.0%) and Employer attributes relevance (A4) (80.0%). This emphasis aligns with the widely recognised highly individualistic culture of the US, which scores 91 on the Individualism Index (Stredwick, 2013, p.439; Wan and Wang, 2025, p.45). Anglo-Saxon nations, including the USA, are frequently distinguished by a heightened emphasis on pay for performance (PfP), both in general and in the specific context of individual performance, reflecting a pronounced individualistic tendency (Brewster *et al.*, 2023, p.184). With regard to the field of corporate reporting, it has been observed that US executives habitually present a favourable perspective on the performance of their firms,

accentuating their accomplishments and attributing success to themselves (Sweeney and McFarlin, 2015, pp.456, 464). This tendency aligns with the prevailing emphasis on individual accomplishment within the corporate landscape.

2. *External factors*: The predominance of requirements pertaining to external attributes and expectations (A4, A6: 60.0%) stands in stark contrast to the minimal emphasis on employees' work emotions (A5) (0.0% cited by US experts). This relative neglect of internal emotional factors may be indicative of the highly formalised and output-control approach that is prevalent in US firms, which tend to rely heavily on reports and performance-related data compared to their European counterparts (Doh, Luthans and Gaur, 2024, p.391). The US approach to HRM, which is often seminal to global thought, is fundamentally geared towards individualised systems such as pay-for-performance, a practice which fits well with employee appraisal (Brewster *et al.*, 2023, p.447).
3. *Labour market context*: Despite its classification within the Anglo-American cluster (Doh, Luthans and Gaur, 2024, p.480), the institutional context in this country differs significantly from that in Germany. Collective bargaining coverage in the USA is suboptimal, with less than 10 per cent of the workforce covered by such agreements. This is indicative of a highly flexible labour market (Brewster *et al.*, 2023, p.99).

(5) Retrospective learning: the necessity of adaptability

A key insight from the cross-national comparison is that a static global EVP model is unlikely to be effective. Instead, the framework must be adaptable to local cultural contexts. While the 50 requirements provide a universal taxonomy of what constitutes an EVP, qualitative data shows that the importance of these components varies significantly across borders.

This confirms the theoretical assertion that global strategies must account for specific *cultural dynamics* to avoid failure (Stock-Homburg and Groß, 2019, p.721). The findings imply a need for contextual fluidity.

- In the *UK context*, for example, the EVP must be designed with pragmatism in mind. The data suggests that a rigid system would clash with the British preference for flexibility and actionability (consistent with the LME model).
- In the *German context*, success depends on precision and emotion. The unique demand for 'profiling' and 'sentiments' indicates that an EVP must satisfy the need for structural security while simultaneously addressing the psychological contract (consistent with the CME model).
- In the *US context*, the focus must shift to individual aspiration. The prioritisation of brand alignment and individual needs suggests that an EVP is primarily viewed as a transactional and aspirational deal.

Consequently, practitioners cannot simply 'roll out' a uniform EVP. Instead, they must utilise the universal requirements as a toolkit, selecting and emphasising specific levers based on the cultural 'institutionalised competence' of the target market.

5.1.3 Comparison by expertise (years in field)

This analysis aims to identify differences and similarities based on the expert's years of experience in employer branding. These groups are used:

- Group 1: *20 and more years in employer branding* (I5, I6, I8, I10, I12, I14, I24, I25, I28) – 9 experts
- Group 2: *10 and more (but under 20) years* (I2, I4, I7, I9, I15, I18, I19, I27) – 8 experts
- Group 3: *5 and more (but under 10) years* (I1, I3, I11, I13, I16, I21, I26) – 7 experts
- Group 4: *Under 5 years* (I17, I20, I22, I23) – 4 experts

Analysis (A) Requirements	Group 1 (20+ yrs.)	Group 2 (10-20 yrs.)	Group 3 (5-10 yrs.)	Group 4 (< 5 yrs.)
A1: Employee & candidate needs	55.6%	25.0%	14.3%	25.0%
A2: Employee preferences	22.2%	37.5%	85.7%	50.0%

Analysis (A) Requirements	Group 1 (20+ yrs.)	Group 2 (10-20 yrs.)	Group 3 (5-10 yrs.)	Group 4 (< 5 yrs.)
A3: Employees' prior work experiences	22.2%	37.5%	14.3%	25.0%
A4: Employer attributes relevance	55.6%	50.0%	85.7%	50.0%
A5: Employees' work emotions	11.1%	0.0%	28.6%	0.0%
A6: Employees' expectations	55.6%	25.0%	57.1%	75.0%
A7: Willingness to contribute	55.6%	12.5%	42.9%	50.0%
A8: Experiences describing employer	77.8%	62.5%	57.1%	50.0%
A9: Employee's behaviour (ethnography)	44.4%	25.0%	14.3%	25.0%
A10: Employer's corporate culture	55.6%	50.0%	28.6%	50.0%
A11: Employer's corporate values	33.3%	50.0%	14.3%	0.0%
A12: Leadership & corporate behaviour	22.2%	25.0%	28.6%	0.0%
A13: Internal communication	22.2%	25.0%	14.3%	0.0%
A14: Quality of current employees	0.0%	12.5%	0.0%	50.0%
A15: Analyse the employer brand	11.1%	50.0%	14.3%	0.0%
A16: Product & corporate brands	22.2%	25.0%	57.1%	0.0%
A17: Employer's benefits for employees	22.2%	62.5%	42.9%	0.0%
A18: Employer expectation for contributions	33.3%	12.5%	28.6%	25.0%
A19: Corporate objectives & strategy	55.6%	62.5%	28.6%	0.0%
A20: Company's structure, size, location	33.3%	37.5%	57.1%	25.0%
A21: Employer's purpose, vision, mission	33.3%	37.5%	57.1%	0.0%
A22: Employer's people strategy	11.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
A23: Employer's strengths & weaknesses	22.2%	25.0%	14.3%	25.0%
A24: Labour markets	22.2%	12.5%	42.9%	0.0%
A25: Labour market influencing trends	22.2%	25.0%	28.6%	25.0%
A26: The competition	44.4%	62.5%	28.6%	0.0%
Creation (C) Requirements	Group 1 (20+ yrs.)	Group 2 (10-20 yrs.)	Group 3 (5-10 yrs.)	Group 4 (< 5 yrs.)
C1: Create a relevant EVP	22.2%	12.5%	14.3%	0.0%
C2: Create an attractive EVP	33.3%	37.5%	42.9%	0.0%
C3: Create a motivating and engaging EVP	33.3%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
C4: Create a EVP reflecting EX	55.6%	50.0%	71.4%	25.0%
C5: Create an EVP reflecting sentiments	33.3%	37.5%	28.6%	25.0%
C6: Create a competitive EVP	44.4%	50.0%	28.6%	25.0%
C7: Create a profiling EVP	0.0%	25.0%	0.0%	0.0%
C8: Create an ownable EVP	33.3%	25.0%	14.3%	0.0%
C9: Create a believable and honest EVP	44.4%	62.5%	42.9%	25.0%
C10: Create an effective EVP	44.4%	25.0%	0.0%	0.0%
C11: Create a deal-related EVP	33.3%	12.5%	42.9%	0.0%
C12: Create a brand-aligned EVP	44.4%	25.0%	57.1%	0.0%
C13: Create a selective EVP	0.0%	25.0%	28.6%	25.0%
Optimising (O) Requirements	Group 1 (20+ yrs.)	Group 2 (10-20 yrs.)	Group 3 (5-10 yrs.)	Group 4 (< 5 yrs.)
O1: Improve employer attributes	33.3%	50.0%	14.3%	25.0%
'Have' (H) Requirements / Characteristics	Group 1 (20+ yrs.)	Group 2 (10-20 yrs.)	Group 3 (5-10 yrs.)	Group 4 (< 5 yrs.)
H1: Ensure the EVP is clear	22.2%	0.0%	14.3%	0.0%
H2: Ensure the EVP is concise	11.1%	12.5%	57.1%	0.0%
H3: Ensure the EVP is measurable	44.4%	12.5%	42.9%	0.0%
H4: Ensure the EVP is robust but flexible	44.4%	12.5%	14.3%	0.0%
H5: Ensure the EVP is structured	33.3%	25.0%	85.7%	25.0%
H6: Ensure the EVP is practical	22.2%	12.5%	14.3%	0.0%
H7: Ensure the EVP is specific	22.2%	12.5%	0.0%	0.0%
H8: Ensure the EVP is validated	11.1%	62.5%	14.3%	25.0%

Tab. 23: Requirement mentions (in %) by experts grouped by experience in years

This comparison indicates distinct patterns in the focus areas of experts based on their years of experience, encompassing analysis, EVP creation, and desired EVP characteristics.

(1) Specific differences: in relation to the expert groups

Group 1: 20+ years in employer branding (highly experienced)

This group demonstrates a profound and holistic understanding of employer branding, with a strong emphasis on deep analytical insights and strategic EVP qualities.

More mentioned areas: They highly prioritise analysing employees' experiences describing the employer (77.8%), reflecting a focus on brand perception. They also show strong interest in analysing employee and candidate needs (55.6%), employees' willingness to contribute (55.6%), and corporate culture (55.6%). In EVP creation, they uniquely highlight creating a motivating and engaging EVP (33.3%) and focus on an effective EVP (44.4%). For EVP characteristics, they strongly advocate for a measurable (44.4%) and robust but flexible EVP (44.4%).

Less mentioned areas: While comprehensive, they show comparatively less emphasis on specific employee preferences (22.2%) and prior work experiences (22.2%).

Not mentioned areas: Notably, they do not mention analysing the quality of current employees (0.0%) or creating a selective EVP (0.0%).

Specific area of difference: This group is the sole mention of analysing employer's people strategy (11.1%), suggesting a top-down, strategic view of HR and employer branding. Their focus on the 'why' and 'how' of EVP effectiveness distinguishes them.

Group 2: 10+ (but under 20) years (experienced)

This group shows a market-oriented and strategic focus, valuing authenticity and competitive positioning in their approach to employer branding.

More mentioned areas: They place the highest emphasis on analysing the employer brand (50.0%), corporate values (50.0%), employer's benefits for employees (62.5%), corporate objectives and strategy (62.5%), and the competition (62.5%). In creation, they lead in developing a competitive EVP (50.0%) and, most significantly, a believable and honest EVP (62.5%). They are also the strongest advocates for creating a validated EVP (62.5%).

Less mentioned areas: They show a lower interest in analysing employees' willingness to contribute (12.5%), measurable (12.5%), or robust but flexible EVP (12.5%) and employer expectations for employee contributions (12.5%).

Not mentioned areas: Several EVP characteristics, such as having a clear (0.0%), concise (0.0%) and creating a motivating, and engaging EVP (0.0%) are unmentioned.

Specific area of difference: This group is the only one to mention creating a profiling EVP (25.0%), indicating a keen interest in distinctiveness and unique employer identity. Their strong focus on 'believable and honest' EVP suggests an understanding of the importance of internal alignment and trust.

Group 3: 5+ (but under 10) years (mid-career)

This group is highly focused on foundational employee understanding and the practical, structural aspects of EVP, often linking it directly to employee experience and organisational attributes.

More mentioned areas: They demonstrate an overwhelming emphasis on analysing employee preferences (85.7%) and the relevance of employer attributes (85.7%). They also lead in analysing the employer's product and

corporate brands (57.1%), company's structure, size and location (57.1%), and employer's purpose, vision and mission (57.1%). In creation, they are significantly focused on an EVP reflecting EX including culture and aspiration (71.4%), as well as an attractive EVP (42.9%), a deal-related EVP (42.9%), and a brand-aligned EVP (57.1%). Crucially, they show an exceptional focus on having a structured EVP (85.7%) and a concise EVP (57.1%).

Less mentioned areas: They mention analysing prior work experiences (14.3%), clear EVP (14.3%) and employer strengths and weaknesses (14.3%) less frequently.

Not Mentioned Areas: They do not mention analysing the quality of current employees (0.0%), and have no mentions for creating an effective EVP (0.0%), or specific EVP (0.0%).

Specific area of difference: Their dominant focus on 'structured' and 'concise' EVP stands out, suggesting that for this group, the methodology and clarity of the EVP characteristics are paramount, possibly indicating a phase where implementation and internal communication of the EVP are key challenges.

Group 4: Under 5 years (newest professionals)

This group appears to have the most concentrated and, at times, narrower focus, with many foundational and strategic aspects of employer branding being unmentioned. Their perspective seems to be more immediately employee-facing.

More mentioned areas: They place the highest emphasis on analysing employees' expectations towards the employer (75.0%) and analysing the employer's quality of current employees (50.0%).

Less mentioned areas: They are generally less involved in most analytical and creation requirements. For instance, they show lower mentions for analysing

employees' prior work experiences (25.0%), employee's behaviour (ethnography) (25.0%), and employer's strengths and weaknesses (25.0%).

Not mentioned areas: This group has a significant number of unmentioned requirements across all categories. In analysis, they do not mention: corporate values (0.0%), leadership and corporate behaviour (0.0%), internal communication (0.0%), the employer brand (0.0%), product and corporate brands (0.0%), employer's benefits for employees (0.0%), corporate objectives and strategy (0.0%), purpose, vision and mission (0.0%), labour markets (0.0%), or the competition (0.0%). In creation, they notably omit: relevant EVP (0.0%), attractive EVP (0.0%), motivating and engaging EVP (0.0%), profiling EVP (0.0%), ownable EVP (0.0%), effective EVP (0.0%), deal-related EVP (0.0%), and brand-aligned EVP (0.0%). Similarly, almost all EVP characteristics are unmentioned, including clear (0.0%), concise (0.0%), measurable (0.0%), robust but flexible (0.0%), practical (0.0%), and specific (0.0%).

Specific area of difference: Their focus is narrower, concentrating on immediate and tangible aspects related to current employees and their expectations. The numerous '0.0%' entries suggest that these more strategic, brand-oriented, or structural considerations may not yet be part of their primary scope or expertise.

(2) Specific differences: in terms of content

Breadth of analysis: Group 1 (20+ years) covers a very broad range of analytical requirements, often with high percentages, indicating a comprehensive approach. In contrast, Group 4 (under 5 years) exhibits a significantly narrower analytical scope, neglecting many strategic and organisational-level analyses. Group 3 (5-10 years) shows a strong internal, employee-centric analytical focus, while Group 2 (10-20 years) balances internal and external (market, competition) analysis.

EVP focus:

- Strategic vs. tactical: More experienced groups (G1, G2) are more concerned with strategic outcomes like effectiveness (G1) and believability/honesty (G2). Less experienced groups (G3, G4) are more focused on immediate qualities like attractiveness (G3) or specific employee expectations (G4).
- Structure and practicality: Group 3 (5-10 years) places a unique and overwhelming emphasis on the structure (85.7%) and conciseness (57.1%) of the EVP, implying a focus on operationalising and communicating the EVP internally.
- Authenticity and validation: Group 2 (10-20 years) clearly distinguishes itself by strongly advocating for believable and honest (62.5%) and validated (62.5%) EVPs, suggesting a maturity in understanding the importance of internal and external trust.

Missing areas for newer groups: The most striking difference lies in the number of requirements not mentioned by Group 4 (Under 5 years). This suggests that while they are gaining experience, many facets of employer branding—from corporate values and strategy analysis to the nuances of EVP qualities like measurability, robustness, or brand alignment—are not yet within their frame of reference or considered less critical at their stage of experience. Similarly, Groups 2 and 3 show gaps in specific areas, but not to the same extent as Group 4.

'People Strategy': Only the most experienced group (Group 1) mentions analysing 'employer's people strategy', underscoring their involvement in higher-level strategic planning.

In conclusion, the data illustrates a clear progression in focus and perceived importance of various employer branding requirements as professionals gain more experience. Newer professionals tend to focus on immediate, direct employee interactions, while mid-career experts focus on building robust, structured EVPs linked to employee experience. More seasoned professionals broaden their scope to strategic, market-driven considerations, and the most

experienced adopt a holistic, deeply insightful, and long-term view of employer branding.

The comparison of expertise across the number of EVP projects conducted produced a result very similar to that of expertise across the years in employer branding. Therefore, these results will not be discussed further here. The table and a few comments can be found in appendix 11, p.307.

5.1.4 Comparison by perspective: internal or external (inhouse or consultant)

This analysis will identify differences and similarities depending on the expert's perspective: internal or external experts. It is important to note the significant disparity in sample size between the two groups (3 in-house vs. 25 consultants). This means that a single mention by an in-house expert represents 33.33% of their group's view, while a single mention by a consultant represents only 4% of their group. Therefore, interpretations of 'more' or 'less' mentioned should consider both the raw counts and the relative percentages within each group. Where an item is not mentioned by a group, it indicates a complete absence from their reported views.

The table below provides a comprehensive breakdown of each requirement, showing the raw counts of mentions and the corresponding percentages for both in-house experts (IH) and consultants (CO).

ID	requirement description	IH Count (out of 3)	in-house %	CO Count (out of 25)	consultants %	difference (CO% - IH%)	notes
A1	Analyse employee and candidate needs	0	0.00%	9	36.00%	+36.00	not mentioned by IH, a key focus for consultants
A2	Analyse employee preferences	2	66.67%	11	44.00%	-22.67	more frequently mentioned proportionally by IH
A3	Analyse employees' prior work experiences	0	0.00%	7	28.00%	+28.00	not mentioned by IH

ID	requirement description	IH Count (out of 3)	in-house %	CO Count (out of 25)	consultants %	difference (CO% - IH%)	notes
A4	Analyse the relevance of employer attributes to employees	2	66.67%	15	60.00%	-6.67	similarly high importance for both groups
A5	Analyse employees' work emotions	0	0.00%	3	12.00%	+12.00	not mentioned by IH
A6	Analyse employees' expectations towards the employer	2	66.67%	12	48.00%	-18.67	more frequently mentioned proportionally by in-house experts
A7	Analyse employees' willingness to contribute + discretionary effort	0	0.00%	11	44.00%	+44.00	not mentioned by IH, significant focus for CO
A8	Analyse employees' experiences describing the employer	1	33.33%	17	68.00%	+34.67	much higher proportional mention by CO
A9	Analyse employee's behaviour (ethnography)	0	0.00%	8	32.00%	+32.00	not mentioned by IH
A10	Analyse employer's corporate culture	1	33.33%	12	48.00%	+14.67	more frequently mentioned by CO, though noted by one IH
A11	Analyse employer's corporate values	0	0.00%	8	32.00%	+32.00	not mentioned by IH
A12	Analyse employer's leadership and corporate behaviour	0	0.00%	6	24.00%	+24.00	not mentioned by IH
A13	Analyse employer's internal communication	0	0.00%	5	20.00%	+20.00	not mentioned by IH
A14	Analyse employer's quality of current employees	0	0.00%	3	12.00%	+12.00	not mentioned by IH
A15	Analyse the employer brand	1	33.33%	5	20.00%	-13.33	higher proportional mention by IH
A16	Analyse the employer's product and corporate brands	1	33.33%	7	28.00%	-5.33	similar proportional relevance for both
A17	Analyse the employer's benefits for employees	0	0.00%	10	40.00%	+40.00	not mentioned by IH, significant focus for CO
A18	Analyse employer expectation for employees' contributions	1	33.33%	6	24.00%	-9.33	higher proportional mention by IH
A19	Analyse employer's corporate objectives and strategy	0	0.00%	12	48.00%	+48.00	not mentioned by IH, very high focus for CO
A20	Analyse company's structure, size and location	1	33.33%	10	40.00%	+6.67	similar proportional relevance for both
A21	Analyse employer's purpose, vision and mission	0	0.00%	11	44.00%	+44.00	not mentioned by IH, significant focus for CO
A22	Analyse employer's people strategy	0	0.00%	1	4.00%	+4.00	not mentioned by IH, low mention overall.
A23	Analyse employer's strengths and weaknesses	1	33.33%	5	20.00%	-13.33	higher proportional mention by IH
A24	Analyse the labour markets	0	0.00%	6	24.00%	+24.00	not mentioned by IH
A25	Analyse labour markets influencing trends	0	0.00%	7	28.00%	+28.00	not mentioned by IH

ID	requirement description	IH Count (out of 3)	in-house %	CO Count (out of 25)	consultants %	difference (CO% - IH%)	notes
A26	Analyse the competition	0	0.00%	11	44.00%	+44.00	not mentioned by IH, significant focus for CO
C1	Create a relevant EVP	0	0.00%	4	16.00%	+16.00	not mentioned by IH
C2	Create an attractive EVP	0	0.00%	9	36.00%	+36.00	not mentioned by IH
C3	Create a motivating and engaging EVP	0	0.00%	3	12.00%	+12.00	not mentioned by IH
C4	Create an EVP reflecting EX	1	33.33%	14	56.00%	+22.67	more frequently mentioned by CO
C5	Create an EVP reflecting sentiments	0	0.00%	9	36.00%	+36.00	not mentioned by IH
C6	Create a competitive EVP	0	0.00%	11	44.00%	+44.00	not mentioned by IH, significant focus for CO
C7	Create a profiling EVP	0	0.00%	2	8.00%	+8.00	not mentioned by IH
C8	Create an ownable EVP	0	0.00%	6	24.00%	+24.00	not mentioned by IH
C9	Create a believable and honest EVP	1	33.33%	12	48.00%	+14.67	more frequently mentioned by CO
C10	Create an effective EVP	0	0.00%	6	24.00%	+24.00	not mentioned by IH.
C11	Create a deal-related EVP	0	0.00%	7	28.00%	+28.00	not mentioned by IH.
C12	Create a brand-aligned EVP	1	33.33%	9	36.00%	+2.67	similar proportional relevance for both
C13	Create a selective EVP	0	0.00%	5	20.00%	+20.00	not mentioned by IH
O1	Improve employer attributes	0	0.00%	9	36.00%	+36.00	not mentioned by IH
H1	Ensure the EVP is clear	0	0.00%	3	12.00%	+12.00	not mentioned by IH
H2	Ensure the EVP is concise	1	33.33%	5	20.00%	-13.33	higher proportional mention by IH
H3	Ensure the EVP is measurable	0	0.00%	8	32.00%	+32.00	not mentioned by IH
H4	Ensure the EVP is robust but flexible	0	0.00%	6	24.00%	+24.00	not mentioned by IH
H5	Ensure the EVP is structured	1	33.33%	11	44.00%	+10.67	more frequently mentioned by CO
H6	Ensure the EVP is practical	0	0.00%	4	16.00%	+16.00	not mentioned by IH
H7	Ensure the EVP is specific	0	0.00%	3	12.00%	+12.00	not mentioned by IH
H8	Ensure the EVP is validated	1	33.33%	7	28.00%	-5.33	similar proportional relevance for both

Tab. 24: Requirements: In-house versus consultants' views

The detailed comparison reveals notable differences in the emphasis placed on various requirements by in-house experts versus consultants.

(1) Requirements more emphasised by consultants

It is noteworthy that a significant number of requirements are not mentioned at all by internal experts (32 of 48), yet are frequently mentioned by consultants.

Comprehensive *employee and candidate analysis* (beyond basic preferences):

- Analyse employee and candidate needs (36.00% consultants vs. 0.00% in-house) (A1).
- Analyse employees' prior work experiences (28.00% consultants vs. 0.00% in-house) (A3).
- Analyse employees' willingness to contribute and discretionary effort (44.00% consultants vs. 0.00% in-house) (A7). This is a particularly significant difference, suggesting consultants delve deeper into motivational and engagement factors.
- Analyse employee's behaviour (ethnography) (32.00% consultants vs. 0.00% in-house) (A9). This indicates consultants recommend more qualitative, in-depth behavioural analysis.

Internal *organisational deep dive* (beyond direct culture/brand):

- Analyse employer's corporate values (32.00% consultants vs. 0.00% in-house) (A11).
- Analyse employer's leadership and corporate behaviour (24.00% consultants vs. 0.00% in-house) (A12).
- Analyse employer's internal communication (20.00% consultants vs. 0.00% in-house) (A13).
- Analyse the employer's benefits for employees (40.00% consultants vs. 0.00% in-house) (A17). This is another major difference, indicating consultants view a thorough benefits analysis as crucial.
- Analyse employer's corporate objectives and strategy (48.00% consultants vs. 0.00% in-house) (A19). This is the highest disparity for analysis requirements, highlighting consultants' emphasis on strategic alignment.

- Analyse employer's purpose, vision and mission (44.00% consultants vs. 0.00% in-house) (A21). Another significant difference, showing consultants prioritising core organisational identity.
- Analyse employer's people strategy (4.00% consultants vs. 0.00% in-house) (A22).

External market and competitive intelligence:

- Analyse the labour markets (24.00% consultants vs. 0.00% in-house) (A24).
- Analyse labour markets influencing trends (28.00% consultants vs. 0.00% in-house) (A25).
- Analyse the competition (44.00% consultants vs. 0.00% in-house) (A26). These three points collectively show consultants' strong focus on external market intelligence, which is entirely absent from the in-house experts' stated requirements.

EVP creation and handling characteristics:

- Creating a relevant, attractive, motivating, engaging, competitive, ownable, effective, deal-related, profiling, selective EVP (ranging from 8.00% to 44.00% for consultants vs. 0.00% for in-house) (C1, C2, C3, C5, C6, C7, C8, C10, C11, C13). This suggests that while in-house experts might implicitly aim for these outcomes, consultants explicitly state them as requirements for EVP creation. The emphasis on a competitive (44.00% consultants) (C6) and attractive (36.00% consultants) (C2) EVP is particularly strong among consultants.
- Improve employer attributes (36.00% consultants vs. 0.00% in-house) (O1).
- Having a clear, measurable, robust but flexible, specific, or practical EVP (ranging from 12.00% to 32.00% for consultants vs. 0.00% for in-house) (H1, H3, H4, H6, H7). The emphasis on measurability (32.00% consultants) (H3) is notable.

(2) Requirements more emphasised by in-house experts

While far fewer in number due to the smaller sample size, some requirements show higher proportional emphasis or similar levels of importance for in-house experts:

Focus on direct *employee perceptions*:

- Analyse employee preferences (66.67% in-house vs. 44.00% consultants) (A2).
- Analyse the relevance of employer attributes to employees (66.67% in-house vs. 60.00% consultants) (A4).
- Analyse employees' expectations towards the employer (66.67% in-house vs. 48.00% consultants) (A6). These points indicate in-house experts are keenly focused on direct employee perspectives and what employees value from the employer, which makes sense given their internal role.

Employer brand and contributions:

- Analyse the employer brand (33.33% in-house vs. 20.00% consultants) (A15).
- Analyse employer expectation for employees' contributions (33.33% in-house vs. 24.00% consultants) (A18).
- Analyse employer's strengths and weaknesses (33.33% in-house vs. 20.00% consultants) (A23). In-house experts seem to have a strong proportional focus on their existing employer brand and internal capabilities, and the reciprocal expectations within the employment relationship. This might be due to their position within the organisation and their access to its internal workings and strategic direction.

EVP characteristics noted by in-house:

- Ensure the EVP is concise (33.33% in-house vs. 20.00% consultants) (H2).

- Ensure the EVP is validated (33.33% in-house vs. 28.00% consultants) (H8). This suggests both groups see value in validation, though one in-house expert mentions it as much as seven consultants.

It can be hypothesised that their in-depth understanding of the company's culture, values, strategy, and the daily employee experience enables them to translate the organisation's aspirational EVP statements into the actual workplace environment.

(3) Specific areas of difference

The analysis points to several specific areas of difference:

1. Scope of analysis

Consultants advocate for a far more extensive and granular analysis across all facets of the EVP development, including in-depth psychological factors (emotions, willingness to contribute, ethnography), strategic alignment (corporate objectives, purpose, mission), and comprehensive external market intelligence (labour markets, trends, competition) (A1, A3, A5, A7, A9, A11, A12, A13, A14, A17, A19, A21, A22, A24, A25, A26). The absence of mention of these 15 analysis requirements by in-house experts is a major distinction. This suggests consultants bring a broader, more systematic, and external-focused analytical framework.

2. Emphasis on outcomes and practicality

While some outcome characteristics are shared, consultants explicitly mention a wider range of desired EVP characteristics related to its effectiveness, competitiveness, uniqueness, and measurability (e.g. relevant, attractive, motivating, competitive, ownable, measurable) (C1, C2, C3, C5, C6, C7, C8, C10, C11, C13, H1, H3, H4, H6, H7). This might reflect their role in delivering a comprehensive solution that meets specific business objectives. In-house experts, perhaps operating within existing structures, focus more on direct

employee perceptions and ensuring the EVP is concise and valid (A2, A4, A6, H2, H8).

3. Strategic depth vs. direct employee insights

In-house experts proportionally highlight direct employee insights (preferences, expectations, relevance of attributes) (A2, A4, A6), suggesting their internal focus is on understanding the immediate human element. In contrast, consultants consistently emphasise the strategic underpinnings (corporate objectives, purpose, vision) (A19, A21) and market context (competition, labour trends) (A24, A25, A26), reflecting their role in shaping a holistic and competitive employer brand strategy.

To summarise, while both groups acknowledge the importance of certain foundational elements of EVP, consultants appear to advocate for a significantly more comprehensive, data-driven, and strategically integrated analytical approach. Their perspective encompasses a broader spectrum of internal and external factors, along with a more explicit articulation of desired EVP characteristics, suggesting a more holistic and often external-facing viewpoint on EVP development. In-house experts, while keenly attuned to immediate employee perceptions, seem to articulate a narrower set of analytical requirements.

It has been hypothesised that consultants may be motivated by commercial interests. However, the depth of their analysis suggests a commitment to methodological rigour and sustainable outcomes. This thoroughness can be attributed to the *reputational capital* of the consulting profession: successful, high-quality projects are vital for establishing a strong market position.

5.1.5 Comparison by experts' academic background

Depending on the expert's academic background, this analysis will identify differences and similarities. For the purposes of this analysis, 27 experts will

be considered, with expert I16 excluded due to missing information. The groups are defined as follows:

- *Humanities and Languages (HL)*: I1, I2, I12, I15, I19, I21, I22, I26, I27, I28 (10 experts)
- *Social Sciences (SoSc)*: I3, I20, I25, I6, I18 (5 experts)
- *Business and Applied Studies (BAS)*: I4, I5, I9, I11, I13, I24, I7, I17, I23 (9 experts)
- *Natural and Formal Sciences (NFS)*: I8, I10, I14 (3 experts)

The percentages below represent the proportion of experts within each specific academic group who mention a particular requirement. This approach allows for a direct comparison of the emphasis placed on each requirement by different academic backgrounds.

Requirements: Analysis (A-codes)	HL (N=10)	SoSc (N=5)	BAS (N=9)	NFS (N=3)
A1: Analyse employee and candidate needs	30%	20%	44.4%	33.3%
A2: Analyse employee preferences	60%	60%	22.2%	33.3%
A3: Analyse employees' prior work experiences	20%	20%	22.2%	33.3%
A4: Analyse the relevance of employer attributes to employees	70%	60%	55.6%	33.3%
A5: Analyse employees' work emotions	10%	40%	0%	0%
A6: Analyse employees' expectations towards the employer	40%	20%	66.7%	66.7%
A7: Analyse employees' willingness to contribute	40%	20%	44.4%	66.7%
A8: Analyse employees' experiences describing the employer	70%	60%	77.8%	33.3%
A9: Analyse employee's behaviour (ethnography)	10%	20%	44.4%	66.7%
A10: Analyse employer's corporate culture	50%	40%	44.4%	66.7%
A11: Analyse employer's corporate values	30%	40%	22.2%	33.3%
A12: Analyse employer's leadership and corporate behaviour	10%	40%	22.2%	33.3%
A13: Analyse employer's internal communication	20%	20%	22.2%	0%
A14: Analyse employer's quality of current employees	10%	20%	11.1%	0%
A15: Analyse the employer brand	30%	0%	33.3%	0%
A16: Analyse the employer's product and corporate brands	40%	40%	11.1%	0%
A17: Analyse the employer's benefits for employees	30%	40%	55.6%	0%
A18: Analyse employer expectation for employees' contributions	10%	40%	11.1%	66.7%
A19: Analyse employer's corporate objectives and strategy	30%	40%	33.3%	100%
A20: Analyse company's structure, size and location	40%	20%	44.4%	33.3%
A21: Analyse employer's purpose, vision and mission	50%	40%	33.3%	0%
A22: Analyse employer's people strategy	0%	0%	0%	33.3%
A23: Analyse employer's strengths and weaknesses	20%	20%	22.2%	33.3%
A24: Analyse the labour markets	20%	40%	0%	33.3%
A25: Analyse labour markets influencing trends	50%	20%	0%	33.3%
A26: Analyse the competition	60%	0%	33.3%	66.7%

Requirements: Creation (C-codes)	HL (N=10)	SoSc (N=5)	BAS (N=9)	NFS (N=3)
C1: Create a relevant EVP	20%	40%	0%	0%
C2: Create an attractive EVP	10%	20%	44.4%	66.7%
C3: Create a motivating and engaging EVP	0%	0%	11.1%	66.7%
C4: Create an EVP reflecting EX including culture and aspiration	50%	60%	55.6%	33.3%
C5: Create an EVP reflecting sentiments	40%	20%	11.1%	66.7%
C6: Create a competitive EVP	60%	20%	22.2%	66.7%
C7: Create a profiling EVP	10%	20%	0%	0%
C8: Create an ownable EVP	40%	20%	0%	33.3%
C9: Create a believable and honest EVP	60%	60%	33.3%	33.3%
C10: Create an effective EVP	20%	0%	22.2%	66.7%
C11: Create a deal-related EVP	20%	20%	22.2%	66.7%
C12: Create a brand-aligned EVP	40%	20%	33.3%	66.7%
C13: Create a selective EVP	20%	0%	22.2%	0%
Requirement: Optimisation (O-codes)	HL (N=10)	SoSc (N=5)	BAS (N=9)	NFS (N=3)
O1: Improve employer attributes	50%	20%	33.3%	0%
Requirements: EVP (H-codes)	HL (N=10)	SoSc (N=5)	BAS (N=9)	NFS (N=3)
H1: Ensure the EVP is clear	20%	0%	0%	33.3%
H2: Ensure the EVP is concise	20%	0%	22.2%	33.3%
H3: Ensure the EVP is measurable	20%	20%	44.4%	33.3%
H4: Ensure the EVP is robust but flexible	20%	20%	11.1%	66.7%
H5: Ensure the EVP is structured	30%	40%	55.6%	33.3%
H6: Ensure the EVP is practical	10%	0%	11.1%	66.7%
H7: Ensure the EVP is specific	0%	20%	11.1%	33.3%
H8: Ensure the EVP is validated	40%	0%	44.4%	0%

Tab. 25: Requirements by academic background group

The comparison demonstrates distinct patterns in the emphasis placed on various requirements by experts with different academic backgrounds.

(1) General trends and high-mentioned requirements

- *Analysis of employees’ experiences and relevance of attributes (A8, A4):* These are consistently highly mentioned across most groups, especially Humanities and Languages (HL) at 70% and Business and Applied Studies (BAS) at 77.8% for A8, and HL at 70% for A4. This suggests a common understanding of the importance of understanding employee perspectives.
- *Creating a comprehensive EVP (C4, C9):* ‘Create an EVP reflecting EX including culture and aspiration’ (C4) and ‘Create a believable and honest EVP’ (C9) are frequently cited across groups, with Social Sciences (SoSc) showing the highest rate for C4 (60%) and HL and SoSc leading for C9

(60%). This indicates a strong consensus on the need for authentic and experience-driven EVPs.

(2) Requirements more mentioned in specific groups

Humanities and Languages (HL):

- Show a higher relative emphasis on analysing employee preferences (A2) (60%), relevance of employer attributes (A4) (70%), employer's corporate culture (A10) (50%), and labour markets influencing trends (A25) (50%).
- They also significantly mention analysing the competition (A26) (60%).
- In creation, 'Create a competitive EVP' (C6) (60%), 'Create a believable and honest EVP' (C9) (60%), create an EVP reflecting EX (C4) (50.0%), and 'Create an ownable EVP' (C8) (40%) are more prominent for this group.
- They show a higher interest in improving employer attributes (O1) (50%).

Social Sciences (SoSc):

- These experts notably emphasise analysing employees' work emotions (A5) (40%) and employer's leadership and corporate behaviour (A12) (40%). This aligns with their focus on human behaviour and organisational dynamics.
- They are also strong in mentioning 'Create a relevant EVP' (C1) (40%) and 'Create an EVP reflecting EX including culture and aspiration' (C4) (60%), create a believable and honest EVP (C9) (60.0%), suggesting a focus on the foundational relevance and depth of the EVP.
- They show the highest percentage for 'Analyse the labour markets' (A24) (40%).

Business and Applied Studies (BAS):

- This group places a strong emphasis on practical and performance-related analyses. This is evident in higher mentions for analysing employees' expectations (A6) (66.7%), employees' experiences (A8) (77.8%), and analysing company's structure, size and location (A20) (44.4%).
- They lead in mentioning analysing employee and candidate needs (A1) (44.4%).
- Regarding EVP structure, they show the highest percentage for 'Ensure the EVP is structured' (H5) (55.6%) and 'Ensure the EVP is measurable' (H3) (44.4%), suggesting a focus on the operational aspects and accountability of the EVP.
- They are also more inclined to mention 'Ensure the EVP is validated' (H8) (44.4%).

Natural and Formal Sciences (NFS):

- This group shows a remarkably high emphasis on strategic and behavioural analysis, often leading by a significant margin. They mention 'Analyse employer's corporate objectives and strategy' (A19) by all their experts (100%).
- They also highly mention 'Analyse employee's behaviour (ethnography)' (A9) (66.7%), 'Analyse employer's corporate culture' (A10) (66.7%), and 'Analyse employer expectation for employees' contributions' (A18) (66.7%).
- In creation activities, they lead in almost all aspects of EVP creation, including 'Create an attractive EVP' (C2) (66.7%), 'Create a motivating and engaging EVP' (C3) (66.7%), 'Create an EVP reflecting sentiments' (C5) (66.7%), 'Create a competitive EVP' (C6) (66.7%), 'Create an effective EVP' (C10) (66.7%), 'Create a deal-related EVP' (C11) (66.7%), and 'Create a brand-aligned EVP' (C12) (66.7%).
- They also show the highest rates for structural aspects like 'Ensure the EVP is robust but flexible' (H4) (66.7%) and 'Practical EVP' (H6) (66.7%).
- 'Analyse employer's people strategy' (A22) is uniquely mentioned by an expert from this group (33.3%), being absent from all others.

(3) Requirements less mentioned or not mentioned

Requirements not mentioned by specific groups (0%):

- Natural and Formal Sciences (NFS) experts completely omit several key 'analysis' activities such as employees' work emotions (A5), employer's internal communication (A13), employer's quality of current employees (A14), employer brand (A15), product and corporate brands (A16), employer benefits (A17), and employer's purpose, vision and mission (A21). They also do not mention 'Improve employer attributes' (O1).
- Social Sciences (SoSc) experts do not mention analysing the employer brand (A15), analysing the competition (A26), 'Create an effective EVP' (C10), 'Create a selective EVP' (C13), 'Ensure the EVP is clear' (H1), 'Ensure the EVP is concise' (H2), and 'Ensure the EVP is validated' (H8).
- Business and Applied Studies (BAS) experts do not mention analysing employees' work emotions (A5), labour markets (A24), labour markets influencing trends (A25), 'Create a relevant EVP' (C1), 'Create a profiling EVP' (C7), 'Create an ownable EVP' (C8), and 'Ensure the EVP is clear' (H1).
- Humanities and Languages (HL) experts do not mention 'Create a motivating and engaging EVP' (C3) and 'Ensure the EVP is specific' (H7).

(4) Specific areas of differences

Quantitative versus qualitative focus:

- The Natural and Formal Sciences (NFS) group shows a clear inclination towards strategic, behavioural, and measurable aspects (A9, A10, A18, A19, C2, C3, C5, C10, C11, C12, H4, H6), often highlighting the 'how' and 'what' of EVP creation and analysis in a results-oriented manner. Their focus on 'corporate objectives and strategy' (A19) and 'people strategy' (A22) suggests a top-down, systemic view. The high mentions of 'motivating and engaging EVP' (C3) and 'reflecting sentiments' (C5) are interesting given their scientific background, potentially indicating a data-driven approach to these 'softer' aspects.

- Social Sciences (SoSc) experts, conversely, appear more attuned to employee emotions, leadership, and the broader social context (A5, A12, A24, C1, C4). Their emphasis on 'relevant' and 'reflecting EX including culture and aspiration' EVPs points to a focus on the intrinsic value and fit from an employee perspective.
- Humanities and Languages (HL) experts seem to focus on the narrative, perception, and competitive positioning (A4, A26, C6, C9). Their high rates for 'relevance of employer attributes' and 'believable and honest EVP' suggest an emphasis on clear and authentic communication of the employer brand.
- Business and Applied Studies (BAS) experts often concentrate on practical application, structure, and measurability (A1, A6, A8, H3, H5, H8). Their high mentions for 'analysing employee needs, expectations, and experiences,' along with 'structured' and 'measurable' EVPs, suggest a hands-on, results-driven approach to employer branding.

Internal versus external focus:

- BAS and NFS groups show a stronger focus on internal organisational elements and strategic outcomes (e.g. A19, A20).
- HL demonstrates a balance, with strong mentions for both internal employee aspects (A2, A4) and external market/competition analysis (A25, A26).
- SoSc shows a tendency towards understanding the internal human element and the broader labour market context (A24).

In conclusion, while there are common high-priority areas across all groups, such as analysing employee experiences and creating a holistic EVP, each academic background brings a unique lens to the requirements. Natural and Formal Sciences experts demonstrate a distinct emphasis on strategic, measurable, and behavioural aspects, often with the highest relative figures. Business and Applied Studies experts lean towards practical application and structured approaches. Humanities and Languages experts focus on communication, perception, and competitive aspects, while Social Sciences experts are

more inclined towards emotional, relational, and societal considerations. These differences underscore the multidisciplinary nature of employer branding and EVP development.

These findings highlight the importance of creating a *diverse and interdisciplinary team environment* within the EVP development process.

5.1.6 Comparison by experts' field background

This analysis will identify differences and similarities. It will depend on the expert's field background in either HR or marketing. The initial step is to verify the groupings and their respective sizes.

- *HR background*: Comprises 7 experts (I3, I4, I5, I6, I7, I17, I23).
- *Marketing background*: Comprises 21 experts (I1, I2, I8, I9, I10, I11, I12, I13, I14, I15, I16, I18, I19, I20, I21, I22, I24, I25, I26, I27, I28).

The analysis below details how frequently each requirement is mentioned by experts within these two groups, expressed in relative figures (percentages) to provide a clear comparison.

The following table (Tab. 26) provides a comprehensive overview of the mentions for each requirement by both HR and Marketing expert groups, including the count of mentions, their respective percentages, and a brief observation on the difference.

ID	Requirement Description	HR Mentions (Count)	HR Mentions (%)	Marketing Mentions (Count)	Marketing Mentions (%)	Key Difference/Observation
A1	Analyse employee and candidate needs	2	28.57%	7	33.33%	Similar emphasis between the groups.
A2	Analyse employee preferences	2	28.57%	11	52.38%	Marketing significantly more often mentions this.

ID	Requirement Description	HR Mentions (Count)	HR Mentions (%)	Marketing Mentions (Count)	Marketing Mentions (%)	Key Difference/Observation
A3	Analyse employees' prior work experiences	1	14.29%	6	28.57%	Marketing more often mentions this.
A4	Analyse employees' relevance of employer attributes	3	42.86%	14	66.67%	Marketing significantly more often mentions this.
A5	Analyse employees' work emotions	2	28.57%	1	4.76%	HR significantly more often mentions this, indicating a deeper focus on internal sentiment.
A6	Analyse employees' expectations towards the employer	4	57.14%	10	47.62%	HR slightly more often mentions this.
A7	Analyse employees' willingness to contribute	2	28.57%	9	42.86%	Marketing more often mentions this.
A8	Analyse employees' experiences describing the employer	6	85.71%	12	57.14%	HR significantly more often mentions this, highlighting an internal, experience-based perspective.
A9	Analyse employee's behaviour (ethnography)	3	42.86%	5	23.81%	HR significantly more often mentions this, indicating a deeper behavioural analysis focus.
A10	Analyse employer's corporate culture	2	28.57%	11	52.38%	Marketing significantly more often mentions this, likely for external branding.
A11	Analyse employer's corporate values	2	28.57%	6	28.57%	Similar emphasis.
A12	Analyse employer's leadership and corporate behaviour	2	28.57%	4	19.05%	HR more often mentions this, aligning with internal organisational dynamics.
A13	Analyse employer's internal communication	3	42.86%	2	9.52%	HR significantly more often mentions this, underscoring its relevance for internal cohesion.
A14	Analyse employer's quality of current employees	1	14.29%	2	9.52%	Similar low emphasis by both groups.
A15	Analyse the employer brand	2	28.57%	4	19.05%	HR more often mentions this, possibly from an internal stewardship perspective.
A16	Analyse the employer's product and corporate brands	2	28.57%	6	28.57%	Similar emphasis.
A17	Analyse the employer's benefits for employees	2	28.57%	8	38.10%	Marketing more often mentions this, possibly for competitive positioning.
A18	Analyse employer expectation for employees' contributions	2	28.57%	5	23.81%	Similar emphasis, with HR slightly higher.
A19	Analyse employer's corporate objectives and strategy	1	14.29%	11	52.38%	Marketing significantly more often mentions this, indicating a broader strategic and market-oriented view.

ID	Requirement Description	HR Mentions (Count)	HR Mentions (%)	Marketing Mentions (Count)	Marketing Mentions (%)	Key Difference/Observation
A20	Analyse company's structure, size and location	4	57.14%	7	33.33%	HR significantly more often mentions this, relating to internal employee conditions.
A21	Analyse employer's purpose, vision and mission	2	28.57%	9	42.86%	Marketing more often mentions this, perhaps for external brand messaging.
A22	Analyse employer's people strategy	0	0.00%	1	4.76%	Only mentioned by Marketing, suggesting a strategic view of people from a brand perspective.
A23	Analyse employer's strengths and weaknesses	1	14.29%	5	23.81%	Marketing more often mentions this, likely in a competitive context.
A24	Analyse the labour markets	1	14.29%	5	23.81%	Marketing more often mentions this, indicating market-focused analysis.
A25	Analyse labour markets influencing trends	0	0.00%	7	33.33%	Only mentioned by Marketing, emphasising external market dynamics.
A26	Analyse the competition	3	42.86%	8	38.10%	Similar emphasis, with HR slightly higher.
C1	Create a relevant EVP	1	14.29%	3	14.29%	Similar emphasis.
C2	Create an attractive EVP	3	42.86%	6	28.57%	HR significantly more often mentions this, perhaps focusing on internal appeal.
C3	Create a motivating and engaging EVP	1	14.29%	2	9.52%	Similar low emphasis, with HR slightly higher.
C4	Create an EVP reflecting EX including culture and aspiration	5	71.43%	10	47.62%	HR significantly more often mentions this, underscoring the importance of internal experience.
C5	Create an EVP reflecting sentiments	2	28.57%	7	33.33%	Similar emphasis, with Marketing slightly higher.
C6	Create a competitive EVP	2	28.57%	9	42.86%	Marketing more often mentions this, reflecting a market positioning focus.
C7	Create a profiling EVP	0	0.00%	2	9.52%	Only mentioned by Marketing, implying a focus on differentiation.
C8	Create an ownable EVP	0	0.00%	6	28.57%	Only mentioned by Marketing, aligning with brand uniqueness.
C9	Create a believable and honest EVP	4	57.14%	9	42.86%	HR more often mentions this, perhaps prioritising internal authenticity.
C10	Create an effective EVP	1	14.29%	5	23.81%	Marketing more often mentions this, focusing on measurable outcomes.
C11	Create a deal-related EVP	1	14.29%	5	23.81%	Similar emphasis, with Marketing slightly higher.
C12	Create a brand-aligned EVP	2	28.57%	9	42.86%	Marketing more often mentions this, which is expected given their background.
C13	Create a selective EVP	1	14.29%	3	14.29%	Similar emphasis.

ID	Requirement Description	HR Mentions (Count)	HR Mentions (%)	Marketing Mentions (Count)	Marketing Mentions (%)	Key Difference/Observation
O1	Improve employer attributes	4	57.14%	5	23.81%	HR significantly more often mentions this, reflecting a focus on internal improvement.
H1	Ensure the EVP is clear	0	0.00%	3	14.29%	Only mentioned by Marketing, highlighting clarity for external messaging.
H2	Ensure the EVP is concise	1	14.29%	5	23.81%	Marketing more often mentions this.
H3	Ensure the EVP is measurable	1	14.29%	7	33.33%	Marketing significantly more often mentions this, emphasising metrics and ROI.
H4	Ensure the EVP is robust but flexible	0	0.00%	6	28.57%	Only mentioned by Marketing, indicating a strategic approach to long-term brand management.
H5	Ensure the EVP is structured	3	42.86%	9	42.86%	Similar emphasis.
H6	Ensure the EVP is practical	1	14.29%	3	14.29%	Similar emphasis.
H7	Ensure the EVP is specific	0	0.00%	3	14.29%	Only mentioned by Marketing, likely for targeting and clarity.
H8	Ensure the EVP is validated	3	42.86%	5	23.81%	HR significantly more often mentions this, possibly for internal credibility and effectiveness.

Tab. 26: Requirement by HR and marketing expert groups

Key areas of differences

The comparison reveals distinct priorities and focus areas between HR and Marketing professionals in relation to the EVP.

Requirements more mentioned by HR experts:

HR professionals demonstrate a stronger emphasis on internal employee experience, organisational culture, and the authenticity of the employer brand.

- Deep employee and internal analysis: HR experts significantly more often mention analysing employees’ work emotions (A5) (28.57% vs 4.76%), employees’ experiences describing the employer (A8) (85.71% vs 57.14%), employee’s behaviour (ethnography) (A9) (42.86% vs 23.81%), and employer’s internal communication (A13) (42.86% vs 9.52%). They also show higher mentions for analysing the employer’s leadership and corporate behaviour (A12) (28.57% vs 19.05%) and

company's structure, size, and location (A20) (57.14% vs 33.33%), suggesting a focus on the tangible and felt aspects of the workplace.

- **Authenticity and internal alignment of EVP:** When it comes to EVP creation, HR experts more frequently mention the need to create an attractive EVP (C2) (42.86% vs 28.57%), one that reflects employee experience (EX), including culture and aspiration (C4) (71.43% vs 47.62%), and is believable and honest (C9) (57.14% vs 42.86%). This suggests a primary concern for the internal reality and lived experience of employees. They also prioritise improving employer attributes (O1) (57.14% vs 23.81%) and having a validated EVP (H8) (42.86% vs 23.81%), indicating a focus on continuous improvement and evidence-based practice concerning the internal employer offering.
- HR also shows a slightly higher emphasis on analysing the employer brand (A15) (28.57% vs 19.05%) and analysing employees' expectations towards the employer (A6) (57.14% vs 47.62%).

Requirements more mentioned by marketing experts:

Marketing professionals tend to focus on external market dynamics, competitive positioning, and the strategic communication of the employer brand.

- **External market and strategic analysis:** Marketing experts significantly more often highlight the importance of analysing employees' preferences (A2) (52.38% vs 28.57%), the relevance of employer attributes (A4) (66.67% vs 42.86%), employer's corporate culture (A10) (52.38% vs 28.57%), and employer's corporate objectives and strategy (A19) (52.38% vs 14.29%). Their focus extends to analysing the labour markets (A24) (23.81% vs 14.29%) and, uniquely, labour markets influencing trends (A25) (33.33% vs 0%).
- **Competitive and measurable EVP:** Marketing professionals underscore the need to create a competitive EVP (C6) (42.86% vs 28.57%), a brand-aligned EVP (C12) (42.86% vs 28.57%), and a concise EVP (H2) (23.81% vs 14.29%). Crucially, they place a much greater emphasis on the measurability of the EVP (H3) (33.33% vs 14.29%), reflecting a results-oriented approach.

- *Unique marketing perspective:* Marketing experts uniquely mention analysing employer's people strategy (A22) (4.76% vs 0%), creating a profiling EVP (C7) (9.52% vs 0%), and creating an ownable EVP (C8) (28.57% vs 0%). They are also the only group to mention having a clear EVP (H1) (14.29% vs 0%), a robust but flexible EVP (H4) (28.57% vs 0%), and a specific EVP (H7) (14.29% vs 0%). These unique mentions emphasise the importance of strategic brand differentiation and external communication.

Requirements with similar emphasis:

Both groups demonstrate similar levels of interest in areas such as analysing employee and candidate needs (A1), analysing employer's corporate values (A11), analysing the employer's product and corporate brands (A16), creating a relevant EVP (C1), and having a structured EVP (H5) and a practical EVP (H6). This suggests common ground in understanding fundamental aspects of the employer-employee relationship and the foundational elements of an EVP.

This detailed comparison highlights the complementary perspectives of HR and Marketing professionals in the realm of employer branding and EVP, with HR focusing more on the internal employee experience and authenticity, and marketing prioritising external market positioning, competitive advantage, and strategic measurability. The average number of requirements by group is also provided in appendix 9, p.305.

5.1.7 Summary

As previously stated, it is imperative to reiterate that the analysis should not be generalised. Nevertheless, it is possible to draw some indications, which may serve to highlight the necessity for further quantitative research.

Five highlights of the intra-empirical comparison:

1. *Country analysis*: It appears that experts from the USA place a significant emphasis on the insights of employees and the authenticity of brands. The majority of UK-based experts in this field advocate a comprehensive and actionable EVP, one which is rooted in employee experience and cultural alignment. German experts have been observed to place significant emphasis on internal emotional aspects, sentiment, and competitive market analysis. The 'Other' group appears to prioritise fundamental employee understanding and EVP structure from the data.
2. *Analysis expertise (in years)*: The study has revealed a marked tendency among newly qualified professionals to prioritise immediate, direct employee interactions. In contrast, the focus of mid-career experts has been shown to be on the development of robust, structured EVPs with a strong emphasis on the employee experience. It is evident that more seasoned professionals tend to expand their purview to encompass strategic, market-driven considerations. The most experienced professionals are characterised by their adoption of a holistic, profoundly insightful, and long-term perspective on employer branding.
3. *Analysis by view (internal / external)*: Consultants are advocating for a substantially more comprehensive, data-driven, and strategically integrated analytical approach. It is evident that their perspective encompasses a broader spectrum of internal and external factors. In addition, there is a more explicit articulation of desired EVP characteristics. This suggests that their viewpoint on EVP development is more holistic and often external-facing. In-house experts, while attuned to immediate employee perceptions, appear to articulate a narrower set of analytical requirements.
4. *Analysis by academic background*: Each academic background introduces a distinct perspective on the requirements in question. Experts in the natural and formal sciences demonstrate a distinct emphasis on strategic, measurable, and behavioural aspects, often with the highest relative figures. Experts in Business and Applied Studies demonstrate a propensity for pragmatic implementation and systematic methodologies. The field of Humanities and Languages focuses on the communication, perception,

and competitive aspects of the employer brand and EVP positioning, while the field of Social Sciences focuses on the emotional, relational, and societal considerations of the EVP development and the employment relationship. The aforementioned differences serve to emphasise the multidisciplinary nature of the development of the EVP.

5. *Analysis by field background*: Human Resources is increasingly orienting its attention towards the internal employee experience and authenticity, while Marketing is prioritising external market positioning, competitive advantage, and strategic measurability.

The intra-empirical comparison confirms that EVP development is a *multidisciplinary* field influenced by regional culture, length of service, and academic background. *Regional priorities* range from the USA's focus on brand authenticity to Germany's emphasis on internal sentiment. Meanwhile, *professional maturity* drives a progression from early tactical tasks to holistic strategy at a veteran level. Furthermore, *consultants* advocate broader, data-driven frameworks than *in-house experts*, who have a narrower focus. Ultimately, the combination of HR and marketing expertise demonstrates that *interdisciplinary collaboration* is essential for mastering the complex EVP development cycle.

5.2 Analysis: Comparison of theory and empirical study

This section synthesises the findings from the systematic literature review (section 2.11.2, p.69) and the empirical expert study (chapter 4, p.134). In line with the research strategy outlined in section 3.1.4, p.88, the comparison takes an abductive approach. Rather than strictly testing the validity of the 27 theoretical requirements (deduction) or disregarding prior knowledge in favour of relying solely on interview data (induction), this analysis oscillates iteratively between general theory and specific empirical insights.

Consequently, expanding the catalogue to 48 practical requirements does not imply that the initial theoretical framework was incorrect. Instead, it shows that the practical reality of professional work requires a more detailed approach to solve the business problem. The discrepancies identified therefore indicate where the abstract concepts of the literature required refinement for practical application.

The comparative analysis is divided into three sections: process phases (5.2.1), similarities and differences (5.2.2) and implicit connections (5.2.3).

5.2.1 Theory-empirical comparison: Process phases

In this section, a comparison is made between theory and empirical evidence across the various process phases.

	number of theoretical requirements	number of practical requirements
Part 1: EVP situation analysis	12	26
Part 2: EVP creation	10	13
Part 3: EVP characteristics	4	8
Part 4: Attribute optimisation	1	1
Sum	27	48

Tab. 27: Comparison theoretical and practical requirements by process part

(1) Situation Analysis

Theoretical requirements focus: In this phase, a careful analysis of complexity takes place to identify and categorise potential EVP attributes into value-creating, value-destroying, or value-neutral categories. It also aims to understand the role of various interactions in the employee experience (EX). Performance-related requirements identified include: Identifying the needs of the target group (S1), determining employee preferences and the causes of discrepancies between wishes and the actual EVP (S2), gaining insights into current employee experiences (S3) and the gap between employee expectations and experiences (S4), collecting information about the company's

culture (S5), values (S6), management style (S7), qualities of current employees (S8), current image (S9), and impression of product quality (S10), examining the requirements of and benefits for employees (S11) and assessing employees' perception of the current EVP (S12) This phase emphasises considering the current situation and the desired target perspective.

theory requirement description	theory requirement ID	interview requirement ID	interview requirement description
Identify the needs of the target group.	S1	A1	Analyse employee and candidate needs.
Determine the preferences of the employees and the causes of any discrepancies between the employees' wishes and the actual EVP.	S2	A2	Analyse employee preferences.
Gain insights into the current experiences of employees.	S3	A8	Analyse employees' experiences describing the employer.
Gain insights into the gap between employees' expectations and experiences.	S4	A6, A8	Analyse employees' expectations towards the employer + analyse employees' experiences describing the employer.
Collect information about the company's culture.	S5	A10	Analyse employer's corporate culture.
Collect information about the company's values.	S6	A11	Analyse employer's corporate values.
Collect information about the company's management style.	S7	A12	Analyse employer's leadership and corporate behaviour.
Collect information about the qualities of the current employees.	S8	A14	Analyse employer's quality of current employees.
Collect information about the company's current image.	S9	A15	Analyse the employer brand.
Collect information about the impression of product quality.	S10	A16	Analyse the employer's product and corporate brands.
Examine the requirements of and benefits for employees.	S11	A17	Analyse the employer's benefits for employees.

Tab. 28: Matching requirements theory and empirical study (situation analysis)

Practical requirements focus: These are detailed analysis activities intended to inform the EVP situation, covering a broader range of specific aspects. They include: Analysing employee and candidate needs (A1), analysing employee preferences (A2), analysing employees' prior work experiences (A3), analysing employees' relevance of employer attributes (A4), analysing employees' work emotions (A5), analysing employees' expectations towards the employer (A6), analysing employees' willingness to contribute and discretionary effort (A7), analysing employees' experiences describing the employer (A8), analysing employee's behaviour (ethnography) (A9), analysing employer's corporate culture (A10), analysing employer's corporate values (A11),

analysing employer’s leadership and corporate behaviour (A12), analysing employer’s internal communication (A13), analysing employer’s quality of current employees (A14), analysing the employer brand (A15), analysing the employer’s product and corporate brands (A16), analysing the employer’s benefits for employees (A17), analysing employer expectation for employees’ contributions (A18), analysing employer’s corporate objectives and strategy (A19), analysing company’s structure, size and location (A20), analysing employer’s purpose, vision and mission (A21), analysing employer’s people strategy (A22), analysing employer’s strengths and weaknesses (A23), analysing the labour markets (A24), analysing labour markets influencing trends (A25), and analysing the competition (A26).

Respectively, the requirements S12 and A3, A4, A5, A7, A9, A13 and A18-A26 have no direct match. Particularly in the employee descriptive analysis, clear differences can be seen (see Fig. 28).

Fig. 28: Comparison of EVP requirements within the employee descriptive analysis

(2) EVP Development 1: EVP Creation

Theoretical requirements focus: To create a convincing and comprehensive offer for employees that describes what they can expect from their

commitment. This offer should make both advantages (value-adding) and burdens (value-destroying) transparent. The goals are to attract potential employees, retain them, and engage those recruited, thereby promoting satisfaction. Performance-related requirements include the EVP being: Employee-centred, attractive, and valuable (K1), fulfilling employee needs and being relevant (K2), potentially harmonised with ESG priorities, a characterisation of the quintessence of the distinctive overall work-place experience and representing the personality of the organisation (K3), ideally linked to a feeling or emotion to encourage associations and facilitate uptake (K4), making employees feel valued and expressing the company's commitment to them (K5), able to assert itself in competition, through differentiation or uniqueness (K6), ensuring the design, positioning, and development of an employer brand profile (K7), authentic and credible (K8), truthful and real (K9), convincing overall (K10). The creation process should consider the current and target situation, real employer attributes, ambition, and both employer and employee sides.

theory requirement description	theory requirement ID	interview requirement ID	interview requirement description
The EVP must be employee-centred, attractive and valuable.	K1	C1, C2	Create a relevant EVP + Create an attractive EVP
The EVP must fulfil employee needs and be relevant.	K2	C1	Create a relevant EVP.
The EVP should be a characterisation of the quintessence of the distinctive overall workplace experience, which guides daily experiences and represents the personality of the organisation.	K3	C4	Create an EVP reflecting EX (Employee Experience) including culture and aspiration.
The EVP should ideally be linked to a feeling or emotion to encourage associations and facilitate uptake.	K4	C5	Create an EVP reflecting sentiments.
The EVP should be able to assert itself in competition, implying differentiation or uniqueness.	K6	C6	Create a competitive EVP.
The EVP should ensure the design, positioning and development of an employer brand profile.	K7	C7	Create a profiling EVP.
The EVP should be authentic and credible.	K8	C9	Create a believable and honest EVP.
The EVP should be truthful and real.	K9	C9	Create a believable and honest EVP.
The EVP should be convincing overall.	K10	C10	Create an effective EVP.

Tab. 29: Matching requirements theory and empirical study (creation)

Practical requirements focus: Specific attributes and characteristics for creating the EVP characteristics. These include creating an EVP that is: Relevant (C1), attractive (C2), motivating, and engaging (C3), reflecting employee experience (EX) including culture and aspiration (C4), reflecting sentiments (C5), competitive (C6), profiling (C7), ownable (C8), believable and honest (C9), effective (C10), deal-related (C11), brand-aligned (C12) and selective (C13).

Respectively, the requirements K5 and C3, C8, C11-13 have no direct match.

(3) The EVP characteristics (formalities)

Theoretical requirements focus: This part covers formal requirements for the EVP, which should contain a clear and concrete statement. Requirements include the EVP being: Simple and easy for every employee to understand (E1), easy to pass on (E2), expressing a lot with few words (E3), measurable (E4). The EVP should be tested and validated internally and externally with the target group prior to introduction.

Practical requirements focus: Attributes describing the nature, structure, and formal characteristics of the EVP characteristics. These include having an EVP that is: Clear (H1), concise (H2), measurable (H3), robust but flexible (H4), structured (H5), practical (H6), specific (H7) and validated (H8).

theory requirement description	theory requirement ID	interview requirement ID	interview requirement description
The EVP should be simple and therefore easy for every employee to understand.	E1	H1	Ensure the EVP is clear
The EVP should also be easy to pass on.	E2	H6	Ensure the EVP is practical
The EVP should express a lot with few words.	E3	H2	Ensure the EVP is concise.
The EVP should be measurable.	E4	H3	Ensure the EVP is measurable.

Tab. 30: Matching requirements theory and empirical study (characteristics)

Respectively, the requirements H4, H5, H7 and H8 have no direct match within the formal coding list (E1-E4), although *validation* is mentioned in the literature text (see p.74).

(4) EVP Development 2: Optimisation

Theoretical requirements focus: It is vital for companies to address the disparity between their stated EVP and the reality of everyday working life (reality-ambition gap). Failure to do so will compromise the authenticity requirement. This phase represents a central requirement: The improvement of EVP attributes (O1), such as improving the employee experience. Optimisations should be based on findings from analysis and development, focusing on employee centricity, brand profiling, competitive assertion, and addressing the reality-ambition gap. It is essential to continuously review and develop the EVP and to evaluate it with the target group before implementation.

Practical requirements focus: Actions related to refining and improving employer attributes to align with the developed EVP (O1).

theory requirement description	theory requirement ID	interview requirement ID	interview requirement description
The improvement of EVP attributes, such as improving the employee experience.	O1	O1	Improve employer attributes.

Tab. 31: Matching requirements theory and empirical study (optimisation)

Overview: The theoretical requirements for the EVP have been distilled from a systematic literature review and categorised into four areas: situation analysis, creation, optimisation, and the EVP characteristics. The analysis resulted in a total of 27 *theoretical requirements*.

In practice, the requirements are broken down into more granular and numerous actionable items. These include 26 analysis requirements (A series),

13 creation requirements (C series), 1 optimisation requirement (O series), and 8 requirements pertaining to the EVP's formal characteristics (H series). This results in a total of *48 practical requirements*, which provide more specific guidance within each phase of EVP development.

The sum of the 27 theoretical requirements and the 48 practical requirements, with 24 of them being common, totals 50 EVP requirements. A small side note at this point: strictly speaking, the common requirements are 25 of the 27 theoretical and 24 of the 48 practical requirements, because the theoretical requirement S4 (the gap between (S4) employees' expectations and experiences) corresponds to the practical requirements A6: Analysis of employees' expectations towards the employer and A8: Analysis of employees' experiences describing the employer.

5.2.2 Theory-empirical comparison: Similarities and differences

In this section, a comparison is made between theory and empirical evidence, highlighting the similarities and differences between them.

(1) Similarities

There is significant alignment between theoretical requirements and the ones expressed by the interviewed experts, particularly regarding the foundational elements of EVP development:

- Employee-centricity: Both theory and practice profoundly emphasise understanding the employee.
 - Analysing employee needs, preferences, and expectations is a cornerstone in both (Theory S1, S2, S4; Practice A1, A2, A6).
 - Crucially, analysing employees' experiences describing the employer is highlighted by theory (S3) and is the most frequently mentioned requirement by experts (A8: 18 experts).

- Authenticity and credibility: A shared conviction is that the EVP must be believable, honest, truthful, and real (theory K8, K9; practice C9: 13 experts). This ensures trust and long-term effectiveness.
- Corporate culture and values: A deep understanding of the employer's corporate culture and values is fundamental for both (theory S5, S6; practice A10: 11 experts, A11: 7 experts).
- Competitiveness: The EVP must be capable of asserting itself in competition, aiming for differentiation or uniqueness (theory K6; practice C6: 11 experts).
- Employer brand and product brand alignment: The theory mentions analysing the company's image and product quality (S9, S10), which corresponds to experts' emphasis on analysing the employer brand (A15: 6 experts) and the employer's product and corporate brands (A16: 7 experts).
- Employee benefits: The employer's benefits for employees are recognised as a vital part of the value proposition in both theoretical analysis (S11(b)) and expert practice (A17: 8 experts).
- Measurability and validation: Both sides insist on the measurability of the EVP (Theory E4; Practice H3: 8 experts).
- Clarity and conciseness: The EVP should be a clear and concrete statement (Theory; Practice H1: 3 experts) and express a lot with few words, being concise (Theory E3; Practice H2: 6 experts).

(2) Differences

While there is significant overlap, both sides also present unique requirements or different emphases, reflecting their respective origins (academic conceptualisation versus practical application).

Requirements emphasised in theory but less explicit in expert interviews:

- Specific attribute categorisation: Theory elaborates on identifying and categorising EVP attributes as value-creating, value-destroying, and value-

neutral. While experts analyse attribute relevance (A4), this specific classification framework is not explicitly mentioned in their requirements.

- Detailed interaction understanding in EX: Theory specifies the need to “understand the role of the various interactions in the employee experience (EX)”. While experts broadly cover EX analysis (A8), this particular depth of interaction analysis is not a standalone requirement.
- General guiding principles: The theory provides overarching principles, such as considering “the current situation and the desired target perspective” and taking into account “both sides, i.e. employers and employees”. While these are fundamental, they are not listed as specific expert requirements.
- Nuance of ambition and aspiration: Theory suggests the EVP should be “based on the real current attributes of the employer, but also demonstrate ambition and aspiration”. While experts mention ‘aspiration’ in C4 (reflecting EX including culture and aspiration), the dual emphasis on real attributes and ambition is more pronounced in theory.
- Simplicity and ease of passing on: Theory explicitly requires the EVP to be ‘simple’ (E1) and ‘easy to pass on’ (E2). While experts mention ‘clear’ (H1) and ‘practical’ (H6), these specific formal requirements are less distinct.

Furthermore, the expert interviews do not cover two requirements identified in theory (see Tab. 32).

requirement	theory reference	expert interview code	expert interview freq.	comparison notes
Employees' perception of current EVP	S12	-	-	theory-specific
Make employees feel valued, express company's commitment	K5	-	-	theory-specific

Tab. 32: Theoretical requirements not identified in the expert interviews (#2)

Requirements emphasised in expert interviews but less explicit in theory:

Expert interviews reveal practical considerations and specific analytical approaches or desired EVP characteristics not explicitly detailed in the theoretical overview, e.g.:

- Broader analytical dimensions:
 - Analysing employees' prior work experiences (A3: 6 experts).
 - Analysing employees' work emotions (A5: 3 experts).
 - Analysing employees' willingness to contribute and discretionary effort (A7: 11 experts).
 - Analysing employee's behaviour (ethnography) (A9: 8 experts) – a specific research method.
 - Analysing company's structure, size, and location (A20: 11 experts) – explicit organisational context.
 - Analysing employer's purpose, vision, and mission (A21: 10 experts).
 - Analysing employer's people strategy (A22: 1 expert).
 - Analysing employer's strengths and weaknesses (A23: 6 experts).
 - Analysing the labour markets and influencing trends (A24: 6 experts, A25: 6 experts).
 - Analysing the competition (A26: 10 experts). While theory implies competition, the analysis as a distinct requirement is stronger from experts.
- Specific EVP creation characteristics:
 - Creating a motivating and engaging EVP (C3: 3 experts).
 - Creating an ownable EVP (C8: 6 experts) – highlighting brand distinctiveness beyond mere differentiation.
 - Creating a deal-related EVP (C11: 6 experts) – emphasising the reciprocal "give and take" explicitly as a characteristic.
 - Creating a selective EVP (C13: 5 experts) – suggesting the EVP might target specific talent segments.
- Structural and practical EVP aspects:

- Having a structured EVP (H5: 12 experts) – a highly mentioned requirement indicating a need for clear organisation.
- Having a specific EVP (H7: 3 experts)

Following a thorough review of the 48 requirements mentioned in the expert interviews, it was found that 24 of these are not supported by the theory (see Tab. 33).

requirement	theory reference	expert interview code	expert interview freq.	comparison notes
Analyse employees' prior work experiences	-	A3	7	expert-specific
Analyse the relevance of employer attributes to employees	-	A4	17	expert-specific
Analyse employees' work emotions	-	A5	3	expert-specific
Analyse employees' willingness to contribute + discretionary effort	-	A7	11	expert-specific
Analyse employee's behaviour (ethnography)	-	A9	8	expert-specific
Analyse employer's internal communication	-	A13	5	expert-specific
Analyse employer expectation for employees' contributions	-	A18	7	expert-specific
Analyse employer's corporate objectives and strategy	-	A19	12	expert-specific
Analyse company's structure, size and location	-	A20	11	expert-specific
Analyse employer's purpose, vision and mission	-	A21	11	expert-specific
Analyse employer's people strategy	-	A22	1	expert-specific
Analyse employer's strengths and weaknesses	-	A23	6	expert-specific
Analyse the labour markets	-	A24	6	expert-specific
Analyse labour markets influencing trends	-	A25	7	expert-specific
Analyse the competition	-	A26	11	expert-specific
Create a motivating and engaging EVP	-	C3	3	expert-specific
Create an ownable EVP	-	C8	6	expert-specific
Create a deal-related EVP	-	C11	7	expert-specific
Create a brand-aligned EVP	-	C12	10	expert-specific
Create a selective EVP	-	C13	5	expert-specific
Ensure the EVP is robust but flexible	-	H4	6	expert-specific
Ensure the EVP is structured	-	H5	12	expert-specific
Ensure the EVP is specific	-	H7	3	expert-specific
Ensure the EVP is validated	-	H8	8	expert-specific

Tab. 33: Expert-specific requirements (#24)

To conclude, there is a strong and coherent understanding of core EVP requirements that is supported by both theoretical frameworks and practical expert insights. Both sides converge on the critical importance of employee-

centricity, authenticity, strategic alignment, and the need for a competitive, measurable, and validated EVP.

However, expert interviews offer a more granular and expanded view of analytical approaches, particularly concerning specific data points like prior experiences, emotions, behaviour (ethnography), and detailed organisational context.

They also highlight practical EVP characteristics like being structured, ownable, and deal-related, reflecting real-world complexities and the evolving demands of the talent market. Conversely, the theoretical framework occasionally provides conceptual depth or general guiding principles that are implicitly implemented in practice but not explicitly enumerated as distinct requirements by the experts.

5.2.3 Theory-empirical comparison: Implicit connections

This section compares theory and empirical results, seeking implicit connections between the missing requirements in each case.

Fig. 29: Practical extension of theoretical requirements

The expert interviews indicate a further 24 detailed requirements (see Fig. 29). Although these requirements are not explicitly listed in the theoretical

framework, they can be integrated into the phases of the EVP development process.

Furthermore, this section examines the existence of identifiable connections for those in theory. Their theoretical counterpart may be implicit, part of a broader concept, or described without a specific named requirement.

1. Analysis phase requirements (A-IDs):

(1) A4: Analyse the relevance of employer attributes to employees

- Theoretical connection: The literature does not analyse attribute relevance. However, it is stated that relevant attributes should be chosen in the creation phase, which implies that their relevance must be analysed in advance. Moreover, the situation analysis aims to identify and categorise potential EVP attributes as value-creating, value-destroying or value-neutral. It also involves determining employee preferences (S2) and examine employee requirements and benefits (S11).

(2) A5: Analyse employees' work emotions

- Theoretical connection: Although not explicitly listed as an 'S' requirement, the theoretical discussion states that the EVP should "ideally be linked to a feeling or emotion to encourage associations and facilitate uptake" (K4). To effectively create an EVP that evokes specific emotions, understanding employees' current work emotions (A5) would be a crucial analytical step. However, missing in the listed requirements.

(3) A7: Analyse employees' willingness to contribute and discretionary effort

- Theoretical connection: The EVP is described as characterising the "give and take between the organisation and employees". This includes examining "the requirements of and benefits for employees" (S11). Analysing employees' willingness to contribute (A7) directly relates to this.

(4) A9: Analyse employee's behaviour (ethnography)

- Theoretical connection: The situation analysis aims to gain insights into “the current experiences of employees” (S3) and the “quintessence of the distinctive overall workplace experience” (K3). Observing employee behaviour through ethnography (A9) is a method to understand and characterise these experiences in a real and authentic way, aligning with the call for the EVP to be “real”.

(5) A13: Analyse employer’s internal communication

- Theoretical connection: On the employer side, EVP development should take into account “employer branding, which includes employee communication”. Analysing internal communication (A13) is therefore a direct prerequisite for effectively managing and integrating employee communication within the employer branding strategy that the EVP supports (K7).

(6) A18: Analyse employer expectation for employees’ contributions

- Theoretical connection: The EVP should make transparent possible requirements or burdens (value-destroying attributes). On the employer side, EVP development should consider the company's skill requirements for employees, i.e. what is demanded of employees. These directly refer to employer expectations for employee contributions.

(7) A19: Analyse employer’s corporate objectives and strategy

- Theoretical connection: This is explicitly mentioned as a factor the EVP development should consider on the employer side: “the strategic direction of the company” and “the company’s objectives”.

(8) A20: Analyse company’s structure, size and location

- Theoretical connection: While not an explicit ‘S’ requirement, the theory emphasises that the EVP should be “authentic and credible” and “based on the real current attributes of the employer”. However, this is only a loose connection.

(9) A21: Analyse employer’s purpose, vision and mission

- Theoretical connection: The EVP development should consider the “brand promise and the value proposition” and the “corporate brand”. A company’s purpose, vision, and mission (A21) are foundational elements of its brand and value proposition, influencing its culture (S5) and values (S6), which are explicitly part of the analysis.

(10) A22: Analyse employer’s people strategy

- Theoretical connection: This aligns closely with the employer's “strategic direction” and “company's objectives”.

(11) A23: Analyse employer’s strengths and weaknesses

- Theoretical connection: The situation analysis aims to identify “value-creating” and “value-destroying” attributes. This inherently involves assessing strengths (value-creating) and weaknesses (value-destroying). Furthermore, for the EVP to “assert itself in competition” (K6), understanding the employer's competitive advantages and disadvantages is critical.

(12+13) A24: Analyse the labour markets and A25: Analyse labour markets influencing trends

- Theoretical connection: The theory states that the “EVP must also be able to adapt to changes in the labour market and among employees”. Analysing the current state and influencing trends of labour markets (A24, A25) is a direct prerequisite for ensuring the EVP remains adaptable and relevant.

(14) A26: Analyse the competition

- Theoretical connection: A key requirement for the EVP is its ability to “assert itself in competition” (K6), implying the need for differentiation or uniqueness. Analysing the competition is fundamental to achieving this goal. However, it is not mentioned in the analysis.

2. Creation phase requirements (C-IDs):

(15) C3: Create a motivating and engaging EVP

- Theoretical connection: A primary goal of the EVP is to engage the employees who have been recruited. Motivation is a key factor in achieving employee engagement.

(16) C11: Create a deal-related EVP

- Theoretical connection: The EVP is fundamentally described as an “offer” that “describes what employees can expect from their commitment to the organisation”, making transparent “both the advantages (value-adding attributes) and possible requirements or burdens (value-destroying attributes), thus characterise the give and take between the organisation and employees”. This aligns perfectly with creating a ‘deal-related’ EVP.

(17) C12: Create a brand-aligned EVP

- Theoretical connection: On the employer side, EVP development should take into account the brand promise and value proposition and the corporate brand, including reputation and image. Therefore, aligning the EVP with the company's brand is implied.

(18) C13: Create a selective EVP

- Theoretical connection: One of the goals of the EVP is to “attract potential employees”. While not explicitly stated as ‘selective’, the act of attraction implicitly involves targeting specific groups, suggesting a degree of selectivity in who the EVP aims to appeal to, on a wider scale.

3. ‘Have’ Attributes (H-IDs):

(19) H4: Ensure the EVP is robust but flexible

- Theoretical connection: The theory explicitly states that the EVP should “endure in the long term” but also “be able to adapt to changes in the labour market and among employees”. This directly corresponds to the ‘robust but flexible’ characteristic (H4).

(20) H8: Ensure the EVP is validated

- Theoretical connection: The theory explicitly states that the EVP should be tested and validated internally and externally with the

target group prior to introduction. Additionally, in the optimisation phase, it is essential to evaluate it with the target group to enable internal and external validation before implementation.

In summary, a deeper look reveals that 20 of the 'missing' 24 practical requirements are indeed underpinned by broader theoretical discussions and objectives outlined in section 2.11.2, p.69. These implicit connections highlight the comprehensive nature of both the theoretical framework and the practical considerations for developing an effective EVP. However, it should be noted that four of the practical requirements have no theoretical foundation in the existing literature research (see all 24 in Tab. 34 and Fig. 30).

requirement	theory reference	expert interview code	expert interview freq.	comparison notes
Analyse employees' prior work experiences	-	A3	7	expert-specific
Analyse the relevance of employer attributes to employees	-	A4	17	theory supported
Analyse employees' work emotions	-	A5	3	theory supported
Analyse employees' willingness to contribute + discretionary effort	-	A7	11	theory supported
Analyse employee's behaviour (ethnography)	-	A9	8	theory supported
Analyse employer's internal communication	-	A13	5	theory supported
Analyse employer expectation for employees' contributions	-	A18	7	theory supported
Analyse employer's corporate objectives and strategy	-	A19	12	theory supported
Analyse company's structure, size and location	-	A20	11	theory supported
Analyse employer's purpose, vision and mission	-	A21	11	theory supported
Analyse employer's people strategy	-	A22	1	theory supported
Analyse employer's strengths and weaknesses	-	A23	6	theory supported
Analyse the labour markets	-	A24	6	theory supported
Analyse labour markets influencing trends	-	A25	7	theory supported
Analyse the competition	-	A26	11	theory supported
Create a motivating and engaging EVP	-	C3	3	theory supported
Create an ownable EVP	-	C8	6	expert-specific
Create a deal-related EVP	-	C11	7	theory supported
Create a brand-aligned EVP	-	C12	10	theory supported
Create a selective EVP	-	C13	5	theory supported
Ensure the EVP is robust but flexible	-	H4	6	theory supported
Ensure the EVP is structured	-	H5	12	expert-specific
Ensure the EVP is specific	-	H7	3	expert-specific
Ensure the EVP is validated	-	H8	8	theory supported

Tab. 34: 20 of the 24 expert-specific requirements are supported by theory

A critical re-evaluation reveals that the initial categorisation was too cautious. In fact, 20 of the 24 expert requirements are underpinned by theory.

On the other side there are two theoretical requirements not met in the interviews: S12: Examine employees' perception of the current EVP and K5: The EVP should make employees feel valued and express the company's commitment to them.

In a re-examination of all the interviews, one expert explicitly stated that he considers "what the staff think it's like to work there right now". While this perspective conceptually aligns with requirement K5, explicitly, the requirement remains unverified within the expert sample.

Fig. 30: Comparison of the theoretical and empirical requirements

In conclusion, the theory-empirical comparison revealed strong alignment on core EVP requirements. However, the experts provided more detailed analytical insights and practical EVP characteristics that were not always explicitly stated in the theory. While many of the experts' requirements had implicit theoretical connections, four lacked a direct theoretical basis. Two theoretical requirements were not mentioned by the experts.

5.3 Reflection on the analysed data

This section integrates the consolidated EVP requirements into the thesis's broader academic and strategic context. Whereas section 5.2 focused on a structural comparison of literature and practice, this reflection evaluates how the findings explicitly address the fundamental challenges identified in section 1.1 and the critical debates set out in section 2.3.

The discussion is structured to demonstrate how the empirical framework responds to the shift in power (5.3.1) and fulfils the strategic imperatives of systemisation and authenticity (5.3.2). Building on this foundation, it synthesises how these requirements mitigate theoretical criticisms regarding unitarism and ethics (5.3.3). Subsequently, it validates the findings against classical marketing frameworks (5.3.4), demonstrating their economic robustness. Finally, it concludes with retrospective methodological insights on the adaptable nature of the EVP (5.3.5–5.3.6).

5.3.1 Response to the shift of power and employee-centricity

Section 1.1 highlights the transfer of power from employer to employee. The results from chapter 5 demonstrate that this dynamic is the overwhelming practical driver for EVP requirements:

- *Foundation in employee perception*: The most significant similarity identified between theory and practice is the shared conviction of employee-centricity. This is confirmed by the finding that requirements related to analysing employee experiences (A8) and relevance of attributes (A4) were the most frequently mentioned across all experts. This directly addresses the need for an employee-centric response strategy.
- *Divergent views on employee depth*: The intra-empirical comparisons (section 5.1) reveal how different expert groups interpret this employee focus, reflecting the multidisciplinary nature of EVP development. For instance, HR professionals emphasise internal employee experience (A8) and authenticity (C9), aligning with the section 1.1 concern about misuse

if promises are not true. Conversely, Natural and Formal Sciences experts focus on behavioural analysis (A9) and measurable aspects (H3), applying a systemic view to employee contributions.

5.3.2 Strategic necessity and systematic development

Section 1.1 positions the EVP as a strategic instrument necessary to counter escalating competition for talent and requires its development to be conscious, systematic, and authentic.

- *Addressing competition*: The theoretical transfer of marketing concepts like USP and UAP aligns with the empirical need for competitiveness. Experts empirically emphasised market analysis (A24, A25, A26) and creation requirements such as Create a competitive EVP (C6) (11 experts) and the practice-specific requirement to Create an ownable EVP (C8). This focus on differentiation is a direct response to the heightened competition mentioned in section 1.1.
- *Systematic structure and gaps*: The comparison (section 5.2) confirms alignment on the four core process phases. However, practitioners introduced requirements that emphasise practicality and structure, which were less explicit in theory. The practical requirement Ensure the EVP is structured (H5) (12 experts), which lacks a direct theoretical foundation, empirically validates the need for a systematized, usable framework.
- *Authenticity and credibility*: The strong consensus on authenticity and credibility (C9) is key to preventing the EVP from being an “unarticulated concept that occurs ‘by accident’” (Veldsman and Pauw, 2018, p.78). The shared focus on the optimisation phase (O1) empirically reinforces the process of continuously improving employer attributes to close the ‘reality-ambition gap’, ensuring the EVP remains credible (Lane, 2016, p.41).

The comparative synthesis demonstrates that the integrated EVP framework effectively bridges the gap between theoretical expectations and empirical practice. It provides a structured, evidence-based response to the strategic imperatives of employee-centricity and authenticity outlined in section 1.1,

while simultaneously countering the ideological and ethical critiques identified in section 2.3. By establishing mechanisms for credibility, measurement, and continuous improvement, the framework presents the EVP as a balanced construct, reconciling organisational goals with employee well-being and thereby strengthening its legitimacy as a sustainable strategic instrument.

5.3.3 Addressing the critical discourse: from criticism to systematic mitigation

Finally, the systematic nature of the identified requirements provides robust empirical evidence to counter the theoretical criticisms of the EVP concept outlined in section 2.3, p.22. The empirical findings demonstrate that a rigorous development process actively mitigates the ideological, ethical and structural risks associated with employer branding.

- *Ideological criticism* (unitarism): The critique that the EVP solely serves as a tool for managerial control and unitarism (Nankervis *et al.*, 2020, p.19) is countered by experts' overwhelming focus on employee-centricity. The mandatory requirement to analyse employee experiences (A8) and preferences (A2) ensures that the EVP functions as a pluralist *give and get* exchange rather than a top-down imposition of corporate will.
- *Ethical criticism* (commodification and authenticity): Concerns that EVPs treat employees like commodities (Armstrong and Taylor, 2023, p.70) or rely on "window-dressing" (O'Leary and Freaney, 2025, p.134) and are empty shells (Stock-Homburg and Groß, 2019, p.171) are dispelled by the experts' strict requirements for honesty (C9) and reality (C4). Crucially, the inclusion of the *optimisation phase* (O1) institutionalises the ethical obligation to close the reality-ambition gap, thereby safeguarding the psychological contract against breach.
- *Structural criticism* (the *black box*): The critique that the EVP lacks causal evidence linking it to performance (Wright, Gardner and Moynihan, 2003, p.21) is addressed by the practical requirements for the EVP to be measurable (H3) and validated (H8).

In summary, this analysis confirms that the empirically derived EVP requirements provide the necessary systematic structure and analytical depth to address the strategic and contextual challenges established in section 1.1, ensuring the EVP functions as a credible, employee-centric, and competitive instrument.

5.3.4 Alignment with classical marketing frameworks

The empirical requirements identified in section 4.1 for the EVP situation analysis phase align strongly with, yet significantly expand upon, the elements of classical marketing situation analysis (Homburg, 2020, p.506; Meffert *et al.*, 2024, pp.251–252).

- The situation analysis, which encompasses 26 practical requirements (A1–A26), covers the five key marketing analysis areas:
 1. *Analysis of target groups*: This is the most heavily emphasised area. The requirements stipulate the analysis of employees' experiences (A8) (18 experts), attribute relevance (A4) (17 experts), expectations (A6) (14 experts), preferences (A2) (13 experts), and needs (A1) (9 experts). This framework comprehensively addresses target group identification, moving beyond mere preferences to encompass emotional (A5) and behavioural (A9) aspects.
 2. *Analysis of the company situation* (internal): In order to achieve a comprehensive understanding of the subject matter, it is necessary for the experts to undertake a thorough investigation into the following areas: corporate culture (A10) (13 experts), values (A11), leadership (A12), strategy (A19) (12 experts), and purpose/vision/mission (A21) (11 experts). This is analogous to the marketing necessity for internal resource and capability assessment.
 3. *Analysis of competitors*: This is strongly supported, requiring analysis of the competition (A26) (11 experts).

4. *Analysis of market conditions and global factors*: The empirical data explicitly address the market factors that were lacking in the theoretical analysis. The analysis of labour markets (A24) (six experts) and labour markets influencing trends (A25) (seven experts) is mandated by experts.
 5. *SWOT Analysis*: The necessity for SWOT analysis is addressed by the requirement to analyse the employer's strengths and weaknesses (A23) (6 experts), which is necessary for identifying value-creating and value-destroying attributes.
- In summary, the empirical findings of section 4.1 demonstrate a more granular and expansive application of the classical marketing situation analysis framework than the theory. Practitioners ensure comprehensive coverage of macro-environmental (A24, A25) and micro-competitive (A26) factors, alongside an intensified focus on internal reality and target group psychology (A8, A4, A7).

5.3.5 Learnings from the research process: saturation versus balance

A retrospective evaluation of the research process reveals a key methodological distinction between achieving data saturation and ensuring sample balance. From a purely functional perspective, consistency in the identification of requirements was achieved by interview 18 (see p.100). As Patton warns, saturation can be reached prematurely if the sampling frame is too narrow (2015, p.301).

In this study, the deliberate decision to *oversample* beyond the saturation point to 28 participants proved essential for validity. This extension allowed the research to move beyond merely confirming the content of the model to validating its transferability (Lincoln and Guba, 1985, p.297). By capturing minority views and including *contrasting cases* from regions such as Denmark, Iran and India, the research achieved what is termed *internal generalisability* (Barbour, 2014, p.507; Maxwell and Chmiel, 2014a, p.541). This

process highlighted that while a smaller sample would have produced the same list of 50 requirements, it would have failed to reveal how the prioritisation of these requirements shifts across different professional and cultural contexts. Thus, the immanent constraint to plausibility (Meuser and Nagel, 1991, p.466) was strengthened not just by the number of experts, but by the diversity of their functional positions.

5.3.6 Lessons learnt on the nature of EVP: conceptual consistency versus contextual execution

The process of transforming research questions into semi-structured interviews revealed a key insight into the nature of EVP: conceptual consistency does not equate to uniform execution. As Patton argues, contexts are “complex dynamic systems” (2015, p.145), meaning static depictions of a phenomenon often misrepresent reality.

The protocol revealed a global consensus on the *what*: experts universally agree on the core ontology of the EVP as a promise or a give and get deal (see section 2.2, p.21). However, the *how* – the weighting and execution of the requirements – is heavily “context-dependent” (Creswell and Poth, 2018, p.44).

- *Regional context*: The cross-national comparison demonstrated that, although the 50 requirements are valid globally, their prioritisation varies by culture. For example, German experts prioritise structure and sentiment, whereas US experts prioritise individual needs and brand alignment (see section 5.1.2, p.184). This divergence confirms the necessity to “dismiss the universalist methodologies” that claim to be applicable to all cultures without modification (Palmerberger and Gingrich, 2014, p.95).
- *Professional context*: Similarly, the professional background influences the approach to building the EVP. While consultants advocate a comprehensive, data-driven market analysis, in-house experts focus intensely on the immediate internal employee experience (see section 5.1.4,

p.203). This reflects the qualitative axiom that knowledge is always “situated and contextual” (Edwards and Holland, 2023, p.4; Mason, 2018, p.110).

Consequently, the key takeaway is that a rigid, *one-size-fits-all* model is inadequate. The *EVP Development Cycle* must therefore be viewed as a flexible framework, with the specific circumstances of each organisation determining which of the 50 requirements are prioritised. Thus, the model functions not as a universal law, but as an adaptable “*middle-range theory*” (Kuckartz and Rädiker, 2023, p.15). It provides an abstract framework for understanding the mechanisms of EVP development which can be tested and calibrated empirically across different professional and cultural contexts.

5.4 Assumptions, limitations, and delimitations

Theofanidis and Fountouki suggest that authors should report their research *limitations, delimitations* and *assumptions* in order to improve the quality of their findings and the interpretation of the evidence presented (Theofanidis and Fountouki, 2019, p.161).

5.4.1 Assumptions

Qualitative research begins with assumptions (Creswell and Poth, 2018, p.35). *Research assumptions* are essentially issues, ideas, or positions found anywhere from the beginning of the study design to the final report, that are taken for granted and viewed as reasonable, and widely accepted (Theofanidis and Fountouki, 2019, p.160).

A well-thought-out and consistent set of assumptions will constitute a credible research philosophy and will shape your choice of research question (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2023, pp.131–132).

Assumptions in this research:

- Four assumptions were made in the sampling: (a) the acquisition of knowledge is inextricably linked to experience; the undertaking of a greater number of EVP projects typically results in a corresponding increase in experience and knowledge in this area, (b) employees within a company have generally participated in fewer EVP projects than employees in employer branding consultancies, (c) individuals lacking expertise in EVP development are unlikely to be able to make a significant contribution and (d) no differences are expected in terms of gender, age, ethnicity, etc. (see chapter 3.2.2, p.93).
- The following assumptions have been made within the research design: (e) the experts do not have a list of requirements to hand, and (f) the list is as extensive as in the theory, or even more so (see chapter 3.1.2, p.80).
- Assumption from chapter 1: The developments in the labour markets, as outlined in chapter 1.1.1, p.2, the resulting power shift (chapter 1.1.2, p.3) and the consequences for companies as employers (chapter 1.1.3, p.4).
- The overall assumption is, that requirements can facilitate the development of a more effective EVP (see chapter 1.2, p.10).

5.4.2 Limitations

While the methodological limitations regarding data collection and sampling were critically reflected upon in section 3.8, p.126, this section outlines the epistemological and structural boundaries of the EVP framework developed. To ensure the appropriate application of the findings, the model's scope is delineated across three dimensions:

1. Stability of the analytical framework (process vs. content)

The primary limitation of the research lies in the distinction between the stability of the analytical framework and the fluidity of the strategic content. The *50 Requirements* identified should not be viewed as a rigid checklist of static attributes at risk of becoming obsolete, but rather as a stable heuristic for critical reflection. This distinction is crucial to avoid what Barbour terms “technical essentialism” (2014, p.507), where a set of procedures becomes reified; instead, the framework serves as a heuristic for critical reflection.

This stability is particularly relevant regarding the extent to which the findings are limited by evolving employment habits (e.g. the gig economy, fluctuating workforces), it is argued that the structural validity of the EVP Development Cycle remains intact, even as the specific content outcomes vary. As Patton observes, contexts are “complex dynamic systems” (2015, p.145), suggesting that static models often fail where flexible frameworks succeed.

2. The cultural boundary: Western-centricity

A further limitation concerns the cultural transferability of the findings. The sample reflects a Western-centric bias derived primarily from the UK, Germany and North America (see Tab. 14, p.101). Consequently, the list of 50 requirements comprehensively answers the research question for Western liberal and coordinated market economies. However, this does not invalidate the model globally, but rather defines its application. As established in section 5.3, the model operates as a *middle-range theory*, allowing for cultural adaptation. While the requirement to *analyse employee preferences* (SA-02) is universal, the weighting of the findings varies. As demonstrated by the expert comparisons, non-Western contexts may prioritise fundamental structural elements over individualistic differentiation (see Tab. 22, p.186). Therefore, the limitation lies not in the tool itself, but in the necessity for cultural calibration. The framework functions as a flexible system of weights and measures that must be adjusted to local institutional contexts.

3. The structural boundary: power dynamics and ethics

Finally, the validity of the framework must be considered in relation to the shifting power dynamics of the labour market. The current model operates

within the *War for Talent* paradigm and is employee-centric. If artificial intelligence (AI) were to reverse this dynamic through *algorithmic gatekeeping*, shifting the market from *attraction* to *automated matching*, the strategic focus of the EVP might change.

In the gig economy, the recruitment process is shifting from traditional human interaction to a process in which workers are matched with “clients” *digitally* via online platforms and algorithms (Collings, Duggan and Rogiers, 2025, p.394; Torrington *et al.*, 2020, p.152). Consequently, the strategic focus of the EVP for this specific segment may need to pivot from *attraction* (creating a compelling narrative) to *optimisation* (ensuring the offer fits the algorithm). In the media sector, this is referred to as *algorithmic gatekeeping* (van Dalen, 2023, p.63).

However, the ethical and procedural requirements would remain stable regardless of this shift. Even in an employer-dominated market, the requirements to create a *believable and honest EVP* (CR-09) and to *improve employer attributes* (OP-01) persist as essential safeguards against a breach of the psychological contract. Therefore, the model provides a durable mechanism for *ethical employer branding*, ensuring that the alignment between promise and reality is maintained, regardless of economic circumstances.

5.4.3 Delimitations

The term *delimitations* refers to the constraints imposed by the researcher on the scope of a research project prior to its initiation. In this context, delimitation signifies the process of establishing boundaries, thereby determining what is to be included and excluded within the scope of the research project (McGregor, 2018, p.171; Theofanidis and Fountouki, 2019, p.157). In that way, delimitations refer to ‘what the researcher is not going to do’ (Ellis and Levy, 2009, p.332; Leedy and Ormrod, 2015, p.62).

The objective is to circumscribe the ambit of the study and make it more manageable. Illustrative examples of this are factors, constructs and/or variables that were intentionally excluded from the study. However, delimitations can impact the external validity or generalisability of the study's results (Ellis and Levy, 2009, p.332).

Delimitations in this research:

- The decision not to conduct a quantitative study (research decision).
- The deliberate exclusion of a specific industry focus to ensure cross-sector relevance.
- The decision to exclude a country focus and focus instead on a wider perspective.
- The distinction in scope: restricting the analysis to the EVP construct rather than the employer brand concept.
- The decision not to evaluate the individual impact of the requirements on the EVP.

This chapter analysed empirical findings and compared them with theoretical requirements, revealing both commonalities and distinctions. Intra-empirical comparisons highlighted diverse priorities influenced by region, experience level, internal/external views, and academic/field backgrounds. For instance, consultants advocated a more comprehensive, data-driven approach than in-house experts. The comparison with theory identified significant overlaps in employee-centricity, authenticity, and competitiveness. However, two theoretical requirements lacked practical endorsement, while 24 practical requirements, including 'Create an ownable EVP', 'Ensure the EVP is structured', and 'Analyse employees' prior work experiences', were not explicitly covered in theory.

The synthesis successfully addressed the research question by compiling this comprehensive list of requirements, thus filling a significant knowledge gap and facilitating a more systematic approach to EVP development and evaluation. The detailed comparison indicates the necessity of integrating both the

conceptual depth of theory and the granular, external focus of expert practice
to create effective EVPs.

6. Conclusion

This chapter summarises and discusses the results, presents the new model and additional contribution to knowledge, and outlines the implications and recommendations. It also suggests areas for further research.

6.1 Summarised results and discussion

The present study yielded two results in relation to the research question. Twenty-seven requirements were identified in theory, and forty-eight in practice. Although the newly developed EVP development process was theoretically based (see Fig. 13, p.63), it was supported by the *fitting in* requirements observed in practice.

The results from the literature review and the empirical research are summarised in this section, and then related to the research question.

6.1.1 Results from systematic literature review

The thesis highlights that labour markets are undergoing significant changes due to various external factors. These changes have led to a paradigm shift, resulting in a transfer of power from employers to employees. Consequently, companies are facing major challenges as employees become a bottleneck factor, intensifying the competition for talent.

The EVP is conceptualised as a succinct crystallisation of what makes your organisation a desirable place to work. Essentially, it is the promise the employer makes to the employee.

The research adopts an EVP definition that focuses on the 'give and get' dynamic between the organisation and the employee. This definition draws upon incentive contribution theory and the net benefit concept as applied to human resource management.

This means that the EVP considers the positive and negative benefits exchanged between the employer and the employee. The definition of EVP used here is as follows: A (slightly favourable) essence of the give and get, in the form of key attributes offering an assertive competitive value package that fulfils the needs of both employees and employers, visualising the net benefit to employees.

The new EVP development process is categorised into four stages:

1. EVP situation analysis: Focuses on understanding the current state and identifying potential EVP attributes.
2. EVP development 1: Creation: Aims to create a convincing and comprehensive offer for employees, transparently outlining both advantages and burdens.
3. The EVP characteristics (formalities): Addresses the structural and communicative aspects of the EVP.
4. EVP development 2: Optimisation: Focuses on closing the gap between the stated EVP and the actual employee experience (the 'reality-ambition gap').

A systematic literature review was conducted to analyse the requirements for EVPs, resulting in the identification of 27. In accordance with the newly developed EVP development process, they were categorised within the four stages (see Fig. 18, p.75).

6.1.2 Results from empirical research

The empirical research involved conducting 28 expert interviews, which demonstrated a total of 48 requirements for the EVP. These requirements were systematically assigned to the new EVP development process.

The findings, which are empirical in nature, provide a practical and detailed perspective on the considerations that may be necessary for the development of an effective EVP. These findings have been informed by experts in the field.

As this is based on qualitative research, the number of experts is generally small. This is even more the case for comparison groups. Therefore, only general trend statements can be made. Furthermore, the experts have described their findings based on their personal project experience. This does not mean that they are always applicable (see the section on the generalisability of qualitative data in section 5.3.5, p.247).

However, as the experts have conducted over 2,000 EVP development projects, the data can be considered somewhat trustworthy. This expertise is also supported by the list of companies for which they developed EVPs. To mention a few: BP, BT, Deutsche Bank, Henkel, Hewlett-Packard (HP), Home Office (UK), Huawei, Nike, Porsche, and Visa. That said, this analysis should not be generalised; it may identify trends and be used for further research.

Additionally, the results of the interviews were compared with each other. The key findings were:

1. Intra-empirical comparisons (expert groupings)

The analysis of expert views, while noting that multiple mentions do not equate to greater importance, highlighted several trends:

Overall expert consensus: Requirements related to analysing employee experiences and their relevance (e.g. how employees perceive the employer, and what attributes are important to them) were the most frequently mentioned. Conversely, requirements such as analysing the employer's people strategy, work emotions, or the quality of current employees were mentioned least often.

Regional differences:

- *USA* (including Canada) *experts* particularly emphasised understanding employee insights and brand authenticity, focusing on employee needs, behaviour, and ensuring the EVP is believable, honest, and aligned with the corporate brand.
- *UK experts* gravitated towards a comprehensive and actionable EVP, rooted in detailed employee experience analysis, cultural alignment, and valuing the EVP being robust, flexible, and structured.
- *German experts* showed a notable focus on internal emotional aspects, sentiment reflection, and competitive market analysis, uniquely highlighting the need for a profiling EVP and strong competitive assessment.
- *The 'other' group* (Denmark, Iran, India) *experts* primarily prioritised fundamental employee understanding and EVP structure, with a strong focus on employee preferences, willingness to contribute, and having a structured EVP, often with less emphasis on broader organisational or market analyses.

Experience levels (years in field and projects): The research observed a clear progression in focus as professionals gained experience:

- Newer professionals (under 5 years/less than 5 projects) tended to concentrate on immediate, direct employee interactions and expectations, with many strategic and organisational aspects unmentioned.
- Mid-career experts (5-10 years/5-10 projects) focused on building robust, structured EVPs and ensuring clarity, often linking it closely to employee experience and organisational attributes.

- Seasoned professionals (10-20 years/10-99 projects) expanded their view to include strategic, market-driven considerations, competitive positioning, and the importance of authenticity and validation.
- The most experienced (20+ years/100+ projects) adopted a holistic, deeply insightful, and long-term perspective on employer branding, emphasising deep analytical insights, strategic impact, and the ultimate effectiveness of the EVP.

Internal versus external view (in-house vs. consultant):

- Consultants advocated for a significantly more comprehensive, data-driven, and strategically integrated analytical approach. Their perspective encompassed a broader spectrum of internal (e.g. corporate values, leadership, communication, benefits, strategy, and purpose) and external factors (e.g. labour markets, trends, competition), alongside a more explicit articulation of desired EVP creation characteristics (e.g. relevant, attractive, competitive, measurable). Notably, 32 out of 48 requirements were mentioned by consultants but not by in-house experts.
- In-house experts, while attuned to immediate employee perceptions, seemed to articulate a narrower set of analytical requirements, focusing more on direct employee preferences, expectations, and the relevance of employer attributes, as well as their existing employer brand and internal capabilities.

Academic background: Each academic background brought a unique lens:

- Natural and Formal Sciences experts strongly emphasised strategic, measurable, and behavioural aspects, with a top-down, systemic view of HR and employer branding.
- Business and Applied Studies experts focused on practical application, structure, and measurability.
- Humanities and Languages experts concentrated on communication, perception, and competitive positioning.

- Social Sciences experts were more inclined towards emotional, relational, and societal considerations.
- This highlights the multidisciplinary nature of EVP development.

Field background (HR versus marketing):

- HR professionals focused on internal employee experience and authenticity, including deep employee and internal analysis, and authenticity in EVP creation and internal improvement.
- Marketing professionals prioritised external market positioning, competitive advantage, and strategic measurability, with a focus on external market and strategic analysis, and creating competitive, brand-aligned, and measurable EVPs.
- Both fields shared emphasis on fundamental aspects like employee needs, corporate values, and having a structured EVP.

2. Theory-empirical comparison

Process phases: Both the theoretical framework and empirical findings align on the four core phases of EVP development process: Situation analysis, EVP creation, the EVP characteristics, and EVP optimisation.

Number of requirements: Theory identified 27 requirements, whereas the expert interviews demonstrate 48 practical requirements. Combining these, considering commonalities, resulted in a total of 50 distinct EVP requirements.

Similarities: There is significant agreement on foundational elements, including the importance of employee-centricity, authenticity and credibility, understanding corporate culture and values, ensuring competitiveness, aligning with employer and product brands, offering employee benefits, and the need for measurability and clarity.

Differences: Theoretical aspects such as detailed attribute categorisation, guiding principles, and aspirational nuances were less explicitly reflected in practice, and two theoretical requirements – analysing current EVP perception and ensuring employees feel valued – were absent. In contrast, practitioners highlighted broader analytical dimensions, practical creation characteristics, and structural attributes that were not specified in the theory. While the majority of the requirements derived from expert opinion were implicitly aligned with the theoretical framework, four practical requirements – namely, the creation of an ownable, structured, or specific EVP, and the analysis of prior work experience – lacked any theoretical foundation.

6.1.3 Results in relation to the research question

The research question: *What are the potential requirements for developing the employer value proposition (EVP)?* has been answered by this research.

The study's primary contribution to knowledge is the compilation of a comprehensive list of requirements for EVP and EVP development. This comprehensive list includes requirements identified from both theoretical literature and empirical research with experts.

The research question was addressed as follows:

- (1) Identification of theoretical requirements: A systematic literature review was conducted, leading to the identification of 27 theoretical requirements for EVPs.
- (2) Identification of practical requirements: Through 28 expert interviews, 48 practical requirements for EVP development were revealed.
- (3) Comparison and synthesis: The study systematically compared these theoretical and practical findings.

By compiling this extensive list, the research provides a comprehensive answer to the question of what the potential requirements for developing the employer value proposition are. The research aim was to compare the existing knowledge of EVP and their development with actual practice. This facilitates the establishment of theoretical and practical conclusions that address the existing knowledge gap in this area. This supports the systematic development and evaluation of EVPs and ultimately contributing to positive social change within the working environment

6.2 New conceptual framework / model

Out of the 27 theoretical and 48 practical requirements, a total of 50 requirements were identified (see Tab. 35 and Fig. 31, p.264).

Please find below a list of the requirements: EVP situation analysis: 27 requirements: SA-01 to SA-27, EVP creation: 14 requirements: CR-01 to CR-14, EVP optimisation: 1 requirement: OP-01 and EVP characteristics: 8 requirements: FM-01 to FM-08.

number	new ID	EVP requirement name and description	practical ID	theoretical ID
EVP Situation Analysis				
1	SA-01	Analyse employee and candidate needs	A1	S1
2	SA-02	Analyse employee preferences	A2	S2
3	SA-03	Analyse employees' prior work experiences	A3	S3
4	SA-04	Analyse the relevance of employer attributes to employees	A4	N/A
5	SA-05	Analyse employees' work emotions	A5	N/A
6	SA-06	Analyse employees' expectations towards the employer	A6	S4
7	SA-07	Analyse employees' willingness to contribute + discretionary effort	A7	N/A
8	SA-08	Analyse employees' experiences describing the employer	A8	S3
9	SA-09	Analyse employee's behaviour (ethnography)	A9	N/A
10	SA-10	Analyse employer's corporate culture	A10	S5
11	SA-11	Analyse employer's corporate values	A11	S6
12	SA-12	Analyse employer's leadership and corporate behaviour	A12	S7
13	SA-13	Analyse employer's internal communication	A13	N/A
14	SA-14	Analyse employer's quality of current employees	A14	S8
15	SA-15	Analyse the employer brand	A15	S9
16	SA-16	Analyse the employer's product and corporate brands	A16	S10
17	SA-17	Analyse employees' perception of the current EVP	N/A	S12
18	SA-18	Analyse the employer's benefits for employees	A17	S11
19	SA-19	Analyse employer expectation for employees' contributions	A18	S11

number	new ID	EVP requirement name and description	practical ID	theoretical ID
20	SA-20	Analyse employer's corporate objectives and strategy	A19	N/A
21	SA-21	Analyse company's structure, size and location	A20	N/A
22	SA-22	Analyse employer's purpose, vision and mission	A21	N/A
23	SA-23	Analyse employer's people strategy	A22	N/A
24	SA-24	Analyse employer's strengths and weaknesses	A23	N/A
25	SA-25	Analyse the labour markets	A24	N/A
26	SA-26	Analyse labour markets influencing trends	A25	N/A
27	SA-27	Analyse the competition	A26	N/A
EVP Creation				
28	CR-01	Create a relevant EVP	C1	K2
29	CR-02	Create an attractive EVP	C2	K1
30	CR-03	Create a motivating and engaging EVP	C3	K1
31	CR-04	Create an EVP reflecting EX including culture and aspiration	C4	K3
32	CR-05	Create an EVP reflecting sentiments	C5	K4
33	CR-06	Create a competitive EVP	C6	K6
34	CR-07	Create a profiling EVP	C7	K7
35	CR-08	Create an ownable EVP	C8	K6
36	CR-09	Create a believable and honest EVP	C9	K8, K9
37	CR-10	Create an effective EVP	C10	K10
38	CR-11	Create a deal-related EVP	C11	N/A
39	CR-12	Create a brand-aligned EVP	C12	K7
40	CR-13	Create a selective EVP	C13	N/A
41	CR-14	Create a feeling of being valued / express commitment	N/A	K5
EVP Characteristics				
42	FM-01	Ensure the EVP is clear	H1	E1
43	FM-02	Ensure the EVP is concise	H2	E3
44	FM-03	Ensure the EVP is measurable	H3	E4
45	FM-04	Ensure the EVP is robust but flexible	H4	N/A
46	FM-05	Ensure the EVP is structured	H5	N/A
47	FM-06	Ensure the EVP is practical	H6	N/A
48	FM-07	Ensure the EVP is specific	H7	N/A
49	FM-08	Ensure the EVP is validated	H8	N/A
EVP Optimisation				
50	OP-01	Improve employer attributes	O1	O1

Tab. 35: The 50 EVP development requirements

Note: The *practical ID* refers to the codes (A, C, O, H) representing requirements identified from the expert interviews. The *theoretical ID* refers to the codes (S, K, E, O) for requirements distilled from the theory. Where a direct conceptual match between a practical and theoretical ID is not explicitly provided "N/A" is used.

Fig. 31: The EVP development cycle calling for 50 EVP requirements

As illustrated in Fig. 31, the EVP Development Cycle encompasses 50 EVP requirements, representing the novel conceptual framework that has emerged from the synthesis of theoretical and empirical findings. This figure provides a visual representation of the 50 distinct requirements that were identified in the research study. These requirements are then aligned with the four stages of the EVP development process:

1. The EVP situation analysis (SA) encompasses a total of 27 requirements, the majority of which are focused on the establishment of a comprehensive information base and the identification of potential EVP attributes.
2. The 14 requirements of EVP creation (CR) provide a comprehensive framework for the development of a compelling offer.
3. The EVP characteristics (FM) is subject to eight requirements, which encompass both the structural and communicative characteristics of the final EVP product.
4. The requirement pertaining to EVP optimisation (OP) is intended to address the continuous effort required to bridge the so-called 'reality-ambition gap'.

6.3 Contribution to knowledge

This thesis makes significant contributions to knowledge by addressing a clear research gap in understanding the requirements for EVP development. It offers a comprehensive and systematic framework that integrates both theoretical insights and practical expertise.

area of contribution	specific contribution	details/explanation
addressing a Research Gap	Compilation of a comprehensive list of requirements for EVP development	This work addresses a significant gap in the literature by providing a comprehensive overview of requirements for EVP and its development, synthesising both theoretical insights and practical expert experiences. This approach enables a more systematic approach to EVP development and serves as an evaluation tool.
conceptual & theoretical advancements	Categorisation of EVP definitions	The study systematically categorises existing EVP definitions, identifying four distinct conceptualisations in the literature. Crucially, it adopts a dynamic <i>give and get</i> perspective (EVP 2), which considers both the employer's offers and demands, embracing the mutual value exchange in the employment relationship.
	Transfer of marketing concepts to HRM: Employer USP & UAP	The research successfully transfers established marketing concepts, specifically the Unique Selling Proposition (USP) and Unique Advertising Proposition (UAP), into Human Resource Management. It introduces the notions of employer USP (based on absolute objective competitive advantages) and employer UAP (rooted in absolute subjective competitive advantages), clarifying how marketing principles can articulate an employer's distinct competitive advantages in the labour market.
	Transfer of marketing concepts to HRM: Employer and Employee Net Benefit	It further enriches the <i>give and get</i> dynamic by applying the marketing concept of <i>net benefit</i> to HRM. This involves defining employee net benefit (positive incentives minus employee contributions and negative incentives from the employee's view) and employer net benefit (benefits from employee performance minus incentives provided by the employer), providing a robust theoretical lens for evaluating mutual value.
	Development of a new Employer Branding Process	Based on a synthesis of existing literature, the study proposes a new four-phase employer branding process: situation analysis, planning, realisation, and evaluation and optimisation.
	Development of a new EVP Development Process	Building on the employer branding process, it introduces a new four-stage EVP development process: (a) EVP Situation Analysis, (b) EVP Creation, and (c) EVP Optimisation. The new optimisation phase is particularly significant as it addresses the critical need for continuous improvement and closing the <i>reality-ambition gap</i> to ensure authenticity.
	Identification of comprehensive theoretical requirements	Through a systematic literature review, the study meticulously identified and categorised 27 theoretical requirements for EVP development and for the EVP characteristics. These requirements are logically aligned with the newly proposed four-stages process, providing a structured theoretical foundation.
	Redefining EVP as a sociological interface (Boundary Object)	Applying the concept of the boundary object to theorise the EVP not merely as a set of attributes, but as a structural translation mechanism that reconciles the competing functional logics of HRM and marketing.
	Development of an adaptable middle-range theory for HRM	Moving beyond static universal laws, it offers a dynamic theoretical structure. The framework validates the stability and transferability of the process (50 requirements), while recognising that the content requires cultural and contextual calibration.

area of contribution	specific contribution	details/explanation
empirical contributions	Identification of practical requirements from experts	The research conducted 28 expert interviews, yielding a total of 48 practical requirements for EVP development. These requirements are systematically categorised within the new EVP development process phases, offering a practical and detailed perspective.
	Detailed intra-empirical comparisons of expert groups	Provides detailed findings from intra-empirical comparisons of expert groups, revealing significant variations in perspectives based on: a) region (USA, UK, Germany, Other), b) experience levels (newer, mid-career, seasoned, most experienced), c) internal vs. external view (in-house vs. consultants), d) academic backgrounds (Natural/Formal Sciences, Business/Applied Studies, Humanities/Languages, Social Sciences) and e) field backgrounds (HR vs. Marketing). These insights highlight the diverse considerations and priorities in EVP development.
	Identification of theoretical gaps in practice	The study found that two theoretical requirements were not explicitly endorsed by the interviewed experts : examining employees' perception of the current EVP (S12) and ensuring the EVP makes employees feel valued and expresses company commitment (K5).
	Identification of practical gaps in theory (novel requirements)	Critically, the study identified four practical requirements lacking a direct theoretical foundation in the existing literature: Create an ownable EVP (C8), Ensure the EVP is structured (H5), and specific (H7), and Analyse employees' prior work experiences (A3). These offer novel practical insights.
synthesised framework	Development of a new conceptual framework / model: the EVP development Cycle	The culmination of these extensive findings is the development of a new conceptual framework presenting a comprehensive list of 50 distinct EVP requirements . This framework synthesises the 27 theoretical and 48 practical requirements, offering a vital tool for the systematic development and evaluation of EVPs.
	Improvement of the EVP determination process	The research provides a new approach that improves the process of determining the EVP by offering a structured framework and detailed guidance that goes beyond general theoretical concepts, making EVP development more structured and impactful.
	Updating the academic curriculum for Employer Branding	It identifies 24 practical requirements that are currently absent from theory, such as 'ownability' and 'structure', and provides a modernised baseline for academic instruction that reflects the operational reality of high-level employer branding.

Tab. 36: Contribution to knowledge of this thesis

Overall, this work makes a substantial contribution by systematically addressing a critical knowledge gap, offering both a detailed framework for practitioners and a robust agenda for future academic inquiry in EVP development.

Updating the academic curriculum: closing the theory-practice gap

This thesis makes a decisive contribution by highlighting a notable discrepancy between current academic literature and professional practice. As demonstrated in the comparative analysis (see section 5.2, p.224), the research identified 24 practical requirements deemed essential by experts for

the EVP development process, which are currently absent from theoretical discourse (see Tab. 33, p.235).

Consequently, this thesis proposes updates to the *academic curriculum* for employer branding. By reconstructing the *normative professional knowledge* of experts (see section 3.3.1, p.94), the research reveals that existing academic models are *lagging behind* the operational reality of the field. While current theory adequately covers foundational concepts such as employee-centricity and values, it fails to account for the structural and strategic necessities required to execute EVP development in a competitive market.

Specifically, this thesis forces academia to acknowledge that the EVP is not just a matter of content (what the employer promises), but also of structure and ownability (how the asset is constructed). Identifying novel requirements such as the necessity for a *structured* EVP (Requirement H5) and an *ownable* EVP (Requirement C8) shows that practice has overtaken theory in these operational areas.

Therefore, this work's contribution extends beyond merely *adding to* the literature; it corrects a deficit in current academic understanding. It provides scholars with a modernised baseline – the *EVP Development Cycle* – that incorporates the pragmatic rigour currently missing from the curriculum. This ensures that future academic instruction reflects the complex, multidimensional reality of high-level employer branding.

Theoretical contribution: The EVP as a sociological interface

Beyond its practical utility, this thesis makes a unique theoretical contribution by redefining the EVP as a sociological interface rather than a functional HR tool. By applying the concept of the "boundary object" (Star and Griesemer, 1989, p.393), this research theorises the EVP as a critical translation mechanism operating between distinct professional domains, rather than merely as a set of attributes.

Specifically, it establishes the EVP as the structural mechanism that forces the *functional logic of HRM* (centred on retention, reward and systems) to reconcile with the *communicative logic of marketing* (centred on attraction, reputation and differentiation).

This theoretical positioning consequently elevates the contribution of this work from the administrative domain of HRM to the level of organisational theory. By establishing the EVP as the construct in which these competing logics must align to ensure organisational legitimacy, the thesis expands the relevant academic field, offering a framework for understanding how organisations manage the tension between their internal reality and their external reputation.

Theoretical contribution: an adaptable middle-range theory

Finally, this research contributes to the epistemological advancement of the field by moving beyond static, universalist models. Instead of proposing a rigid normative law, this thesis contributes an adaptable theory of middle range for strategic HRM.

By validating that the 50 requirements function as a stable analytical framework (the process) while allowing for variable weighting (the content) (see section 5.3.6, p.248), this work resolves the tension between standardisation and localisation. It offers scholars and practitioners a theoretical structure that is robust enough to standardise the EVP process, yet flexible enough to accommodate the specific economic logics of diverse sectors and cultures. This elevates the EVP from a tactical tool to a dynamic theoretical construct capable of navigating complex organisational realities.

Synthesis of rigour and relevance

Revisiting the philosophical commitment established in section 3.1.3, this research aimed to reconcile the dichotomy between the *truth tests* of academia and the *utility tests* of professional practice (Patton, 2015, pp.728–730). The

successful development of the EVP Development Cycle demonstrates how these dual demands can be reconciled.

The *truth test* – the requirement for validity and epistemological rigour – was met through a systematic literature review and transparent application of reflexive thematic analysis. This ensured that the core constructs of the EVP were grounded in established theoretical frameworks such as incentive-contribution theory and the resource-based view.

Conversely, the *utility test* – the requirement for actionable relevance – was met by integrating the *institutionalised competence* (Meuser and Nagel, 2016, p.345) of 28 industry experts. By reconstructing 24 practical requirements absent from theoretical discourse, such as the necessity for an *ownable* (C8) and *structured* (H5) EVP, the research has generated “actionable answers” (Patton, 2015, pp.171–177). Consequently, the resulting framework is a pragmatically validated tool that solves the specific business problem of unsystematic EVP development while retaining academic integrity, rather than being merely a theoretical abstraction.

6.4 Implications

As discussed in section 5.4.2, the EVP Development Cycle is most applicable to large multinational enterprises (MNEs) and competitive mid-sized companies within Western market economies. While the principles of authenticity remain universal, the comprehensive scope of the 50 requirements is optimised for organisations with the resources to conduct in-depth strategic alignment.

In terms of *professional reach*, however, this model makes a distinct contribution by bridging the traditional disciplinary gap. An empirical comparison revealed that HR experts prioritise internal cultural authenticity, whereas

marketing experts prioritise external differentiation. The new model integrates these distinct perspectives into a single, cross-functional lexicon.

- For *HR professionals*: It provides the marketing rigour required to build a competitive (CR-06) and measurable (FM-03) proposition.
- For *marketers*: It enforces the organisational depth needed to make the brand believable and ensure it is rooted in corporate culture.

Thus, the framework acts as a *boundary object*, professionalising the collaboration between internal culture management and external talent attraction. The implications of this work are divided into theoretical and practical ones.

6.4.1 Theoretical implications

As a qualitative study designed to explore, this work contributes to the generation of theory in an area that has lacked in-depth exploration, by identifying novel requirements and deepening the understanding of existing concepts. So, this research addresses a knowledge gap.

By systematically identifying and comparing these requirements, the study facilitates a more structured approach to EVP development and offers a valuable tool for assessing compliance with these requirements. Furthermore, it improves the process of determining the EVP by providing a new approach.

The research findings, derived from the systematic identification of 50 distinct EVP requirements, intersect critically with the three conceptual lenses – HRM, Organisational theory (OT), and marketing – through which the EVP is examined in section 2.4. The comparison and synthesis in chapter 5 validate the multidisciplinary nature of EVP development.

1. EVP in relation to HRM theory

From the HRM standpoint, the EVP is designed to strategically align talent management, recruitment, retention, and rewards with corporate strategy, often conceptualised as the espoused psychological contract (Nankervis *et al.*, 2020, p.363).

- (1) *Strategic fit and alignment*: The findings strongly validate the fundamental HRM requirement of vertical alignment (Binder, 2016, p.410). Experts frequently mentioned the need to analyse employer's corporate objectives and strategy (A19) and corporate values (A11), ensuring the EVP supports organizational effectiveness. Furthermore, the requirement to analyse the employer's people strategy (A22), although mentioned infrequently, directly supports the HRM goal of aligning talent practices.
- (2) *Psychological contract and mutual exchange*: The synthesized requirements strongly embrace the HRM concept of the psychological contract, particularly the 'give and get' dynamic (Dubey and Rana, 2021, p.87). Expert requirements, such as Analyse employees' willingness to contribute and discretionary effort (A7) and Analyse employer expectation for employees' contributions (A18), empirically operationalize this reciprocal expectation, influencing HR functions like performance management and rewards.
- (3) *Closing the gap*: The explicit and heavily endorsed Optimisation requirement (OP-01: Improve employer attributes) serves as the theoretical mechanism to ensure that HR's promises align with the employee's experience, which is a core tenet of effective HRM practice (Lane, 2016, p.51).

2. EVP in relation to Organisational theory (OT)

Organisational theory situates the EVP within broader frameworks of identity, culture, motivation, and institutional legitimacy.

- (4) *Identity and culture*: The OT perspective emphasises that the EVP is linked to organisational identity and culture (Backhaus and Tikoo, 2004, p.504). This is overwhelmingly confirmed by the consensus on

requirements to analyse corporate culture (A10) and create an EVP reflecting EX including culture and aspiration (C4).

- (5) *Authenticity and legitimacy*: OT stresses that misalignment with culture risks undermining legitimacy (Fustier, 2022, p.22). The requirement to create a believable and honest EVP (C9) and the Optimisation phase (OP-01) ensure credibility, aligning the EVP with institutional logics and internal consistency. It is argued that promises must be credible and enacted internally (McCartney and Fu, 2022, p.298; Meyer and Rowan, 1977, p.352).
- (6) *Motivational frameworks (expectancy and self-determination theory)*: Motivational theories, such as Vroom's expectancy theory (Vroom, 1964, p.15), inform EVP design by clarifying what employees value for their contributions. The most frequently cited analytical requirements – understanding employee needs (A1), preferences (A2), and the relevance of employer attributes (A4) – provide the granular data necessary to predict how employees will be motivated, directly applying these theoretical frameworks in practice.

Furthermore, the experts explicitly demanded that the EVP address meaning and culture (Requirements A10 and A21). This empirical finding is supported by self-determination theory (SDT), which states that the psychological need for relatedness is a prerequisite for intrinsic motivation. Therefore, the experts' emphasis on a strong culture is not merely a branding exercise, but a psychological necessity for engagement.

3. EVP in relation to marketing theory

Marketing provides the conceptual tools for framing, researching, and communicating the EVP as a differentiated brand promise.

- (7) *Employee-centricity (customer-centricity)*: The marketing mindset of customer centricity aligns perfectly with the HRM principle of employee centricity (Holbeche, 2022, p.114). The massive empirical emphasis on analysing employee perspectives (A8) and relevance (A4)

demonstrates that the workforce is treated as a critical target audience whose value must be strategically researched.

- (8) *Differentiation and competitive advantage*: The successful transfer of the USP and UAP concepts into HRM theory is strongly supported by the empirical data. Practitioners mandate strategic requirements such as Analyse the competition (A26) and Create a competitive EVP (C6). Furthermore, the practice-driven requirement to Create an ownable EVP (C8), which lacks theoretical foundation, serves to reinforce the marketing objective of achieving a distinct and defensible position in the labour market.
- (9) *Brand alignment and communication*: Marketing ensures the EVP is a credible brand promise (Kotler *et al.*, 2019, p.240). This is confirmed by the requirements to Create a brand-aligned EVP (C12) and structurally ensure the EVP is clear (H1) and concise (H2) for effective external and internal communication.

theoretical lens (section 2.4)	core theoretical concept	empirical evidence and implications (requirements)
HRM theory	psychological contract / mutual exchange	Findings validate the 'give and get' dynamic, operationalised by requirements to analyse employee contributions (A7, A18). The optimisation phase (OP-01) institutionalises continuous attribute correction, supporting contract credibility.
organisational theory (OT)	identity, culture, and legitimacy	Empiricism confirms the link between EVP and organisational culture. Requirements demand analysis of corporate culture (A10) and creating an EVP reflecting employee experience (C4). The mandate for authenticity (C9) counters threats to institutional legitimacy.
marketing theory	differentiation / competitive advantage	The EVP acts as a tool for differentiation. Practitioners mandate analysis of competition (A26) and creation of a competitive EVP (C6). The practice-driven requirement to Create an ownable EVP (C8) reinforces the strategic need for distinct market positioning.

Tab. 37: Empirical evidence and implications with regard to external theories

Collectively, these findings substantiate the empirically validated requirements, thereby positioning the EVP as a pivotal strategic integrator. This integration encompasses the convergence of employee experience, organisational identity, and brand reputation across the disparate theoretical frameworks of HRM, organisational theory, and marketing. The resulting systematic framework thus serves to consolidate the EVP's theoretical standing as a

credible and sustainable tool for achieving mutual benefit and authenticity in competitive labour markets.

6.4.2 Practical implications

This research has the capacity to fundamentally alter the nature of EVP development, transforming it from an opaque creative exercise into a measurable, auditable, and systematic business process. Previous literature has described EVP development as an “unarticulated concept that occurs ‘by accident’”, frequently reducing it to a mere formality. This research shifts this paradigm by establishing the EVP Development Cycle and a set of 50 validated requirements. Specifically, the extent of the impact can be defined in three dimensions:

1. Standardisation as a diagnostic protocol

To a significant extent, this work standardises a fragmented field. By identifying 32 practical requirements mentioned by consultants but absent from the perspectives of in-house experts, the thesis highlights inconsistencies in EVP development. The new framework closes this gap by transforming the 50 requirements from a passive list into an industry diagnostic protocol. Prior to this research, organisations could often only speculate as to why an EVP failed to engage talent. With this model, however, practitioners can now perform a *forensic diagnosis*. By auditing a failing EVP against the 50 requirements, managers can pinpoint exactly which step was missed, whether it was a failure to analyse *work emotions* (SA-05) or a failure to ensure the proposition was *ownable* (CR-08). This transforms the contribution into an active management tool for solving business problems through rigorous auditing.

2. Ethical intervention: protecting the psychological contract

The impact extends beyond operational rigour to ethical intervention. In theory, the EVP acts as the *espoused psychological contract*. Any discrepancy between the promise and the lived experience constitutes a breach of this contract. This framework acts as a structural safeguard against such

breaches. By mandating the *optimisation phase* (Requirement OP-01) and *honesty* (Requirement C9), the model compels organisations to actively bridge the *reality-ambition gap*. It dictates that the EVP cannot remain a static marketing slogan, but must drive tangible organisational change. Consequently, this research provides practitioners with the necessary mechanisms to protect the workforce from over-promising, thereby transforming the EVP into a tool for building sustainable trust.

3. Strategic elevation

Finally, the work elevates the EVP from a tactical HR task to a strategic imperative. By empirically validating the need to analyse *corporate objectives* (SA-20) and *labour markets* (SA-25), the framework demonstrates that a robust EVP is a means of achieving competitive advantage. It provides HR practitioners with the *net benefit logic* needed to gain the support of the board, thus turning the EVP into a vital business tool.

The research provides a systematic framework and a detailed, comprehensive list of 50 requirements to help practitioners develop and evaluate EVPs more effectively. It offers practical, tailored guidance that goes beyond general theoretical concepts, making the EVP development process more structured and impactful.

However, it is important to consider the issue of transferability, i.e. non-statistical generalisation. While qualitative research is not typically intended for statistical generalisation to larger populations, its findings can be transferred to similar cases or settings.

Interpreting prevalence for prioritisation

While the frequency of mentions in the empirical study does not dictate theoretical significance, as discussed in chapter 4, it is a useful heuristic for practitioners when prioritising implementation.

- *High-frequency requirements* (the baseline): Requirements mentioned by a large majority (e.g. A4, A8 and C4) represent the established

professional standard. Organisations that ignore these risk falling below the market baseline and failing to meet the fundamental hygiene factors of a credible EVP.

- *Low-frequency requirements* (the differentiators): Requirements mentioned by a smaller number of experts (e.g. A5, C7 and A22) often represent more advanced or specialised practices. For organisations with a mature EVP, focusing on these less common requirements offers the greatest opportunity for differentiation and competitive advantage.

Therefore, practitioners should first audit their EVP against the high-frequency requirements to ensure stability before using the lower-frequency requirements to drive innovation.

Guide to utilising the 50 EVP requirements

The 50 synthesised requirements, which encompass theoretical and empirical findings, are divided into four stages: EVP situation analysis (SA-01 to SA-27), EVP creation (CR-01 to CR-14), the EVP characteristics (FM-01 to FM-08) and EVP optimisation (OP-01). These requirements provide a robust toolkit for practitioners. It is up to the development team to decide whether each requirement is potentially applicable in the given context.

SA-01 to SA-27: What should be considered to be analysed?

The 27 requirements in the situation analysis phase define a comprehensive information base that may be necessary to anchor the EVP in reality. Basically, the EVP must be based on data. The requirements can help you decide which data you need for development. All 27 requirements focus on understanding the current status and identifying potential EVP attributes.

CR-01 to CR-14: What should be considered during development?

The 14 requirements in the creation phase aim to produce a convincing, comprehensive offer that transparently presents both advantages and burdens (*give and get*).

FM-01 to FM-08: What should come out?

The eight requirements for the EVP characteristics are suggestions that relate to the structural and communicative characteristics of the final EVP 'product'.

OP-01: What should be optimised?

The optimisation phase, which is characterised by its explicit focus on closing the 'reality-ambition gap', involves only one requirement.

Global application and cultural weighting

Practitioners must recognise that applying this framework requires acute cultural sensitivity. A key finding of this study is that, although the 50 requirements function as a *universal analytical tool*, their strategic *weighting* must be calibrated according to culture. Drawing on the principle of *glocalisation*, the framework is a flexible system of weights and measures. For instance, creating an EVP that *reflects sentiments* (CR-05) is a universal process step. However, as the findings show, German practitioners may prioritise this to ensure emotional resonance, whereas US practitioners may deprioritise it in favour of *brand alignment* (CR-12). Therefore, rather than stripping down the model, the implication for global management is to adjust the *volume* of specific requirements to match local institutional contexts.

The reach of the framework: sectoral applicability**(1) Industry dynamics: Transaction costs versus resource value**

The comprehensive nature of the model raises the question of its transferability to other sectors (see section 5.4.2, p.250). A key implication is that the

weighting of requirements adapts to the industry's specific *economic logic*, as discussed in section 2.4.1, p.27.

- **Applicability to the *gig economy* (*TCE logic*):** In sectors that rely on transient workforces or project-based expansion, the employment relationship is often governed by transaction cost economics principles, whereby firms weigh the costs of internal employment against external contracting (Wood *et al.*, 2025, pp.154–155). Here, the strategic goal shifts from long-term retention to immediate transactional efficiency. Consequently, requirements focusing on deep *corporate culture* (SA-10) may be deprioritised. Instead, the focus shifts to the immediate *deal* (CR-11) and *remuneration* (SA-18) in order to reduce search costs and enable swift onboarding. The EVP acts as a rapid *self-selection tool* (CR-13) to streamline the transaction.
- **Applicability to *creative industries* (*RBV logic*):** Conversely, the resource-based view is often considered dominant in creative or knowledge-intensive sectors because competitive advantage depends on *people-embodied know-how* rather than physical assets (Boxall *et al.*, 2022, p.95; Snell and Morris, 2023, pp.53–54). Since human capital is rare, valuable and non-substitutable in these sectors (i.e. the *talent*), the EVP must focus on *differentiation* and retention. The focus shifts towards requirements such as *create an ownable EVP* (CR-08) and *align with the product brand* (SA-16) to ensure aspirational appeal and competitive advantage through unique human assets.

Consequently, the 50 requirements should be viewed as a *scalable heuristic* that adapts to the economic reality of the sector, whether driven by transaction costs or resource value.

(2) Knowledge intensity: Applying Self-Determination Theory

Furthermore, the framework's scope can be refined by distinguishing between industries based on their knowledge intensity. Although the list of 50 requirements remains a universal analytical tool, the way in which these requirements are applied strategically varies according to the dominant

psychological needs of the workforce, as theorised by *self-determination theory (SDT)* (see section 2.4.2, p.33).

- *Knowledge-intensive industries* (e.g. technology and consulting): In sectors where human capital is the primary source of value creation (RBV), employees are often driven by high levels of intrinsic motivation. Consequently, the EVP must prioritise the SDT needs for autonomy and competence (Ryan and Deci, 2020, p.2). In practice, this means that the *creation phase* must prioritise requirements demonstrating *career growth and professional mastery* (Requirement SA-18/A17), as the desire to feel effective and overcome challenges is a key motivator in these fields (see section 2.4.2). Additionally, analysing *leadership behaviour* (Requirement SA-12) is paramount to ensure that the promise of autonomy is not undermined by micromanagement.
- *Labour-intensive industries* (e.g. retail, manufacturing): Conversely, in sectors often characterised by repetitive tasks or higher turnover rates, the psychological driver for retention shifts towards relatedness. Here, the EVP must focus on fostering a sense of belonging and social connection to mitigate fluctuation. Therefore, the strategic focus shifts towards *corporate culture* (Requirement SA-10) and *internal communication* (Requirement SA-13) to satisfy the desire to feel connected to others (Ryan and Deci, 2020, p.1). While *competence* remains relevant, the decisive factor for retention in these industries is often the strength of the social fabric (culture) and the provision of security (hygiene factors) rather than the promise of autonomous mastery.

As illustrated in Tab. 38, the application of the 50 requirements is not static, but rather contingent on the economic logic of the industry. The framework serves as a scalable heuristic: the process remains stable, but the strategic weighting shifts.

strategic dimension	context A: gig economy / labour-intensive	context B: creative and knowledge-intensive
dominant economic logic	Transaction Cost Economics (TCE) (<i>Williamson, 1975</i>)	Resource-Based View (RBV) (<i>Barney, 1991</i>)
strategic goal	transactional efficiency focus on reducing search costs and friction to enable swift onboarding.	differentiation and retention focus on securing unique human assets that are rare and inimitable.
primary function of EVP	self-selection tool: To streamline the transaction and help candidates quickly decide if they fit.	brand signal: To build an aspirational identity and emotional connection.
priority requirements (<i>volume turned up</i>)	focus on the deal and clarity: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (CR-11) Create a deal-related EVP • (SA-18) Analysis of benefits/remuneration • (CR-13) Create a selective EVP 	focus on culture and uniqueness: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (CR-08) Create an ownable EVP • (SA-16) Alignment with product brand • (SA-12) Leadership behaviour
psychological driver (<i>self-determination theory</i>)	clarity and relatedness Focus on removing ambiguity and fostering social connection in repetitive tasks [Source 1216].	autonomy and competence Focus on professional mastery, career growth and overcoming challenges [Source 1215].

Tab. 38: The reach of the framework: adapting EVP strategy to economic logic

Thus, the 50 requirements function as a diagnostic instrument that allows practitioners to emphasise specific attributes – *growth (competence)* for knowledge workers, or *culture (relatedness)* for service workers – to align with the industry’s specific motivational profile.

The identified requirements also serve as an evaluation tool for assessing compliance throughout the EVP development process or evaluate past processes. The ultimate purpose is to improve the EVP development process and create more effective EVPs that benefit both employers and employees.

Specific, practical insights were gained by comparing different expert groups. These trend statements highlight the awareness that these factors may influence the development of the EVP. They also enable practitioners to be aware of these dynamics and adapt their EVP strategies and teams according to their particular circumstances, experience and professional background.

This leads to more informed job decisions, enhanced employee experiences, optimised resource allocation, and improved team performance and

retention. This is particularly crucial in changing labour markets, where companies face a shift in power towards employees and increased competition for talent.

6.5 Further research

The research conducted identifies several implications for further study.

6.5.1 Novel theoretical avenues arising from practice-theory gaps

The primary theoretical avenue involves building theory around the four practical requirements that were found to lack a direct theoretical foundation in the existing literature:

Creating an Ownable EVP (C8):

- (1) Theoretical Implication: Research needs to conceptually define '*ownability*' within the context of employer branding and competitive advantage. While theory covers differentiation and uniqueness (K6), ownability suggests a higher threshold of strategic control and intellectual property over the promise, akin to sustainable competitive advantage. Future theory should explore how the Employer USP concept can be refined to incorporate this notion of exclusive, defensible ownership.

Having a Structured EVP (H5):

- (2) Theoretical Implication: The empirical emphasis on a structured EVP (mentioned by 12 experts) suggests that theoretical models of EVP and Employer Branding need to explicitly integrate structural design principles. This requirement (H5) relates to the necessity of pillars and thematic organisation. Theory generation could focus on developing prescriptive models for EVP architecture, linking structure to

implementation success, practitioner usability, and theoretical concepts like Total Rewards complexity.

Having a Specific EVP (H7):

- (3) Theoretical Implication: The requirement for specificity implies that EVPs should move beyond broad statements toward concrete, actionable claims relevant to distinct target groups. Theoretical work could explore the relationship between EVP specificity and its effectiveness in talent self-selection (C13), testing whether highly specific EVPs (H7) lead to better organisational fit and reduced turnover than highly clear (H1) but vague EVPs.

Analysing Employees' Prior Work Experiences (A3):

- (4) Theoretical Implication: This analytical requirement (A3) suggests that future EVP theory must incorporate the influence of an employee's pre-joining professional history on their current perception of the employer. This deepens the theoretical scope of the Situation Analysis phase beyond current needs (A1) and expectations (A6). Research could integrate concepts from Social Comparison Theory or Psychological Contract formation, focusing on how prior contract breaches or positive experiences elsewhere shape current attraction and retention drivers.

Revisiting undersubscribed theoretical requirements: Future studies could also investigate why two specific theoretical requirements – examining employees' perception of the current EVP (S12) and ensuring the EVP makes employees feel valued and expresses company commitment (K5) – were not explicitly endorsed by practitioners. This exploration is crucial for determining their actual influence on EVP development and refining theory.

The omission of the theoretical requirement K5 by practitioners necessitates ambitious theoretical work to assess its true impact. This research would bridge the gap between measurable authenticity (C9) and the 'softer' psychological elements of dignity and self-worth, potentially integrating

sophisticated social exchange theory to model the cost of neglecting relational requirements versus prioritising transactional ones.

6.5.2 Novel theoretical avenues arising from empirical data by group

Further research is indicated by six entry points that have been identified through the group comparisons.

(1) *Regional and cultural nuances*: The study observed distinct priorities across different countries/regions (UK, Germany, USA, and 'Other' experts). Future research, potentially with larger and more balanced samples from each region, could delve deeper into these cultural and market-specific influences on EVP development.

Furthermore, in order to determine whether these differences persist or move towards convergence due to economic globalisation and technological harmonisation, ambitious longitudinal comparative research is required. This research would contribute to a more robust theoretical understanding of HRM convergence and divergence in the context of global talent wars.

(2) *Evolution of expertise*: The realisation that the focus of EVPs evolves significantly with increasing professional experience justifies longitudinal studies. These studies could track this development and its causes, thereby deepening our understanding of how expertise is acquired and implemented in EVP practice over time. As an alternative hypothesis, in-depth interviews with experts at differing levels of seniority could be utilised to track this progression and its underlying factors.

(3) *Consultant versus in-house perspectives*: Consultants displayed a significantly more comprehensive, data-driven, and strategically integrated analytical approach compared to in-house experts, who focused more narrowly

on direct employee perceptions. Given the sample size disparity, a dedicated comparative study with a more balanced representation of both groups could provide richer insights into these divergent viewpoints.

Testing Consultant-Driven Analytical Depth (A24, A25, A26): The research found that consultants strongly advocated for detailed external analysis of labour markets (A24), influencing trends (A25), and competition (A26). It is recommended that future research endeavours quantitatively examine the correlation between this deep analytical investment and the success of the resulting HR communication campaigns.

Moreover, it would be worthwhile to ascertain whether this phenomenon is also applicable to other consultant fields. While the present study is delimited solely to experts within employer branding and EVP development, the drivers identified for the consultants' broad analytical scope suggest the behaviour may be universal to the consulting function:

- (a) The overarching *objective of consultants* is to explicitly link their recommendations to corporate objectives and strategy (A19) and external market intelligence (A24, A25, A26). This core requirement is evident across various strategic consulting disciplines. This stands in stark contrast to the practices of in-house teams, which are characterised by a narrower focus on immediate employee perceptions.
- (b) *Reputational necessity:* Consultants are strongly motivated by reputation, meaning they aim for detailed, comprehensive, and good results to secure future projects. This finding indicates that external consultants, irrespective of their specialisation (e.g. IT, finance, strategy), are required to utilise a more extensive analytical framework compared to their in-house counterparts, who frequently operate within the constraints of operational practices.

Consequently, future research should entail a dedicated comparative study across multiple consulting fields to ascertain whether this analytical breadth is an intrinsic characteristic of external expertise itself.

(4) *Other influencing factors in the EVP development process*: Once the above factors are confirmed, it is possible to investigate why this is the case and whether there are other contributing factors.

(5) *Investigating niche requirements*: Requirements mentioned least frequently, such as analysing employer's people strategy (A22) or creating profiling EVP (C7), warrant further investigation to determine if they are niche, emerging, or underestimated aspects of EVP development.

(6) The question of whether *gender or diversity* are possible factors is a salient one. It is imperative to verify this.

6.5.3 General avenues for theory generation

Finally, the research explicitly suggests several broad theoretical avenues stemming from the overall findings and limitations:

- (1) *Reasons why some requirements are mentioned more often than others*: this may be attributable to a number of factors: (a) the requirements could be of lesser importance, (b) it could be one that is rarely used, because it is rarely important, or (c) it could be one that is rarely used, and only a few experts are aware of its importance.
- (2) *Evaluation of requirement impact* (e.g. Kano theory): Future quantitative research could focus on assessing the individual impact of the 50 identified requirements on EVP effectiveness. This could involve applying theoretical models like the Kano theory (Boltz and Trommsdorff, 2022, p.320; Swoboda and Schramm-Klein, 2025, p.248), separating requirements into basic factors, performance factors, and excitement factors to understand their differential impact on the EVP development and employee satisfaction and engagement.
- (3) *Role of emotions and behavioural analysis* (A5, A9): Further qualitative research should explore the theoretical underpinning and practical application of 'softer' requirements like analysing employees' work

emotions (A5) and employee behaviour (ethnography) (A9). This could integrate psychological theory with HRM practice.

- (4) *Multidisciplinary team theory*: The clear differences in priorities based on academic (e.g. Natural/Formal Sciences vs. HL) and field backgrounds (HR vs. marketing) suggest a need for theoretical development regarding optimal interdisciplinary team composition for EVP development.
- (5) *Addressing limited generalisability*: As a qualitative study with an inherently small sample size, the findings are not statistically generalisable. Future research could employ quantitative methods to validate the reconstructed trends and requirements across larger populations, providing broader insights.
- (6) *Further investigation of EVP requirements*: Although 50 requirements is impressive already, there may be more to reconstruct. Further research could reveal more.
- (7) *Continuing along the process*: This research focused on the core EVP development process. Further research could be carried out regarding the later stages (see Fig. 14, p.64), for example on the implementation of the EVP.
- (8) *Analyse the reciprocal process for optimising the employer attributes*: The literature review indicated a necessity to continuously improve the attributes. Future studies could aim to investigate the framework conditions and implementation in the context of the identified reciprocal process for optimising the employer attributes.
- (9) *Empirical validation of employer USP and UAP*: The research introduced the theoretical notions of employer USP (based on objective advantages) and employer UAP (based on subjective competitive advantages). Future studies could undertake large-scale *HR communication experiments* in order to ascertain the relative effectiveness of communication strategies that are derived from *employer USPs* as opposed to those that are derived from *employer UAPs*. The primary objective of this analysis could be to ascertain the extent to which these strategies are able to attract external talent and influence market perception. This would provide empirical grounding for the theoretical transfer.

- (10) The predictive *power of employee net benefit (EENB)* is a key consideration in the field of organisational psychology. The work applied the marketing concept of net benefit to define employee net benefit (EENB) and employer net benefit (ERNB). Further research could involve quantitative studies that utilise market research methodologies to ascertain whether the EENB calculation – positive incentives minus contributions and negative incentives – functions as a superior predictor of a candidate’s attraction to a company in comparison to conventional measures of compensation or brand perception.

The presented framework of 50 requirements establishes a robust, multidisciplinary agenda for further inquiry, necessitating ambitious quantitative validation and continued theoretical model development to secure the long-term effectiveness and strategic credibility of the EVP. This sustained research effort is essential for transitioning EVP development into a systematically managed and rigorously evidenced strategic discipline.

6.5.4 The looming paradigm shift: AI and algorithmic gatekeeping

Finally, a critical limitation of the current study is its assumption of an ongoing power shift towards employees (see section 1.1.2, p.3). Although the EVP Development Cycle is intended for the current talent-short market, the advent of an “algorithmically infused society” (Wagner *et al.*, 2021, p.197) could introduce a factor that would reverse this dynamic. As discussed in relation to algorithmic gatekeeping (van Dalen, 2023, p.63; Vos and Russell, 2019, p.2340), this technology could dominate recruitment and transform the EVP from a tool for attracting talent to a tool for automated matching. Consequently, the balance of power may shift back towards the employer. Therefore, future research must investigate whether the strategic necessity of the EVP persists in a market where human choice is increasingly mediated or even replaced by automated decision-making.

Ultimately, future research should explore how *ethical employer branding* can serve as a normative anchor in an automated future. This would ensure that the EVP remains a fair 'give and get' mechanism, rather than merely an algorithmic output.

6.6 Summary

In this chapter, the research findings are systematically summarised, the resultant conceptual framework is presented, the contributions to knowledge are detailed, and the implications and avenues for further study are outlined.

Summarised Results and Conceptual Framework

The chapter confirms that the central research question, "*What are the potential requirements for developing the Employer Value Proposition (EVP)?*", has been answered. The work identified 27 theoretical requirements via a systematic literature review and 48 practical requirements through 28 expert interviews.

The synthesis of these findings produced the EVP Development Cycle, a new conceptual framework featuring a comprehensive list of 50 distinct EVP requirements. This cycle is structured into four stages.

1. EVP Situation Analysis (SA-01 to SA-27): Focusing on the establishment of a comprehensive information base.
2. EVP Creation (CR-01 to CR-14): Focusing on formulating a persuasive and exhaustive proposal.
3. EVP Characteristics (FM-01 to FM-08): Addressing the structural and communicative requirements of the final product.
4. EVP Optimisation (OP-01): Focusing on continuous improvement to bridge the 'reality-ambition gap'.

Key Findings and Contributions to Knowledge

The research validates the multidisciplinary nature of EVP, confirming strong consensus across theory and practice regarding employee-centricity and authenticity.

Significant contributions to knowledge include:

- *Theoretical advancements:* The thesis contributes to the theoretical understanding of the construct by providing a precise definition: The EVP constitutes a strategically curated articulation of the mutual exchange between employer and employee. It synthesises the organisation's core value-creating attributes into a differentiated, competitively positioned offering that simultaneously addresses organisational and individual needs. By making the net benefit to the employee explicit, the EVP functions as a communicative mechanism that conveys the unique advantages of employment within the organisation. Furthermore, the new EVP Development Process was formalised to incorporate the critical optimisation phase and bridge the reality-ambition gap.
- *Empirical insights:* Intra-empirical comparisons highlighted significant variations in requirements based on expert groupings (e.g. consultants advocated for a dramatically more comprehensive, data-driven analytical approach than in-house experts).
- *Identification of gaps:* The study revealed that two theoretical requirements (S12 and K5) were neglected in practice, while four practical requirements lacked theoretical foundation (C8, H5, H7, and A3). These findings provide novel insights for academic focus.

Implications and Further Research

The findings offer substantial practical implications, providing practitioners with a detailed tool (the 50 requirements) to make the development process more structured, systematic, and impactful.

The following ambitious projects, among others, are proposed for future research: firstly, the evaluation of the impact of the 50 requirements using

Kano theory; secondly, the design of frameworks for the 'ownership capability' of EVPs (C8); and thirdly, the theory of the optimal multidisciplinary team.

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1. Appendix 1: EVP Acronym Resolution

<p>Authors using <i>employer</i> value proposition:</p> <p>(Biswas and Suar, 2016, p.58; Botha, Bussin and Swardt, 2011, p.6; Christiaans, 2013, p.5; Gladka, Fedorova and Dohadailo, 2022, p.47; Goncalves, 2017, p.229; Keohane, 2009, p.37; Kristia, 2023, p.295; Kucherov <i>et al.</i>, 2023, p.2107; Lane, 2016, p.24; Lee and Abdullah, 2024, p.62; Minchington, 2012, p.18; Näppä, Ek Styvén and Foster, 2023, p.73; Nurmi and Varis, 2021, p.45; Sharma, Verma and Taluka, 2021, p.144; Steffen, 2019, p.114; Theurer <i>et al.</i>, 2018, p.156; Walter and Kremmel, 2016, p.20; Wölki, Gibb and Pfahler, 2025, p.364)</p>
<p>Authors using <i>employee</i> value proposition:</p> <p>(Aguinis, Beltran and Cope, 2024, p.2; App, Merk and Büttgen, 2012, p.262; Baran, 2018, p.47; Barrow and Mosley, 2005, p.113; Bronlet <i>et al.</i>, 2024, p.280; Chambers <i>et al.</i>, 1998, p.46; Confetto <i>et al.</i>, 2023, p.124; Dubey and Rana, 2021, p.87; Green, 2019, p.101; Jędrzejczyk, 2020, p.3; Kaliannan <i>et al.</i>, 2023, p.14; Kumar, Devadas and Dhammika, 2021, p.21; Lassleben and Hofmann, 2023, p.547; Leatherbarrow and Fletcher, 2018, p.181; Lesenyeho, Barkhuizen and Schutte, 2018, p.3; Mascarenhas, 2019, p.99; McLean-Conner, 2015, p.18; Mehta and Kappal, 2024, p.1; Mortensen and Edmondson, 2023, p.45; Muller, 2023, p.52; Phungula, Dhanpat and Braine, 2022, p.46; Reddy, 2017, p.34; Sahoo and Srivastava, 2024, p.1298; Setiawati, 2019, p.143; Soeling, Ajeng Arsanti and Indriati, 2022, p.2; Sparrow and Makram, 2015a, p.251; Veldsman and van der Merwe, 2025, p.4),</p>
<p>Authors using <i>employment</i> value proposition:</p> <p>(Backhaus and Tikoo, 2004, p.510; Heger, 2007, p.121; Srivastava and Bhatnagar, 2010, p.27; Szegedi, Németh and Körtvési, 2023, p.5)</p>
<p>Authors using <i>unique employment</i> proposition (UEP):</p> <p>(Ewing <i>et al.</i>, 2002, p.11; Immerschitt and Stumpf, 2019, p.38).</p>

Tab. 39: EVP Acronym Resolution (authors)

2. Appendix 2: Four approaches of the value within the EVP (authors)

EVP 1: Focusing on the offers of the employer
(Alloush, 2020, p.3; Armstrong and Taylor, 2023, p.248; Backhaus and Tikoo, 2004, p.502; Barrow and Mosley, 2005, p.125; Biswas and Suar, 2016, p.58; Bronlet <i>et al.</i> , 2024, p.280; Confetto <i>et al.</i> , 2023, p.124; Deepa and Baral, 2019, p.80, 2021, p.883; Dubey and Rana, 2021, p.87; Edwards, 2010, p.7; Fournier <i>et al.</i> , 2019, p.31; Green, 2019, p.101; Heger, 2007, p.121; Kumar, Devadas and Dhammika, 2021, p.21; Mehta and Kappal, 2024, p.4; Näppä, Ek Styvén and Foster, 2023, p.75; Pattnaik and Misra, 2016, p.16; Pawar and Charak, 2014, p.2; Phungula, Dhanpat and Braine, 2022, p.47; Saini, Rai and Chaudhary, 2013, p.97; Setiawati, 2019, p.143; Staniec and Kalińska-Kula, 2021, p.37; Theurer <i>et al.</i> , 2018, p.156)
EVP 1a: Focusing on the offers of the employer as a competitive advantage
(Kucherov <i>et al.</i> , 2022, p.135; Künzel, 2013, p.51; Theys and Barkhuizen, 2022, p.3)
EVP 1b: Focusing on the offers of the employer as a uniqueness
(Eger and Schrank, 2012, p.774; Ingham, 2006, p.21; Mostafa, 2022, p.2; Scholz, 2014, p.489)
EVP 2: Focusing on the offers and demands of the employer.
(Arasanmi and Krishna, 2019, p.388; Keohane, 2009, p.37; Leatherbarrow and Fletcher, 2018, p.181; Leford, 2003, p.22; Lesenyeho, Barkhuizen and Schutte, 2018, p.3; Munsamy and Bosch Venter, 2009, p.187; Nurmi and Varis, 2021, p.45; Robinson, 2019, p.7; Sartain and Schumann, 2006, p.77)

Tab. 40: Four approaches of the value within the EVP (authors)

3. Appendix 3: 27 theoretical requirements and their sources

requirement ID	requirement description	source(s)
S1	Identify the needs of the target group.	[NAZ and ZAHIDI, 2021, p.4]
S2	Determine the preferences of the employees and the causes of any discrepancies between the employees' wishes and the actual EVP.	[ALLOUSH, 2020, p.5]
S3	Gain insights into the current experiences of employees.	[BOUKIS, 2019, p.238; BRIDGER and GANNAWAY, 2024, p.53; FOX, 2012, p.42]
S4	Gain insights into the gap between employees' expectations and experiences.	[BOUKIS, 2019, p.238; BRIDGER and GANNAWAY, 2024, p.53; FOX, 2012, p.42]
S5	Collect information about the company's culture.	[BACKHAUS and TIKOO, 2004, p.502; BRIDGER and GANNAWAY, 2024, p.53]
S6	Collect information about the company's values.	[BACKHAUS and TIKOO, 2004, p.502; BRIDGER and GANNAWAY, 2024, p.53]
S7	Collect information about the company's management style.	[BACKHAUS and TIKOO, 2004, p.502; BRIDGER and GANNAWAY, 2024, p.53]
S8	Collect information about the qualities of the current employees.	[BACKHAUS and TIKOO, 2004, p.502; BRIDGER and GANNAWAY, 2024, p.53]
S9	Collect information about the company's current image.	[BACKHAUS and TIKOO, 2004, p.502; BRIDGER and GANNAWAY, 2024, p.53]
S10	Collect information about the impression of product quality.	[BACKHAUS and TIKOO, 2004, p.502; BRIDGER and GANNAWAY, 2024, p.53]
S11	Examine the requirements of and benefits for employees.	[FOX, 2012, p.42]
S12	Examine employees' perception of the current EVP.	[BOUKIS, 2019, p.238]
K1	Be employee-centred, attractive, and valuable.	[HENEMAN, JUDGE and KAMMEYER-MUELLER, 2019, p.605; KUCHEROV et al., 2022, p.135; PAWAR and CHARAK, 2014, p.8]
K2	Fulfil employee needs and be relevant (e.g., harmonised with ESG priorities).	[DUBEY and RANA, 2021, p.86; ERIBO and ANDRADI, 2024, p.55; KEOHANE, 2014, p.67; PAWAR and CHARAK, 2014, p.6]
K3	Be a characterisation of the quintessence of the distinctive overall workplace experience, guiding daily employee experiences and representing the organisation's personality.	[BOTH A, BUSSIN and SWARDT, 2011, p.6; DUBEY and RANA, 2021, p.104; GREEN, 2019, p.101]
K4	Ideally be linked to a feeling or emotion to encourage associations and facilitate uptake.	[ALLOUSH, 2020, p.5; HATUM, 2010, p.39]
K5	Make employees feel valued and express the company's commitment to them.	[ALLOUSH, 2020, p.2; DEEPA and BARAL, 2019, p.80; PHUNGULA, DHANPAT and BRAINE, 2022, p.47; SETIAWATI, 2019, p.142]
K6	Be able to assert itself in competition, through differentiation or even uniqueness.	[ALLOUSH, 2020, p.5; BRIDGER and GANNAWAY, 2024, p.53; HATUM, 2010, p.39; KEOHANE, 2014, p.67; NAZ and ZAHIDI, 2021, p.4]
K7	Ensure the design, positioning, and development of an employer brand profile.	[ALLOUSH, 2020, p.5; MASCARENHAS, 2019, pp.99–100; MCLEAN-CONNER, 2015, p.18; MORTENSEN and EDMONDSON, 2023, p.45; REDDY, 2017, p.36]
K8	Be authentic, credible, and real.	[ABBOTT, 2019, p.15; BRONLET et al., 2024, p.280; FOURNIER et al., 2019, p.31; GREEN, 2019, p.101; HATUM, 2010, p.41; Kristia, 2023, p.298]
K9	Be truthful.	[ALLOUSH, 2020, p.5; HATUM, 2010, p.39]
K10	Be convincing overall.	[DUBEY and RANA, 2021, p.86]

requirement ID	requirement description	source(s)
O1	Improvement of EVP attributes (e.g., improve the employee experience).	[ARMSTRONG and TAYLOR, 2023, p.411; PATTNAIK and MISRA, 2016, p.15; VELDSMAN and VAN DER MERWE, 2025, pp.8–9]
E1	Be simple and therefore easy for every employee to understand.	[ABBOTT, 2019, p.15]
E2	Be easy to pass on.	[BOUKIS, 2019, p.238]
E3	Express a lot with few words.	[LEHMANN, 2012, p.37]
E4	Be measurable.	[BOUKIS, 2019, p.238]

Tab. 41: 27 theoretical requirements and their sources

4. Appendix 4: Linking the assumptions made with the results of the analyses

Four assumptions were made:

- (a) knowledge goes hand in hand with experience, i.e. more EVP projects generally lead to more experience and knowledge in this area,
- (b) employees within a company have generally carried out fewer EVP projects than employees in employer branding consultancies,
- (c) participants without expertise in EVP development are unlikely to be able to make a significant contribution,
- (d) no differences are expected in terms of gender, age, ethnicity, etc.

Ad a) Knowledge goes hand in hand with experience

category	subcategory	avg. no. of requirements mentioned
experience in employer branding	20+ years	15.78
	10–19 years	14.25
	5–9 years	15.29
	Under 5 years	7.00
EVP project experience	100+ projects	15.00
	11–99 projects	15.80
	5–10 projects	14.50
	Under 5 projects	8.00

Tab. 42: Average number of requirements per expertise group

The assumption was generally correct when looking at experience of under and over five years respectively under and over five conducted EVP development projects. However, after that, the results become more inconsistent.

Ad b) Internal experts carried out fewer projects on average.

category	subcategory	conducted projects	average number of requirements mentioned
role	in-house experts	2.33	6.67
	consultant experts	84.32	14.48

Tab. 43: Average projects and number of requirements per perspective group (internal vs. external)

This assumption was generally correct, at least among the experts interviewed. Moreover, this also applies to the average number of requirements

Ad c) Participants without expertise

Not checked. No interview was conducted with a non-expert.

Ad d) Gender, age, ethnicity, etc.

category	subcategory	avg. no. of requirements mentioned
gender	female experts	12.75
	male experts	14.95

Tab. 44: Average number of requirements per gender group

Although the evaluation shows a slight difference, the number of experts per gender was also different: eight women and 20 men. This may also account for the two additional requirements on average.

Other criteria were not analysed.

5. Appendix 5: The interviewees

No.	Date of Interview	CF	ID	Company	Position	Country
1	15.02.2024	P	I1	Consultancy	Head of Division	D
2	16.02.2024	F	I2	Consultancy	Country Manager Germany	D
3	19.02.2024	F	I3	Consultancy	Research Lead	UK
4	21.02.2024	F	I4	Consultancy	CEO	UK
5	21.02.2024	F	I5	Consultancy	Co-Founder and MD	CAN/USA
6	27.02.2024	F	I6	Consultancy	Employer Branding Lead & Principal	D
7	27.02.2024	F	I7	Consultancy	CEO	UK
8	28.02.2024	F	I8	Consultancy	CEO	UK
9	01.03.2024	F	I9	Consultancy	CEO	USA
10	04.03.2024	F	I10	Consultancy	CEO	UK
11	04.03.2024	F	I11	Consultancy	Client Partner	UK
12	04.03.2024	F	I12	Consultancy	CEO	UK
13	05.03.2024	F	I13	Consultancy	Head Operations (Employer Branding)	India
14	05.03.2024	F	I14	Consultancy	Solutions and Strategy	UK
15	06.03.2024	F	I15	Consultancy	Founder, MD	D
16	06.03.2024	F	I16	Consultancy	Founder and CEO	D
17	07.03.2024	P	I17	Company	Head of HR	D
18	07.03.2024	F	I18	Consultancy	Co-Founder / MD	D
19	07.03.2024	F	I19	Consultancy	CEO	USA
20	08.03.2024	F	I20	Company	Employer Branding Strategist	Iran
21	11.03.2024	F	I21	Company	Head of Global Employer Brand	USA
22	15.03.2024	F	I22	Consultancy	Partner	UK
23	25.03.2024	F	I23	Consultancy	Co-Founder	DK
24	29.03.2024	F	I24	Consultancy	VP Employer Brand Strategy	USA
25	16.04.2024	F	I25	Consultancy	Founder / CEO	UK
26	18.04.2024	F	I26	Consultancy	Founder / CEO	UK
27	02.05.2024	F	I27	Consultancy	CEO	D
28	14.05.2024	F	I28	Consultancy	Strategy & Consulting Director	UK

Tab. 45: The interviewees: overview

No.	expert ID	# projects	view	Country	academia	field	years
1	I1	30	consultant	D	Communications	Marketing	8
2	I2	10	consultant	D	German	Marketing	11
3	I3	15	consultant	UK	Psychology	Human Resources	5
4	I4	200	consultant	UK	MBA	Human Resources	17
5	I5	200	consultant	CAN/USA	MBA	Human Resources	25
6	I6	250	consultant	D	Social Science	Human Resources	23
7	I7	10	consultant	UK	Business	Human Resources	18
8	I8	100	consultant	UK	Science	Marketing	27
9	I9	35	consultant	USA	MBA	Marketing	13
10	I10	60	consultant	UK	Science	Marketing	25
11	I11	30	consultant	UK	Marketing	Marketing	6
12	I12	100	consultant	UK	German/French	Marketing	20
13	I13	3	consultant	India	MBA	Marketing	5
14	I14	100	consultant	UK	Science	Marketing	20
15	I15	100	consultant	D	Communications	Marketing	16
16	I16	50	consultant	D	?	Marketing	9
17	I17	1	in-house	D	Business	Human Resources	3
18	I18	10	consultant	D	Social Science	Marketing	10
19	I19	50	consultant	USA	English	Marketing	15
20	I20	2	in-house	Iran	Urban Studies	Marketing	3
21	I21	4	in-house	USA	Communications	Marketing	7
22	I22	15	consultant	UK	Theology	Marketing	3
23	I23	20	consultant	DK	Business	Human Resources	3
24	I24	350	consultant	USA	Economics	Marketing	20
25	I25	35	consultant	UK	Anthropology	Marketing	20
26	I26	5	consultant	UK	German	Marketing	7
27	I27	300	consultant	D	Communications	Marketing	18
28	I28	30	consultant	UK	Art	Marketing	25
		2,115					382

Tab. 46: The interviewees: intra-empirical comparison criteria

Expert ID	Number of Mentioned Requirements
I14	30
I25	22
I3	21
I2	19
I12	19
I7	18
I9	18
I11	18
I5	16
I16	16
I1	15
I15	15
I26	15
I4	14
I10	14
I19	14
I21	14
I8	12
I22	12
I24	11
I23	10
I27	10
I28	10
I6	8
I13	8
I18	6
I17	3
I20	3
	386

Tab. 47: The interviewees by number of mentioned requirements

The average number of mentioned requirements over all experts is 13.79.

6. Appendix 6: The code book

Category	Description
1. Information basis requirements	The necessary data and insights gathered from various sources to inform the creation or development of an EVP.
1.1 Information basis: Employees	Information gathered from employees regarding their needs, motivations, expectations, experiences, and perceptions of the company as an employer.
1.2 Information basis: Employer	Information about the company's internal reality, including culture, values, leadership, policies, current offerings, structure, and existing data.
1.3 Information basis: Markets and competition	Information about the external environment, such as industry trends, labour market dynamics, and the employer branding efforts of competitors.
1.4 Information basis: Strategy	Information regarding the overall business strategy, future vision, mission, goals, and specific HR/People strategies that guide the EVP development.
2. Development requirements	Essential aspects and steps within the process of creating, refining, or activating the Employer Value Proposition.
2.1 Development: EVP creation	The process and principles involved in articulating and formulating the core message of the EVP.
2.1.1 Creation: aligned w/ employee insights	Ensuring the developed EVP genuinely reflects and resonates with the authentic feelings, experiences, and expectations of current employees.
2.1.2 Creation: aligned with employer reality	Ensuring the EVP is credible, truthful, and reflects the actual current state and offerings of the employer, avoiding over-promising.
2.1.3 Creation: aligned w/ markets (trends/comp.)	Developing an EVP that considers the external market and competitor landscape, aiming for clear differentiation and relevance to target talent.
2.1.4 Creation: aligned with the desired future	Integrating the company's future vision, strategic direction, and aspirations into the EVP, balancing it with current reality.
2.2 Development: Optimising attributes	Identifying and enhancing specific aspects of the employee experience or company offerings to strengthen the overall value proposition.
3. Requirements EVP characteristics	Key characteristics and qualities that define an effective and impactful Employer Value Proposition.
4. EVP optimisation requirements	This refers to the continuous improvement of employer attributes (e.g. the employee experience) in order to bridge the gap between the EVP promise and operational reality (i.e. closing the reality-ambition gap).

Tab. 48: Code book

7. Appendix 7: Ethic approval by the University of the West of Scotland

10/06/2022

Dear Philip Wölki,

Your application 18008: Analysis of the information base for the determination of the EVP, submission 15274, has been approved by the Business and Creative Industries SEC. You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before acting on them.

Good luck with your research.

Dr John Quinn

8. Appendix 8: The expert IDs

expert ID	mentioned requirements (IDs)	mentioned requirements (new IDs)	number of mentioned requirements
I1	A2, A4, A5, A8, A10, A16, A24, A25, A26, C6, C8, C9, C12, H1, H2	SA-02, SA-04, SA-05, SA-08, SA-10, SA-16, SA-24, SA-25, SA-26, CR-06, CR-08, CR-09, CR-12, FM-01, FM-02	15
I2	A2, A4, A11, A13, A19, A20, A23, A24, A25, A26, C2, C4, C6, C8, C9, C11, O1, H4, H5	SA-02, SA-04, SA-11, SA-13, SA-19, SA-20, SA-23, SA-24, SA-25, SA-26, CR-02, CR-04, CR-06, CR-08, CR-09, CR-11, OP-01, FM-04, FM-05	19
I3	A2, A4, A5, A7, A8, A12, A13, A16, A17, A18, A20, A21, A24, C1, C2, C4, C9, C11, C12, O1, H5	SA-02, SA-04, SA-05, SA-07, SA-08, SA-12, SA-13, SA-16, SA-17, SA-18, SA-20, SA-21, SA-24, CR-01, CR-02, CR-04, CR-09, CR-11, CR-12, OP-01, FM-05	21
I4	A3, A8, A10, A11, A15, A16, A19, A20, A26, C4, C9, O1, H6, H8	SA-03, SA-08, SA-10, SA-11, SA-15, SA-16, SA-19, SA-20, SA-26, CR-04, CR-09, OP-01, FM-06, FM-08	14
I5	A1, A4, A6, A8, A9, A13, A20, A21, A26, C2, C3, C4, C9, C12, O1, H3	SA-01, SA-04, SA-06, SA-08, SA-09, SA-13, SA-20, SA-21, SA-26, CR-02, CR-03, CR-04, CR-09, CR-12, OP-01, FM-03	16
I6	A5, A8, A9, A10, A12, C4, C5, C9	SA-05, SA-08, SA-09, SA-10, SA-12, CR-04, CR-05, CR-09	8
I7	A2, A4, A6, A8, A11, A13, A15, A17, A26, C2, C4, C5, C6, C10, O1, H2, H5, H8	SA-02, SA-04, SA-06, SA-08, SA-11, SA-13, SA-15, SA-17, SA-26, CR-02, CR-04, CR-05, CR-06, CR-10, OP-01, FM-02, FM-05, FM-08	18
I8	A4, A7, A10, A19, A22, C3, C4, C6, C11, H2, H4, H6	SA-04, SA-07, SA-10, SA-19, SA-22, CR-03, CR-04, CR-06, CR-11, FM-02, FM-04, FM-06	12
I9	A1, A3, A4, A6, A8, A9, A10, A12, A15, A17, A19, A21, C2, C4, C9, C12, H3, H7	SA-01, SA-03, SA-04, SA-06, SA-08, SA-09, SA-10, SA-12, SA-15, SA-17, SA-19, SA-21, CR-02, CR-04, CR-09, CR-12, FM-03, FM-07	18
I10	A1, A6, A8, A9, A18, A19, A23, A26, C2, C5, C10, C12, H4, H5	SA-01, SA-06, SA-08, SA-09, SA-18, SA-19, SA-23, SA-26, CR-02, CR-05, CR-10, CR-12, FM-04, FM-05	14
I11	A4, A7, A10, A12, A16, A17, A19, A20, A21, C2, C4, C11, C12, C13, H2, H3, H4, H5	SA-04, SA-07, SA-10, SA-12, SA-16, SA-17, SA-19, SA-20, SA-21, CR-02, CR-04, CR-11, CR-12, CR-13, FM-02, FM-03, FM-04, FM-05	18
I12	A4, A6, A7, A8, A13, A16, A19, A20, A26, C4, C6, C8, C10, C12, O1, H1, H3, H4, H5	SA-04, SA-06, SA-07, SA-08, SA-13, SA-16, SA-19, SA-20, SA-26, CR-04, CR-06, CR-08, CR-10, CR-12, OP-01, FM-01, FM-03, FM-04, FM-05	19
I13	A2, A6, A7, A8, A9, A17, H3, H5	SA-02, SA-06, SA-07, SA-08, SA-09, SA-17, FM-03, FM-05	8
I14	A2, A3, A4, A6, A7, A9, A10, A11, A12, A18, A19, A20, A24, A25, A26, C2, C3, C4, C5, C6, C8, C9, C10, C11, C12, O1, H1, H3, H6, H7	SA-02, SA-03, SA-04, SA-06, SA-07, SA-09, SA-10, SA-11, SA-12, SA-18, SA-19, SA-20, SA-24, SA-25, SA-26, CR-02, CR-03, CR-04, CR-05, CR-06, CR-08, CR-09, CR-10, CR-11, CR-12, OP-01, FM-01, FM-03, FM-06, FM-07	30
I15	A1, A4, A10, A15, A17, A19, A21, A25, A26, C1, C5, C6, C13, O1, H8	SA-01, SA-04, SA-10, SA-15, SA-17, SA-19, SA-21, SA-25, SA-26, CR-01, CR-05, CR-06, CR-13, OP-01, FM-08	15
I16	A2, A3, A4, A6, A16, A18, A19, A20, A21, A24, C2, C4, C5, C13, H2, H5	SA-02, SA-03, SA-04, SA-06, SA-16, SA-18, SA-19, SA-20, SA-21, SA-24, CR-02, CR-04, CR-05, CR-13, FM-02, FM-05	16
I17	A6, A8, A18	SA-06, SA-08, SA-18	3
I18	A11, A14, A17, A19, A23, C7	SA-11, SA-14, SA-17, SA-19, SA-23, CR-07	6
I19	A2, A3, A8, A9, A12, A16, A18, A20, A21, C6, C8, C9, C12, C13	SA-02, SA-03, SA-08, SA-09, SA-12, SA-16, SA-18, SA-20, SA-21, CR-06, CR-08, CR-09, CR-12, CR-13	14
I20	A2, A4, A10	SA-02, SA-04, SA-10	3
I21	A2, A4, A6, A15, A16, A20, A21, A23, C4, C9, C12, H2, H5, H8	SA-02, SA-04, SA-06, SA-15, SA-16, SA-20, SA-21, SA-23, CR-04, CR-09, CR-12, FM-02, FM-05, FM-08	14
I22	A2, A3, A4, A6, A7, A8, A14, A25, C4, C5, C9, O1	SA-02, SA-03, SA-04, SA-06, SA-07, SA-08, SA-14, SA-25, CR-04, CR-05, CR-09, OP-01	12

expert ID	mentioned requirements (IDs)	mentioned requirements (new IDs)	number of mentioned requirements
I23	A1, A6, A7, A9, A14, A20, A23, C6, C13, H5	SA-01, SA-06, SA-07, SA-09, SA-14, SA-20, SA-23, CR-06, CR-13, FM-05	10
I24	A1, A4, A7, A8, A10, A17, A23, C10, C11, H5, H8	SA-01, SA-04, SA-07, SA-08, SA-10, SA-17, SA-23, CR-10, CR-11, FM-05, FM-08	11
I25	A1, A2, A3, A4, A6, A8, A11, A16, A18, A21, A24, A25, A26, C1, C4, C6, C8, C9, H3, H4, H5, H7	SA-01, SA-02, SA-03, SA-04, SA-06, SA-08, SA-11, SA-16, SA-18, SA-21, SA-24, SA-25, SA-26, CR-01, CR-04, CR-06, CR-08, CR-09, FM-03, FM-04, FM-05, FM-07	22
I26	A1, A2, A4, A6, A8, A11, A21, A25, A26, C4, C5, C6, C11, H3, H5	SA-01, SA-02, SA-04, SA-06, SA-08, SA-11, SA-21, SA-25, SA-26, CR-04, CR-05, CR-06, CR-11, FM-03, FM-05	15
I27	A8, A10, A17, A21, A26, C5, C7, C9, C10, H8	SA-08, SA-10, SA-17, SA-21, SA-26, CR-05, CR-07, CR-09, CR-10, FM-08	10
I28	A1, A7, A8, A10, A11, A15, A17, A21, C1, O1	SA-01, SA-07, SA-08, SA-10, SA-11, SA-15, SA-17, SA-21, CR-01, OP-01	10

Tab. 49: Experts and their IDs and mentioned requirements

9. Appendix 9: Average number of requirements by group

category	subcategory	avg. no. of requirements mentioned
role	in-house experts	6.67
	consultant experts	14.48
gender	female experts	12.75
	male experts	14.95
experience in employer branding	20+ years	15.78
	10–19 years	14.25
	5–9 years	15.29
	Under 5 years	7.00
EVP project experience	100+ projects	15.00
	11–99 projects	15.80
	5–10 projects	14.50
	Under 5 projects	8.00
country	United Kingdom	17.08
	Germany	11.50
	USA / Canada	14.60
	other (Denmark, Iran, India)	7.00
field background	HR	12.86
	Marketing	13.86
academic background	Humanities & Languages	14.30
	Social Sciences	12.00
	Business & Applied Studies	12.89
	Natural & Formal Sciences	18.67
overall average	all experts	13.79

Tab. 50: Average number of requirements by group

10. Appendix 10: EVP Development Process with the 50 requirements

Fig. 32: EVP Development Process with the 50 requirements

11. Appendix 11: Comparison by expertise (# EVP projects)

The analysis will identify differences and similarities based on the expert's experience in the number of EVP development projects. Groupings of experts:

- Group 1 (G1): 100 and more EVP projects (9 experts: I4, I5, I6, I8, I12, I14, I15, I24, I27)
- Group 2 (G2): Over 10 and under 100 EVP projects (10 experts: I1, I3, I9, I10, I11, I16, I19, I23, I25, I28)
- Group 3 (G3): 5-10 EVP projects (4 experts: I2, I7, I18, I26)
- Group 4 (G4): Less than 5 EVP projects (5 experts: I13, I17, I20, I21, I22)

Analysis (A) Requirements	G1 (N=9) %	G2 (N=10) %	G3 (N=4) %	G4 (N=5) %
A1: Employee & candidate needs	33.3%	50.0%	25.0%	0.0%
A2: Employee preferences	11.1%	50.0%	75.0%	80.0%
A3: Employees' prior work experiences	22.2%	40.0%	0.0%	20.0%
A4: Employer attributes relevance	55.6%	60.0%	75.0%	60.0%
A5: Employees' work emotions	11.1%	20.0%	0.0%	0.0%
A6: Employees' expectations	33.3%	50.0%	50.0%	80.0%
A7: Willingness to contribute	44.4%	50.0%	0.0%	40.0%
A8: Experiences describing employer	66.7%	70.0%	50.0%	60.0%
A9: Employee's behaviour (ethnography)	33.3%	40.0%	0.0%	20.0%
A10: Employer's corporate culture	77.8%	40.0%	0.0%	40.0%
A11: Employer's corporate values	22.2%	20.0%	100.0%	0.0%
A12: Leadership & corporate behaviour	22.2%	40.0%	0.0%	0.0%
A13: Internal communication	22.2%	10.0%	50.0%	0.0%
A14: Quality of current employees	0.0%	10.0%	25.0%	20.0%
A15: Analyse the employer brand	22.2%	20.0%	25.0%	20.0%
A16: Product & corporate brands	22.2%	50.0%	0.0%	20.0%
A17: Employer's benefits for employees	33.3%	40.0%	50.0%	20.0%
A18: Employer expectation for contributions	11.1%	50.0%	0.0%	20.0%
A19: Corporate objectives & strategy	55.6%	50.0%	50.0%	0.0%
A20: Company's structure, size, location	44.4%	50.0%	25.0%	20.0%
A21: Employer's purpose, vision, mission	33.3%	70.0%	25.0%	0.0%
A22: Employer's people strategy	11.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
A23: Employer's strengths & weaknesses	11.1%	20.0%	50.0%	20.0%
A24: Labour markets	11.1%	40.0%	25.0%	0.0%
A25: Labour market influencing trends	22.2%	20.0%	50.0%	20.0%
A26: The competition	66.7%	20.0%	75.0%	0.0%

Creation (C) Requirements	G1 (N=9) %	G2 (N=10) %	G3 (N=4) %	G4 (N=5) %
C1: Create a relevant EVP	11.1%	30.0%	0.0%	0.0%
C2: Create an attractive EVP	22.2%	50.0%	50.0%	0.0%
C3: Create a motivating and engaging EVP	33.3%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
C4: Create an EVP reflecting EX	55.6%	50.0%	75.0%	40.0%
C5: Create an EVP reflecting sentiments	44.4%	20.0%	50.0%	20.0%
C6: Create a competitive EVP	44.4%	40.0%	75.0%	0.0%
C7: Create a profiling EVP	11.1%	0.0%	25.0%	0.0%
C8: Create an ownable EVP	22.2%	30.0%	25.0%	0.0%
C9: Create a believable and honest EVP	55.6%	50.0%	25.0%	40.0%
C10: Create an effective EVP	44.4%	10.0%	25.0%	0.0%
C11: Create a deal-related EVP	33.3%	20.0%	50.0%	0.0%
C12: Create a brand-aligned EVP	33.3%	60.0%	0.0%	20.0%
C13: Create a selective EVP	11.1%	40.0%	0.0%	0.0%
Optimising (O) Requirements	G1 (N=9) %	G2 (N=10) %	G3 (N=4) %	G4 (N=5) %
O1: Improve employer attributes	44.4%	20.0%	50.0%	20.0%
Have (H) Requirements	G1 (N=9) %	G2 (N=10) %	G3 (N=4) %	G4 (N=5) %
H1: Ensure the EVP is clear	22.2%	10.0%	0.0%	0.0%
H2: Ensure the EVP is concise	11.1%	30.0%	25.0%	20.0%
H3: Ensure the EVP is measurable	33.3%	30.0%	25.0%	20.0%
H4: Ensure the EVP is robust but flexible	22.2%	30.0%	25.0%	0.0%
H5: Ensure the EVP is structured	11.1%	60.0%	75.0%	40.0%
H6: Ensure the EVP is practical	33.3%	10.0%	0.0%	0.0%
H7: Ensure the EVP is specific	11.1%	20.0%	0.0%	0.0%
H8: Ensure the EVP is validated	44.4%	10.0%	50.0%	20.0%

Tab. 51: Requirements mentioned per expert group (in percent)

The comparison reveals distinct patterns in how different experience groups perceive and prioritise the requirements for EVP projects. Generally, more experienced groups (G1 and G2) tend to mention a wider array of requirements, indicating a more comprehensive understanding of the EVP lifecycle and its strategic implications. Less experienced groups (G3 and G4) often exhibit a narrower, more foundational focus, with numerous omissions.

(1) Specific areas of differences

1. Foundational employee and market understanding (more mentioned by G3 & G4):

- Employee preferences and expectations (A2, A6): Group 4 (least experienced) shows the highest emphasis on analysing employee preferences (A2: 80.0%) and expectations towards the employer (A6: 80.0%). This suggests that for less experienced practitioners, a primary focus is on

basic employee data collection. Group 3 also scores highly on A2 (75.0%) and A4 (75.0%) (relevance of employer attributes).

- External market factors (A25, A26, C6): Group 3 (5-10 projects) places a significantly higher emphasis on analysing the competition (A26: 75.0%) and labour market influencing trends (A25: 50.0%). This translates into a strong focus on creating a competitive EVP (C6: 75.0%), where they also lead other groups. This suggests that practitioners with moderate, but limited, experience are particularly attuned to competitive positioning.

2. *Corporate identity and brand alignment (more mentioned by G2 & G3):*

- Corporate values (A11): Group 3 (5-10 projects) stands out, with 100.0% of its experts mentioning the analysis of employer's corporate values. This is a unique and very strong emphasis compared to other groups (G1: 22.2%, G2: 20.0%, G4: 0.0%).
- Purpose, vision, and mission (A21): Group 2 (over 10 and under 100 projects) shows a strong lead (70.0%) in analysing the employer's purpose, vision, and mission. This indicates that experts in this mid-level experience bracket connect EVP creation closely with the core identity and direction of the employer.
- Brand-aligned EVP (C12): Group 2 also demonstrates the highest focus on creating a brand-aligned EVP (60.0%), reinforcing their emphasis on integrating the EVP with the overall corporate brand.

3. *Strategic depth and impact (more mentioned by G1):*

- Corporate culture (A10): Group 1 (most experienced) places a much higher emphasis on analysing employer's corporate culture (77.8%) compared to other groups (G2: 40.0%, G3: 0.0%, G4: 40.0%). This suggests that highly experienced experts see a deep understanding of culture as fundamental to EVP success.
- Corporate objectives and strategy (A19): Group 1 (55.6%) mentions analysing employer's corporate objectives and strategy slightly more than other active groups, indicating a strong link between EVP and overall business goals.

- Motivating, engaging, and effective EVP (C3, C10): Group 1 is the only group to mention creating a motivating and engaging EVP (C3: 33.3%). They also place a significantly higher focus on creating an effective EVP (C10: 44.4%). This highlights their concern for the qualitative impact and ultimate success of the EVP.
- Practicality and validation (H6, H8): Group 1 shows higher percentages for a practical EVP (H6: 33.3%) and validated EVP (H8: 44.4%), underscoring a focus on actionable, evidence-based, and proven EVP solutions.
- Improve employer attributes (O1): Group 1 (44.4%) and Group 3 (50.0%) show higher focus on improving employer attributes than Group 2 (20.0%) and Group 4 (20.0%). This suggests that more experienced practitioners view EVP not just as a communication tool but also as a lever for organisational improvement.

4. Areas of less/no mention by group:

- Group 1 (100+ EVP projects): Uniquely, this highly experienced group does not mention the analysis of the employer's quality of current employees (A14: 0.0%).
- Group 2 (Over 10 and under 100 EVP projects): This group does not mention analysing employer's people strategy (A22: 0.0%), creating motivating and engaging EVP (C3: 0.0%), or creating profiling EVP (C7: 0.0%).
- Group 3 (5-10 EVP projects): This group has several significant omissions, including analysing employees' prior work experiences (A3: 0.0%), work emotions (A5: 0.0%), willingness to contribute (A7: 0.0%), employee behaviour (A9: 0.0%), corporate culture (A10: 0.0%), leadership and corporate behaviour (A12: 0.0%), product and corporate brands (A16: 0.0%), employer expectations for contributions (A18: 0.0%). In terms of EVP creation, they do not mention creating a relevant EVP (C1: 0.0%), motivating/engaging EVP (C3: 0.0%), brand-aligned EVP (C12: 0.0%), or a selective EVP (C13: 0.0%). They also omit clarity (H1: 0.0%), practicality (H6: 0.0%), and specificity (H7: 0.0%) in EVP characteristics.
- Group 4 (Less than 5 EVP projects): This group demonstrates the most extensive list of omissions, failing to mention a considerable number of analytical requirements such as employee/candidate needs (A1: 0.0%),

work emotions (A5: 0.0%), corporate values (A11: 0.0%), leadership and corporate behaviour (A12: 0.0%), internal communication (A13: 0.0%), corporate objectives and strategy (A19: 0.0%), purpose/vision/mission (A21: 0.0%), people strategy (A22: 0.0%), labour markets (A24: 0.0%), and competition (A26: 0.0%). For EVP creation, they do not mention relevant (C1: 0.0%), attractive (C2: 0.0%), motivating/engaging (C3: 0.0%), competitive (C6: 0.0%), profiling (C7: 0.0%), ownable (C8: 0.0%), effective (C10: 0.0%), deal-related (C11: 0.0%), or selective (C13: 0.0%) EVP. They also omit many EVP characteristics like clarity (H1: 0.0%), robustness (H4: 0.0%), practicality (H6: 0.0%), and specificity (H7: 0.0%).

(2) Overall conclusions on differences

- Breadth of scope: Experts with 100 or more EVP projects (G1) and those with 10 to 100 projects (G2) exhibit a much broader and more integrated approach to EVP development, encompassing both internal and external factors, corporate strategy, and the quality/effectiveness of the EVP characteristics.
- Focus evolution: As experience increases, the focus shifts from a purely employee-centric and competitive analysis (G4, G3) to a more holistic, strategic, and outcome-oriented perspective that includes corporate culture, brand alignment, and the practical implementation and validation of the EVP (G1).
- Strategic vs. tactical: The less experienced groups (G3, G4) appear to focus on more tactical elements of EVP (e.g. direct employee input, basic competitive analysis), while the more experienced groups (G1, G2) delve into the strategic implications and the deeper organisational elements such as corporate culture and objectives.
- Completeness: Group 4, in particular, demonstrates a significantly less comprehensive understanding of the diverse requirements involved in EVP projects, likely reflecting their limited practical exposure.

12. Appendix 12: Publications and conferences in relation to this thesis

Publications:

Wölki, P. (2020): *Implementing the HR Situation Analysis to Master the HRM Challenges*, 3rd International Management, Quality and Marketing Conference: 16-18th April, 2020. Moscow, pp. 123–141.

Wölki, P. (2022): *Integration der Diversität als gesellschaftlicher Trend in den Entwicklungsprozess des EVP zur Nutzung in der Unternehmenskommunikation im Employer Branding* (English: *Integration of diversity as a social trend in the EVP development process for use in corporate communications in employer branding*), in: Boßow-Thies, S. und Stumpf, M. (eds.): EUKO 2022 – Diversity in der Wirtschaftskommunikation. Proceedings zur 22. interdisziplinären Tagung des Forschungsnetzwerkes Europäische Kulturen in der Wirtschaftskommunikation – European Cultures in Business and Corporate Communication (EUKO). Essen, pp. 55–56.

Wölki, P., Gibb, S. und Pfahler, T. (2024): *Defining the Employer Value Proposition as an image / idea of the employer in the heads of the employees*, in: Banholzer, V.M., Wintermayr, A. and Seiler, E. (eds.): EUKO 2024 Zukunft in der Wirtschafts- und Unternehmenskommunikation Proceedings: „Zukunft“ als Thema in der Wirtschaftskommunikation. Nürnberg, pp. 63–67.

Wölki, P., Gibb, S. und Pfahler, T. (2025): *HRM and HR Communication: Challenges of changing Employment Deal processes and new generations*, in: Allemann-Ravi, V. (ed.) New Generation Communication: Die Kommunikation in einer veränderten Welt. Wiesbaden: Springer Fachmedien, pp. 349–375.

Wölki, P., Gibb, S. und Pfahler, T. (in print): *Employer Value Proposition als strategisches Instrument zur Personalgewinnung – Anforderungen und Entwicklung* (English: *Employer value proposition as a strategic tool for recruiting personnel – requirements and development*), in: Engelkenmeier, U. et al. (eds.): Praxishandbuch Personalgewinnung in Bibliotheken: Berlin: de Gruyter Saur.

Conferences:

3rd International Management, Quality and Marketing Conference:

16th-18th April 2020. Moscow.

Contribution: Virtual presentation: *"Implementing the HR Situation Analysis to Master the HRM Challenges"*

UWS Research week 2022,

20th-24th June 2022, Paisley.

Contribution: Virtual poster presentation: *"A good Employer Value Proposition is no fraud. How to develop it?"*

22nd Interdisciplinary conference of the European Cultures in Business Communication Research Network (EUKO): *"Diversity in der Wirtschaftskommunikation"* (English: Diversity in business communication),

6th-9th October 2022, Hamburg.

Contribution: Poster presentation: *"Integration der Diversität als gesellschaftlicher Trend in den Entwicklungsprozess des EVP zur Nutzung in der Unternehmenskommunikation im Employer Branding"* (English: *Integration of diversity as a social trend in the EVP development process for use in corporate communications in employer branding*)

UWS Research week 2023,

22nd-24th May 2023, Paisley.

Contribution: Poster presentation: *"Integration of social trends into the development process of the EVP in employer branding"*

23rd Interdisciplinary conference of the European Cultures in Business Communication Research Network (EUKO), New Generation Communication: Die Kommunikation in einer veränderten Welt (English: New Generation Communication: Communication in a changing world),

19th-21st October 2023, Luzern.

Contribution: Presentation: *"The shift in the balance of power between employers and employees will significantly determine the working world of tomorrow"*

HAW Promovierendentag 2023,

8th November 2023, Hamburg.

Contribution: Poster presentation: *"The district / quartier as a possible asset in the employer branding of ad agencies"*

UWS Research week 2024.

20th-22nd May 2024, Paisley

Contribution: 3MT presentation: *"What information is required to develop an Employer Value Proposition"*

24th Interdisciplinary conference of the European Cultures in Business Communication Research Network (EUKO): Fortschritt, Innovation, Vision – Szenarien, Bilder, Metaphern und sprachliche Konzepte von Zukunft in der Wirtschaftskommunikation,

24th-26th October 2024. Nürnberg.

Contribution: Presentation: *"Defining the Employer Value Proposition as an image / idea of the employer in the heads of the employees"*

25th Interdisciplinary conference of the European Cultures in Business Communication Research Network (EUKO): Storytelling: The power of stories and narratives in business communication and media discourses,

23rd-25th October 2025, London.

Contribution: Presentation: *"Storytelling for the Development and Communication of the Employer Value Proposition (EVP)"*

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